

**An Analysis of Learner Engagement with MOOCs in
Higher Education in China**

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Author's Declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, this thesis is the result of the researcher's own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institutions.

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Abstract

With the rapid development of science and technology, the widespread use of the Internet has brought significant benefits to education, providing greater convenience for both students and teachers. The integration of the Internet into teaching has removed the time and space limitations of traditional face-to-face classroom settings, offering greater flexibility for learners. However, the traditional university teaching system still faces numerous challenges and difficulties, highlighting the urgent need for innovative teaching reforms. MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) have emerged as a new educational model with distinct advantages, offering high-quality learning environments that promote independent learning for university students. As more countries and their universities introduce MOOCs and create their own MOOCs, China has joined this global trend, with its universities increasingly participating in MOOC-based teaching and learning. However, along with the benefits of MOOCs, several challenges have also gradually emerged. Issues such as low completion rates, limited learner engagement, decreased learner focus, and insufficient support for autonomous learning have been observed.

This study, therefore, aims to examine learner engagement with MOOCs in higher education in China, identifying the factors that may affect this engagement, and analyse the potential challenges to Chinese students in relation to MOOC learning, with a focus on enhancing motivation, developing learner engagement autonomy and building autonomy, as well as discussing the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the continued development of MOOCs. It aims to provide insights with the intention to fill the gap in the existing literature on MOOCs and learning in the Chinese context, in order to raise the issue among educationalists to support both learners and teachers in this context, and help learners explore, understand, and engage more effectively with their MOOC experiences in Chinese higher education.

The theoretical framework emphasises that learners' awareness of their own learning process is more important than the courses themselves, that the focus should be given to how learners engage with learning and develop an understanding of the factors that facilitate their engagement. The shift from "focusing on teaching" to "focusing on learning" can be challenging, as it requires students to take the initiative in acquiring knowledge and emphasises that a student-centred approach is significantly more effective than a teacher-oriented one in fostering learner autonomy. This framework guided the analysis of the literature and informed the analysis and discussion of participant data on MOOC learning focusing on the role of learner motivation and learner autonomy in MOOCs.

This study adopts an interpretive approach, with a small-scale positivist element, using a mixed-methods design to analyse data collected from students and teachers at two universities of the same level in China, one which delivered MOOCs officially and the other which did not. Initial data on participants' MOOC learning backgrounds and experiences were obtained through questionnaires, and those who demonstrated greater interest in the topic were selected for semi-structured interviews, providing rich qualitative data for the study.

The findings reveal a consensus among students and teachers that they are conscious of the development of MOOCs. Most of the student participants recognise that MOOCs can enhance their autonomous learning ability and so increase their motivation and engagement in learning. They also discuss the significance of MOOCs as an immediate response to the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as agreement on the benefits of MOOC study. Participants shared valuable insights regarding their learning experiences, including how MOOCs developed during the pandemic, their

reasons for choosing MOOCs, factors influencing their learning behaviours, challenges faced within MOOC environments, and their perspectives on the future of MOOCs. Participation in MOOCs in Chinese universities is steadily increasing. With the COVID-19 pandemic's impact on education, MOOCs have become a valuable supplement to traditional classrooms and now play an increasingly significant role in the development of teaching and learning.

This study aims to increase awareness of both teachers and learners about the importance of MOOC implementation in Chinese higher education. The research emphasises the transformative potential of MOOCs in enhancing educational access, flexibility, and learner autonomy, advocating for the integration of MOOCs with traditional classroom methods and making use of the strengths of both online and face-to-face learning environments. This mixed approach can offer students more diverse and flexible learning pathways, enabling them to tailor their educational experiences to meet their individual needs and schedules.

Through this study, it is intended that learners will better understand how to develop their autonomy while enhancing their motivation and engagement in their MOOC learning. Teachers will gain insight into how they can support students in learning via MOOCs, such as by offering more personalised feedback, creating engaging course materials, and guiding students in setting clear learning goals. This awareness can ultimately contribute to better learning outcomes, higher completion rates, and better use of MOOCs as an effective learning tool in China's higher education.

Thus, the thesis adds new knowledge specifically in the area of the participants' improved awareness of independent learning, extending the relevance of this theory to the Chinese context. The research indicates that a growing number of Chinese

students are still engaging with MOOCs, post the COVID-19 pandemic, motivated by various factors, including the fact that they enjoyed the increased flexibility of MOOC learning, alongside traditional classroom teaching. Highly motivated students are more likely to take MOOCs and participate in discussions and course activities. By addressing a gap in the literature concerning Chinese learner engagement with MOOCs, this study provides a foundation for future research. It highlights the potential for MOOCs to play an important role in the future of education in China and suggests new directions for the continued development of online learning.

Glossary of Terms

CALL: Computer Assisted Language Learning

CPL: Continuous Professional Learning

ECM: Expectation-Confirmation Model

ERT: Emergency Remote Teaching

MALL: Mobile-Assisted Language Learning

MAPL: Mobile-assisted Personalised Learning

MOOC: Massive Open Online Course

SDT: Self-Determination Theory

SPOC: Small Private Online Course

TELL: Technology Enhanced Language Learning

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This chapter serves as an introduction to this study. It presents and discusses the rationale for this study as well as the research questions and aims. It explores and analyses learners' engagement with MOOCs in higher education in China by researching the selected participants' learning experiences with MOOCs in two Chinese universities and exploring their responses in relation to the literature consulted. The investigation will focus on two groups of teacher participants and student participants whose university officially delivers MOOCs and participants whose university does not deliver MOOCs, in order to discover whether there are any differences in their attitudes towards participation in MOOCs and the relationship between the MOOC completion, learner autonomy and motivation. In addition, the research background and the significance of this study are introduced.

The study will explore the different motivations of the participants whose university has officially launched MOOCs and those whose university has not launched MOOCs, to discuss what their perceptions of MOOCs are, how they engaged with MOOCs, what their ideas for the future development of MOOCs are, what they believe, in their experience, to be the strengths and weaknesses of MOOCs, the current involvement with MOOCs and learners' autonomous learning in Chinese universities, as well as the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the development of MOOCs. A consideration of the literature relevance of the research, which has led to the development of the study's research questions and the research questions helped me to construct both questionnaires and interview questions to elicit what should be an interesting set of data. In later chapters I will present the analysis of the findings based on the participants' perceptions from the data provided by both groups of participants from both questionnaires and interviews in relation to the literature discussed in Chapter 2.

1.2 Rationale for the Study

Since 2012, top universities in the United States have begun to set up online learning platforms and offer free online courses called MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses). The Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) is an online course aimed at unlimited participation and open access via the web (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2016). In addition to traditional course materials such as filmed lectures, readings, and task-based learning, many MOOCs provide interactive user forums to support community interactions among students, teachers, and teaching assistants. The subsequent rise of the three main course provider platforms Coursera, Udacity and edX has consequently provided more students with the possibility of systematic and autonomous learning at a time suited to them. These three main MOOC platforms are all aimed at higher education and learners, while the providers were committed to developing the course content just as real universities do, with their own learning and management systems. Moreover, most of their courses are free to access (Sandeen, 2013).

The study will analyse the recent and developing phenomenon of MOOCs as the Internet is now more important than ever in people's daily lives. People can do more and more things online, especially related to study, which, for some, may be much more convenient and advantageous to learners than traditional classroom learning. MOOCs, in recent years, have been a popular learning method of accessing learning in education in China, but until now, MOOCs have only been delivered in some developed countries or developed areas of China and top universities around the world (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2016). They are not delivered officially in most cities and universities globally. Some students can only participate in MOOCs on MOOC study platforms that are not regulated and lack professional quality assurance, which

can lead to a low student completion rate. Therefore, for this study I have considered, discussed and analysed the current development in MOOCs, in relation to Chinese learners' completion rates in order to evaluate MOOCs to discuss and to raise issues around completion rates.

The selection of this research topic was driven by both personal and academic motivations. Firstly, it was chosen in relation to my personal experiences. Before beginning my PhD, I worked in a tutoring institution in China, where I observed a strong preference among Chinese parents and students for face-to-face classroom education, despite the inherent advantages of online courses in terms of resource availability and flexibility. During the recruitment process, I often visited high schools and universities to promote our programmes, particularly during parent-teacher conferences. Many parents rejected our services due to the distance of the institution from their homes, yet they remained reluctant to consider online classes. From their perspective, learning is more effective in a traditional classroom under the supervision of a teacher. Secondly, as a student, I have a strong interest in online education. I have had prior experiences with online courses and have transitioned from initially disregarding online learning to preferring it. My master's research focused on learner motivation, and I am eager to further develop my work in this area by investigating learner engagement and motivation in the context of MOOCs, which are gaining popularity in China particularly since the COVID-19 pandemic. Initially offered by top universities in America, MOOCs offer numerous advantages over other online courses, including more comprehensive course structures and higher-quality assurance. They are increasingly relevant within the broader context of education, particularly higher education in China.

Through my Master's research in TESOL, which focused on learner motivation in English Language Learning within Chinese higher education, I discovered that learners' awareness of the importance of autonomous learning significantly influences their academic performance. Ames and Archer (1988) suggest that instructional psychology is closely related to the enhancement of learning and found that students with higher motivation and a positive attitude are more engaged in their studies and tend to perform better in related tasks and assessments. According to their research, most students with a higher educational background are adults who have already established fixed learning attitudes and habits, which I believe may influence their attitudes toward MOOCs, as they are the main group of people who are interested in MOOCs. Johnstone (1993) argues that good learning habits are not inherently developed and must often be taught, especially to teenagers. The ability of adolescents to take responsibility for developing their learning habits as they mature will determine how they approach new learning experiences and their behaviours during the learning process. These findings highlight the importance of understanding learners' habits and attitudes, especially as many teenage learners progress to university study, which has motivated me to analyse how these factors influence their engagement with MOOCs for this study.

The main aim of this research is to explore and analyse the challenges and benefits of MOOC learning for Chinese students, with a particular focus on how MOOCs influence their motivation, engagement, and autonomy. Understanding learner engagement in MOOCs has significant social and practical implications, potentially aiding students and teachers in recognising the value of online education. A key feature of online education is the emphasis on students' autonomous learning, which is an important reason for selecting this topic. Through my research, I aim to offer insights, particularly for students who are interested in MOOCs, encouraging them to become aware of the importance of the development of independent learning skills

and effectively utilise the Internet's vast educational resources. Building on my Master's dissertation, I seek to further analyse the factors influencing learners' motivation in MOOCs and how these courses can enhance student involvement in their studies. Specifically, I intend to explore the factors that affect students' learning habits and their awareness of learning, in relation to their previous experiences in both online and classroom settings. Additionally, I will investigate how students engage with online education. This research could help me better understand the development of MOOCs in Chinese universities and provide valuable insights for institutions aiming to address issues related to MOOC completion rates.

1.3 Research Questions

This study plans to analyse learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education. In order to examine this, the study was guided by the following research questions after a rigorous examination of the literature:

1. What are the potential challenges and benefits to Chinese students in relation to MOOC learning, with regarding to enhancing motivation, developing engagement and building autonomy?
2. In what ways have MOOCs affected aspects of teaching and learning such as traditional classroom practices and learner engagement?
3. What are the specific factors, in relation to student motivation and the development of autonomous learning, that might affect learners' engagement with their learning via MOOCs? In what ways are learners affected by this new method of learning?

4. What is the possible future of MOOCs? In what ways can MOOCs contribute to the development of stronger learner engagement in Higher Education in China in future?

5. How and in what ways did MOOCs develop a different education practice and delivery during the COVID-19 pandemic to support students' individual motivation, and engagement in their learning?

1.4 Research Aims

The research aims, which support the research questions are presented as follows:

1. To explore and analyse the potential challenges and benefits of MOOC learning for Chinese students, with a specific focus on how this affects their motivation, engagement, and autonomy.

2. To explore and analyse the impact of MOOCs on various aspects of teaching and learning, with a specific focus on how they have influenced traditional classroom practices and learner engagement.

3. To investigate the specific factors related to student motivation and the development of autonomous learning that might affect learners' engagement with MOOCs, and to understand how individual learners are impacted by this new method of learning.

4. To explore the possible future development of MOOCs and how they might contribute to the development of stronger learner engagement in Chinese Higher Education in the future, particularly through enhancing motivation and autonomy.

5. To analyse the ways in which MOOCs developed different educational practices and delivery methods during the COVID-19 pandemic to support individual student engagement in their learning.

1.5 Research Approach

This research is situated within the interpretivist paradigm, incorporating a small positivist element to examine participants' roles and experiences, allowing for the summary and analysis of factors which may affect this particular group of participants' engagement in learning via MOOCs. According to Scotland (2012), interpretivism posits that reality is subjective and varies among individuals, suggesting that research participants may offer unique interpretations rather than generalized conclusions. By adopting an interpretivist approach, researchers can gain a comprehensive understanding of specific contexts and explore the factors influencing particular developments through the collection and interpretation of qualitative data. This approach enables the generation of profound insights and conclusions that may differ from those derived from other perspectives (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). I conducted a small-scale study to gather individuals' perceptions, identifying, discussing, and analysing the findings. To address the research aims, a mixed-method approach was employed to collect in-depth information from students and teachers. Data was gathered through questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, allowing for thorough analysis based on participants' experiences and perceptions. The choice of an interpretivist paradigm with a small positivist element was intended to facilitate the collection of rich, detailed data and to analyse participants' experiences and perceptions of MOOCs. The methodology will be further developed and discussed in Chapter 4.

1.6 Outline of the Study

This study is organised into six chapters. Following this introductory chapter, Chapter 2 explores the educational context of MOOCs and reviews the relevant literature, including the introduction and background to, as well as the characteristics of MOOCs. This chapter also discusses MOOCs in relation to learning theories and examines factors influencing MOOC completion rates. Additionally, it addresses the appeal of MOOCs to Chinese university students and compares MOOCs with other online learning methods such as MALL and SPOCs. The challenges and opportunities of implementing MOOCs in China and the influence of MOOCs for Chinese learners, specifically regarding their motivation, engagement and autonomy is explored, along with the changes MOOCs have introduced. The chapter also discusses the development of MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on China's experience with online education, including policies, lessons learned, and challenges. Furthermore, English language education in China, along with MOOCs and related policies, is explored and discussed. Chapter 3 outlines the theoretical framework and methodology employed in this research, explaining the key theories that support and guide the study, demonstrating how this work builds on and extends existing research. The chapter introduces and discusses the research methodology, including the research methods, data collection tools, and the epistemological and ontological stances of the chosen paradigm. The process of data analysis is set out, along with ethical considerations and my insider position as an English major during my master's studies. Chapters 4 and 5 presents and analyses the data collected in this research. Chapter 4 focuses on the analysis of questionnaire data, while Chapter 5 examines the data from semi-structured interviews. Chapter 6 concludes the study by discussing and evaluating the findings from Chapters 4 and 5, addressing the research questions and summarising the study's implications and recommendations for the development of MOOCs in China. This chapter also reflects on the limitations of the current study

and summarises my personal growth throughout the research process. Additionally, the chapter explores the potential future of MOOCs in Chinese higher education.

1.7 Research Background of the Study

In recent years, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have gained significant attention in higher education in China. This surge in popularity has been bolstered by government support for online education as a means of expanding access to high-quality education globally (Zhang *et al.*, 2019). Research on learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education has primarily focused on identifying factors that influence engagement, such as course design, promotion by teachers and universities, and learner motivation (Jung and Lee, 2018). Additionally, previous studies have examined the relationship between learner engagement and anticipated learning outcomes, including knowledge acquisition and skill development (Impey and Formanek, 2021). Some research has also explored the potential of MOOCs to address issues of educational equity and the lack of access to higher education in China, particularly for learners in less-developed regions or those with limited financial and educational resources (Tang and Carr-Chellman, 2016).

MOOCs have already been integrated into higher education in China. Since 2013, institutions such as the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Beijing University, Tsinghua University, and the Chinese University of Hong Kong have begun offering online courses. This initiative has allowed courses from Chinese universities to reach a global audience via the Internet. In May 2013, Chinese universities made their first foray into MOOCs when lectures from Tsinghua University and Beijing University delivered courses on EdX. Fudan University and Shanghai Jiaotong University officially signed with Coursera in July of the same year.

Subsequently, more universities started to deliver MOOCs, such as Nanjing University (Zheng, Chen and Burgos, 2018).

The development of the Internet has made learning more flexible. According to Li, Li and Chen (2008), personalised education can be partially realized through online learning, with the general aim of meeting individual needs. However, MOOCs are not the final, idealized form of learning, as they make it challenging to ensure learners' autonomous study without the supervision of teachers and universities. Despite these challenges, MOOCs remain highly popular in China. Huang (2019) suggests that MOOCs may redefine the roles of universities, teachers, and even students, requiring all three to undergo change and collaborate. Although MOOCs have been regarded as an effective learning method, however, recent studies have highlighted issues such as high attrition rates and dropout rates, with some MOOCs experiencing dropout rates as high as 95% (Yousef *et al.*, 2014). A common problem across many MOOCs is that, despite initial interest and enthusiasm from learners, the lack of sufficient supervision often leads to interruptions in participants' studies, which ultimately leads to a high dropout rate of MOOCs.

Although MOOCs offer numerous advantages and potential benefits for higher education in China, low student engagement and course completion rates remain significant challenges (Nong, Buavaraporn and Punnakitikashem, 2022), which is a trend observed in other countries as well. Therefore, researchers have been investigating the factors that may influence MOOC engagement in Chinese higher education, intending to enhance teaching strategies to improve learner participation and completion rates. Therefore, this study aims to investigate and examine students' engagement with MOOCs in higher education in China. In order to address gaps in the existing research, I selected the research participants from two different groups to

gain insights into Chinese university students' MOOC learning experiences and analysed their motivation for engaging with MOOCs. By exploring learner engagement with MOOCs in higher education in China, I intended to investigate factors that affect learner engagement and draw conclusions about how to increase learner motivation in MOOCs. In addition, I explored participants' perceptions of MOOC learning at their universities to find out how students view the possible future of MOOCs, ultimately making recommendations for the development and promotion of MOOCs in Chinese higher education.

1.8 Significance of the Study

The analysis of the chosen topic will contribute to the future development of MOOCs in China, which may have significant implications for scholars and universities in designing and delivering MOOCs. This research could contribute to increasing learner engagement with MOOCs in higher education in China by summarising and analysing the learners' experiences of MOOCs. While there are limitations such as the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic, the research method resulted in me having to change the planned interviews with participants from face-to-face to online. These changes do not diminish the value of the findings; instead, they highlight areas for future research. In conclusion, this research addresses the gap in the literature regarding MOOCs and Chinese learner engagement, providing a foundation for future studies and informing the potential future development of MOOCs in China.

This thesis also makes theoretical contributions by refining existing theories related to learner engagement in the context of MOOCs and higher education. The theoretical framework adopted in this study emphasises that learners' awareness of their learning processes is more important than the courses themselves. What is important for the learners is not the courses, but how they engage in the courses, and how they develop

an understanding of what helps them to engage in the courses. The attempt by students to change "focusing on teaching" to "focusing on learning" can be challenging, as it requires students to take the initiative in acquiring knowledge, which provides a clear direction for this study to analyse MOOC learning. Guided by this theoretical framework, the thesis discusses and analyses learner engagement with MOOCs and offers recommendations to students on autonomous learning. The theory of Mackness, Mak and William (2010), which guided this thesis, was based on the research in the background of Iran. This thesis extended and developed this theory and applied it to the context of Chinese higher education.

Before this research, I believe there was a gap in the scholarly literature with regard to learner awareness of autonomous learning in the context of MOOCs within Chinese higher education. This thesis closes this gap by providing new insights, data, and evidence on this topic, offering a foundation for future research in this area. The study also examines access to MOOCs during the remarkable period of the COVID-19 pandemic, contributing to the understanding of how MOOCs have developed in this context. Unexpected elements, such as the impact on the delivery, method and content of the COVID-19 pandemic, emerged during the research. The result has been the introduction of significant changes in education, including the rapid expansion of online learning. Within this transformed landscape, one of the key contributions of this research lies in the contextual insights it provides. There has previously been a limited exploration of learner awareness of autonomous learning within this new educational environment. My research uncovers new insights and offers a more recent perspective on the state of awareness of autonomous learning in Chinese universities, particularly those offering MOOCs. The study captures the unique challenges and opportunities presented by the pandemic in terms of learner engagement and autonomous learning awareness.

1.9 Summary

This research focuses on analysing learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education. This chapter has provided a comprehensive introduction to the study, outlining its rationale, aims, and research questions. The chapter has also discussed the significance of MOOCs in the broader context of higher education in China, highlighting the potential benefits and challenges associated with their implementation. Furthermore, the chapter has introduced the research methodology, situating the study within the interpretivist paradigm while incorporating a small positivist element to ensure a thorough analysis of participants' experiences which situates the experience of the participants in preparation for the individual interviews. The study's mixed-method approach, comprising questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, has facilitated the collection of rich, detailed data. This chapter, thus, sets the stage for the subsequent chapters by establishing the study's purpose and framework, which guides the investigation of learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education.

Chapter 2: MOOCs and the Literature

This chapter will focus on the literature and academic sources related to MOOCs and learner engagement, MOOCs and completion rates, MOOCs and MALL and the attractions of MOOCs to learners, which will inform the discussion central to this study. By summarising and analysing the literature, much of the relevant information informed my approach as the research, enabled me to consider the issues in depth, and related the literature to the findings which will arise from the participant data.

2.1 What are MOOCs?

MOOCs, or Massive Open Online Courses, represent a significant advancement in educational opportunities enabled by the Internet (Deng, Benckendorff and Gannaway, 2019). These courses are designed to be accessible to the general public via the Internet, catering to the needs of distance learning and can also supplement the needs of the traditional classroom, or in-person learning. As noted by Deng, Benckendorff, and Gannaway (2019), MOOCs are a recent development in remote education, evolving from the use of open educational resources. Daniel (2012) further asserts that MOOCs are not merely a collection of online courses, but a platform for connecting lecturers and learners globally around common topics or themes. MOOCs are generally open to all, with minimal prerequisites for learners. Most courses provide a basic structure, including a general timetable, topics, regular lectures, assignments, discussions, and reading seminars. MOOCs cover a wide range of subjects and disciplines, and many platforms or special courses offer certificates of completion to learners who meet specific requirements or pass exams (Toven-Lindsey, Rhoads and Lozano, 2015).

Many MOOCs are free and accessible to anyone with an internet connection, without geographical restrictions (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2016). These courses integrate various social networking tools and digital resources to form diverse learning tools and rich courses and create a multi-learning environment, that is, an educational setting that combines traditional classroom methods with digital, online learning platforms to enhance student engagement, and promote autonomous learning, meeting different learning styles and needs (Zhang, 2018). According to Hollands and Tirthali (2014), MOOCs enable more learners to access high-quality educational resources by "sharing renowned teachers and excellent courses". The basic teaching components of MOOCs as well as face-to-face instruction from the academic delivering the course often include short videos and interactive exercises among students. Their evaluation and assessment methods remain similar to those of offline courses. Most of the MOOCs delivered on online platforms are free, and only some of the courses are available as a fee-based service called 'Signature Track', which learners can purchase at their own discretion (Manzoor, 2015). Typically, MOOCs do not offer academic credits and do not count towards undergraduate or postgraduate degrees. However, learners continue to participate, valuing the educational content and hoping that accreditation may be offered in the future, which may further enhance their engagement (Rai and Chunrao, 2016).

In China, the typical duration of a MOOC is eight to ten weeks, with each course module delivered through ten to twenty-minute micro-videos that explain specific concepts, principles, or topics (Li *et al.*, 2022). To maintain learner engagement and minimise distractions in online learning, these videos often include embedded questions for the course participants that encourage students to concentrate their attention. Thus, the MOOC platform also features robust interactive functions, enabling communication between students and teachers through forums as part of the course delivery. The system automatically corrects responses to objective questions,

while subjective questions or essays are evaluated through assignments. The platform also analyses common problems and offers suggestions for improvement (Li *et al.*, 2022).

Globally recognised MOOC platforms include Coursera, edX, and in China, the Chinese University MOOC. These platforms aggregate high-quality courses from prestigious universities worldwide, providing extensive learning opportunities for users. Learners can gain knowledge and earn certification by completing assignments and online exams. As a pioneering model of online education, MOOCs have significantly expanded access to educational resources, promoting educational equity and facilitating global knowledge sharing (Ossiannilsson, 2021).

2.2 Background to MOOCs

Although MOOCs have a relatively short history, their development spans a longer period. Bardini (2000) noted that, in 1962, American inventor and knowledge innovator Douglas Engelbart proposed a research project titled “Enhancing Human Intelligence: A Conceptual Framework at the Stanford Research Institute.” In this project, Engelbart emphasised the potential of using computers as collaborative tools to enhance learners' intelligence. The research also advocated for the widespread dissemination of personal computers and discussed how they could be integrated with interconnected computer networks to create a global, effective information-sharing phenomenon (Engelbart, English and Evans, 1969).

Following this, numerous computer enthusiasts and educational researchers published academic articles and studies promoting the idea of opening up the educational process through the application of computer technology. They argued that this

approach could transform the existing educational system, which they perceived as flawed (Grudin, 2018). Berezytskyi and Oleksyuk (2016) observed that since 2008, a significant number of educators from institutions such as the University of Mary Washington and York College of the City University of New York have adopted online course structures and successfully launched their own MOOCs. This demonstrates the potential of MOOCs to be utilised by academics.

The most significant breakthrough occurred in the autumn of 2011, when 160,000 people from around the world registered for Stanford University's free course, "Introduction to Artificial Intelligence." This period also witnessed the establishment of the three major MOOC platforms, the Udacity, Coursera, and edX, becoming a significant milestone in the expansion of MOOCs within the educational landscape (Gore, 2014).

2.2.1 The Early Period of MOOC Development

According to Zhang and Gao (2018), an early prototype of the massive open online course (MOOC) was taught at Utah State University in August 2007. This postgraduate course, initially comprising only five participants, was later opened to a global audience, attracting 50 students from eight countries. This marked the beginning of widespread participation in MOOCs, which eventually expanded worldwide, including in China. Thus, MOOCs ushered in a new phase of educational development.

During this period, the concept of MOOCs was primarily influenced by the Open Educational Resources (OER) movement and the trend for connectivist learning, which emphasises the role of networks in the acquisition and sharing of knowledge

and believes that learning happens through the creation of connections between information sources, learners, and technology (Goldie, 2016). However, the precise origins of MOOCs remain a subject of debate. Some evidence suggests that MOOCs first originated in Canada. For example, in 2008, George Siemens and Stephen Downes of Athabasca University in Canada introduced the concept of cMOOCs (connectivist MOOCs), which were based on a connectivist theoretical model of learning (Wang, Anderson and Chen, 2018).

Despite this, the United States has played an important role in the development of MOOCs. In 2012, Stanford University launched the Class2Go platform, which significantly contributed to the growth and development of MOOCs. Additionally, top U.S. universities rapidly developed leading MOOC platforms such as Udacity, Coursera, and edX, which became the world's three largest MOOC providers. Overall, the early development of MOOCs evolved from the Open Educational Resources movement in connectivist learning, initially proposed by Professor David Wiley at Utah State University in the United States, and then further developed and refined in Canada. These early initiatives laid the foundation for the subsequent global dissemination and application of MOOCs.

2.2.2 The Development Period of MOOCs

A significant breakthrough in massive open online courses happened in the autumn of 2011, when over 160,000 people enrolled in an artificial intelligence course offered through a newly established lab, now known as Udacity. In 2012, top universities in the United States began creating online learning platforms and offering free courses. The emergence of the three major MOOC platforms, Coursera, Udacity, and edX greatly expanded opportunities for systematic and autonomous learning (Pappano, 2012).

After 2014, an increasing number of top universities outside the United States began offering MOOCs. Some MOOC providers planned collaborations with prestigious universities in Canada, Mexico, Europe, China, Singapore, Japan, and Australia, while also expanding partnerships with additional American institutions (Kang, 2020). Coursera, one of the prominent MOOC providers based in California, USA, added four languages of instruction for MOOCs in Chinese, French, Spanish and Italian, to provide about 90 new courses in the coming months. Czerniewicz *et al.* (2014) noted that the co-founder of Stanford University recognised that offering instruction in multiple languages would enable a broader range of students to access their courses through MOOCs.

2.3 MOOCs and Learning Theories

MOOCs can be analysed and evaluated through various learning theories, including behaviourism, cognitivism, constructivism, and connectivism, to understand their development (Kesim and Altinpulluk, 2015). Two main types of large-scale open network courses have emerged: cMOOCs and xMOOCs. cMOOCs require learners to exercise significant autonomy, attracting those interested in personal or professional development. This model is closely related to social learning theories, such as social constructivism. In contrast, xMOOCs, developed by prominent American universities, are guided by behaviourist learning theory (Kennedy, 2013).

These two MOOC models involve and support different learner groups, employ different teaching approaches, and utilise varied instructional methods (Watted and Barak, 2024). For example, xMOOCs are more commonly delivered through media platforms. The key difference between cMOOCs and xMOOCs lies in their educational focus: cMOOCs emphasise the importance of creativity, autonomy, and

social network learning, while xMOOCs rely on traditional learning methods such as video presentations and tests (Kesim and Altınpulluk, 2015). In other words, cMOOCs prioritise knowledge creation and generation, whereas xMOOCs focus more on knowledge duplication and delivery. The difference between the focus points of xMOOCs and cMOOCs influences teachers' course delivery methods selection. Courses that demand creativity and practical application may be more suited to the cMOOC model, while subjects that require knowledge accumulation, such as English language learning or literature, might align better with the xMOOC model (Watted and Barak, 2024). It further influences learners' course selection and engagement.

However, it is possible that MOOC developers may not be fully familiar with Chinese teaching content, and students in Chinese higher education may lack experience in selecting appropriate courses.

2.4 Characteristics of MOOCs

This thesis aims to analyse the characteristics of MOOCs in order to help learners better understand and engage with these courses. MOOCs are primarily offered by universities or online learning platforms and are designed to serve a large number of students simultaneously. In recent years, MOOCs have gained popularity in China due to their accessibility, flexibility, and other advantages. Some key characteristics of MOOCs can be summarised as follows:

Firstly, MOOCs provide rich resources. According to Abeer and Miri (2014), MOOCs cover a wide range of subjects and academic disciplines, including computer science, mathematics, and English language learning. Learners can choose from various courses offered by different instructors or platforms, thereby enriching their learning

experiences. MOOCs are capable of offering diverse resources by integrating multiple social networking tools and various forms of digital content, creating a comprehensive curriculum resource platform for learners (Ko and Rossen, 2017). These resources often include short videos and interactive exercises aimed at participants, making teaching and learning both richer and more flexible. Additionally, most MOOCs are either free or available at a low cost, significantly reducing financial barriers to accessing high-quality educational resources.

Secondly, MOOCs are characterised by their high degree of flexibility as well as they are easy to use. Unlike traditional classroom teaching, which is constrained by time and space, MOOCs allow learners from around the world to access courses from prestigious universities at any time and from any location. This flexibility enables learners to register and participate in MOOCs autonomously, accessing course materials, lectures, and assignments entirely online. The ability to study at one's own pace allows learners to start and complete courses according to their individual schedules, catering to the needs of participants from different geographic regions and time zones. Given these characteristics, the literature consulted has led to the development of the second research question: In what ways have MOOCs affected aspects of teaching and learning such as traditional classroom practices and learner engagement?

MOOCs offer open access to a diverse range of learners. They provide opportunities for learners from various educational backgrounds, financial situations, and geographic locations to access high-quality educational courses and resources at no cost or minimal cost. According to Ramirez-Asis *et al.* (2022), the characteristics of no restrictions on the number of participants and indeed of geographic location enable MOOCs to support lifelong learning, enabling learners to be educated at any time and

place. The ability of MOOCs to engage a large number of participants with no enrolment limits also broadens the reach to a wider learning community.

Moreover, MOOCs effectively utilise short periods of time. As noted by Andone *et al.* (2015), MOOCs, as a new teaching model, differ significantly from traditional classroom delivery. The courses are typically delivered in short video segments, allowing students to engage with the content during their own time, including brief moments of spare time. This structure is a powerful and innovative feature of MOOCs, as it enables students to make the most of limited time (Yuan and Powell, 2013). This learning method emphasises learner autonomy and requires strong self-discipline and independent learning skills to enable full participation on the part of the students. Additionally, MOOCs are able to offer personalisation of learning services, such as adapting content to an individual's learning ability and progression, as well as interests. MOOCs usually include a large number of interactive elements, such as real-time discussions, assignments and quizzes, which enhance the potential for interactivity in the online classroom and the timeliness of feedback for participants.

Another significant feature of MOOCs is their subject diversity. MOOCs cover a wide range of disciplines, including computer science, mathematics, social sciences, business, arts, and languages (Abeer and Miri, 2014). This diversity allows learners to find courses that match their interests or educational needs, supporting or enhancing their primary learning goals. MOOCs deliver high-quality learning resources globally through online platforms, facilitating the sharing and dissemination of knowledge. For example, MOOC platforms such as Coursera and edX assembled a large number of free, high-quality courses from prestigious international institutions, providing learners with abundant educational resources. In this context, MOOCs emphasise both learner autonomy and diversity, enabling students to select courses based on their

individual interests and needs. This allows for personalised learning experiences, as students can choose from a broad spectrum of courses that cater to their preferences and educational objectives.

Jung (2019) noted that MOOCs are grounded in theories of connectivism and the open pedagogy of networked learning. These open online courses can follow a structured progression similar to traditional classroom courses, guiding students from beginner to advanced levels. MOOC platforms offer a wide range of courses across various educational levels, including introductory courses for beginners, intermediate courses, and advanced courses. Depending on learners' needs and objectives, MOOCs can provide foundational knowledge for students, advanced skills, or specialised training for professionals. As a product of the "Internet + education" paradigm discussed by Zhao (2022), MOOCs have profoundly impacted the traditional higher education model. They challenge the conventional practice of knowledge transmission within schools by introducing a new mode of knowledge dissemination and learning. This innovative teaching model has not only transformed educational concepts, education systems, and teaching methods but has also redefined the role of universities. For example, universities are no longer serving only on-campus students. Through MOOCs, they act as global educators, offering online courses to millions of learners worldwide, which broaden their influence and reputation. Universities also increasingly collaborate with companies and other institutions to create digital learning content. This collaboration has redefined them as producers of educational resources.

Moreover, with the development of artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies, MOOCs continue to evolve and improve. The integration of these technologies into the education context enhances the quality and efficiency of

MOOCs and drives the future transformation of education. MOOCs are not only a significant force for educational change but also serve as an important way for cultural communication and development on a national level, for example, they contribute to the balanced development of education by addressing disparities between urban and rural areas and helping to resolve issues related to unequal access to education. All students are welcome, from any area or background. Furthermore, the MOOC platform may evolve into a national educational infrastructure, further solidifying its status within the education system.

MOOCs also cater to learners' interests and career advancement (Impey and Formanek, 2021), offering opportunities for professional development and career enhancement. According to Honea, Castro, and Peter (2017), some MOOC platforms provide courses focused on specific job-related skills, industry-specific knowledge, and career advancement strategies. Certain MOOCs are even designed in collaboration with industry partners to ensure that the course structure is clear and comprehensible, and that the content is both relevant and current with job market demands. Many courses also include assignments related to the course material and practical exercises, such as mock interviews, to help learners develop their professional skills.

The characteristics of MOOCs, therefore, extend beyond the change of educational modes, the sharing of educational resources, and the promotion of learner autonomy and diversity. They also encompass aspects such as technology-driven development, market potential, evolving trends, social impact, and cultural dissemination (Chang, Gütl and Ebner, 2018). However, MOOCs face challenges that require continuous improvement and refinement. For example, the quality of MOOCs can be difficult to ensure, and the lack of teacher supervision of students can lead to issues such as

cheating during quizzes and exams. Additionally, fostering creativity and critical thinking ability, and collaboration among students remain important issues that future educators must take into consideration when developing MOOCs further.

Despite the numerous advantages of MOOCs, it is important to acknowledge that one of the characteristics of MOOCs is their low completion rates. While MOOCs have high enrolment numbers, they also experience significant dropout rates (Yousef *et al.*, 2014). For detailed analysis of completion rates and MOOCs, please see section 2.7, and for China, 2.12 below.

2.5 MOOCs and Learning Models

MOOCs promote a rethinking of the roles and interactions among learners, instructors, institutional providers, and the outcomes of collective learning activities. Early discussions around MOOCs emphasised the new roles and responsibilities of learners in a networked learning environment, where all the participants contributed to the share of knowledge (Downes, 2012). These courses were highly experimental and were considered groundbreaking because they enabled learners, rather than teachers or experts, to determine the course of learning. Designed with a network approach to education, often referred to as the connective or cMOOC model, these courses view individuals as nodes within a digital network, where connections between nodes represent learning. Learners construct knowledge by creating and sharing content such as blog posts, microblogs, or other forms of media, which can then be commented on or edited by peers and experts. This connective approach parallels constructivist theories, where learners actively build knowledge with guidance from more experienced individuals.

In contrast, instructivist pedagogical practices within MOOCs ensure that the teachers are the primary source of knowledge, assembling learning artefacts for students to use. These instructivist MOOCs are known as xMOOCs and aim to provide anyone, anywhere with access to the same or similar type of formal education typically experienced on university campuses. xMOOCs are designed around online versions of traditional lectures, readings, and discussions. However, the online application of these teaching methods differs qualitatively from the on-campus experience. Many universities have shifted from teacher-centred courses with predefined materials to learner-centred approaches, where students can learn from one another (Otukile-Mongwaketse, 2018).

The connective approach (cMOOCs) can be seen as more democratic than traditional online learning methods (xMOOCs) because it emphasises the importance of the learner, rather than the teacher, assembling and sharing knowledge. However, cMOOCs may not always acquire democratic participation, as they assume that all learners are equipped with the necessary cognitive, behavioural, and affective characteristics to navigate their own learning pathways. Research indicates that not all learners possess the digital capability, confidence, or self-efficacy required to fully engage in this model (Littlejohn *et al.*, 2016). Thus, the focus on the individual as an active learning agent may advantage those already equipped perhaps from previous experience of education to learn autonomously.

cMOOCs are aligned with the "principles of connectivism, openness, and participatory teaching" (Jacoby, 2014, p76), and they emphasise "human agency, user participation, and creativity within a dynamic network of connections enabled by online technology" (Ebben and Murphy, 2014, p333). These courses were developed as platforms for collaborative knowledge construction, where learners self-organise

their participation according to their learning goals, prior knowledge, and common interests. Conversely, xMOOCs follow a more traditional instructional model rooted in cognitivist-behaviourist approaches (Hew and Cheung, 2014), focusing on content delivery through video presentations, readings, and automated assessments (Bayne and Ross, 2014). Learners who prefer xMOOCs often value the structure and predictability of traditional pedagogical methods.

Three key discussion points emerge from this exploration of MOOCs for English language teachers: the distinction between cMOOCs and xMOOCs, the wide variation within xMOOCs, and the implications of this variation (Mohamed and Hammond, 2018). While MOOCs are commonly classified as either cMOOCs or xMOOCs, this distinction may not always be helpful, particularly in the context of teacher education. Many professional development courses for teachers resemble xMOOCs, relying on instructional design models within a single platform. These courses typically use structured, centralised content created by course designers, a pattern evident in platforms like Coursera, Udacity, edX, and Future Learn. The two types of MOOCs differ in several key aspects, including the types of media used, the degree of networking and interaction, the use of discussion forums, and the level of openness in course materials (Mohamed and Hammond, 2018). At the beginning, cMOOCs were a disruptive approach to teaching and learning, which appears to have been integrated into a more traditional instructional model (xMOOCs). This trend may reflect a broader pattern in the history of information and communication technology, where technology is assimilated rather than adapted to fundamentally new approaches. While cMOOCs are not necessarily better than xMOOCs, one explanation is that xMOOCs align more closely with the expectations of both designers and learners. For example, in Chinese universities, xMOOCs are often preferred because they focus on teacher-centred teaching, which aligns with traditional learning habits. In summary, cMOOCs adhere to open-learning principles, promoting learner interaction within an

open network where participants collaboratively construct knowledge. In contrast, xMOOCs typically employ a more conventional, teacher-centred pedagogical approach (De Lima and Zorrilla, 2017). cMOOCs are based on connectivism, which emphasises learning as a networked process that integrates and shares knowledge across connections (Downes, 2012), thus challenging traditional cognitivist learning models by redefining learning as an inherently networked activity.

While both cMOOCs and xMOOCs are widely used, they differ significantly in their teaching methods and philosophies (Luo, Zhou and Li, 2018). cMOOCs emphasise open learning, cooperation, and interaction among participants, making them suitable for courses that require active participation and collaboration, such as those in the humanities, social sciences, and creative arts. On the other hand, xMOOCs adopt a more structured, teacher-centred approach, making them appropriate for subjects requiring the large-scale delivery of knowledge, providing course videos, tests and other learning materials to enable students to learn according to predetermined learning routes, so that they are suitable for courses such as engineering, business, and science.

The differences between cMOOCs and xMOOCs also extend to their learning approaches. cMOOCs emphasise social interaction and collaborative learning, with teachers providing content while students construct knowledge through dialogue and social media engagement. In contrast, xMOOCs emphasise individual learning and autonomous learning, using video lectures and real-time assessments to promote student learning (Li, Du and Yu, 2024). xMOOCs also leverage big data to track student progress and provide personalised learning recommendations.

When designing MOOCs, it is necessary to consider the diverse backgrounds, motivations, and learning styles of students. Teachers who design MOOCs as part of their classes should adopt a variety of teaching methods to meet these diverse needs, combining resources like textbooks, online multimedia, and teaching videos to enrich platform functionality and support different learning modes. Additionally, MOOC design should focus on online classroom interaction, encourage participatory learning, and stimulate student interest to improve the quality of teaching. Both cMOOCs and xMOOCs should continue to innovate and evolve to meet the needs and preferences of diverse learners.

2.6 The Appeal of MOOCs to Chinese University Learners

2.6.1 The Appeal of Certification

As Knowlton (2000) points out, traditional online classrooms have largely centred on the transfer and dissemination of knowledge, with formal recognition of learning, such as certification, being tied exclusively to university attendance. In this conventional model, students must enrol in a university, complete a full course, and pass a final exam to earn a certificate. This approach posed significant barriers for those unable to commit to full-time, in-person study. However, the rise of MOOC platforms like Coursera and edX has fundamentally transformed the landscape of higher education, especially in China, where access to prestigious institutions can be highly competitive.

MOOCs offer an alternative way for participants to access to and get certification, which is particularly appealing to Chinese university learners. These platforms allow students to enrol in courses from top universities worldwide, access high-quality content, and earn certification upon course completion, often for free or at low cost.

Wang (2018) notes that the ability to earn a certificate by connecting to the Internet, passing the final exam, and paying a small fee is highly beneficial for learners. For many Chinese learners, this model offers flexibility and access that traditional educational structures may lack. The certification from reputable institutions also carries significant value in the job market, where employers may view these credentials as a mark of expertise and self-discipline.

According to Hossain (2023), the appeal of certification in MOOCs also offers Chinese learners the opportunity to engage in lifelong learning, acquire skills on demand, and enhance their employability without the need to enrol in a full-time curriculum. Furthermore, with China's increasingly competitive job market, certification from well-known global universities can add credibility to a candidate's profile, offering a competitive edge that traditional Chinese universities may not always be able to provide.

2.6.2 The Appeal of Educational Equity

Ma and Lee (2019) highlight that learning via MOOCs presents a significant opportunity for many students, particularly those facing limited educational resources. This includes learners from remote regions who lack teaching resources and those from poor families who cannot afford additional tuition, a common practice in China. According to Yuan and Powell (2013), most of the MOOC platforms, both domestic and international, are now free to access, allowing learners to obtain higher education from top universities around the world and thus achieve greater educational equity. Daphne Koller, a computer scientist from Stanford University, referred to this as "real democracy in higher education" (Afsari-Mamagani, 2014).

Laurillard (2016) also notes that MOOCs have facilitated high-quality resource sharing, maximising the benefits for learners. Through online courses, renowned professors and scholars from prestigious universities worldwide can teach and assist students in solving learning challenges independently. These well-designed and produced courses are accessible to students at home for free, offering a level of quality that can rival traditional classroom education. However, it is important to note that issues related to low completion rates can affect the overall effectiveness of MOOCs.

2.6.3 The Appeal of Networking and Global Collaboration

MOOCs offer Chinese students the opportunity to engage in the global learning environment, which is attractive for many learners. Freire (2020) believes that MOOC platforms such as Coursera and edX can support interaction among students from all over the world, enabling learners to engage in discussions, group work, and peer assessments with individuals from diverse cultural and academic backgrounds. This exposure to global perspectives can broaden students' understanding of their academic areas and enhance their critical thinking abilities and problem-solving skills. Moreover, MOOCs can encourage networking opportunities for both peers and instructors. According to Voudoukis and Pagiatakis (2022), MOOCs provide a platform for learners to build international networks that can lead to future academic collaborations or professional opportunities. For Chinese students, who may not have frequent opportunities to study abroad or interact with international scholars, MOOCs offer a valuable gateway to global academic networks.

2.6.4 The Appeal of Lifelong Learning and Skills Development

MOOCs support the growing trend for lifelong learning, where individuals can continue to acquire new knowledge and skills outside universities and even throughout their lives. For Chinese university learners, MOOCs provide an opportunity to engage in continuous education beyond their formal degree programmes. Lifelong learning is increasingly valued in China's competitive job market, where employers seek candidates with current skills and knowledge. In addition, it can also meet the learning needs of older people, who may have missed opportunities to learn when they were young.

As Ossiannilsson (2021) highlights, MOOCs offer a flexible and accessible way for learners to acquire new skills, follow industry trends, and adapt to the rapidly changing demands of career development. This focus on lifelong learning is beneficial to Chinese students, who recognise the importance of continuous skills development in maintaining their employability in a competitive global economy.

2.7 Factors Influencing MOOC Completion Rates Internationally

MOOCs do have lower completion rates, a phenomenon that has been confirmed in several studies and reports. For example, statistics from the Graduate School of the University of Pennsylvania, based on 16 courses offered through Coursera, indicate that only 4% of enrolled students completed their courses. Additionally, other studies report that MOOC completion rates typically fall below 5% (Evans, Baker and Dee, 2016). However, some research suggests that completion rates may be higher in certain regions or with specific types of MOOCs. For example, a study conducted by the University of Washington found that MOOC completion rates were higher in

developing countries or regions, indicating that educational backgrounds and learning environments significantly impact MOOC completion rates.

There may be several reasons for the low completion rates of MOOCs. Firstly, the massive openness of MOOCs is one of their distinguishing features, which also attracts a large number of unsolicited learners who may lack the motivation or time to complete the courses. Secondly, various elements such as learner characteristics, course content, and the platform itself may influence MOOC completion rates. For example, some MOOCs may be too simple or taught in a boring way, which can also lead to a loss of student interest and motivation (Kennedy, 2013). Completing MOOC courses requires strong self-directed learning abilities, which not all students possess. A lot of learners who study MOOCs encounter problems, even those who are motivated to learn through MOOCs may struggle with issues such as less teacher supervision, frequent interruptions, and concentration challenges, all of which contribute to higher dropout rates. Although MOOCs are increasingly integrated into Chinese universities, there is currently no standardised regulation governing their use in Chinese higher education, which is discussed in this section.

2.7.1 MOOC Completion Rates, Currently

MOOCs have been observed to have lower engagement and completion rates compared to traditional courses, and the reasons for this are complex and varied. Ferrari-Lagos, Martinez-Abad and Ruiz (2020) identify several challenges that learners face when engaging with MOOCs, including lower learning motivation, unclear learning objectives, and untimely feedback.

Recent studies have shown that attrition and dropout rates in MOOCs can be as high as 95% (Yousef *et al.*, 2014). According to Veletsianos (2020), a survey conducted in China revealed that while the number of MOOC users grew to about 650,000 in the previous year, the dropout rate remains a significant challenge, with an estimated 75% of learners failing to complete their courses. Similarly, international data indicate that up to 90% of MOOC students do not complete their courses, with a University of Pennsylvania study reporting a dropout rate of 96%. The Guokr MOOC Academy, a popular Chinese MOOC platform, released a survey showing that only 6% of users completed all their courses, 15% completed some courses, and 67% did not finish a single course. Furthermore, the 2020 World MOOCs Conference reported that only 3.3% of MOOCs have more than 100,000 enrolments, highlighting the ongoing challenges in maintaining engagement and completion.

2.7.2 Learning Theories Affecting MOOC Completion Rates

There are theories that guided and affected MOOC completion rates. The theory of continuous use of information systems seeks to determine whether users will continue to engage with information technology after they first adoption (Bhattacharjee, Perols and Sanford, 2008). These researchers believed that although the initial adoption of information technology by users is important to the success of that technology, the ultimate success of information technology depends more on continuous engagement by users and proposed the Expectation-Confirmation Model (ECM), which suggests that the perceived usefulness and satisfaction of a system are key factors influencing users' continued engagement. This model has been widely used in China e-commerce such as online banking, digital learning platforms and academic blogs (Chen, Lai and Ho, 2015). In the context of MOOC learning, a learner's first impression, influenced by their expectations and initial experience, plays a critical role in their willingness to continue using the platform.

However, with the increasing use of the Expectation-confirmation model, scholars have found that the ECM does not fully explain user behaviour in specialised areas like online gaming, online learning, mobile learning, and social media (Sorebo, Halvari and Gulli, 2009). The ECM primarily considers extrinsic motivation factors, such as performance improvement, rewards, and punishment, while ignoring intrinsic motivation factors like interest, challenge, enjoyment, and attention. When applied to MOOCs in Chinese higher education, this suggests that course design should focus on aligning with learners' expectations for certification and credit to improve completion rates.

In contrast, Self-Determination Theory (SDT) posits that intrinsic motivation has a greater impact on the sustainability of user behaviour than extrinsic motivation (Ryan and Deci, 2000). Self-determination theory (SDT) asserts that motivation, whether extrinsic or intrinsic, directly influences individual behaviour. Extrinsic motivation is driven by external rewards or avoidance of negative outcomes such as pursuing achievements or avoiding punishment (Ryan and Deci, 2000), while intrinsic motivation is fueled by personal interest, challenge, and enjoyment in the learning process. Zheng *et al.* (2015) discuss how learners' motivations for engaging with MOOCs often include fulfilling current needs, preparing for their future career, satisfying curiosity, connecting with other people, or accessing subjects of interest, and all of which are directly relevant to this study.

Ryan and Deci (2000) found that intrinsic motivation leads to better persistence, performance, and satisfaction compared to extrinsic motivation. Self-determination theory (SDT) also highlights three basic psychological needs, autonomy, competence, and relatedness, that influence whether intrinsic or extrinsic motivation will dominate.

Autonomy refers to the desire to initiate and manage one's own behaviour. The increase in self-support is conducive to the improvement of the individual's intrinsic motivation (Ryan and Deci, 2000). It reflects the degree of individual self-support when people participate in certain activities (Behzadnia and FatahModares, 2023); competence refers to the individual desire to feel influential or have control in achieving important results (Deci and Ryan, 1980), which indicates that people are more efficient in interacting or performing in the learning environment (Bandura, 1989); and relatedness pertains to the need for a sense of belonging and support from others or to remain relevant to them (Deci and Ryan, 1980). which requires the support and attention of important people who may be managers, parents, teachers, and team members. Self-determination theory is widely used in the study of individual motivation in learning and education, physical education and sports science, organisational management, and the use of information technology (Roca and Gagne, 2008). In MOOC learning, these factors can significantly influence participation and completion rates, particularly among Chinese learners, who may be motivated by their desires, interests, and learning environment. Once the MOOCs satisfy most of their needs, learners' motivation should increase along with the MOOC completion rates.

The issue of low MOOC engagement and completion rates has garnered significant attention. White *et al.* (2015) argue that learners' lack of autonomy contributes to insufficient initiative. They noted that the rapid increase in courses and enrolments has exacerbated the crisis of quality within MOOCs, such as poor learner experiences, and ineffective interaction and feedback between teachers and learners which make personalised learning more difficult on such a large scale and may cause a lower MOOC completion rate. This concern led to the development of the third research question: What are the specific factors, in relation to student motivation and the development of autonomous learning, that might affect learners' engagement with

their learning via MOOCs? In what ways are learners affected by this new method of learning?

Autonomous learning in MOOCs primarily refers to students independently using resources organised by teachers (Boud, 2012). MOOC instructors focus on distance education and answering students' questions; especially in situations when teachers and students are in different places, student-centred autonomous learning is really important. While this method offers benefits like lower costs, faster implementation, and higher flexibility, it also presents challenges, including reduced interaction between learners and teachers, a diminished learning atmosphere, and higher demands for student autonomy (Woolf, 2010).

In order to succeed in MOOCs and as well as other mobile-assisted learning methods conducted online, learners must be highly autonomous and self-disciplined (Rosell-Aguilar, 2018). Although MOOCs provide flexibility and convenience, allowing students to choose courses that fit their schedules, they may not adequately support learners' pacing or timely feedback from instructors and peers. Learners may not know where to continue and how to learn when they are left alone, without the support and supervision of teachers. During the COVID-19 pandemic, MOOCs became the preferred choice for many universities, enabling social distancing and continued education. However, MOOCs also reduced teacher-student interaction, as effective MOOC participation only requires internet access and a digital device such as mobile and laptop. Traditional classroom interactions, which foster communication and discussion, are often lacking in MOOCs, potentially affecting students' communication abilities (Yu, 2015).

Yuan and Powell (2013) emphasise that MOOCs, as a popular form of open online learning, demand greater learner autonomy. Mackness, Mak, and Williams (2010) found that autonomy, diversity, openness, and interactivity are key characteristics of MOOC classes. Through MOOCs, students can develop self-learning awareness and discover effective learning methods that integrate online and traditional classroom learning. They believe it is more important for learners to notice the learning methods and the significance is greater than the courses themselves. Nosratinia and Deris (2015) suggest that this shift from "focusing on teaching" to "focusing on learning" encourages students to take initiative in acquiring knowledge, fostering independence and reducing reliance on teacher instruction.

MOOCs, therefore, should always provide sufficient content in each video course module to ensure learners gain value from the courses. Benson and Voller (2014) argue that passive learning is less effective, particularly given the time constraints in traditional classroom settings. In Chinese universities, a typical semester includes 16 weeks of classroom teaching, with limited hours per week and each course is only delivered once or twice a week. Although MOOCs may be shorter, they allow students to take initiative in learning, reading, thinking, and communicating, making full use of available materials and optimising their time. From this discussion, arose another research question: What are the potential challenges and benefits to Chinese students in relation to MOOC learning, with regarding to enhancing motivation, developing engagement and building autonomy?

2.7.3 The Relationship between Engagement, Motivation, and Autonomy in MOOC Learning

Jiang and Peng (2023) believe that in the context of MOOC learning, engagement, motivation, and autonomy are deeply connected and collectively shape the learners'

experiences and their learning outcomes. Autonomy, as a main feature of MOOCs, enables learners to choose how, when, and what they study freely. This self-directed learning approach allows students to tailor their learning to their own personal needs and preferences. When learners have a strong desire to access their learning, their intrinsic motivation is increased, which is important for sustaining engagement in the flexible and individual-focused MOOC environment (Lan and Hew, 2020). Students have to navigate a self-paced learning model that lacks the traditional structure of face-to-face, in-person classroom settings.

Motivation plays an important role in keeping students engaged in MOOCs, especially considering their self-directed nature. According to Fishbach and Woolley, (2022), highly motivated learners, particularly those with intrinsic motivation, for example, personal interest or enjoyment in the learning, are more likely to engage with course materials, complete tasks, and participate in discussions. Intrinsic motivation often arises when learners find personal relevance or meaning in the content they are studying, making them more motivated to stay engaged and persist in their learning. MOOCs offer a flexible learning environment, but this flexibility can lead to disengagement for learners who lack the self-discipline to navigate courses independently (Nawrot and Doucet, 2014). Both intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation act as a driving force that enables learners to make the most of the autonomy that MOOCs provide. This also highlights the potential of the unique role of motivation: while it can support learners to make the most of the autonomy MOOCs offer, its absence can lead to a lack of engagement and ultimately, lower course completion rates.

Engagement refers to the active involvement of learners in the courses, which is essential for successful learning outcomes in MOOCs. For learners to remain engaged,

they must not only be motivated but also have the autonomy to make decisions about how they interact with content. In MOOC learning, engagement is typically reflected in how consistently learners participate in activities such as watching videos, completing assignments, or interacting with peers (Pursel *et al.*, 2016). Jung and Lee (2018) suggest that the relationship between autonomy and engagement is closely mediated by motivation. When learners feel empowered to direct their learning autonomy and are motivated, their level of engagement increases, which leads to higher course completion rates and deeper learning outcomes. However, if learners struggle with maintaining motivation or lack the necessary self-regulation skills required for autonomous learning, their learning outcomes will be lower. Therefore, autonomy in MOOCs enables learners to manage their learning methods, but motivation sustains this autonomy, driving continued engagement with the material.

Wong *et al.* (2019) highlight that the relationship between engagement, motivation, and autonomy is cyclical in their research; that autonomy fosters motivation, motivation fuels engagement, and sustained engagement enhances the overall learning experience in MOOCs. In this cyclical relationship, each element, autonomy, motivation, and engagement, reinforces the others. Reeve (2009) highlights that autonomy provides the foundation for motivation, enabling learners to align their studies with their personal interests and learning needs. Motivation, whether intrinsic or extrinsic, drives learners to engage actively with the course material. Engagement, in turn, strengthens learners' connection to the course and encourages them to continue exercising their autonomy and motivation. However, this cycle can also work negatively; learners who lack motivation may struggle to stay engaged, leading to diminished autonomy and weaker learning outcomes. Therefore, understanding how these three factors interact is important for MOOC learning.

2.8 MOOC, MALL, SPOC and Other Online Learning Courses

In addition to MOOCs, other popular online learning methods are widely used in China, such as MALL (Mobile-Assisted Language Learning), SPOC (Small Private Online Courses), and flipped classrooms. Each of these methods offers distinct advantages and disadvantages within the context of higher education in China. MOOCs are favoured for their large-scale resource sharing and high degree of flexibility, but they also present challenges, such as limited interpersonal communication and low completion rates. In contrast, other online learning methods can complement MOOCs by offering different strengths, contributing to a more diverse and enriched learning experience. The choice of an online learning method should be guided by specific learning needs and goals.

2.8.1 MOOC and MALL

2.8.1.1 The Role of MALL in Online Learning

Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) refers to the use of mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablets, to support and enhance language learning (Kukulska-Hulme and Traxler, 2007). MALL contains a variety of language learning activities, including listening to audio recordings, watching videos, practising grammar and vocabulary through apps, participating in language exchange communities, and engaging with language learning games. As mobile technology becomes increasingly ubiquitous and affordable, MALL is gaining popularity. Its key advantage lies in allowing learners to engage in language learning activities anytime and anywhere, as long as they have their mobile devices with them (Yudhiantara and Nasir, 2017). Additionally, MALL offers a personalised and flexible learning method, enabling learners to select language learning activities that best suit their individual needs and preferences.

Jarvis and Achilleos (2013) state that the language teaching area of Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) has also become a new and related development of Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) Research and Technology Enhanced Language Learning (TELL) Research. This evolution has contributed to current trends in online and autonomous learning. Since mobile Internet usage surpassed traditional desktop Internet usage around 2016 (GlobalStats, 2016), the availability of mobile learning resources and tools has expanded, driven by the widespread adoption of smartphones and the fast-paced nature of modern society (Wenxiu, 2015). Consequently, the growth of MOOCs in China has paralleled the rise of mobile learning.

Azar and Nasiri (2014) recommend that learners enhance their learning by leveraging the unique characteristics of Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL). They suggest utilising small chunks of time for learning, which not only makes these brief periods more meaningful but also enables the student to learn cumulatively during this time. This ability to capitalise on short periods is a key feature of mobile learning, enabling learners to study flexibly. Lamb (2004) agrees that for learners with busy schedules, such as those working long shifts, it can be challenging to find sufficient time to study each day. Thus, utilising small chunks of time effectively addresses the problem of limited study time and ensures high-frequency language exposure (Gersten and Baker, 2000). For example, even if learners only have fifteen minutes available every two hours, they can access their learning content frequently throughout the day. Many mobile apps are designed around this concept, offering minimal daily tasks such as practicing oral English every day or memorising words and sentences. These tasks can be completed in just a few minutes, with some requiring less than five minutes, such as reciting ten words and verifying their meanings through multiple responses. Fitzgerald *et al.* (2007) assert that learning in short bursts is a small-step, high-frequency method that aligns with continuous

learning principles. In China, where universities often operate on schedules that differ from those in Western countries, beginning at eight in the morning and ending at eight at night, this incremental learning approach is particularly beneficial for Chinese MOOC learners.

Another effective MALL strategy involves students signing in daily to specific English learning apps. For Chinese MOOC learners, the voluntary and autonomous features of learning and the lack of supervision can easily lead to challenges, such as incomplete courses or neglected assignments and discussions. As Yafu (2014) notes, English language competency is developed not through the length of exposure to the target language but through the frequency of exposure. Consequently, some mobile learning apps, like the reading app "Mint Reading," incorporate a check-in function that helps learners monitor their progress. Even if an app lacks this feature, Chinese learners can use social media functions on their mobile devices to share their learning achievements on platforms such as on their WeChat circle of friends, in order to introduce social supervision mechanisms, and complete learning tasks with supervision and attention. (Wang, 2017). In China, where WeChat is widely used, this method of self-monitoring is easily accessible.

Competing with peers can also enhance the learning process by making it more engaging and stimulating learners' motivation (Krashen, 1982). Many current mobile learning apps incorporate this aspect of MALL into their design of outline and operation. Learners can easily log in through social media accounts such as WeChat and participate in learning competitions with their peers. For example, some English WeChat Mini Programmes allow users to invite friends to engage in vocabulary challenges. Jia and Hew (2022) suggest that this type of learning, which occurs through meaningful and enjoyable activities, can help learners persist in their studies,

particularly for Chinese learners accustomed to frequent use of learning apps. Gregory and Kaufeldt (2015) also support this view, arguing that implicit learning methods are more effective than traditional classroom approaches and can be particularly beneficial for English language teaching.

2.8.1.2 Similarities between MOOC and MALL

MOOCs and MALL are particularly popular among Chinese university learners due to their attractive features and advantages. Both provide easy access to high-quality, rich educational resources and learning materials. Through MOOCs, Chinese university students can enrol in courses offered by prestigious universities worldwide, gaining access to learning opportunities that may not be available at their own institutions. The flexibility of autonomous learning in both MOOCs and MALL allows students to study at their own pace, enabling them to fit learning into their schedules and balance their academic pursuits with daily life.

MOOCs and MALL are especially well-suited for studying outside of traditional work and university attendance times. Ulrich and Nedelcu (2015) note that, compared to classroom teaching, MOOCs represent a unique teaching mode, characterised by short, intensive video sessions conducive to fragmented learning. This method allows learners to set their own learning pace within a specified timeframe, making it particularly beneficial for lifelong learners and those who study outside the traditional classroom context, such as in-service teachers who need the flexibility to learn in their free time. The flexibility inherent in MOOCs, which can be accessed via mobile devices, shares many of the same advantages and features as MALL. Both emphasise voluntary, autonomous learning and offer learners the freedom to choose courses of interest, leading to high course retention rates. Chauhan (2014) adds that Chinese learners can benefit from MOOC online discussions, which facilitate communication

with peers across the country and around the world, enhancing the mobile learning experience.

Margaryan, Bianco, and Littlejohn (2015) note that MOOCs differ significantly from previous online courses and traditional classroom courses due to their systematic feature. In MOOC courses, learners are required not only to watch instructional videos and read relevant materials but also to engage with other students through online tools, complete exercises, answer test questions, and submit final assignments and examinations where applicable. Once completing these tasks and meeting the assessment criteria, learners can complete the course and receive a corresponding certificate. Although MOOCs are open courses, particularly those offered by universities, are available only for a limited time. If learners miss the available times in which the course is delivered, they have to wait for the next offering time. Therefore, MOOCs are rigorous courses that provide learners with a more systematic and comprehensive acquisition of knowledge, making them an effective form of self-learning. Kim and Maloney (2020) emphasise that MOOCs, as an emerging and innovative mode of online education, have garnered significant attention from scholars worldwide over the past decade. This interest was sparked by the Global Open Educational Resources Movement, with the earliest MOOC being Stanford University's 2011 artificial intelligence course, which attracted 160,000 participants from 190 countries, because the course was delivered by a prestigious university and was also available as an open learning course and thus attractive to learners who would be able to access it at any time (Rodriguez, 2012).

Similarly, MALL (Mobile-Assisted Language Learning) also relies on digital tools and online platforms to deliver its content, focusing on providing rich language learning resources to enhance flexibility and efficiency (AbuSa'aleek, 2014). MALL allows learners to communicate with their teachers anytime and anywhere, which

further help increasing the flexibility of their educational experience. Both MOOCs and MALL offer remote learning opportunities accessible from any location with an internet connection, making education more flexible and inclusive. Additionally, both approaches enable learners to manage their study pace in the courses, participating in courses and accessing learning materials at their own speed. The flexibility offered by MOOCs and MALL is particularly well-suited to accommodate diverse schedules and learning preferences.

Moreover, MOOCs are often more affordable than traditional university courses or professional training programmes. According to Manzoor (2015), most MOOCs are free or low-cost, allowing Chinese higher education learners to access high-quality education from prestigious universities worldwide without incurring significant tuition expenses. MOOCs offer learners the chance to study with eminent experts and broaden their perspectives within diverse cultural contexts. Similarly, MALL platforms provide free or low-cost language learning resources, reducing the financial burden on learners seeking to improve their language proficiency. MALL also facilitates connections with English-speaking communities, enabling learners to practice language skills in authentic contexts (Sun *et al.*, 2017).

2.8.1.3 Differences between MOOC and MALL

MOOCs and MALL differ in several key aspects. MOOCs typically follow a structured course format, with clearly defined sections for video lectures, assessments, discussions, and, in some cases, exams (Shapiro *et al.*, 2017). MOOC platforms offer a broad range of subjects, attracting a diverse group of learners. In contrast, MALL (Mobile-Assisted Language Learning) focuses specifically on language acquisition and creates a more personalised learning environment to enhance learners' language skills (Song, Tan and Awang, 2021). The learning objectives of these platforms also differ: while MOOCs cover a wide range of subjects including language learning. The

variety of options allows the learners to explore more fields, acquire new knowledge, and enhance their academic abilities. In contrast, MALL, as its name suggests, mainly focuses on language learning and aims to develop learners' language proficiency, vocabulary, and communication skills and provides opportunities for Chinese learners to improve their English language skills, which is highly valued in academic contexts and is in professional demand. In addition, Learners can learn via MOOCs through many devices, including computers, laptops, tablets, and smartphones. MALL, however, is typically on mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets. It makes full use of mobility and generality to facilitate language learning.

2.8.1.4 Language-learning MOOCs and MALL

Language-learning MOOCs, as a subset of MOOCs, provide structured and tailored courses designed to achieve language acquisition goals (Motzo and Proudfoot, 2017). These MOOCs are specifically developed to teach second or foreign languages and are accessible to learners worldwide through the Internet. Language-learning MOOCs offer a wealth of learning resources, including videos, texts, audio, and interactive tools, aimed at improving language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing (Silva *et al.*, 2023). Typically offered by higher education institutions, these courses cover a wide range of languages, such as English, Spanish, French, and Chinese. In contrast, Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) emphasises flexibility and mobile access to language learning resources. MALL often involves informal, interactive methods, including language apps, chatbots, or gamified learning environments (Wang, 2017). The differences between MOOCs and MALL highlight their unique approaches to addressing learners' language development needs, particularly in terms of pedagogy, accessibility, and adaptability.

In China, language learning has significantly advanced with the adoption of both Language-learning MOOCs and MALL tools. These technologies specifically address

the growing demand for English language proficiency throughout China. Language-learning MOOCs offered by platforms such as Xuetang and Coursera are widely utilised for structured language teaching. These MOOCs are often designed to align with learners' academic goals, offering comprehensive curricula that include modules on grammar, vocabulary, listening, and speaking. Delivered by experienced instructors from prestigious institutions, these courses frequently provide certificates upon completion, which appeals to learners seeking academic or career achievement.

For learners, both options offer significant opportunities and by comparing these paradigms, learners can better understand their complementary roles in modern education. Language-Learning MOOCs are ideal for formal, in-depth study, following a traditional course format that guides learners through structured content and assessments. MALL, on the other hand, offers supplementary, accessible options for continuous practice. This comparison enables learners to assess the unique contributions of each approach in enhancing language proficiency and engagement. As all my participants in this study were English language learners and engaged in English-language MOOCs, I took the decision to focus on comparing English-language MOOCs and MALL. This comparison serves as important evidence for later sections, as discussed in detail in Sections 2.14 and 3.3.6.

2.8.2 MOOC and SPOC

MOOCs and SPOCs are both popular forms of online education that have recently gained widespread use in Chinese higher education. However, they differ in characteristics and purposes. Comparing these two types of online teaching methods can help learners understand their respective strengths and weaknesses, enabling them to choose the approach that best aligns with their learning needs and aims.

SPOC, or Small Private Online Course, refers to a small-scale online course. Unlike MOOCs, which are massive and open, SPOCs are characterised by their limited size and restricted access. The term "small" refers to the number of students, typically ranging from several to a few hundred, while "private" indicates that the course provider sets specific admission criteria that students must meet to enrol in SPOC courses (Guo, 2017). For those admitted to a SPOC, there are specific requirements regarding learning intensity and time commitment. If learners can participate in online discussions, complete the homework and assignments, and pass exams, they will obtain a certificate.

Although SPOCs are also online teaching methods like MOOCs, they are designed for smaller and more targeted participants. The concept of SPOCs originated at the University of California, Berkeley (Sun, 2020). With a small-scale restrictive online teaching model, the "Software Engineering" SPOC course was launched on the edX platform. In this model, students engage in both online and offline learning, often submitting assignments online first and receiving timely grades and feedback during face-to-face classroom sessions. According to Ruiz-Palmero *et al.* (2020), SPOC courses are tailored to the needs of a specific group of participants, allowing learners to be grouped into personalised and targeted teaching groups based on their individual learning requirements. Liu (2021) notes that SPOCs sometimes incorporate and repurpose MOOC resources, reorganising the learning process to support a blended approach that combines online and offline instruction. This strategy is considered effective for enhancing the quality of learning. Sanchez-Gordon and Luján-Mora (2015) also agree that SPOCs can utilise existing MOOC materials, enriching course content and fostering collaboration between MOOCs and SPOCs.

Implementing SPOCs (Small Private Online Courses) in some Chinese universities can enhance students' learning efficiency and outcomes. Some institutions combine online and offline classes, with both components carrying equal weight in assessments. As a blended teaching approach that combines traditional and online education, SPOCs set restrictions for the number of participants, typically selecting students from specific classes, and others may also be allowed to observe. This approach not only provides personalised learning experiences but also ensures the openness of teaching resources.

Both MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) and SPOCs are delivered online, allowing learners to access resources and participate in classes remotely (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2016). They offer courses with clear learning objectives, professional lectures, and assignments facilitated through technology such as videos, online forums, and assessments. These platforms share advantages in terms of flexibility and interactivity, and both play significant roles in the current educational transformation in China. According to Yousef (2021), while MOOCs and SPOCs are popular online learning methods, they differ in aspects such as scale, target participants, and accessibility. Firstly, MOOCs are designed to attract a large number of learners globally. These courses are open to anyone interested in the subject matter and are typically structured to accommodate as many participants as possible. In contrast, SPOCs are designed for smaller, more targeted groups, focusing on specific audiences with particular goals, such as students from a particular educational institution, company employees, or members of an organisation (Mutawa, 2017). While MOOCs offer a flexible and convenient learning pace, allowing learners to study whenever and wherever they choose, SPOCs emphasise more personalised learning experiences. However, SPOCs often feature more fixed schedules and deadlines, which is similar to the traditional courses. This results in less flexibility but provides a more guided and targeted learning experience in SPOC classes. Additionally, although many

MOOCs now offer completion certificates or credits for learners who meet course requirements, these certificates are often not accredited by educational institutions or professional organisations (Pundak, Sabag and Trotskovsky, 2014). However, Jaramillo-Morillo *et al.* (2020) noted that SPOCs also offer certificates or credits, these certificates are typically more recognised and valued within specific educational institutions, organisations, or industries. They also believe that SPOC's evaluation mechanism is more developed, making the associated certificates more credible.

2.8.3 MOOCs and Other Online Taught Courses

With the rapid development of economics and technology, multimedia has been widely integrated into various fields, including education (Bates, 2005). The emergence of MOOCs has significantly increased the number of people engaging in online learning, with many utilising MOOC platforms to further devote themselves to education. Simultaneously, other forms of online courses, such as micro-courses, have also been adopted by universities. While the frequency of online teaching has gradually increased, there are notable differences between MOOCs and other online courses.

In terms of scale, MOOCs and other online courses differ significantly. As large-scale open online courses, MOOCs have now been launched around the world and are widely welcomed (Pappano, 2012). In contrast, micro-courses remain relatively small in scale and are primarily popular in specific regions or countries (Yang, 2018). Regarding target participants, MOOCs cater to a broad participant, including university and professional education sectors, and have partnered with prestigious universities such as Stanford, Duke, and Yale. MOOCs focus more on universities but not other online learning platforms. Traditional online classes, however, are more commonly focused on primary and secondary education, and their content is delivered

by using different types of apps (Roschelle *et al.*, 2000). The method by which students receive recognition for completing online courses has also evolved; after collaborating with universities, students can now earn certificates upon completing a MOOC and passing the examination (Daniel, 2012).

Additionally, university students may earn academic credits by taking MOOC courses offered by their institutions. More and more companies in the United States are recognising the qualifications obtained through MOOCs, indicating a growing trend towards their acceptance in professional settings. In contrast, other online courses typically do not offer certificates or credits, limiting their formal recognition. Students only learn the corresponding knowledge after watching micro-courses, without certificates or credits. Furthermore, MOOCs now allow students to evaluate courses and teachers, and teachers can also evaluate each other, which supports the development of high-quality MOOCs. Other online courses, however, currently lack evaluation mechanisms (Spyropoulou *et al.*, 2015).

From a commercial perspective, MOOC platforms like Coursera and edX have introduced paid certification systems on the world's leading MOOC websites. While registration and courses are currently free, the integration of MOOCs with business models is necessary (Mazoue, 2013). Some commercial companies are also collaborating with universities to design targeted, skill-based courses, which they launch on MOOC platforms. These companies may even offer employment opportunities to learners who complete the courses and pass the exams. In contrast, other online courses are primarily used for teaching purposes and are usually developed by universities or individual teachers.

Large-scale online courses have faced numerous challenges, particularly concerning software, hardware, and network quality, as well as learner motivation. In China, a significant issue has been the lack of attention some universities and teachers give to online classes, often shifting the responsibility of supervising students to their parents. Parents are sometimes required to take pictures of their children studying, upload them to the site, and check in with the teachers (Cui *et al.*, 2021). This approach has led to different reactions; while some educators support it, others criticize it, which cannot get a balance. Additionally, some inexperienced learners may be vulnerable to scams, such as being asked to pay for courses after registration or encountering irrelevant advertisements. However, MOOCs can address some of these issues. According to Andersen *et al.* (2018), one key difference between MOOCs and traditional online teaching is that MOOCs are typically launched by universities or established platforms rather than individuals. This institutional support makes the autonomous learning process safer for students, reducing their susceptibility to online scams and ensuring a higher standard of educational quality.

2.9 MOOCs and Related History and Policies in China

2.9.1 History of Traditional Chinese Education

Traditional Chinese education is a system with a long history and profound influence (Yan, 2021). Historically, this system has been primarily guided by Confucianism, which emphasises moral cultivation, the transmission of knowledge, and the development of personal integrity. This educational approach was particularly prominent in ancient China, where the imperial examination system played a central role in selecting officials based on their performance in rigorous examinations (Qian, 2023). Although the modern Chinese education system has evolved significantly, the influence of traditional education remains deeply embedded. According to Zhang (2022), modern Chinese society is a multicultural entity that integrates both traditional

and contemporary elements, as well as national and Western cultures. This suggests that the values and beliefs of traditional education continue to be relevant in today's society. Education has historically been and continues to be, not only about acquiring knowledge but also about developing moral character and understanding one's role in society. Zhang (2022) argues that a well-educated individual contributes to a harmonious and well-governed society.

Traditional Chinese education encompasses various cultural practices and societal values that have shaped the country's educational philosophy and approach. While Confucianism was the dominant educational philosophy, other schools of thought such as Taoism, Legalism, and Mohism also influenced the educational landscape. These philosophies offered diverse perspectives on ethics, governance, and the nature of reality, which were integrated into the broader educational curriculum (Tu, 1996).

Education in traditional China was not limited to formal schools and institutions, family education also played an important role in instilling values and social norms from an early age (Tu, 1996). The family was seen as the basic unit of society, and its role in education was considered as important as that of formal schools. Whether learning at home or in the classroom, the traditional Chinese education system emphasises classroom teaching and face-to-face communication between teachers and students. It upholds the dignity of teachers, the discipline of students, and the importance of classroom interaction. Through direct teacher-student interaction, students not only receive knowledge but also develop moral values and a sense of social responsibility within the classroom environment. This teaching method is used today and is the mainstream teaching method in Chinese education.

2.9.2 The Characteristics of MOOCs and How They Compare to the Characteristics of Traditional Chinese Education

As discussed earlier in this chapter, scholars such as Abeer and Miri (2014) and Ko and Rossen (2017) have highlighted the many characteristics and advantages of MOOCs. A notable feature of MOOCs is their openness, which allows educational resources to be widely disseminated beyond registered students. MOOCs offer significant flexibility, enabling learners to study according to their own schedules without being constrained by geographical location. Furthermore, MOOCs typically incorporate short videos, interactive exercises, and other tools to enhance learner engagement and interactivity. They also provide personalised learning experiences tailored to meet the diverse needs of learners. Given the widespread availability of online platforms, MOOCs are generally offered at a low cost, making high-quality education accessible to a broader audience.

However, traditional Chinese education also has rich characteristics and advantages. In this system, education is seen as an integral part of the social structure, with many educational issues considered as social issues that must be addressed and resolved within the broader societal context. Ethical instruction is a key focus, as ancient Chinese education placed a strong emphasis on the teaching of ethics and morality (You, Rud and Hu, 2018). Confucian classics hold a central place in traditional education, with students required to study and understand this foundational knowledge. Additionally, traditional education emphasises autonomous learning, irrespective of age or social class, and values direct communication between teachers and students.

When comparing MOOCs with traditional education, several notable differences emerge. Firstly, in terms of the teaching environment, MOOCs offer a flexible, online

learning environment, while traditional education relies on physical classrooms and face-to-face instruction (Deng, Benckendorff and Gannaway, 2019). Secondly, regarding teaching modes, Deng, Benckendorff and Gannaway (2019) observe that MOOCs employ flexible and diverse instructional approaches, emphasising innovation and interactivity. In contrast, traditional education typically follows a more fixed, teacher-centred teaching process. Thirdly, for the targeted learner group, MOOCs attract a broad range of participants, including domain experts, company employees, homemakers, and students, while traditional education primarily targets on-campus students (Sun *et al.*, 2015). MOOCs enable anyone with internet access to choose courses that meet their specific needs, making learning both flexible and accessible. In relation to cost and resources, MOOCs are able to reduce education costs through the use of online platforms, enabling more people to receive a high-quality education, while traditional education requires a higher investment in physical resources, such as classrooms and textbooks.

While these authors have highlighted the benefits of MOOCs, I also explored, for this study, the experiences of my participants in comparing MOOCs with traditional education. MOOCs and traditional Chinese education each have distinct advantages and limitations. MOOCs have rapidly gained global popularity due to their openness, flexibility, interactivity, and low cost, while traditional education excels in providing comprehensive ethical and moral education, shaping personality, and fostering personal development (Hanafiah *et al.*, 2024). In the future, there is potential for these two educational approaches to complement each other and combine to achieve higher-quality educational outcomes.

Over the past decade, the Chinese government has emphasised the importance of online education in policy initiatives such as the "Decision of the CPC Central

Committee and the State Council on Comprehensively Promoting Quality Education" and the "Notice of the State Council's Approval of the Ministry of Education on the 21st Century Education Revitalization Action Plan." According to statistics (Sim, Sim, and Quah, 2021), the number of registered students in the 68 online universities approved by the Ministry of Education reached 2.3 million, reflecting the government's recognition of distance education and its acknowledgement of the growing importance of online learning. In terms of finance, the Chinese government gave so much support that the investment in online education projects was as much as 3.6 billion Yuan, and social investment was more than one billion Yuan.

2.9.3 The Growth and Impact of MOOCs in China

According to Vladimirovna, Vladimirovna and Rinatovich (2021), by August 2019, approximately 270 million people in China had taken massive open online courses (MOOCs). With around 15,000 courses available, China has established an extensive MOOC network that offers a wide range of subjects across various disciplines. Notably, about 80 million users were university students (Vladimirovna, Vladimirovna and Rinatovich, 2021).

Research by Yeung and Shen (2004) highlights that China's vast territory and large population have led to imbalanced educational development, particularly in Western regions like Xizang and Xinjiang, which lack adequate educational resources. To address this, several ministry-sponsored programmes have encouraged colleges and universities in these less-developed areas to incorporate open online courses into their curricula and train lecturers in integrating online and offline teaching methods. In the year 2019, more than 8,000 courses were introduced online or in a blended format, and 50,000 university teachers and lecturers received training to combine MOOC instruction with traditional classroom teaching (Ministry of Education, 2020).

Wang, Chen, Fan, *et al.* (2018) also noted that MOOCs have significantly contributed to educational equity by transferring educational resources and courses from the world's top universities to Chinese institutions, particularly in underdeveloped regions. The Ministry of Education planned to launch a bilingual gateway website for China MOOC by the end of 2019, which aimed to connect around 20 Chinese MOOC websites, a goal that has been achieved by 2023 (Keshavarz and Yuan, 2023). Additionally, the Chinese Academy of Cyberspace Studies was established in 2018, further indicating that MOOCs have played an important role in narrowing the educational gap between first-tier cities like Beijing and Shanghai and less developed areas such as Yunnan and Xizang (Chinese Academy of Cyberspace Studies, 2018). MOOCs are thus recognised as an effective tool for improving the autonomous English learning capabilities of minority college students (Yuan and Powell, 2013).

2.9.4 Online Education Policy in China

China's online education policy serves as the guiding principle and action standard set by the government to achieve its development goals in the online education sector (Chen *et al.*, 2014). This policy plays an important role in regulating and promoting the construction of online education. Ullrich *et al.* (2010) also noted that China has a large number of higher education graduates as well as non-academic education graduates. Due to the limited capacity and scale of traditional campuses, not all learners have the opportunity to attend universities. Therefore, online education may offer an efficient solution to solve this issue by admitting a larger number of learners.

China also needs to prioritize higher education on the national agenda to make it more accessible to Chinese learners. With a large population and a significant number of learners, the country must provide adequate educational opportunities for these

potential students. According to Zou (2022), China's higher education population reached 240 million by the end of May 2022, indicating the growing demand for educational resources. Online learning can help alleviate the pressure on physical attendance at universities by offering alternative educational pathways.

Over the past 40 years, since the implementation of the "Reform and Opening Up" policy, the development of online education in China has experienced three distinct stages (Wei and Hu, 2018). The first stage, from 1978 to 1988, focused on the recovery and reconstruction of the education system, laying the groundwork for modern online education. The second stage, from 1989 to 1998, was characterised by policy-driven expansion and scale development of online education. The current stage, beginning in 1999 and continuing to the present, is marked by the goal of sharing high-quality resources among higher education institutions across China (Wei and Hu, 2018).

According to Wang (2013), China has also developed specific policies related to modern online education in the past decades, which also referred to as distance education, to supported and encouraged the development of online education. For example, in 1999, the State Council formulated the "Action Plan for Education Revitalization for the 21st Century," which formally introduced the "modern distance education project" to establish an open network. In 2000, the Ministry of Education issued the "Interim Administrative Measures for Stations and Network Schools" and the "Opinions on Supporting the Construction of Network Education Institutes of Several Colleges and Universities to Carry out the Pilot Work of Modern Distance Education," providing a framework for establishing a new network education model (Wang, 2013).

2.9.5 Use of Online Materials in China

2.9.5.1 Differences Between General MOOCs and Chinese University-Specific MOOCs

Significant differences exist between general standard MOOCs and those designed specifically for Chinese universities in terms of design concepts, course content, and platform functions. General MOOCs are typically offered by top universities worldwide, emphasising internationalisation and diversity. They aim to provide global learners with access to high-quality educational resources from around the world through open online courses (Castillo *et al.*, 2015). In contrast, MOOCs tailored for Chinese universities focus on adapting to China's specific context nationally, and higher education needs, emphasising personalised learning and localised content. These courses integrate the strengths of mainstream MOOC platforms, both domestic and international, and can be customised to meet the specific learning requirements of Chinese students (Zheng, Chen and Burgos, 2018).

According to Abeer and Miri (2014), MOOCs cover a broad range of disciplines, from basic sciences to literature and art, philosophy and history to engineering technology, economics, management, and law. MOOCs specifically designed for Chinese universities place special emphasis on high-level courses from the '985 universities', which are considered the top-tier institutions in China. The '985' project, initiated by the Ministry of Education in May 1998, aims to build world-class universities and a group of world-renowned research institutions, currently encompassing 39 universities. MOOCs from these universities offer courses that range from foundational science to advanced professional knowledge. Additionally, Chinese university MOOCs have launched specialised courses, such as those for postgraduate entrance exams and further education, catering to the diverse needs of various user groups.

In addition, general MOOC platforms are typically operated by a single internet company or educational institution, with centralised functions primarily focused on providing online learning and management-related systems. In contrast, MOOCs designed specifically for Chinese universities are learning platforms jointly developed by NetEase and the University Society. These platforms not only offer online learning but also reduce the burden of note-taking by allowing students to access past course content at any time. Additionally, Chinese university MOOCs provide a wealth of courses designed by renowned teachers, including some national prize-winning courses, making it the largest Chinese MOOC platform. While general MOOCs are aimed at learners worldwide, allowing local and global participants to choose courses freely, Chinese university MOOCs focus not only on broad societal learners but also place special emphasis on the needs of university students. This approach can provide more targeted courses and services, specifically tailored to meet the demands of the Chinese higher education system.

2.9.5.2 The Development and Impact of MOOCs in Chinese Universities

In 2013, the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Peking University, Tsinghua University, and the Chinese University of Hong Kong began offering MOOCs. This development not only allowed Chinese students to participate in courses from top universities around the world but also enabled domestic universities in China to deliver their courses globally via the Internet (Zheng and Yang, 2017). In May 2013, Chinese universities took their first steps into the MOOC landscape, with Tsinghua University and Peking University moved some courses to EdX. Fudan University and Shanghai Jiaotong University officially partnered with Coursera in July of the same year, followed by other institutions like Nanjing University (Zheng, Chen and Burgos, 2018). By the end of August 2013, Chinese language courses from Taiwan University and the Chinese University of Hong Kong were first delivered on Coursera. As more Chinese universities participate in MOOC delivery, the influence

of MOOCs is expected to grow, increasing Chinese students' awareness and engagement with these courses (Zhao, Wang and Sun, 2020).

Zheng, Chen and Burgos (2018) note that one of the originators of the MOOC platform in China suggested that MOOCs could be regarded as a new revolution in Chinese education. The previous educational revolution marked the transition from apprenticeship to formal school education. Apprenticeships, which involve on-the-job training under the guidance of a master, allow practitioners to gain certification or licensure in various trades or professions (Ifechukwu-Jacobs, 2022). However, apprenticeships are limited in scale and focus on individualised training, unlike traditional school teaching, which can accommodate many students simultaneously. Similarly, personalised education, which is popular in the United States and often delivered through homeschooling, emphasises individualised learning directed by parents (Trainor, 2010). However, with advancements in technology, personalised education through the Internet has become increasingly feasible. Intelligent algorithms and big data now enable a degree of personalised learning, aiming to meet individual needs. While MOOCs are not yet the idealised form of education, since ensuring consistent learning quality for all learners at scale is challenging, they have gained significant popularity. The emergence of MOOCs has the potential to redefine universities, teachers, and even students (Huang, 2019).

Zhang *et al.* (2019) have observed that the significant advantages of MOOCs and online education lie in promoting educational equity and providing rich resources, allowing learners to study anytime and anywhere. As the MOOC teaching philosophy continues to evolve and as learners become more accustomed to autonomous learning, MOOCs are likely to become more prevalent and useful in Chinese universities. However, since MOOCs were introduced to China relatively recently, with university

adoption beginning in 2013, many students lack a systematic understanding of these courses or have not received sufficient recommendations from teachers and universities. Some students were even unable to distinguish MOOCs from other online courses or did not value MOOCs, this lack of familiarity may have contributed to lower engagement (Ma and Lee, 2019).

2.9.5.3 Learning Methods in Chinese Universities

Chinese universities primarily employ two main learning methods: face-to-face classroom teaching and online teaching (Wuensch *et al.*, 2006). While traditional classroom teaching remains prevalent, recent years have seen the rapid development of other learning methods, including D-learning (distance learning), M-learning (mobile learning), B-learning (blended learning), and U-learning (ubiquitous learning) (Henno, Jaakkola and Makela, 2014). The emergence of these methods is largely due to the continuous improvement and expansion of E-learning (electronic learning). E-learning, which is based on Internet networks such as LANs and satellite broadcasting networks, emphasises independent, learner-centred education (Al-Qahtani and Higgins, 2013). It aims to enhance learners' knowledge and skills by providing an interactive digital learning environment, including online courses, multimedia materials, courseware, and question banks. The rise of E-learning has introduced new opportunities for educational development in the information age.

Traditionally, education has focused on teachers, teaching materials, and classrooms as the central components of the learning process, with an emphasis on cultivating students' analytical, deductive, and critical thinking abilities, overall thinking ability and ability to accept knowledge (Brown and Warschauer, 2006). However, this model may also neglect students' initiative and independence. In this traditional learning framework, learners often receive knowledge passively from teachers and follow a

solid learning process, which is not conducive to enabling students to explore their own creative potential and innovative qualities.

Kukulska-Hulme and Traxler (2007) describe mobile learning refers to a kind of learning method using portable computer equipment such as laptops, tablets and smartphones. With the rapid development of smartphones and mobile internet, mobile learning has become a mainstream approach to lifelong learning, giving rise to new formats like micro-learning and MOOCs. Most universities now offer MOOCs and other online courses through the Internet, allowing learners in China to access them via their mobile devices. This shift to online classrooms represents a transition from traditional teaching models to internet-based platforms. The flexibility and abundance of learning materials available through online education have garnered significant attention from the academic community (Gore, 2014). MOOCs, in particular, have shifted the focus of the classroom from teachers to students, where students engage in discussions about lecture content, and teachers provide evaluations afterwards. Li, Ren, and Wang (2019) believe that this interactive classroom model not only saves teachers time and energy but will also enable students to change and develop themselves from their previous passive acceptance of learning experiences as passive learners to active explorers of learning. As a result, students' abilities to innovate, discuss, and summarise are enhanced. They suggest that this shift from teacher-centred to student-centred education greatly improves students' sense of self-identity and engagement.

2.10 China's Experience of Online Education during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Policies, Lessons and Challenges

2.10.1 The Use of Emergency Remote Teaching

Emergency distance learning (ERT) is a method of rapidly transforming teaching modes during crisis situations, typically used to replace traditional face-to-face teaching (Hodges *et al.*, 2020). Unlike traditional online teaching, ERT focuses on quickly establishing a temporary solution to an emergency which has interrupted traditional classroom teaching, rather than creating a new and carefully planned, long-term online education course. ERT employs online meeting software (such as Zoom and Microsoft Teams), learning management systems (such as Moodle and Canvas), and various digital resources (such as video courses and e-books) to conduct teaching. To accommodate the diverse technical conditions, time constraints, and geographical environments of students and teachers, ERT often emphasises flexible arrangements, which can benefit all learners, no matter where they are based. However, due to time and resource constraints, ERT may fall below the standards of 'normal' online or face-to-face teaching in terms of course quality, interactivity, and technical support, because of its 'emergency' nature and the lack of time for preparation of activities.

ERT serves as a means of continuing learning when schools and universities are unable to open due to natural disasters such as earthquakes or floods. It may also be employed during wars or political crises when teaching activities are interrupted due to conflicts (Ikwuka *et al.*, 2021). For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, educational institutions worldwide rapidly transitioned to remote learning modes to ensure the health and safety of teachers and students.

2.10.1.1 Emergency Remote Teaching during the COVID-19 Pandemic

During the COVID-19 pandemic, many countries around the world were forced to change their teaching mode to Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT) and encourage the development of digital technologies for learning and teaching. (Kasperskia, Poratb and Blau, 2023). The primary purpose of ERT is to provide temporary teaching support during crises to ensure the continuity of education, using existing distance learning tools (Hudrea, Spoaller and Urs, 2023). It is clear that this mode of delivery was relevant to the learning context during the Covid-19 pandemic.

ERT differs from traditional online learning as it is conducted without sufficient preparation, often by rapidly adapting existing distance learning tools to replace face-to-face or blended courses. According to Grammens *et al.* (2022), ERT typically involves synchronous teaching modes, where teachers and students interact in real-time using tools such as video conferencing. Therefore, universities and schools were able to continue their teaching activities despite the challenges brought by lockdowns and social distancing measures during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Although ERT provides temporary teaching support, it faces challenges, including some teachers' and lecturers' lack of experience with digital tools, students' difficulties adapting to self-directed learning, and a lack of effective teacher-student interaction (Broadbent *et al.*, 2023). ERT is not intended to establish a permanent online education system but serves as a transitional solution, with teaching expected to return to its original mode once the crisis is over.

2.10.1.2 Emergency Remote Teaching in China

The COVID-19 pandemic triggered an unprecedented global shift to online learning, often characterised as 'Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT). Unlike structured online

learning platforms such as MOOCs or SPOCs, ERT involves the rapid adaptation of face-to-face course materials to an online format, often with minimal preparation time or resources (Hodges *et al.*, 2020). This distinction is particularly important when examining the experiences of educators and learners during the pandemic, which is the subject of this study.

In China, while some universities transitioned to using MOOCs and SPOCs to deliver structured course content, many educators initially relied on ERT to maintain instructional continuity during the COVID-19 pandemic. These approaches highlight the possible nature of digital education during crises, where ERT can serve as an immediate solution while MOOCs or SPOCs represent more stable, long-term alternatives for online learning.

Emergency remote teaching in China during the pandemic was a collaborative effort involving the government, universities, teachers, and students. The government implemented multiple measures, including organising distance education, ensuring the smooth implementation of graduation exams and registration systems, and providing support for monitoring and evaluating the quality of distance education. In the early stages of the pandemic, the Ministry of Education quickly issued a notice delaying the start of the academic year and mobilised universities to prepare for online teaching under the policy of "Class Suspended but Learning Continues" (Ministry of Education, 2020). Universities launched emergency response plans, organised remote education, managed and supported teachers, and monitored campus health data. For example, the School of New Energy at China University of Petroleum conducted online teaching of pressure vessel experiments, adopting a process-based assessment system, strengthening teacher-student interaction, and gradually forming a comprehensive online experimental course mode (Sun *et al.*, 2022).

Although China implemented various measures to address the challenges of ERT during the COVID-19 pandemic, certain issues persisted, such as providing diverse, high-quality online learning resources for different groups and enhancing the learning and teaching functions of existing online education platforms. Thus, through the joint efforts of the government, universities, teachers, and students, China successfully implemented large-scale distance education during the pandemic, ensuring the continuity of education.

2.10.2 The Rise of MOOCs in China During the COVID-19 Pandemic

In December 2019, a coronavirus epidemic emerged in Wuhan, China (Jiang, Du and Shi, 2020). To effectively reduce public gatherings and prevent further spread of the virus, the State Council convened a conference on January 26, 2020, which requested the postponement of the spring semester (Ministry of Education, 2020). On January 27, the Ministry of Education issued a directive instructing all local schools to delay the start of the spring semester, with specific reopening dates to be communicated by regional educational administrations. Furthermore, on January 29, the Ministry launched an initiative to facilitate online learning, emphasising the need for "Class Suspended but Learning Continues" (Ministry of Education, 2020).

Subsequently, education administrations in various places in China responded quickly and launched online learning guidance and programmes. By February 10, 2020, most provinces and cities had established clear guidelines for online teaching. Numerous universities, middle schools, and primary schools developed their own online teaching programmes and released corresponding instructional materials. For example, a search on the WeChat platform using the phrase "Class Suspended but Learning

Continues" revealed over 7,700 messages related to various online learning initiatives by February 11. Additionally, education-related companies also responded to the situation. According to statistics from third-party media specialising in online education (Nan and Qi, 2020), more than 130 online education companies had provided diverse online education resources and tools, including platform services, to Wuhan and other affected areas by February 11, 2020. During this extended school closure period, various online teaching methods emerged in China, including online courses, live broadcast instruction, self-learning through MOOCs, and educational programming via television. Within such a specific context, online teaching faces many challenges, but it also presents significant opportunities.

2.10.3 Navigating the Pandemic: The Development of MOOCs in Higher Education

Wu Yan, Director of the Department of Higher Education at the Ministry of Education, stated at a conference on February 29, 2022, that by the end of February 2022, the number of MOOCs in China would exceed 50,000, with nearly 800 million learners enrolled and taking the courses and over 300 million students earning MOOC credits. This achievement positions China first in the world for both the number of MOOCs and demonstrating a rapid growth trend (Ministry of Education, 2020).

According to Zhou *et al.* (2020), during the COVID-19 pandemic, the Ministry of Education organised large-scale online teaching practices using MOOCs and other digital methods. This initiative not only effectively addressed the challenges of suspended teaching and learning but also transformed the situation into an opportunity, igniting a "learning revolution" in higher education. In the spring semester of 2020, 1.08 million university instructors delivered 1.1 million online courses, engaging 22.59 million students participated in learning through the Internet. As a result, the

digital transformation of higher education in China has deepened, with the proportion of university teachers employing blended teaching methods that combine MOOCs or other online courses with traditional classroom instruction, rising from 34.8% before the pandemic to 84.2%. This shift highlights significant progress in digital learning tailored to China's unique educational context, including classroom philosophy, teaching technologies, educational standards, teaching methods, and evaluation (Huang *et al.*, 2020). During the pandemic, MOOCs in China experienced significant development and growth. Scholars such as Chengjie (2015) have noted that MOOCs offer numerous advantages and will contribute to the evolution of Chinese education and the transformation of traditional pedagogies. The benefits of online education became particularly evident during nationwide and global lockdown events. During this period, MOOCs experienced significant growth and became increasingly integral to higher education in China (Huang, 2020). MOOC platforms became increasingly popular during the COVID-19 pandemic period of lockdown, as people were required to keep social distance and adhere to restrictions. This led to a further research question: How and in what ways did MOOCs develop a different education practice and delivery during the COVID-19 pandemic to support students' individual motivation, and engagement in their learning?

When I began to analyse learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education, the COVID-19 pandemic had not yet occurred. I initially aimed to focus on the basic development and application of MOOCs in Chinese universities. However, the emergency accelerated the rapid development and dissemination of MOOCs, underscoring their advantages, such as flexibility, adaptability, and continuity, which can be systematically integrated with traditional education in the post-pandemic era (Huang *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, this thesis will further analyse learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education by surveying students' perceptions of their learning experiences. By comparing participants' learning situations before and after

the pandemic, aims to identify strategies for better integrating MOOCs into Chinese education in the future.

2.10.4 The Expansion and Integration of MOOCs in Chinese Higher Education During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Duan (2021) noted that the Chinese government recognised the importance of online education during the COVID-19 pandemic and actively supported the development of MOOC platforms. The government encouraged universities and educational institutions to offer online courses, provided funding for research and development, and promoted partnerships between universities and MOOC providers (Yang, Shen and Xu, 2022). During this period, the collaboration between MOOCs and traditional classroom courses expanded rapidly as many Chinese universities integrated online courses into their curricula. Some universities further combined traditional classroom teaching with online components, offering students more flexible and accessible courses (Yang, Shen and Xu, 2022). As a result, the COVID-19 pandemic significantly expanded the number of MOOC platforms, leading to increased enrolment on existing platforms such as XuetangX, iCourse, and Tencent Classroom. These platforms collaborated with universities, educational institutions, and industry experts to develop and offer courses that served as viable alternatives to traditional classroom teaching.

Following the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, the number of MOOCs grew rapidly. According to Yang and Huang (2021), from January 27 to February 10, 2020, the number of daily active MOOC users in Chinese universities increased more than fivefold. By the end of October 2020, 40,000 MOOCs had been launched online, with the number of learners in China reaching 540 million.

During the restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, MOOCs played an important role in sharing educational resources and ensuring that universities could continue online operations despite campus closed down according to government policy. On January 29, 2020, the Chinese Ministry of Education announced plans to launch the ‘National Cyber Cloud Class’ on February 17 (Hong, 2020). On February 5, the Ministry issued a policy titled “Focusing on the Organisation and Management of Online Teaching in Colleges and Universities,” which required all colleges and universities to leverage MOOCs, high-quality online course resources, and platforms developed at the provincial and university levels to conduct online teaching and learning. These resources were made freely available to universities nationwide. More than 24,000 courses were delivered online, ensuring that online teaching was substantially equivalent to offline instruction (Ministry of Education, 2020). In addition to the free online courses provided on the national platform, numerous non-governmental organisations, online education companies, communities, and consortiums launched open online courses and other educational resources, such as those offered by China University MOOCs, Classes Online, Good Universities Online, the Excellent Class Alliance, and the Wisdom Tree platform.

MOOCs were widely used as the main method of learning during this significant period. Many colleges and universities published online teaching plans that primarily recommended the use of MOOC and SPOC (Small Private Online Course) teaching methods. Additionally, student Q&A groups were established to facilitate the launch of new curricula. For example, Tsinghua University’s online teaching programme utilised the “Rain Classroom” tools developed by the university to conduct scheduled online lectures. These tools supported interactive lectures, Q&A sessions, discussions, seminars, tests, and independent learning modules (Wang and Chen, 2018). During the unique circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic, MOOCs enabled universities

to address the challenges of transitioning to online education, consolidate their strengths, and enhance their reputations. Meanwhile, both university teachers and students quickly adapted to the online learning environment.

Similarly, South China University of Technology launched its entire curriculum online on February 5, 2020. The university selected appropriate online teaching platforms, such as Classes Online, Wisdom Tree Network, and Huagong Online Teaching, and implemented suitable online teaching methods, including MOOCs, SPOCs, and live broadcasts. The university also published detailed online teaching manuals, which were highly operational and of great significance for teachers and students participating in online learning (South China University of Technology, 2020).

2.10.5 Policies implementation during the COVID-19 Pandemic

2.10.5.1 Implementation of the ‘Class Suspended but Learning Continues’ Emergency Plan of the Ministry of Education

Gu and Li (2022) argue that the key to sustaining education during the COVID-19 pandemic was ensuring the accessibility and availability of high-quality online learning resources, which significantly impacted learners' behaviour. To fulfil this need, a series of policies and measures were implemented to enhance the provision of online resources.

On February 17, 2020, the Ministry of Education launched the "National Network Cloud Platform," designed to host learning resources specifically tailored for primary and secondary school students (Ministry of Education, 2020). Earlier, on February 4, 2020, the Ministry issued the "Guidance on the Organisation and Management of Online Teaching and Learning in Regular Higher Education Institutions During the

Epidemic Prevention and Control Period" (Ministry of Education, 2020). This directive encouraged higher education institutions to utilise online platforms to facilitate remote learning, recommending 22 platforms that offered over 24,000 courses free of charge. Most of these platforms were developed by leading Chinese universities or enterprises and provided a range of course materials, including massive open online courses (MOOCs), small private open courses (SPOCs), and virtual simulations across 12 undergraduate disciplines and 18 higher vocational fields. As a result, more than half of Chinese higher education institutions transitioned to spring semester teaching programmes online, with many incorporating online course content and live-streamed classes.

2.10.5.2 Implementation of Strengthening Science and Technology Infrastructure Provision

Successful online learning relies heavily on the availability of reliable and stable technological infrastructure. According to Gu and Li (2022), in response to the need for improved internet connectivity during the COVID-19 pandemic, the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology issued a notice in March, 2020, announcing plans to enhance broadband coverage to support online education. Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, the Ministry of Education collaborated with the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology and telecommunications operators to ensure adequate network services were available for schools and educational platforms at all levels. They provided high-quality network bandwidth, cloud service capabilities, and free mobile data to facilitate the effective implementation of online teaching during the pandemic.

Subsequently, on March 16, 2020, the Ministry of Education issued guidelines aimed at enhancing the use of information technology to ensure access to quality education (Xinhua News Agency, 2020). According to Wang (2020), online platforms such as

DingTalk, Rain Classroom, Xuedutong, and Tencent Conference experienced rapid growth during the COVID-19 pandemic. For instance, Rain Classroom saw an increase of 26 million users, with an average monthly active user base exceeding 30 million, covering over 6,000 schools and institutions. Xuedutong added 18 million new users, with 13.5 million active users, serving more than 4,000 schools and institutions. By March 31, 2020, DingTalk had over 300 million users and supported online classes for 140,000 schools of different levels, 3 million classes, and 130 million students across China.

Some provinces took additional steps to support students' access to online education. For example, Liaoning Province allocated seven million RMB in subsidies to approximately 20,000 university students, helping them cover expenses related to internet access and digital devices (Liu, 2020). The Provincial Education Department in Shandong also issued guidelines for younger students, recommending that individual online teaching sessions should be limited to 15–20 minutes for primary school students and 25–30 minutes for secondary school students. Additionally, the total recommended duration of online study each day was capped at 80 minutes for primary school students, 120 minutes for secondary school students, and 180 minutes for senior high school and university students.

2.10.6 Contrasting Online Learning in India during the COVID-19 Pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the global transition to online education, necessitating the rapid adaptation of traditional pedagogical approaches to digital formats. In India, a neighbouring country to China with a similarly large population, schools and universities remained closed for over a year. The Indian educational

department was compelled by the government to migrate academic courses from conventional, face-to-face modalities to online platforms.

However, the transition in India was less seamless than in China, and numerous challenges emerged. According to Kaushik and Kaushik (2024), despite government efforts to enhance online educational infrastructure, the transition was marked by significant complexities. These challenges included the need for widespread access to smartphones or computers, a stable internet connection, and comprehensive online educational platforms. Although the Indian government worked to improve the capabilities of online education platforms, the digital divide persisted and still does, particularly in rural and remote areas, hindering students' access to stable internet connections. The financial burden of procuring necessary devices for online learning fell heavily on families, with some parents resorting to selling assets or taking out loans to afford these devices. Despite these efforts, many children were forced to drop out of school due to a lack of resources (Yu, 2024).

India experienced one of the longest lockdowns globally during the COVID-19 pandemic (Li, 2020). According to a research report by Thinktank published in Global Net (2022), many Indian schools and universities were closed from March 2020 for over 18 months, which means that schools and universities did not open for three or four semesters, resulting in the longest period of closure in India's peacetime history. In many regions of India, MOOCs and other online teaching methods proved impractical due to poverty and inadequate infrastructure. Many families could not afford electronic devices, and even more struggled to stable internet connections. According to Siddiqui *et al.* (2020), the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on India's education system has been "catastrophic." Fewer than a quarter of Indian families had access to the internet, with the situation worse in rural areas, where only 8% of

families could connect to online platforms. Younger children, who often rely more on parental support for their education, were especially disadvantaged, as poorer families lacked the financial and technological resources to facilitate online learning. Internet connectivity issues further complicate online education in India. Yu *et al.* (2022) revealed that of 7500 Indian students participating in a survey, only 15% had access to broadband, while 72.6% relied on mobile hotspots, with 97% experiencing significant signal issues. These challenges made it difficult for students to watch instructional videos smoothly, and frequent power outages often interrupted their learning.

Moreover, Indian universities lacked a unified online education platform, leading to frequent changes in platforms, from WhatsApp and Zoom to the Indian startup video platform 'Impartus' and Microsoft Teams. This constant shifting required teachers and students to constantly adapt to new online education platforms. Many Indian teachers were unfamiliar with online media tools, making it difficult to complete online instruction. Additionally, India's linguistic diversity posed a challenge, as most online education platforms only supported a few official languages, putting students who speak regional languages at a disadvantage. In contrast, Chinese students generally had access to engage in online learning resources at any time and could easily communicate with their teachers and peers. The development of MOOCs and other online courses in China was more rapid and successful than in India, in response to their different educational environments.

In response to these challenges, multinational companies like Google and Microsoft started funding online education in India. Google partnered with the Indian government to provide free educational services to students and teachers, while Microsoft offered cloud education services to technical colleges. By 2022, the Indian

education system had returned to a relatively normal state and made significant progress toward a "new education paradigm" (Wu, 2023). The government has since launched several initiatives to promote the digitisation of education, including DIKSHA (Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing), NIOS-related online MOOCs, the e-Pathshala portal, and the National Repository of Open Educational Resources (NROER), which provide online content for students, teachers, educators, and parents. In addition to these government initiatives, private educational institutions have also strengthened digital infrastructure, trained teachers in ICT, and integrated blended learning into their curricula.

2.10.7 Return of Face-to-Face Learning in China

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Chinese students engaged in a year-long period of online learning. Traditional classroom teaching began to resume gradually in the autumn semester of 2020. Due to the vastness of China and the varying levels of pandemic control across regions, schools, universities, and other educational institutions did not fully reopen until the end of 2022. Different provinces adopted diverse policies to monitor the pandemic situation, resulting in varied timelines for the resumption of in-person education based on the fluctuating number of positive cases.

According to a report by China Education News Network (2022), China employed a cautious and phased approach to the resumption of traditional teaching programmes. The Ministry of Education set a goal to fully restore normal educational and teaching activities by the autumn semester of 2020. This goal was informed by the positive outcomes of China's pandemic prevention and control measures, as well as the successful implementation of online teaching and the attempted reopening of schools and universities in the spring semester.

Following the requirements for prevention and control of the pandemic, various areas adopted the strategy of opening schools and universities in phases, in batches and at staggered times and peaks. The result was that different grades and schools started at different points in time to minimise the risk of people gathering and potential infection. According to Xu (2020), face-to-face instruction resumed in some areas beginning in September 2020, with 31 provinces, including Guangdong and Shandong, clarifying their arrangements for the start of the autumn semester. However, some provinces and cities, such as Jilin and Shanghai, experienced significant increases in positive cases of infection and adopted individual lockdown strategies, leading to delays in resuming in-person education. In December 2022, the Chinese government declared the full liberalisation of the country, lifting all remaining COVID-19 restrictions. By March 2023, spring enrolment had resumed nationwide, and university learning had fully returned to normal.

2.11 Challenges for Using MOOCs in China

Due to the fact that COVID-19 spread so rapidly, the transition to remote learning and online education was a sudden and novel experience for students. In a study by Gu and Li (2022), which surveyed over 12,000 students from 33 provinces across China about their online learning experiences during the pandemic, 80% of participants expressed dissatisfaction with learning from home. A similar proportion (80%) reported that their home environment was less conducive to learning compared to the university setting. In October 2020, Shell Net, a recognised Chinese MOOC platform, conducted a survey of Chinese users of MOOCs. The results showed that 67% of university users did not complete a single course, while 16% completed less than half of the MOOCs. Only 6% of users finished all their selected courses. When asked about the reasons for not completing MOOC courses, the top three responses included learning issues (59%), lack of perseverance (55%), and language barriers (55%) (Shell Net, 2020).

The low participation and high dropout rates in MOOCs can be attributed to several factors, including insufficient motivation, poor teacher-student interaction, lack of self-management skills among students, inexperienced course design and lack of course structure and student support services such as credit recognition issues. Many learners struggled to complete courses, resulting in a high dropout rate. For example, research by Qiao, Sun, and Shan (2022) found that in a vocational education MOOC, 45.72% of learners enrolled in a course but did not complete it, and 27.13% did not even view any course videos in full. This lack of motivation, coupled with insufficient communication and guidance for students during the learning process, often led learners to give up. Another challenge is that MOOCs and other online courses were not simply a transfer of traditional teaching content to the Internet. In order to create high-quality online courses, teachers had to adapt their familiar teaching methods and restructure their courses to align with the principles of online learning. This was difficult for those teachers who did not have any online teaching experience. According to Xinhua News Agency (2020), during the COVID-19 pandemic, Tsinghua University established a temporary expert group comprising 15 teachers from various disciplines, all with extensive online teaching experience. This group was responsible for providing training and guidance to teachers across the university. They shared their valuable experiences through information technology, fostering a supportive network among teachers. However, most of the universities and institutions were not able to support this.

The low completion rate of MOOCs is evident from these findings. Many learners enrolled in MOOCs out of curiosity or a desire to explore new topics, rather than with a commitment to complete the course. This mindset often resulted in high dropout rates. Additionally, MOOCs frequently lacked the sense of community and peer interaction found in traditional classroom settings, which often led to feelings of

isolation among learners. Limited direct interaction with teachers made it difficult for learners to receive timely feedback and support, reducing their engagement and satisfaction. MOOCs which depended heavily on passive content delivery also affected learners' engagement; for example, lengthy videos could not attract learners effectively. Technical issues, such as platform accessibility, navigation problems, and poor video quality also hindered learners' engagement. Moreover, learners may have had trouble seeing the real-world applicability of course content, further decreasing their motivation to engage in MOOCs.

Low engagement in MOOCs remains a significant challenge that affects their overall effectiveness and success. In order to effectively enhance the learning engagement of MOOCs, it is necessary to consider the improvement and optimisation of these aspects. Therefore, my fourth research question was designed as: What is the possible future of MOOCs? In what ways can MOOCs contribute to the development of stronger learner engagement in Higher Education in China in future?

2.12 Factors Influencing Student Engagement in MOOCs in China

2.12.1 Students' Learning Needs and Learning Preferences

Students' engagement in MOOCs can be influenced by individual characteristics, external conditions, and the course styles of specific platforms (Lai *et al.*, 2021). The encouragement and guidance provided by university faculty can significantly enhance students' completion rates in MOOCs. Additionally, individual attributes such as gender, academic performance, and online learning expectations also play an important role in shaping students' choices (Lee, 2006). Previous experiences with MOOCs also have notably impacted student participation and dropout rates, and further affect the overall engagement in online courses. According to Lee (2006),

external conditions such as peer attitudes significantly influence students' learning behaviours; however, family support and hardware conditions, such as IT infrastructure, have a comparatively lesser impact. In addition, the quality of course content on MOOC platforms directly correlates with student engagement. High-quality content and appealing teaching styles are more likely to engage students effectively. Moreover, the diverse needs of students from different backgrounds and institutions can affect MOOC completion rates, as not all learners may find MOOCs suitable for their educational requirements (Pursel *et al.*, 2016). For example, students in higher vocational colleges may not engage well with MOOCs due to strong professional requirements or application-oriented learning goals. In this case, the characteristics of the participation in MOOC learning, or what factors have led to their early drop out from the class need to be analysed. Which kinds of students should be regarded as targeted participants for MOOCs still needs to be considered.

Rizvi *et al.* (2022) argue that specific learning activities may facilitate progress in one context while hindering it in another, indicating that the effectiveness of learning activities depends on the specific learning context, learning environment and conditions. Similarly, Liaw and Huang (2013) note that the learning environment significantly impacts the efficacy of educational activities. Activities that are effective in one educational setting may not yield the same results in another. China's diverse learner population possesses varying cognitive styles, experiences of educational backgrounds, and cultural contexts. A particular learning activity may benefit some learners while being ineffective for others. Different teaching objectives necessitate tailored learning activities; for example, courses emphasising theoretical understanding may require distinct activities compared to those focused on practical skills.

The effectiveness of learning activities can also be constrained by the technological resources available to Chinese learners. When learners lack access to specific resources, the effectiveness of certain activities is lower. Consequently, teachers could employ flexible teaching methods tailored to various learning situations, including adapting strategies, utilizing diverse assessment methods, and providing additional learning materials. This perspective emphasises the importance of sensitivity to the diversity of learning contexts and highlights critical factors to consider when designing and implementing educational activities.

As global and open online courses, MOOCs attract learners from diverse cultural backgrounds, leading to varied responses to learning activities across platforms. MOOC platforms embody the concept of learning diversity and aim to meet the needs of various learners through flexible designs and rich activity types. This aligns with the views of Rizvi *et al.* (2022), who emphasise that the effectiveness of learning activities can vary based on subject matter, cultural context, and participant differences and experiences.

Previous research indicates disproportionate participation and subsequent preferences for specific types of learning activities among MOOC learners. For example, Kizilcec and Halawa (2015) found that learners from African, Asian, and Latin American countries tend to exhibit lower persistence in accessing resources and examination materials. Liu and Dong (2013) identified differences between English-speaking countries and Asian countries in their test-taking behaviour and discussion forum participation. Moreover, researchers such as Stich and Reeves (2017) argue that factors such as ethnicity, average neighbourhood household income, the national Human Development Index, and levels of social integration can influence MOOC participation across different cultural groups. They highlight the substantial gap in

retention and completion rates between learners from less developed and more developed countries. Uchidiuno *et al.* (2018) noted that preferences for learning activities may vary by region, with some learners prefer reading-based materials while others prefer video-based content.

2.12.2 Different Educational Backgrounds and Ideological Perspectives

MOOCs are primarily offered by Western universities and taught by Western lecturers. Due to the diverse educational backgrounds and cultural contexts of learners, some courses may reflect distinct ideological perspectives or convey the personal values of the lecturers (Hairston, 1992). These factors can significantly influence learners' choices and engagement with MOOCs. For example, learners might not be comfortable with or understand the foreign political contexts or personal stances presented in the courses. As a result, students may not be interested in those types of courses or disagree with the content, resulting in decreased motivation, lower engagement, and a higher likelihood of course incompleteness.

Altbach (2015) believes that, for students from countries such as China, India, or those in the Middle East, the cultural and ideological content of MOOCs may feel unfamiliar or may be difficult to understand. For example, learners might encounter discussions on topics such as democracy, human rights, or economic policies that reflect Western ideological perspectives (Liang, 2022). Such topics may be different from the cultural or political norms of the learners' countries, making it challenging for them to engage fully with the course material. Furthermore, these learners might find it difficult to relate to the case studies or examples used, which may not be relevant or applicable to their own experiences. As a result, this can lead to lower motivation, engagement, and even course dropout.

In addition, different educational systems emphasise different approaches to learning, which can also affect engagement in MOOCs. For example, Western educational systems often promote critical thinking, individual expression, and active participation (Liang and Fung, 2021). These differences in pedagogical approaches can pose challenges for students who are unfamiliar with or uncomfortable in such learning environments. Language barriers may also further influence learners' engagement in MOOCs. Although some of the MOOC platforms offer subtitles, the primary language is often English, which may not be the first language of many learners. This linguistic challenge can add to pressure on students when they engage in MOOCs, as students must focus not only on understanding the course content but also, for some, on translating the language of delivery.

2.12.3 Different Course Characteristics

Another possible reason for high dropout rates in MOOCs is that these platforms may not be well-suited for certain courses, particularly those requiring hands-on, practical learning, such as engineering courses (Staubitz *et al.*, 2015). For example, language programming, a fundamental component of computer science education, requires students to grasp complex concepts like computer system architecture, assembly language design, and development methods. The current MOOC platforms cannot provide the necessary interactive and practical experiences required for mastering these skills. According to Gillett-Swan (2017), the limitations of online courses are evident in subjects that traditionally require in-person instruction, such as anatomy. These courses are not ideally taught entirely online, as students may not acquire the necessary depth of knowledge if it is only delivered through videos on MOOC platforms. In the context of Chinese higher education, where both teachers and students are accustomed to traditional classroom settings, it may be more effective to

combine MOOCs with offline courses. This mixed approach can serve as a valuable supplement to conventional teaching methods, aligning better with students' learning habits and thereby enhancing their engagement with MOOCs.

Although students might theoretically choose to transition certain courses to MOOC platforms based on their classroom experiences, their previous online learning experiences play a more important role in their decision to attend MOOCs. This thesis will, therefore, analyse the strengths and weaknesses of MOOCs by surveying students' experiences with these platforms, aiming to explore the potential challenges MOOCs face in Chinese higher education, for example, in relation to course selection.

2.12.4 Rigidity

Since most MOOC platforms offer completely open and free registration with no limits on enrolment, many learners register with initial enthusiasm, driven by interest or curiosity. However, as time passes, this enthusiasm often wanes, and they gradually give up learning (Zheng *et al.*, 2015). This phenomenon is common, contributing to the consistently high dropout rates observed in MOOCs. For example, on the edX platform, jointly offered by MIT and Harvard University, more than over 150,000 learners registered for the Circuits and Electronics course, only 8,240 students completed the 14-week course and took the final exam, the rest of the students gave up the course at different times, resulting in a dropout rate of 95% (Breslow *et al.*, 2013). This issue is not unique to edX. In 2011, Stanford University launched the “Introduction to the Database” course, where out of more than 90,000 registrants, only about 7,000 learners completed the course (Morris, 2013).

2.12.5 Teachers' Attitudes and the Quality of the Courses

A survey in Chinese People's Daily in 2014 showed that teachers' attitudes toward participating in MOOCs are generally not positive, and students' evaluations are mixed. The findings suggest that regardless of the mode of instruction, whether in the classroom or online, teachers remain essential. According to Xu, Deng and Zhao (2020), one of the challenges in the development of MOOCs at Chinese universities is the difficulty in finding suitable teachers to record and deliver these courses. While there are volunteers eager to experiment with MOOCs, most teachers prefer to wait and assess the effectiveness of MOOCs before participating. They are concerned that focusing on MOOC design may require a much time investment, potentially detracting from their teaching and research responsibilities.

Robb and Shellenbarger (2021) argue that capturing students' attention in MOOCs added additional challenges. Traditional classroom teachers may lack the experience needed to effectively teach on MOOC platforms, and they cannot ensure that their courses are relevant to students' diverse learning backgrounds. This uncertainty may contribute to teachers' reluctance to attempt online teaching. Furthermore, these challenges can also lead to lower student engagement, as some courses may fail to meet students' learning needs. Wu and Wang (2022) also argue that the core competitive element of MOOC teaching is the quality of the courses. While there are many courses available on MOOC platforms, without experienced teachers' design and delivery, the quality of the courses varies significantly, which leads to too few high-quality offerings to attract students effectively. This lack of high-quality courses leaves both teachers and students feeling frustrated, which can negatively impact student engagement.

2.12.6 Ineffective Credit Transfer

In addition, there are fewer credit transfer opportunities for MOOCs, and it is also a reason why students are not motivated. However, some regions and universities are developing new measures to address this issue (Zheng, Chen and Burgos, 2018). For example, the Guangdong Provincial Department of Education issued the "Opinions on the Implementation of the Credit System Management in Ordinary Colleges and Universities," pointing out that colleges and universities will also explore the credit system certification for Internet learning platforms such as MOOCs later. Universities like Tsinghua University, Shanghai Jiaotong University, and Shenzhen University have also attempted to integrate a credit system into MOOC teaching to acknowledge students' academic achievements through online courses. In Tsinghua University's "Circuit Principles" class in 2017, several students earned credits by studying via MOOCs and passing the final exam (Zheng, Chen and Burgos, 2018). These changes suggest that it is beneficial for students to participate in MOOCs if there is accreditation of their learning, which may increase students' motivation to complete the whole course.

2.12.7 Integrity Issues

Ensuring that students who earn credits and diplomas through MOOCs are the ones who complete the coursework is a significant challenge, particularly without traditional face-to-face classes and assessments with teachers (Northcutt, Ho and Chuang, 2016). University teachers have expressed concerns about the credibility of MOOC accreditation, noting the lack of effective methods for verifying student identity and work. For example, Fox's (2013) research showed that a professor at the University of California at Berkeley, discovered 20 similar assignments submitted in his software engineering course, highlighting the issue of widespread plagiarism.

In traditional classroom settings, class sizes typically range from 20 to 100 students. At the postgraduate level, small class sizes of around 20 students are often used to ensure and enhance teaching quality. However, MOOCs are characterised by their potential for large-scale enrolment, with student numbers reaching hundreds of thousands. To maintain teaching quality, MOOC providers have implemented various methods, such as computer-aided analysis, examinations, and peer evaluations, which allow students to learn from and assess each other but some integrity issues still exist and are difficult to solve (Yousef *et al.*, 2014), which also raised concerns about the credibility and reliability of the credentials awarded through some MOOC platforms (Smahi, Labouidya and El Khadiri, 2023).

2.12.8 Issues Around Developing Comprehensive Ability

Huang (2021) believes that during a university education period, beyond acquiring knowledge from various courses, it is important to develop a range of skills and improve comprehensive qualities such as collaboration, communication, and social interaction. These essential skills, however, are not easily cultivated through online learning alone. Huang (2021) further observes that many people consider their university years to be among the most significant periods of their lives, with the most impactful memories often stemming from living with classmates and forming deep friendships during their studies.

In contrast, MOOCs primarily facilitate the transfer of knowledge and information but cannot replicate the authentic campus atmosphere or the richness of the university experience. According to Xie, Siau, and Nah (2020), the emotional connection between teachers and students, which is integral to traditional classroom settings, is difficult to foster in MOOCs. As a result, learners may perceive MOOCs as mere online courses, lacking the depth and engagement of in-person education. This

emotional disconnect can lead students to view MOOCs as less important, further affect their level of engagement.

2.12.9 Content Updating Issues

With the development and innovation in science and technology, many courses, especially those in the fields of law, medicine, and computer science, require frequent updates to remain relevant and accurate. For example, in disciplines such as law, where legislative changes and legal cases continually reshape the content, each revision of legal regulations introduces new concepts that students must learn, making it necessary to regularly update course materials to reflect the latest developments. This arose a challenge for MOOCs, as their content is typically pre-recorded and not easily adjusted.

Additionally, challenges also related to teacher resource allocation and recording costs must be effectively coordinated and addressed (Zheng *et al.*, 2016). Ensuring that MOOCs remain up-to-date demands significant time, energy and resources. MOOC instructors must spend time revising course content, re-recording lectures, and updating supplementary materials to reflect current knowledge and practices. This process is complex, especially when considering the involvement and time required in recording high-quality video content and integrating new materials into existing courses. Moreover, the cost of updating and maintaining MOOCs is significant. Recording new lectures, editing videos, and updating digital platforms all require substantial financial investment. Without proper planning and allocation of resources, MOOCs risk falling behind in delivering up-to-date knowledge, ultimately impacting the learning experience and value for students (Guerrero, Heaton and Urbano,2021).

2.12.10 Issues with Teachers' Ability

According to Neo and Neo's (2004) research, under the traditional university teaching system in China, teachers primarily rely on textbooks and informational multimedia tools for their teaching strategies and methods. In the classroom, multimedia stations are equipped with materials such as audio, video, and graphics, which can be used easily by university teachers with a basic level of IT skills and experience. However, in the context of online education, teachers face greater teaching pressure and more requirements of MOOCs. They are required not only to possess a high level of teaching literacy and experience but also to have advanced new media teaching skills (Traxler, 2018). For example, teachers must be able to create and develop video content, edit and produce these videos, and upload them to deliver high-quality teaching materials to their students. Additionally, university teachers must effectively use the Internet to collect, organise, and upload high-quality resources that meet the diverse learning needs of their students in order to give better support. While not all university teachers may possess these skills, it is essential that some within a department are capable of managing these courses effectively (Keengwe, Onchwari and Agamba, 2014).

2.12.11 Issues with Learner Motivation

Several motivation theories are relevant to the issues discussed in this thesis, particularly in the field of education. These include intrinsic and extrinsic motivation theory (Ryan and Deci, 2000), self-determination theory (SDT) (Ryan, 2017), the ARCS model (Keller, 1987), social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1989), and expectancy theory (Van Eerde and Thierry, 1996). Each of these theories can independently contribute to understanding outcomes in the learning process without reliance on other educational theories.

Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation Theory discusses motivation in two aspects: intrinsic motivation, which refers to engaging in activities driven by people's internal desires, and extrinsic motivation, which is influenced by the outside environment or factors such as rewards or the avoidance of punishment (Ryan and Deci, 2000). Both types of motivation play a significant role in learning and are widely employed in educational studies to analyse learners' behaviours (Abeysekera and Dawson, 2015). Another one is the Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which posits that autonomy, competence, and relatedness are three fundamental psychological needs that can contribute to intrinsic motivation and optimal functioning (Ryan, 2017). This theory emphasises the importance of autonomy, suggesting that individuals should have control over their actions while seeking challenges and acquiring skills to achieve a sense of accomplishment and foster emotional connections with others. When these three needs are met, individuals are more likely to engage intrinsically and have positive learning experiences. Moreover, the ARCS Model, an acronym for Attention, Relevance, Confidence, and Satisfaction, argues that these four elements can enhance engagement and effective learning experiences (Keller, 1987). "Attention" refers to maintaining focus through strategies that stimulate learners' curiosity and interest. "Relevance" emphasises the connection between the learning material and the learners' personal and practical interests. Learners are more motivated and better engaged when they understand how the content relates to their goals and interests. Strategies such as providing clear instructions and offering opportunities for practice and efficient feedback can boost learners' confidence and motivation. "Satisfaction" involves recognising learners' achievements through feedback and acknowledgement (Keller, 1987).

Social Cognitive Theory is also famous, which highlights the role of observational learning, cognition, and social interactions in shaping people's behaviours and development (Bandura, 1989). The core to this theory is the idea that individuals learn

through observation and modelling, acquiring new behaviours, attitudes, and skills by observing others. In addition, the Expectancy Theory (or expectancy theory of motivation) posits that individuals choose specific behaviours based on their expectations of the outcomes (Van Eerde and Thierry, 1996). This theory focuses on how individuals deal with different motivational elements.

All these theories emphasise the importance of autonomy in learning and have been developed further. Dornyei (2002) asserts that learning motivation is the driving force behind learners' persistence, shaping their consciousness, enthusiasm, inclination, and selectivity in participating in learning activities. The learner's behaviour is influenced by various motivational factors, making it essential to enhance both internal and external motivation to cultivate interest in learning, thus encouraging participation and completion of MOOCs to reduce dropout rates. Zhenguo *et al.* (2017) argue that it benefits MOOC platforms to encourage Chinese learners to engage actively in discussions and complete courses by offering incentives such as points, scholarships, and credits. For example, grades could be exchanged for certificates or scholarships which can be redeemed for future study. This is in accordance with both expectancy theory and self-determination theory. In China, certificates are significant for evaluating graduates and selecting new employees, suggesting that providing certification may enhance learners' motivation to participate in and complete MOOCs, thereby reducing dropout rates.

Dillahunt *et al.* (2016) suggest that MOOC platforms could collaborate with recruitment websites to recommend relevant job opportunities for learners who have completed MOOCs, thereby attracting more participants. This approach aligns with the self-determination theory. Additionally, MOOC platforms could also cooperate with some Chinese universities to launch online degree programmes. After

completing all the courses and successfully passing the exams, the student would be able to obtain a relevant certificate through MOOCs, which are recognised by the university. This would enable learners aiming for specific jobs to enhance their employability in companies requiring particular skills and knowledge. According to the competitive job market in China, such initiatives could significantly assist learners in securing relevant employment.

2.12.12 Design of MOOCs Content

Some scholars argue for the need to optimise the design of MOOC teaching content. De Freitas, Morgan, and Gibson (2015) note that because MOOCs employ a new online teaching method, some teachers and researchers do not consider MOOCs to be a comprehensive teaching approach. Instead, they view them only as teaching resources or tools, which is similar to other free online courses. Therefore, they believe MOOCs are less important and relevant to students compared to traditional face-to-face classroom methods. This perception has led to a lack of attention to the design of MOOC teaching content, with the specific educational characteristics and instructional design principles of MOOCs often being ignored. Moreover, García-Peñalvo, Fidalgo-Blanco, and Sein-Echaluce (2018) observe that MOOCs, which originated in American universities, incorporate the fundamental elements of a traditional curriculum, such as teacher-student interaction and online interactive sessions. They believe it is necessary to design MOOCs systematically in order to deal with the learning needs of students, clarify the learning objectives and formulate learning objectives to standardise evaluation and teaching strategies. This approach could help Chinese learners identify similarities between MOOCs and traditional classroom courses, thereby encouraging them to engage more with the MOOC learning method and adjust their study habits accordingly.

Jing (2015) further suggests that MOOCs differ from conventional courses in their potential to shift the focus from teacher-centred to student-centred learning. However, teachers delivering MOOCs may encounter challenges, such as lower learner engagement and a lack of direct supervision. Jing (2015) advocates that MOOC platforms and content designers should integrate specific design principles and educational theories to create suitable teaching methods that meet the demands of teaching strategies and align with Chinese learners' needs and learning preferences. Such an approach could facilitate the development and effectiveness of MOOCs in China.

Rizvi *et al.* (2022) believe that there is no ideal combination of learning activities that works for all learners. This view acknowledges the diversity among learners and emphasises that each individual has unique learning styles, needs, and educational backgrounds. Therefore, no single set of learning activities can be universally effective for all learners. Their perspective supports the concept of personalised learning, which suggests that teaching should prioritise individualised methods and resources to better meet learners' needs. For example, teachers should be flexible in adapting instructional strategies to accommodate the diverse learning requirements of students. MOOCs, in this context, can be regarded as a valuable method of learning. By offering personalised learning options, MOOCs enable learners to choose courses and materials that align with their interests, subject needs, and learning aims (Milligan and Littlejohn, 2017).

As previously discussed, MOOCs provide a variety of teaching resources, including text, videos, interactive modules, and other methods which can be tailored to different learning preferences. Some learners may prefer acquiring knowledge through reading, while others might like watching videos or engaging in online discussions. For

example, a strong preference for video content over text has been observed among learners from South Asia (Rizvi *et al.*, 2022). MOOCs support autonomous learning by encouraging learners to ask questions, seek answers, and receive feedback. This process helps to build learning autonomy and fosters a sense of responsibility in learners. Additionally, the flexibility of MOOCs allows learners to arrange their study schedules according to their personal timetables.

While there is no single learning method that fits all learners, it is still possible to identify effective teaching strategies that achieve positive results in most situations. Assami, Daoudi, and Ajhoun (2018) note that many MOOCs employ customised assessment methods, encouraging learners to demonstrate their knowledge in various ways. This approach helps reduce the potential disadvantages of a standardised assessment method, ensuring a fairer evaluation process for all learners.

2.12.13 Continuing Professional Learning for Staff

Hew and Cheung (2014) believe that the challenges of online teaching arise from the varying levels of preparedness among the different groups involved. As far as relevant groups are concerned, learners, teachers, and education managers may not have been fully prepared for the challenges of delivering MOOCs, which could influence engagement and completion rates. For example, during the recent COVID-19 pandemic, which can be regarded as a fast-developing period of MOOCs. When the COVID-19 pandemic suddenly broke out, many educators lacked the knowledge, attitudes, and skills necessary for transitioning from traditional classroom teaching to online courses. Teachers with no prior experience in online instruction required targeted training on how to develop and deliver online content effectively. Additionally, students also needed guidance on how to adapt to this new mode of

learning. As well as school administrators and local education administration departments, also faced significant challenges in managing this shift.

Initially, some educational staff underestimated the complexities of the government's "Class Suspended but Learning Continues" directive, simply asking classroom teachers to conduct live-streamed or recorded lessons. This may have affected learner engagement, highlighting the need for comprehensive training for those delivering MOOCs, especially during such specific periods. However, after the government announced remote teaching and universities decided to transition to online instruction, many institutions began offering formal training and guidance for MOOCs and other online teaching methods. This support enabled both teachers and students to better understand and adapt to using MOOCs, ultimately allowing them to overcome the challenges posed by the pandemic and even to foster new approaches to online learning (Zhang *et al.*, 2019). With official backing and instruction, universities and learners were able not only to navigate the difficulties of the COVID-19 pandemic but also to drive innovation in MOOC education.

2.12.14 Guidance for Learner Engagement with MOOCs

In online learning, analysing learner characteristics is fundamental to selecting and organising teaching content and designing effective strategies (Reigeluth and Curtis, 2013). They argue that even a basic analysis of learner characteristics can significantly inform the choice of teaching methods and media. MOOC learners differ notably from traditional classroom students. According to Alario-Hoyos *et al.* (2017), MOOC participants often have clear learning goals, substantial practical experience, high self-learning abilities, and a need for effective instruction. However, they typically have limited free time, varying levels of autonomous learning skills, and an uneven foundation in online learning. Based on the analysis of the characteristics of

MOOC learners, some researchers suggest that their engagement could lead to a lower completion rate. Dornyei (2002) notes that motivation significantly influences learning behaviours, and many MOOC learners lack motivation due to the challenges mentioned above.

Xiong *et al.* (2015) argue that one reason for lower engagement in Chinese MOOCs is that teachers often have a limited understanding of learners' prior knowledge and cognitive abilities. They do not conduct adequate needs analyses to identify the gaps between learners' current ability and their expected achievements. Due to China's large and diverse student population, educational backgrounds vary significantly across different regions, reflecting the uneven development of education. In this context, Sergis, Sampson, and Pelliccione (2017) suggest that course descriptions should clearly inform the teaching objectives, course duration, content types, and other relevant information. A short promotional video can be an effective way to provide this information, allowing learners to make suitable decisions about course selection. In Chinese universities, providing such detailed course descriptions can help students choose the appropriate courses, thereby increasing engagement and completion rates. As noted by Wigfield, Cambria, and Eccles (2012), using different kinds of methods to reinforce and improve learners' motivation is important, which will be discussed in detail later.

2.12.15 Redefining MOOC and Lower Completion Rates

The previous sections discussed completion rates in MOOCs, noting that while these courses attract high enrolment, they also experience significant dropout rates (Yousef *et al.*, 2014). To successfully complete MOOC content on time, learners must possess strong self-learning abilities (Kennedy, 2013). In China, however, many learners lack self-motivation for online learning, and their limited learning autonomy may

negatively affect their engagement with MOOCs (Sun *et al.*, 2019). This thesis aims to identify the factors influencing low MOOC engagement and analyse these issues through research on student engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education.

Scholars offer varying perspectives on MOOC completion rates. Stevanovic's (2014) research indicates that fewer than 10% of MOOC learners complete the final exams and courses. Similarly, Jordan (2014), who analysed 39 MOOCs, found completion rates ranging from 0.9% to 36.1%, with most courses averaging around a 5% completion rate. Perna *et al.* (2014) also found completion rates ranging from 3% to 4% after analysing 16 MOOCs at the University of Pennsylvania. Although the completion rates of MOOCs are often low, they do not necessarily indicate failure; instead, they highlight potential challenges in MOOC teaching and learning.

Jin, Huang, and Yin (2018) note that in the six years since MOOCs gained popularity in China and became a popular learning tool, the educational model has been praised for its new educational model and its impact on teaching and learning, and also provoked some reviews and criticisms. A common critique is the "low user completion rate" (Yousef *et al.*, 2014), with many participants dropping out sharply within one or two weeks after starting a course. For example, Harvard's courses on the edX platform have a completion rate of only 6% (Ho *et al.*, 2014).

Li (2015) shared his experience of taking multiple MOOCs, completing only one and receiving a completion certificate, but still gaining valuable knowledge and experience. He shared his experiences of participating in MOOCs on the ChinaX platform: although he did not finish all of them, he was still happy that he learned something, which illustrates that the most important significance of MOOCs for learners is no longer to receive one certificate from one course but to acquire more

experience and knowledge. Li (2015) also added that students should be proud of participating a small part in these MOOC programmes. Although MOOCs have always had low completion rates, there is also an indication that a lot of learners have participated in the courses. Large scales of participation can also be seen as evidence of the development of online learning. This also suggests that for some learners, the primary value of MOOCs lies not in obtaining a certificate but in acquiring knowledge.

Supporting Li's perspective, Pugh, the vice president of edX, argues that the often-cited 5% completion rate reflects only those who received a certificate, not the active learners who can benefit from the MOOCs (Li, 2015). Zheng *et al.* (2015) also emphasise that the motivation to learn via MOOCs often stems from a desire for knowledge rather than certification. Therefore, scholars should focus less on completion rates and more on understanding students' motivations for enrolling.

Xing *et al.* (2016) also believe that MOOCs, as massive open learning resources, naturally exhibit low completion rates due to their size and openness. Onah, Sinclair, and Boyatt (2014) share a similar view, suggesting that low completion rates should not be seen as a barrier to MOOC development. It is a common situation that exists in online learning methods and should not be the only indicator for evaluating MOOCs. Unlike university courses, which have strict course completion requirements for graduation, MOOCs do not impose such obligations. Thus, MOOCs are less binding than traditional classroom courses.

2.12.16 Challenges for MOOCs in the Field of Public Awareness

Bozkurt and Keefer (2018) believe that knowledge and pedagogy are inherently interconnected and cannot exist independently. They are reflective of specific academic traditions, methodological orientations, and teaching philosophies that characterise particular academic systems. Academics from developed countries, who often shape the content of MOOCs, are likely motivated to engage a global audience (Khan *et al.*, 2018). However, their work may be influenced by their own academic orientations. Since the majority of materials used in MOOCs are derived from Western academic systems, the examples and content typically originate from the United States or Europe, which can lead to cultural dissonance when these courses are delivered in other contexts, such as China.

Altbach (2014) agrees, noting that the dominance of Western countries in academic literature renders them particularly influential. The scholars who create and design MOOCs generally come from top universities in English-speaking countries, and their course content is often shaped by their own educational backgrounds (Altbach, 2014). However, the millions of students worldwide who enrol in MOOCs appear less concerned with the underlying knowledge or pedagogical philosophy they are studying. Likewise, universities in China and other developing countries that adopt MOOCs do not seem to prioritise the origins or orientations of the knowledge or the educational philosophies behind the MOOC pedagogy. This lack of consideration could potentially lead to cultural tensions (Altbach, 2014).

2.13 Opportunities and Changes Brought by MOOCs

2.13.1 Changing the Traditional Concept of Teaching and Learning

MOOCs have significantly transformed traditional concepts of teaching and learning (Chengjie, 2015). With the widespread development and implementation of MOOCs by numerous colleges and universities, traditional educational practices are being challenged by multiple requirements and changes. As Serdyukov (2017) observed, MOOCs are no longer dominated by a single lecturer nor confined to a single teaching system. The transformation from manual teaching management to intelligent teaching management has altered the traditional image of education. In the information age, the teaching models facilitated by MOOCs are gradually gaining acceptance (Serdyukov, 2017). This trend is particularly important for Chinese learners, as it provides them with greater access to current, relevant, and online learning resources, which will be beneficial to enhance their educational experience. This diversification of teaching practices allows for a more dynamic and learner-centred approach, which contrasts with the often rigid structures of traditional classrooms.

The changing concept of teaching and learning also extends to how teachers and universities perceive their roles in the educational process. In traditional classroom settings, teachers often act as the primary source of knowledge for students, controlling the flow of information. MOOCs, however, have made it easier to reframe the teacher's role. Teachers no longer only deliver content; instead, they curate materials, encourage collaboration, and support autonomous learning (Adam, 2023). This development in the traditional concept of teaching challenges traditional power in education, promoting a more equal relationship between teachers and students.

2.13.2 The Democratisation of Education and Learning

Littlejohn *et al.* (2016) note that the initial promise of MOOCs to democratise education and offer future-focused, high-quality learning for all people through improved access and radically new forms of learning methods has diminished in recent years, particularly in the Western world.

Several factors have contributed to the decrease in enthusiasm for MOOCs. While early MOOCs attracted a large number of learners with their free and open features, later, people began to pay attention to the lower completion rate and dropout rate. Many learners give up after starting a course, resulting in relatively few completing the course, leading to questions about the actual impact and effectiveness of MOOCs. Additionally, some early MOOC platforms, initially appealing because of their reduced fees or, in some cases, free access, have faced challenges in sustaining this business model. Some platforms have later shifted from free-open to a fee-based model, which may undermine their original intention of promoting the democratisation of education (Rambe and Moeti, 2017).

2.13.3 Expanding the Content of Traditional Teaching

MOOCs have expanded the scope of traditional teaching (Chengjie, 2015). Supported by modern information technology, MOOCs connect students to huge amounts of knowledge and information, which can be immediately relayed to the students easily and then integrated into the teaching. In the context of this information explosion, MOOCs have emerged as a significant educational innovation (Boyatt *et al.*, 2014). The MOOC teaching model has expanded traditional content by incorporating courses from other universities and resources from various platforms and enhancing both professional skills and knowledge integration. Through MOOCs, learners can easily

access learning resources, creating an engaging learning environment that boosts their motivation and autonomous learning ability.

MOOCs can integrate resources from multiple universities and platforms, allowing for a great diversity of subject matter and instructional perspectives, which greatly enhances the variety of education available to students (Qi, Zhang and Zhang, 2023). This expansion is particularly important in fields where knowledge is rapidly evolving, such as law, technology, and medicine. By incorporating MOOCs into traditional teaching models, teachers can supplement their curriculum with up-to-date research, emerging technologies, and the latest academic resources. In addition to professional skills, MOOCs support knowledge integration across multiple disciplines. In traditional teaching environments, access to academic programmes is often limited, with fewer opportunities for cross-disciplinary learning. MOOCs, by contrast, promote a more comprehensive educational approach, allowing students to access courses from diverse fields and integrate knowledge from multiple disciplines into their studies (Williams, 2024). For example, a student studying environmental science could also enrol in MOOCs on data analytics, economics, or political science, thus gaining a more nuanced understanding of how environmental issues intersect with other global challenges.

2.13.4 Improving the Efficiency of Traditional Teaching

Khalil and Ebner (2014) noted that one of the key characteristics of the MOOC education model is its use of the developed network technology to publish course information and content. The Internet's rich resources, flexibility, and accessibility have significantly enhanced efficiency in both academic and teaching contexts. This teaching model also encourages teachers to reflect on their methods and provide constructive feedback. Khalil and Ebner's (2014) analysis demonstrate the impact of

MOOCs on traditional teaching, showing how MOOCs efficiently enrich classroom content through the Internet and thus increase learner engagement and knowledge acquisition.

MOOCs can improve efficiency by enabling teachers to reach a larger number of students without the need for classroom or requirements such as attendance in-person. Traditional classrooms are typically limited by space and time, requiring in-person attendance and regular scheduling. MOOCs can reduce these limitations, enabling teachers to deliver content to thousands of learners or more. This method not only expands the reach of educational institutions but also allows for more efficient use of teaching resources, particularly in contexts where educators may be limited in number or where access to education is geographically restricted.

2.13.5 Enhancing the Collaboration between Universities and Enterprise

MOOCs have strengthened collaboration between universities and enterprises (Burd, Smith and Reisman, 2015). Universities are responsible for providing the courses, while information technology companies are responsible for setting up the platforms and ensuring teachers' access and background maintenance. These technology companies play an essential role in enhancing the visibility of the university's brand and course offerings. As MOOC platforms support companies in launching high-quality courses, universities' reliance on these platforms also increases (Burd, Smith and Reisman, 2015). This collaboration enables both universities and enterprises to leverage their strengths: universities can focus on curriculum development and academic rigour, while the companies can ensure the scalability, accessibility, and technical functionality of MOOCs. The growing reliance on these partnerships can also enable the development of higher education by merging academic and corporate expertise.

2.13.6 Changing the Traditional Chinese Classroom Teaching

Method

The traditional approach to teaching at Chinese universities is typically "teacher-centred," where the student's role in the classroom is often underemphasised. This model can significantly impact students' motivation and initiative, leading to inefficiency and lower teaching quality (Garrett, 2008). However, integrating MOOC resources into classroom instruction can enhance students' motivation and effectiveness. The flexibility of MOOCs, such as "small pieces of time" learning, allows students to choose when, where, and how they learn, improving efficiency and stimulating initiative (Liu, 2020). The MOOC teaching model also enables the traditional classroom content and tasks to be scientifically and rationally divided into multiple parts and presented in the form, as well as offering video for students. This approach not only sparks students' interest and curiosity but also enhances their autonomy and autonomous learning to engage better in study, which effectively improves the situation of the traditional Chinese universities' single-teaching model of teacher-centred teaching.

2.13.7 Creating Personalised Educational Experiences

According to McLoughlin and Lee (2010), MOOCs generate significant amounts of educational data related to learners, leading to more personalised educational experiences. On the Internet, the data on the student's learning process can be collected and analysed. By applying psychological principles and models, alongside learning sciences and statistics, students can better adapt to their individual learning modes, allowing for more personalised choices. McLoughlin and Lee (2010) stated that this approach aligns with the continuous development of customisation in online

education, which advocates for individualised learning plans based on learners' abilities and characteristics.

Stella and Gnanam (2004) highlight that online education represents the integration of the Internet and education across borders. Information technology has transformed teaching, learner management, and evaluation in traditional education, enhancing the efficiency of educational services and providing diverse environments to optimise autonomous learning. This integration breaks the service boundaries of educational organisations, allowing previously closed education systems to adopt collaborative structures (Stella and Gnanam, 2004). MOOCs bring together a wealth of resources, both human and material, and create new divisions of labour in teaching and learning. They offer students timely learning experiences aligned with their interests, which can be adjusted based on their feedback, enabling the development of education for younger students. Simultaneously, the teacher's role has also changed and developed.

Mazoue (2013) notes that MOOCs facilitate strong interactivity, which can reduce learning costs and enhance learning efficiency, making them attractive to both learners and educators. This interactivity significantly promotes the long-term development of university teaching. With the deepening reform of the education system in China, the construction of quality online education curricula is an important link in education transformation. To ensure the quality and effect of construction, MOOC platforms should be rationally developed and applied to share educational resources, while the government and universities should provide for the construction of quality education courses.

2.14 English Language Education in China and Autonomous Learning

English language instruction, an essential subject in Chinese universities, facilitates students' further studies and international opportunities. This subject is particularly well-suited for online education, as it does not require hands-on experimentation like fields such as chemistry and can be effectively taught remotely. This study plans to conduct research among participants from English major programmes, so it is necessary to have a brief introduction to the history of English language learning in China.

English language learning has a long history in China and has gained increasing significance with globalisation. English became a compulsory subject in Chinese high schools in the mid-1920s (Yang, 2000). Following the government requirements, high schools began to offer English courses to be a foundation for English learning in universities. By the 1980s, English was also made compulsory for junior high school students. During this period, the Chinese government stipulated that students must pass English language tests at each educational transition, from junior high to high school, high school to university, and university to postgraduate studies. In 1986, it was mandated that university students pass the College English Test Band Four (CET-4) to receive their degree certificates (Zheng and Cheng, 2008), which required Chinese students to have a more professional level of English.

From 1976 to the present, China has experienced rapid development, and English language education has been recognised as an important tool for national modernisation and development. In 1982, English became the primary foreign language taught in Chinese junior high schools. The first International Conference on English Teaching was held in Guangzhou in 1985 (Lam, 2005), leading to an increase

in the number of English-language institutions and students majoring in English. By 1996, the number of English major students reached 55,899 (Cen, 1997), and the number of institutions offering English major courses grew from 8 in 1952 to 304 in 1996 and 420 in 2002 (Supervision Committee for Foreign Language Majors, 2002). By 2001, there were 150,000 students enrolled in English major programmes. China's accession to the World Trade Organisation in November 2001 and Beijing's hosting of the 2008 Olympic Games further accelerated the development of English education in China (Yuhua, 2002).

As a lingua franca, English facilitates international exchanges in culture, technology, and economics. Wong and Looi (2010) note that advancements in mobile technology and the Internet have prompted a shift in English education from traditional classroom settings to online formats. This transition allows learners to experience a more independent and personalised learning environment, enabling them to organise their studies according to their prior knowledge and ability levels.

Holec (1996) identifies two primary goals of foreign language teaching: one is to help students acquire language knowledge and communication skills, while the other is to cultivate their ability to learn independently. He defines autonomy as a learner's capacity to take responsibility for their own learning, a potential that can be realised in specific environments but may not be universally applicable. Little (2003) expands on this concept, describing autonomy as the independent ability to think critically. With autonomy, learners can make informed decisions and exhibit independent behaviours. Joshi (2011) emphasises that autonomous learning is fundamentally a psychological connection between the learning process and the learners' context, meaning that learners are fully engaged in their education. Dickinson (1995) also believes that learner autonomy broadly refers to the educational process that can lead

to the development of personal self-thinking ability, and it narrowly refers to the ability to independently make decisions related to learning activities and the ability to successfully implement these decisions. These responsibilities must be embraced by autonomous learners through supportive content, diverse learning methods, personalised learning progress, flexible scheduling, suitable materials, and self-monitoring techniques. These skills are essential for Chinese learners to develop through their engagement with MOOCs.

Although definitions of "learning autonomy" vary among researchers, a consensus exists on several key aspects. Scholars such as Gamble *et al.* (2012), as well as Sakai, Takagi, and Chu (2010), agree that learner autonomy involves taking responsibility for one's own learning and recognising that decision-making abilities are not inherently possessed. To develop learner autonomy, it is important for both teachers and learners to cultivate awareness of the learning process, including active participation. Teachers play a significant guiding role in this regard (Kartel *et al.*, 2022). Lamb (2009) and Dickinson (1995) suggest that there are varying degrees of learner autonomy and that it is an unstable factor influenced by numerous conditions, including time, energy, and physical health. Therefore, diverse methods should be employed to cultivate learner autonomy across different teaching environments, taking into account the specific circumstances and characteristics of learners.

2.15 Summary

In recent years, online education has transformed conventional perceptions of traditional education. The shift from basic "face-to-face" or "teacher-centred" instruction to the utilization of the Internet has broadened the scope of knowledge and elevated the social status of universities, contributing to the centralisation of knowledge. This evolution, driven by advancements on the Internet and online

learning, has reshaped learners' cognition and awareness, resulting in innovative changes in educational concepts and teaching methods (Bakkenes, Vermunt and Wubbels, 2010). Despite the increase of online courses and the widespread adoption of MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic, the integration of MOOCs with traditional classroom education remains a significant area for further investigation. This thesis will analyse the current engagement of learners with MOOCs in Chinese higher education, aiming to identify potential challenges faced by Chinese universities in delivering MOOCs, investigate the specific factors related to student motivation and the development of autonomous learning that might affect learners' engagement with MOOCs and to explore the future prospects of MOOCs in this context.

MOOCs have also introduced several new education forms, such as automatic correction, artificial intelligence problem solving, immediate learning outcomes, instant feedback, and online Q&A, which can be an improvement and supplement of the traditional classroom teaching form (Glance, Forsey and Riley, 2013). However, a comprehensive data model for personalised education has not been established, and virtual reality technology remains underdeveloped. In addition, the dropout rate needs to be reduced. Society, universities and learners themselves all need to adjust to MOOCs (Zhou, 2016). Despite these challenges, online education is still in the development stage. A review of the literature reveals several characteristics of MOOCs; while they offer numerous advantages, their development in China presents specific challenges. This thesis aims to identify these challenges, enhance the learners' autonomous learning ability via MOOCs and investigate the future development of MOOCs in Chinese higher education.

The literature indicates that, following rapid growth, MOOCs have established a strong reputation for integrating pedagogical resources within Chinese universities

(Zhou, 2016). The quantity of MOOC offerings surged from 3,200 in 2017 to 12,500 in 2021, representing nearly a threefold increase (Zhao, Jing and Zhao, 2021). Meanwhile, the number of enrolled students rose from 55 million to over 200 million. The variety of courses has expanded from general public offerings to include foundational professional courses, specialised courses, and experimental courses. As Czerniewicz, Deacon, and Small (2014) noted, MOOCs are forming a system that encompasses a broader range of professional categories and narrows the educational gaps online.

Throughout this literature review, numerous studies have highlighted the significance of MOOCs for Chinese learners and teachers. MOOCs represent a novel learning paradigm that may eventually supplant traditional classroom instruction. Emphasising learner engagement can assist teachers in developing more effective courses. Furthermore, this process encourages learners to reflect on optimising their online study time. Despite extensive research on MOOCs by scholars such as Li (2015), Jing (2015), and Huang (2019), the topic of learner engagement in higher education in China warrants further exploration and analysis. Thus, this research aims to investigate the challenges associated with delivering MOOCs in Chinese higher education, examine the factors influencing learner engagement, and explore how traditional teaching methods can be effectively integrated with MOOCs for Chinese students. The subsequent chapter will outline the methodologies for data collection in this study.

Chapter 3: Theoretical Framework and Methodology

3.1 Introduction

Previous research and literature have highlighted areas that remain underexplored in the context of learner engagement with MOOCs in higher education in China. While existing studies provide a broad overview of MOOCs in China, they often lack an in-depth examination of specific aspects such as participants' experiences with MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic. These gaps in the literature present an opportunity for further investigation into this new research. In this thesis, the identified gaps have informed the development of research questions, focusing on MOOCs, and learner motivation and engagement, learning autonomy within MOOCs, the role of MOOCs in China's educational context, and the evolution of MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic. The relevant literature underpins this study, forming the theoretical framework that guides the research.

By analysing the previous research and investigating the gaps in the literature, there are five research questions which have been developed and designed for this study:

1. What are the potential challenges and benefits to Chinese students in relation to MOOC learning, specifically with regarding to enhancing motivation, developing engagement and building autonomy?
2. In what ways have MOOCs affected aspects of teaching and learning such as traditional classroom practices and learner engagement?
3. What are the specific factors, in relation to student motivation and the development of autonomous learning, that might affect learners' engagement with their learning via

MOOCs? In what ways are learners affected by this new method of learning?

4. What is the possible future of MOOCs? In what ways can MOOCs contribute to the development of stronger learner engagement in Higher Education in China in future?

5. How and in what ways did MOOCs develop a different education practice and delivery during the COVID-19 pandemic to support students' individual motivation, and ultimately engagement in their learning?

Varpio *et al.* (2020) argue that a theoretical framework offers a mode of thinking and an explanatory structure to help researchers understand and explain research phenomena. Methodology, on the other hand, guides the specific operational steps and technical approaches necessary for implementing the study and ensuring the reliability of results. Theoretical frameworks and methodologies are interdependent (D'Amour *et al.*, 2005). According to Grant and Osanloo (2014), the theoretical framework provides the foundation and direction for research, while the methodology supplies the techniques needed to achieve research objectives. In this thesis, the research questions will inform the selection of the theoretical framework by identifying the key concepts and relationships the study aims to explore, which will, in turn, support the methodology and guide the development of questionnaires and interview questions for the participants.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

Bibri (2019) states that “theories are formulated to explain, predict, and understand phenomena and, in many cases, to challenge and extend existing knowledge within

the limits of critical bounding assumptions” (p.179). In research, the theoretical framework is an important component, serving as the structure that underpins the theory of the study. It introduces and describes the theories that focus the research and guide the answering of research questions. According to Swanson and Chermack (2013), a theoretical framework encompasses concepts that help readers understand the theory and principles of the research objective, frame the research, and reference relevant literature, as well as incorporate existing theories used in the study.

The theoretical framework aims to present and explain key theories that form the foundation of the research. These theories support the research analysis, aid in interpreting the results, and provide generalizations where applicable (Swanson and Chermack, 2013). In this section, I have outlined two key theories that inform this study, demonstrating how the research builds upon established ideas. Exploring foundational theories developed by other researchers is essential for understanding relevant concepts and connecting the researcher to existing knowledge through the guidance of relevant theories (Osanloo and Grant, 2016). In the context of examining student engagement with MOOCs in higher education in China, the theories related to autonomous learning and motivation factors influencing online learning will be presented and analysed to further the development of this research.

3.2.1 Theoretical Framework of This Thesis

According to the literature related to this thesis, various factors may influence learner engagement with MOOCs in higher education in China, such as the development of MOOCs, internet-related challenges, educational diversity, and the benefits MOOCs offer learners after graduation. Factors inhibiting learner engagement may also arise, such as disparities in educational resources and differing social policies across regions, as discussed in the context and literature review chapters.

Theoretical frameworks in educational research emphasise the customization of learning in online and networked environments, offering learners greater autonomy and flexibility, resulting in more personalised learning experiences (Saadatmand and Kumpulainen, 2014). Their research explores the personalisation of learning in digital and networked settings. In China, some universities offer fully online courses, while others do not, and some students engage entirely in online learning, while others do not. A key issue for Chinese students, however, is how to provide greater autonomy and flexibility, allowing for more personalised learning experiences. For many students, this approach may be useful in developing learning habits and skills, but most Chinese students are accustomed to teacher-centred education. This reliance on teacher-centred learning brings a challenge, as it hinders the development of autonomous learning skills (Cheng and Ding, 2021).

Cheng and Ding's (2020) recent research indicates that while learner-centred instruction has led to positive changes in students' learning behaviours, it has not successfully fostered autonomy and self-directed learning in all students. Scholars, such as Downes (2010), believe that making links between learners, resources, and networks, and creating networks of personal knowledge mediated by ubiquitous technology is the nature of learning. However, the most significant factors affecting learning behaviours and engagement in MOOCs are learner motivation and autonomy, as demonstrated by an analysis of the literature and the Chinese educational context, which is the focus of this thesis. Chinese learners, shaped by specific educational experiences, often lack learning autonomy, and this may present challenges in the context of MOOCs (Cheng and Ding, 2020).

3.2.2 Learner Motivation and Learner Autonomy in MOOCs

Hollands (2014) argue that, despite the flexibility and variety of MOOCs, participation in MOOCs has traditionally been autonomous, a learning experience unfamiliar to Chinese students who are accustomed to teacher-led instruction. While MOOCs have high enrolment rates, they also experience high dropout rates. This contrasts with traditional Chinese classrooms, where student attendance and participation are strictly monitored, thus minimizing dropout rates. MOOCs, however, require learners to have strong self-regulation to engage in the courses and present autonomous learning skills and abilities which many Chinese students lack either habit or awareness due to their limited experience of self-learning (Cheng and Ding, 2020). This inconsistency in learner engagement may affect their motivation to complete the course, which is a central focus of this thesis. The research questions were created from these issues, and the theoretical framework will guide the exploration of MOOCs in the Chinese context.

Mackness, Mak, and Williams (2010) identified autonomy, diversity, openness, and interactivity as key characteristics of MOOCs. These features cultivate students' awareness of suitable learning methods and foster self-regulated learning. However, for Chinese students, transitioning from teacher-led to autonomous learning represents a significant shift (Adams and Sargent, 2013). Chinese university students, having been immersed in a teacher-centred system, may struggle to develop personalised learning strategies because they have never questioned their learning styles and autonomy. This challenge is one of the key issues this research aims to explore.

It may take time for Chinese students to adjust to MOOCs and other unfamiliar learning methods, as they transition from classroom-based learning to online or blended learning formats. Research suggests that learner awareness of different

learning strategies is critical, as it enables them to identify methods that could help them as individuals to develop as learners (Khan *et al.*, 2017). Mackness, Mak, and Williams (2010) emphasise that the key significance is not the courses themselves but how learners engage with them and develop their understanding of effective learning strategies, such as what helps them to engage in the courses.

In this research, it has been significant to investigate the work of Mackness, Mak and Williams (2010) as this will help me to examine how Chinese learners have adapted to learning via MOOCs, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, when many learners were required to study at home and discover how their learning awareness was formed or changed. By investigating the challenges faced by these learners, the study will address the research questions related to learner engagement.

Nosratinia and Deris (2015) also highlight the challenges of changing from "focusing on teaching" to "focusing on learning". This requires students to take the initiative in acquiring knowledge, which is essential in MOOCs. Cheng and Ding (2020) discuss the fact that Chinese students who have been previously completely focused on teaching, are accustomed to teacher-led instruction, face difficulties in developing the autonomy needed for MOOCs. MOOCs to some extent force learners to think about how they can learn by themselves, as these courses demand that learners find knowledge independently and foster their own interests in learning, without the direct guidance of a teacher.

Nosratinia and Deris (2015) build on Mackness, Mak, and Williams' (2010) theory by stressing the importance of students taking responsibility for their learning, such as finding knowledge for themselves and developing their own interests and autonomy. Their research, set in a context of Iran, shows that students' reliance on classroom

organisation, standard and typical practice in their classrooms and teacher direction inhibits the development of learning autonomy. This situation parallels the Chinese educational system, where students are similarly dependent on teachers and lack experience in self-directed learning. These learners, previously, have not had to notice how they learn and why they learn because of the standard practice of teacher-centred teaching in Chinese classrooms. However, in MOOCs, Chinese students must adapt to learning autonomously.

Nosratinia and Deris' (2015) research supports this theoretical framework by demonstrating how students in different contexts engage with online learning differently than in traditional classrooms and how this guided their learning experiences. In their study on the relationship between EFL learners' self-regulation and willingness to communicate, they found that student-centred approaches were more effective than teacher-centred ones. They also commented on and agreed with Hsu's (2006) opinion that while enhancing learners' willingness to communicate, the teacher's attitude and teaching style will influence learners' willingness to participate. In general, teachers can provide students with helpful guidelines to inform them of the ways that can contribute to learning more independently and effectively, which means students need to learn how to find knowledge by themselves. These findings suggest that students must be guided toward independent learning, a key focus of this thesis on learner engagement in MOOCs. This theory will lead me to focus more on the importance and improvement of autonomous learning in MOOC study to answer the research questions related to learner engagement and autonomy. This accords with the research aim of this research and forms the basis and the fundamental theory for this research. Through this process, I will strive to understand the learners' behaviour through MOOC study or other online courses better and reflect on the information gained which may inform further research.

Mackness, Mak, and Williams (2010), along with Nosratinia and Deris (2015), provide the theoretical foundation for this study because they exemplify and explain issues related to the context of Chinese students. They help me understand how Chinese learners engage with MOOCs and how they develop self-awareness in their online learning experiences. This theoretical framework aligns with the qualitative nature of this study, which aims to explore students' experiences and learning outcomes through MOOCs. As Austin and Sutton (2014) explain, qualitative research allows for the examination of participants' experiences through interviews and discussions. In this study, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with student participants to explore their experiences with MOOCs, supplemented by questionnaires to gather background information that will inform the interviews.

3.2.3 Motivation Theories

Theories of motivation were previously discussed in the Literature Review chapter. In summary, motivation is a theoretical concept used to explain human behaviour and decision-making. It provides insight into why individuals act to fulfil their needs. Motivation can also be defined as the driving force behind goal-directed behaviour, guiding individuals to initiate and sustain actions toward achieving specific objectives (Cook and Artino, 2016). Essentially, motivation prompts individuals to take action in order to achieve a goal or meet an expectation. Therefore, a theoretical framework based on the two motivation theories discussed in Section 2.3 is appropriate for this qualitative study, as it allows for an in-depth examination of Chinese students' experiences with MOOCs during and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

In the context of MOOCs and online learning, motivational theories, elaborated upon in the Literature Review, are particularly relevant. The theoretical framework of this research is grounded in motivation theory because it enables me to explore student

engagement and learner autonomy with MOOCs in Chinese higher education. This new way of engagement for the learners with online learning will also help me further investigate the different nature of online learning. This form of engagement, distinct from traditional classroom learning, is especially significant for Chinese students. Motivational theories will guide the development of interview questions aimed at understanding students' online learning behaviours and how these differ from their classroom experiences.

The data gathered from questionnaires and semi-structured interviews will be analysed to explore how students and teachers perceive the development and usefulness of MOOC in higher education in China as well as their engagement with MOOCs, the importance of learning autonomy and the potential future and challenges of MOOCs. Additionally, it will compare MOOCs with traditional classroom teaching methods in the Chinese university context.

3.2.4 Motivation Theories in Relation to MOOCs during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Upor (2023) notes that more than 1.58 billion children and adolescents, representing 91.3% of all registered students worldwide, were forced to study at home due to the sudden and unexpected outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. Although the pandemic persisted for several years, China achieved phased success in controlling and preventing the virus, allowing the country to gradually return to normal work and life by 2020. The impact of the pandemic on education was significant: as learning changed from traditional classrooms to online platforms, it became more critical for students to develop the skills and methods for effective learning, rather than simply acquiring knowledge, which was already categorized and systematized on MOOCs.

This change was particularly challenging for Chinese university students, whose prior learning experiences emphasised "learning knowledge" over "learning cognition." Without the direct supervision of teachers, many students, especially those lacking self-awareness of learning strategies and skills, may have struggled with online learning, which may have directly affected their later online learning experience.

This likely affected their overall experience with MOOCs. During the pandemic, students who thrived in their studies tended to be conscientious and capable learners, reflecting on their own learning abilities. In contrast, students who were unable to learn effectively because they were out with the teacher's supervision and were perhaps even supervised by their parents, as they needed to complete their learning tasks may have met the additional challenge of moving from teacher supervision to parental supervision. For these students, enhancing both their learning awareness and motivation became essential. Once the students have mastered the ability to engage with MOOCs, they are able to engage in learning activities in appropriate ways.

3.2.5 Summary

In this section, I explored and discussed two key theories. Mackness, Mak, and Williams (2010) argue that the important factor for learners is not merely the courses they choose, but how they engage with them and develop an understanding of what facilitates their engagement. Nosratinia and Deris (2015) further developed the idea and emphasising that a student-centred approach is significantly more effective than a teacher-oriented one in fostering learner autonomy. This thesis adopts these two theories as its theoretical framework, focusing on the role of learner motivation and learner autonomy in MOOCs to help learners explore, understand, and engage more effectively with their MOOC experiences.

This theoretical framework has guided the researcher in developing the methodology, selecting appropriate data collection methods, and choosing data analysis techniques, ensuring the data can effectively address the research questions, as discussed in detail in the following section.

3.3 Methodology

3.3.1 Introduction

This section outlines and discusses the methodology for this thesis, providing the rationale for selecting the approach for investigating learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education. It examines the research paradigm, along with the ontology and philosophy that support the study, which informs the research questions and objectives. The primary aim of this study is to examine the impact of MOOCs on traditional teaching methods and classroom practices in Chinese universities, particularly in relation to how MOOCs support the development of students' learning autonomy, motivation, and engagement, analysing how these factors affect MOOC study and further improve the MOOC completion rates. This chapter also introduced different elements involved in designing the research.

In order to collate sufficient data on students' experiences with MOOCs in Chinese higher education, both questionnaires and semi-structured interviews were employed. The section also addresses sampling techniques, data collection methods, and the ethical considerations of the study. A mixed-methods approach is adopted, where the questionnaire provides primarily quantitative data to gather relevant information about potential participants. The final question of the questionnaire, however, elicits

qualitative responses, enabling me to select participants for semi-structured interviews, thereby leading to a predominantly qualitative study.

3.3.2 Research Paradigm

In guiding the researcher's approach, it is essential to identify the worldview, or paradigm, that most closely aligns with the research goals (Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2011). Research paradigms provide broad frameworks that influence how knowledge is acquired, interpreted, and applied within a specific field, shaping the methods, theories, and assumptions researchers use to investigate and understand phenomena (Magolda, 2004). Different research paradigms offer distinct perspectives on how knowledge is developed and accepted. The most widely used research paradigms are regarded as positivism, realism, and interpretivism, each playing an important role in the process and the management of research.

The positivist paradigm, rooted in the natural sciences, emphasises objectivity, quantification, and empirical observation (Park, Konge and Artino, 2020). Positivist researchers seek to discover universal laws and generalizations that explain cause-and-effect relationships. They rely on structured methods such as experiments and surveys, using deductive reasoning while maintaining a neutral stance to minimize personal bias. Henderson (2011) notes that post-positivism, an evolution of positivism, acknowledges the limitations of complete objectivity in research. While still valuing empirical evidence and scientific methods, post-positivism recognises that researchers' perspectives and biases can influence the process. Post-positivists try to minimize subjectivity and bias by using rigorous methodologies and multiple data sources (Henderson, 2011).

Interpretivism, also referred to as constructivism or phenomenology, is more common in the social sciences and humanities (Schwandt, 1994). It focuses on understanding the subjective meanings and interpretations individuals assign to their experiences. This paradigm highlights the importance of context, cultural factors, and the researcher's role in shaping the research (Antwi and Hamza, 2015). Originating as a critique of positivism in the social sciences, interpretivism prioritizes qualitative analysis over quantitative analysis. Interpretivist researchers use qualitative data collection tools and generate more descriptive data to provide valuable findings, such as interviews, observations, and content analysis are often used to explore and interpret human behaviour and social phenomena.

There is an additional pragmatism paradigm which is grounded in the belief that the validity and effectiveness of knowledge are determined by its practical implications and usefulness (Barlas and Carpenter, 1990). Pragmatists focus on problem-solving and the practical application of research findings. Similarly, realism posits that an objective reality exists independently of individuals' perceptions and emphasises the practical usefulness of research findings (Sobh and Perry, 2006).

In this study, the dominant paradigm guiding the exploration of participants' roles and experiences in MOOC engagement is interpretivism, supplemented by a small positivist element. Consequently, a mixed-methods approach is employed, with the questionnaire largely quantitative in nature, enabling the selection of participants for semi-structured interviews. According to Kent (2007), interpretivism refers to a sociological approach that emphasises the importance of understanding and analysing individuals' beliefs, thoughts, and experiences to comprehend social reality. Kent argues that human experience is not a passive perception of external reality but an active process of interpretation and understanding. Similarly, Saunders, Lewis, and

Thornhill (2012) assert that cognition is realised through studying individuals' lived experiences and perspectives. Interpretivist researchers must engage with real-world contexts to explain and reconstruct the meanings individuals assign to their experiences. Therefore, this research aims to explore learners' engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education, focusing on both learners' and teachers' experiences. The study seeks to understand whether and how they engage with MOOCs. Participants' experiences and perspectives were collected through questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, with qualitative insights supplemented by quantitative data from the questionnaire.

3.3.3 Epistemological and Ontological Stance

According to Blanche *et al.* (2006), research paradigms are always mainly characterised by their ontological, epistemological and methodological dispositions. They note that researchers using these approaches adopt specific ways of perceiving how the world is structured and how to answer research questions, significantly influencing the research methods selected.

Epistemology originally comes from the Greek word *epistêmê*, which refers to the philosophy of knowledge or how people come to know and is also regarded as the philosophical study of the nature, origin, and limits of human knowledge (Schlag, Junk and Daase, 2015). Methodology, while also concerned with how people come to know, is more practical in nature. It focuses on the specific methods used to better understand the world. Epistemology and methodology are closely related: the former involves the theory of knowledge, while the latter involves the practical application of that knowledge (Griffiths, 2011).

Different scholars have provided perspectives on these approaches. Lawson (2000) believes that epistemology focuses on questions related to the sources of knowledge, the criteria for determining truth, and the ways of knowing. It is concerned with providing a philosophical grounding for deciding what kinds of knowledge are possible and how to ensure it is adequate and legitimate. According to Alharahsheh and Pius (2020), the most common epistemological perspectives are positivism and interpretivism. Positivists advocate for empirical evidence obtained through rigorous scientific methods to establish objective knowledge, relying on observable and measurable phenomena. They often employ quantitative methods to test hypotheses and identify causal relationships (Park, Konge and Artino, 2020). In contrast, interpretivists emphasise understanding the subjective meanings and interpretations individuals and groups assign to their experiences (Hiller, 2016). They argue that social phenomena are best understood through qualitative methods, acknowledging the researcher's subjectivity and the importance of context in shaping the research process.

The core idea of interpretivist epistemology is that the researcher actively participates in the research and interprets the data (Al-Ababneh, 2020). Ormston *et al.* (2014) explain that interpretivism is interested in specific contexts, believing that reality and knowledge are not objective but shaped by individuals within those particular environments. To acquire knowledge of the complex world, interpretivist researchers study the experiences and perspectives of those living in it. The researcher has to examine further the real world to understand, explain and analyse these concepts and ideas through scientific means and language, which include the methods of interactive interviews, participatory observation and others. Therefore, this study used questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, aligning with the interpretivist paradigm.

Ontology, closely related to epistemology, concerns 'the study of being' (Crotty, 1998) or 'the nature of reality' (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). It addresses what reality is and what can be discovered about it (Moon and Blackman, 2014), helping researchers determine how certain they can be about the existence and nature of the phenomena they are studying.

The researcher's ontological stance influences how they perceive the research objects and conduct their study. Two main ontological approaches exist realism and constructivism. Realists maintain that an objective reality exists independently of human perception, asserting that the social and natural world exists beyond people's understanding and observation (Sobh and Perry, 2006). Constructivists, on the other hand, argue that reality is socially constructed, and shaped by the perspectives, interpretations and interactions of individuals and groups (Dudley-Marling, 2004). They insist that there is no single objective reality, but multiple realities shaped by different experiences and cultural contexts.

Researchers who adopt a constructivist view are interested in understanding the subjective meanings and interpretations of individuals' experiences. In this study, a qualitative semi-structured interview was used to gather participants' opinions about their MOOC learning experiences, which is in accordance with the constructivist phenomenon as participants can express and share their perceptions of the topic and I collected and analysed their interview responses. Therefore, this study is based on constructivist ontology.

Though academic researchers define these approaches differently, it is clear that each interpretive approach allows for a deep understanding of the social context. This study employs relevant ontological and epistemological approaches, with a small positivist

element drawn from the questionnaire. The interpretivist approach guided the investigation of learner engagement in MOOCs in Chinese higher education. Data was collected primarily through qualitative methods, but the questionnaire results enabled me to do the participant selection for semi-structured interviews to understand their experiences with MOOCs. Throughout the research process, a relationship developed between the researcher and participants, allowing for a discussion of their experiences. This aligns with interpretivism's ontological stance, where researchers discover 'reality' and the reasons behind it within a certain realm of probability. The aims of this research fit with interpretivism as ontological and epistemological stances; the positivist nature of most questionnaire questions informs these positions.

3.3.4 Research Method

Research methods are the specific procedures used for collecting and analysing data, and developing accurate methods is a critical aspect of research design (Trochim and Donnelly, 2001). Numerous academic research methods exist, including case studies, narrative research, phenomenology, and grounded theory (Creswell and Poth, 2016). In relation to the discussion above, this study adopts constructivist phenomenology as the ontological framework, as it aims to investigate learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education based on the perceptions of learners and teachers. This relies on the participants' own perceptions and opinions. The focus on participants' views aligns with the interpretive tradition, which emphasises studying participants' experiences within their specific contexts (Creswell and Poth, 2016).

Several scholars have provided insights into these approaches. Amaratunga *et al.* (2002) identify three common research approaches in academic studies: quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods. The key difference among these methods is the type

of data collected: quantitative researchers gather numerical data, qualitative researchers collect words, images, and personal insights, while mixed-methods researchers use both. In line with these distinctions, this study adopts a mixed-methods approach. According to Thompson (2015), an interpretive approach to social research is predominantly qualitative, using tools such as unstructured interviews or participant observation. In this study, the target research method fits the requirement of the interpretive stance as I interpreted the participants' perspectives on a specific context, that is, Chinese students' experience of MOOCs, and gathered descriptive data of participants' views and feelings through qualitative research tools, which were used in this research. This research is combined with quantitative research from the questionnaires which gathered clear common features about the participants' background and general experiences of the MOOC study which informed the qualitative data; this is, therefore, a piece of mixed-methods research.

As Denzin and Lincoln (2011) note, qualitative research is a significant branch of multi-method research that involves an interpretive, naturalistic approach to its subject matter. Qualitative researchers study phenomena in their natural settings, seeking to interpret these phenomena in terms of the meanings individuals attribute to them. This method is primarily exploratory, used to gain insights into underlying reasons, opinions, and motivations, and often helps in generating ideas or hypotheses for subsequent quantitative research (Surbhi, 2016). On the contrary, quantitative research is a systematic and empirical method used to gather and analyse numerical data to answer specific research questions and test hypotheses. It is a structured method that uses statistical and mathematical techniques to draw conclusions about a population. Quantitative research is usually employed in the natural sciences, social sciences, and various other disciplines where measurable data is essential (Tuli, 2010). Apuke (2017) highlights that quantitative research is ideal for questions that require measurable data and a high degree of accuracy and objectivity. However, it may be

less suitable for studying complex social phenomena or exploring in-depth individual experiences, which are better addressed through qualitative research.

Researchers typically use qualitative methods when seeking subjective insights, views, and conclusions. In this study, questionnaires were distributed to collect data on learners' and teachers' perspectives, helping to explore and explain learner engagement with MOOCs. Semi-structured interviews further investigated participants' attitudes, fitting within qualitative research methods. In addition, as the study aims to examine the current state of learners' engagement with MOOCs, which considered an individual reality, collecting quantitative data on participants' experiences is essential. As a result, this research adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods.

3.3.5 Sampling Techniques for This Study

Sampling techniques are methods used by researchers to select a subset from a larger population for study (Taherdoost, 2016), aiming to draw meaningful conclusions about the entire population based on the sample's characteristics. This research employed non-probability sampling techniques, which did not require consideration of the entire population. Unlike probability sampling, which involves random selection, non-probability sampling does not (Trochim and Donnelly, 2001). Schreuder, Gregoire, and Weyer (2001) note that quantitative researchers often rely on non-probability samples in exploratory or evaluative research, ensuring that studies following a quantitative design are not abandoned due to the impracticality of probability sampling. Accordingly, this study used purposive, or judgmental, sampling, a non-random technique where the sample is chosen with a specific purpose in mind (Trochim and Donnelly, 2001).

In this study, the predefined groups consist of learners and teachers from two universities, whether or not they have engaged with MOOCs. Purposive sampling is particularly useful in situations requiring a targeted sample where proportionality is not the primary concern, enabling researchers to obtain relevant opinions from the target population. based on the study's aim to explore and analyse the current state of MOOCs in Chinese higher education, purposive sampling was used to select participants from two universities. The qualitative sample size is relatively small, with respondents selected to meet a specific quota. For the questionnaires, a total number of ten teachers and twenty students were selected from the two specific universities of the same level in China, in which their educational backgrounds are similar, so there should be consistency in their learning experiences. One university has already launched MOOCs while another has not. These are target samples but not chosen randomly, which accords with the principles of non-probability sampling techniques.

3.3.6 Design of the Study

3.3.6.1 Design and Implementation

To assess learning engagement in MOOCs among Chinese university students, a combination of questionnaires and semi-structured interviews was selected as the primary research methods. As a carrier of online education, MOOCs and other online courses have gained increasing popularity in Chinese universities, they have become important platforms for students to acquire knowledge and earn credits. However, the effectiveness of these platforms in supporting student learning needs further evaluation (Hew and Cheung, 2014). This study aimed to analyse students' cognition, acceptance, engagement and satisfaction with MOOCs, as well as identify the challenges they faced in engaging with MOOCs. By gathering responses from both learners and teachers, I explored whether low engagement rates existed and provided insights and references for the further construction of online courses.

I interviewed the participants from two Chinese universities of similar ranking. These institutions were selected to ensure comparability, as universities of differing levels may vary in terms of equipment, facilities, and student abilities, which could lead to inconclusive results. Institutions of the same level typically share comparable faculty resources and student populations, making them ideal for this study. The research examined students' and teachers' attitudes toward MOOCs, the learning processes involved, and the outcomes of online learning. Recommendations for improvement were made based on the findings, evaluating whether MOOCs can effectively supplement traditional classroom instruction or evolve into a new format for university courses. Additionally, the study identified the challenges and benefits of MOOCs and assess their potential future role in higher education.

3.3.6.2 Primary Sources

A primary source, also known as an original source, refers to an artefact or document, such as a diary, manuscript, autobiography, recording, or any other material created during the period under study (Barton, 2005). It provides direct evidence on the subject. Primary data refers to the first-hand information collected or created by the researchers themselves through various data collection methods (Hox and Boeije, 2005). It serves as the first reflection of the research questions from participants. Examples of primary sources include legal texts and original documents, such as newspaper reports written by eyewitnesses or those quoting participants. According to Hox and Boeije (2005), primary data may also come from questionnaires and interviews. In this research, the researcher designed a questionnaire consisting of multiple-choice and open-ended questions. The responses constituted primary data, offering insights into participants' experiences with MOOCs in Chinese higher education. Similarly, data from interviews provided first-hand accounts of participants' personal opinions and perceptions. The questionnaire results were

recorded in tables or charts and analysed to address the research objectives. These findings were presented in the findings section and discussed in the analysis and conclusion sections.

3.3.6.3 Secondary Sources

Secondary sources differ from primary sources in that they cite, comment on, or build upon primary sources (Barton, 2005). These sources are one step removed from the original material, often quoting or using primary sources to provide interpretation and analysis. They can cover the same topic but add a layer of interpretation and analysis. According to Hox and Boeije (2005), secondary sources include books, scholarly articles, analyses of data, and documentaries, particularly those created by individuals not directly involved in the original events or data collection. In essence, secondary sources are second-hand information summarised from existing literature (Reddy and Agrawal, 2012). In this research, secondary sources were drawn from the literature chapter and analysed alongside primary data to ensure that findings were fully explored, research questions were thoroughly addressed, and conclusions were reached.

3.3.6.4 Participants

In qualitative research, participant selection was purposeful, with participants chosen based on their ability to provide insights into the research questions and enhance their understanding of the phenomenon under study (Palinkas *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, identifying appropriate participants was an important task during the study design phase, as selection decisions were informed by the research questions and theoretical framework.

This study began by administering a questionnaire on students' engagement with MOOCs. The sample consisted of ten students from the same class and five teachers from the same teaching group at each university. The questionnaire included questions aimed at gathering both student and teacher perspectives on MOOCs. The number of participants in the research was confirmed ahead of the survey in order to make enough preparation for the questionnaire papers and for the space and time required for the research, in case of any issues with absence or participants who were interested in the topic and need more time to do the survey. The selection of ten learners was enough for data analysis and choosing five teachers from the same group was a suitable number of people to get targeted results: I had an insider position as a former student at one of the targeted universities, was well-positioned to select participants efficiently and I knew that it was straightforward to select ten participants from the student group and five from the teacher group at this university. Another reason was that the teachers, who belonged to the same department and taught different subjects, were familiar with the students and were expected to provide valuable data.

While the number of interviews needed in qualitative research is debated, scholars suggest a range of 5 to 50 participants as adequate (Dworkin, 2012). The sample size used in qualitative research methods is often smaller than that used in quantitative research methods (Sandelowski, 1995) because qualitative research methods are often concerned with an in-depth understanding of a phenomenon, which is often regarded as the how and why of a particular issue, process, situation, scene or set of social interactions. For this study, participants for semi-structured interviews were selected based on their responses to the final open-ended question in the questionnaire. To compare and analyse the data, four participants were interviewed during the COVID-19 pandemic and four afterwards.

In China, universities are generally classified into three levels based on student qualifications (Gao, Ping and Liu, 2020). However, recent policy changes have reclassified these into two groups: the first batch of top universities and the second batch of ordinary universities. The chosen universities for this study fall into the second category, representing typical institutions in Northeast China. University B, one of the target institutions, had not officially launched any MOOCs. The participants were English majors from a foreign language academic department during the year 2017, who were studying in their second semester of the third year, chosen for convenience as the researcher was an alumnus and could easily contact teachers for help in recruiting participants. English majors were particularly relevant to this study, as MOOCs were originally introduced in English-speaking countries, and most MOOC content is in English (Shapiro *et al.*, 2017). English major students were likely to be more motivated to use MOOCs for language learning and professional development (Dornyei, 2002). I efficiently distributed and collected questionnaires from students after class, ensuring timely and complete participation. University A, the other target institution, had already delivered MOOCs, allowing for the collection of data from students with more MOOC experience. The data from both universities were compared to draw meaningful conclusions. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with participants who expressed interest in the MOOC topic based on their questionnaire responses. These interviews investigated deeper into their experiences and perceptions of MOOCs.

Additionally, five experienced English teachers from the foreign language departments of both universities participated in the research. These teachers, who were familiar with online learning and had been working with the students, provided valuable insights into the students' engagement and learning. The teachers, representing both genders and different English courses, were contacted via email and asked to complete electronic questionnaires, ensuring convenience and timely

responses. Their responses enriched the data, contributing to a comprehensive analysis of MOOC engagement in Chinese higher education.

3.3.6.5 Research Instruments

As previously discussed, this study utilised two data collection methods: semi-structured interviews and questionnaires.

Questionnaires

One instrument used in this study was a set of two questionnaires, each consisting of fourteen questions, one for students and one for teachers. These questions aimed to assess the extent of learners' engagement with MOOCs, with the final question addressing how both students and teachers perceive that engagement. Adams and Cox (2008) highlight several advantages of questionnaires: they can quickly and easily collect a large amount of useful data. Most questions in these questionnaires developed for this study are multiple-choice, while the final question is open-ended. This format not only saves time but also allows participants to directly express their opinions (Weimer, 2015). The open-ended question, in particular, provided more detailed insights into participants' perspectives on the subject. Completing the questionnaire took only five to ten minutes and was done collectively after their normal class.

Semi-structured Interviews

This study also employed semi-structured interviews to gain an in-depth understanding of learners' and teachers' experiences with MOOCs. Participants were asked a series of questions related to their MOOC study experiences and their perceptions of MOOCs.

Interview is an important data-gathering technique, fostering communication between the researcher and participants. They are widely used in survey designs, exploratory, and descriptive studies, making them one of the most common methods in qualitative research (Bryman, 2016). According to Brinkmann and Kvale (2015), interviews establish data or knowledge through interaction between the researcher and participants, allowing the social world to be understood from the informants' perspectives. There exists a range of approaches to interviews, from unstructured ones in which the participants are allowed to express freely about whatever they want, to highly structured interviews in which the participants only respond to the questions that are directly answered.

In structured interviews, interviewers ask pre-determined questions in a specific order, which simplifies data analysis by allowing easy comparison of responses, as researchers can compare the different answers collected from the same questions. In contrast, unstructured interviews are often considered unreliable, as they lack prepared questions and follow an informal approach to data collection (Brinkmann, 2014). This study used semi-structured interviews, combining elements of both structured and unstructured formats. In semi-structured interviews, the interviewer asked the same core questions but might also ask additional questions for clarification or elaboration. This flexible approach allowed for the collection of rich data while giving participants the freedom to express their views.

The study aimed to explore learners' and teachers' engagement with MOOCs. Semi-structured interviews were deemed to be an appropriate data-collection tool for this study, as they balance structure with flexibility, providing rich, detailed data (Brinkmann, 2014). Eight participants took part in these interviews, sharing their experiences with MOOCs, including how they were introduced to MOOCs, their

feelings about MOOC learning, how it compared to traditional classroom teaching, the factors that influenced their motivation and learning autonomy and their views on MOOCs' future in Chinese higher education. Additional questions might be asked depending on the participants' responses.

In this study, the semi-structured interviews were conducted in two phases. The first group of participants were interviewed during the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on their experiences of MOOC learning during that time. The second group were interviewed after COVID-19 restrictions had been lifted. Comparing these two sets of data enabled an analysis of MOOCs' use before and after the pandemic, contributing to the discussion of their significance and future development.

Follow-up Semi-structured Interviews

In order to obtain more information about the participants' experiences of MOOC, additional interviews were conducted with four of the original participants E, F, G, and H, two from each university, who had previously been interviewed in the initial semi-structured interviews in 2022 after the COVID-19 pandemic. I returned to four of the original eight interviewees to request their agreement to be re-interviewed and to obtain further information about their feelings and experiences related to their learning via MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic period.

The reason for this was that, after an initial outline and discussion of the original interview data, I realised there were still some gaps in the participants' responses which would answer the research questions, for example, the particular development of MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic. In the original interviews, participants were asked about the promotion of MOOCs, and while the pandemic was recognised as a potential catalyst for online learning, this topic was not fully explored and

discussed in the interview questions or responses. Therefore, I developed a new set of questions to specifically investigate participants' MOOC learning experiences during the COVID-19 period.

I initially wanted to re-interview all eight participants, but this was not feasible due to difficulties in contacting them. The participants from the first round of interviews in 2021 had graduated, and most had started careers in different regions of China and were not in contact with me. Consequently, I focused on the four participants who remained accessible. The participants from the second round of interviews, Participants E, F, G, and H, who had more recently completed their studies, were still in contact with me on occasion through social media, so I was able to ask for their permission. After explaining the purpose of the follow-up interviews, two participants agreed to participate. The two participants were more willing to be re-interviewed because they had attended the university where I had studied, and we knew each other well. The other two participants expressed their concerns about the accuracy of their memories of the COVID-19 period and were initially afraid that they might provide incorrect information. However, after I explained and clarified the content of the follow-up interview questions, they became less worried. I explained the focus was on their learning experiences rather than specific dates, policies, or course details, so they felt more confident in providing honest responses and agreed to take the interview.

As these participants had also graduated and were working, I scheduled interviews during a holiday period when they were available. This facilitated the collection of additional data that addressed the research questions more comprehensively. Interviewing the original participants rather than the new participants provided more reliable and consistent data. The revised set of questions focusing on their MOOC

learning experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic and the detailed interview responses were presented in Appendices H and I.

3.3.6.6 Data Collection

The questionnaires were sent to teachers via email, allowing them to complete the survey in their spare time, while students received paper copies after their regular classes to ensure they received clear instructions for filling out the questionnaires. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting difficulties in accessing participants in person, the questionnaires were conducted online. Once completed, the questionnaires were sent back to me via email. The data collected consisted of individual responses from both teacher and student participants. The expected time for each participant to complete the questionnaire is approximately ten minutes. They selected their answers to the multiple-choice questions and responded to the final open-ended question before submitting the questionnaire.

In addition, participants' responses to the open-ended question were summarised and analysed. Open-ended questions offered valuable insights by allowing participants to express their views in their own words, helping me gain a deeper understanding of the participants' perspectives. These responses might vary, providing either similar or divergent viewpoints. Open-ended questions, presented as a statement requiring a response, often elicited detailed information that might not be captured by multiple-choice questions, making them particularly important for the research (Connor Desai and Reimers, 2019).

Due to COVID-19 restrictions, the semi-structured interviews also took place online. A total of eight participants, selected based on their expressed interest in the topic and the depth of their responses to the open-ended questions, participated in these

interviews. The semi-structured interviews were conducted via WeChat, with an expected average duration of 30 minutes. If any data or responses require clarification, additional discussions might be arranged. Participants were informed of this possibility in advance.

In order to identify the key themes, the recorded interviews were reviewed multiple times, and thematic grids were created (see Appendices D, E, F, G, H, I) to highlight the main themes and corresponding participant comments. All data collected in this study were thus coded thematically and analysed by interpretive phenomenological methods.

3.3.6.7 Data Analysis

Thematic analysis is a commonly used method for analysing qualitative research (Braun and Clarke, 2006). It focuses on identifying, examining, and recording themes or patterns within the data. The primary goal of thematic analysis is to uncover themes that can help interpret and make sense of qualitative data (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). This approach enabled me to explore the underlying motivations, ideas, and assumptions within the participants' responses.

The data analysis for this thesis followed the six-step framework proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006). The first step involved familiarising oneself with the data. I began by transcribing the interviews into text and listening to the recordings extensively to identify important elements. This process ensured a deep understanding of the content, which is critical for subsequent stages of analysis. Once familiar with the data, I generated initial codes that highlighted significant features alluded to and discussed, breaking the data into smaller, manageable units for effective regrouping and analysis (Spencer *et al.*, 2013).

The next step was identifying themes by synthesising and combining the codes. This enabled me to establish logical connections between emerging themes and sub-themes, which ultimately shaped the analysis. Following this, I reviewed the themes in a self-checking process to clarify the direction of the research (Wight *et al.*, 2016). At this stage, I evaluated the relevance and coherence of each theme in relation to the research questions. I ensured that the initial themes met key criteria, such as relevance to the research questions, sufficiency of textual data for discussion, and alignment with theoretical frameworks (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Once the themes were reviewed, I defined and named them, analysing each theme in detail and determining which data were included. I organised the data into a coherent and internally consistent narrative, ensuring that the themes aligned with the study's focus.

The final stage was producing the report, where I related the developed themes to existing literature and presented the interpretative findings. The report went beyond mere description by offering in-depth analysis supported by empirical evidence, directly addressing the research questions.

3.3.6.8 Discussing the Findings in Two Chapters

Chapter 4 and Chapter 5 set out the findings from the research. I made the decision to separate the discussion of the findings into two chapters to provide clarity to make them more straightforward to analyse.

In Chapter 4, in my investigation into the participation of Chinese university students in MOOCs, I conducted a mixed-methods approach as outlined in the methodology chapter. I distributed a questionnaire to students and teachers from each of the two selected universities, collecting responses from ten student participants and five teacher participants at each university. This questionnaire aimed to collect relevant information about the students, including their experiences with MOOCs, learning habits, and attitudes toward MOOCs. The results provided an overview of student engagement with MOOCs in both universities. The questionnaires given to teachers also gave me rich information about their students' learning experiences via MOOCs, as reported in the previous chapter. Based on the responses to the questionnaires, I identified students who showed a high level of interest in this topic and could offer diverse opinions about their MOOC experiences and selected four potential interview participants from each university. This selection was guided by their engagement levels, as well as their varied perspectives on MOOC learning. The questionnaires outlined the general situations and learning patterns related to MOOCs by an analysis of the responses of the participants, offering a subjective perspective on student participation in MOOCs.

In Chapter 5, the second set of data collected for this research, my semi-structured interviews provided a more qualitative understanding of individual experiences, challenges, and motivations. The semi-structured interviews were conducted in separate stages. As outlined in the methodology, the first set of interviews involved four participants, two from each university, and was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic. The second round of interviews took place in late 2022, after the pandemic, and involved another four students, two from each university. An additional set of interviews, designed to gather further reflections, was conducted in early 2024, two and a half years after the pandemic, and revisited the four participants from the second round for more detailed responses and reflections on the learning experiences

via MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic. This structure allowed for a comprehensive analysis, combining and comparing rich data and getting in-depth and detailed reflections from students directly involved in MOOC learning.

3.3.7 Ethical Considerations

Bell, Bryman and Harley (2022) emphasise key ethical principles that must be adhered to in dissertations, including obtaining full consent from participants, ensuring the protection of their privacy, and maintaining the confidentiality of research data.

Ethical considerations arise both before and during the research process (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). In this thesis, all participant information was anonymised during the questionnaire phase; participants would not disclose their names or universities and will be identified by codes (e.g., TEACHER A, TEACHER B, etc., and STUDENT A, etc.). With the participants' agreement, interviews were recorded using an online tool, ensuring the full data collection. This study adhered to all University of the West of Scotland regulations, and ethical approval was obtained. The original recordings of the semi-structured interviews were stored on a password-protected device and destroyed upon the project's completion. Personal information, including participants' names, would not appear in the transcripts, the final dissertation, or any resulting publications.

3.3.7.1 Position of the Researcher

In this research, the context of the study remained anonymous, as participants would not provide their names, and the universities were referred to as University A and University B. These two institutions were selected as the target universities for

distributing questionnaires and conducting semi-structured interviews. I previously studied at University B, which facilitated access to participants and benefited from the position of being the insider researcher. As an insider researcher, I had a similar educational background to the participants, which allowed for a deeper understanding of the unique learning experiences of Chinese students.

3.3.7.2 Insider Research and the Insider Researcher

Insider research refers to studies conducted within a social group, organisation, or culture to which the researcher currently belongs or previously belonged. This approach has its roots in ethnographic field research, particularly within the disciplines of anthropology and sociology (Sikes and Potts, 2008). Loxley and Seery (2008) define insider research as the investigation of one's own social group or society. They further describe it within the context of social sciences, noting that insider research is undertaken by individuals who share specific characteristics, such as cultural, biological, or occupational traits with the group being studied.

3.3.7.3 The Advantages and Disadvantages of Insider Research

Insider researchers often do not need to orient themselves to the research environment and participants, as their similar experiences enable them to adapt to different situations with minimal mistakes (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). This familiarity can enhance the researcher's understanding of participants' opinions and facilitate the collection of richer data. In addition, insider researchers are able to “understand the cognitive, emotional, and psychological precepts of participants” and have a deeper knowledge of the historical and practical contexts of the field (Chavez, 2008). Dwyer and Buckle (2009) also believe that insider researchers, being acquainted with the group and social setting, know how to extract information from individuals effectively. In contrast to outsider researchers, who may lack connections within the social groups or members, insider researchers can access the field “more quickly and intimately,” a

phenomenon referred to as the “expediency of access” (Chavez, 2008). In this research, I previously studied at University B. My similar learning experiences, knowledge of the university's teaching strategies, course structures, and class compositions helped me to collect and analyse the data better.

However, some scholars argued that insider researchers may become too familiar with the participants and the group, which can narrow their perspectives and limit their ability to analyse social and cultural structures effectively (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). Delyser (2001) notes that greater familiarity may lead to a loss of “objectivity,” increasing the risk of making assumptions based on the researcher’s prior knowledge or experience. Additionally, insider research is frequently accused of being inherently biased, as researchers are considered to be too close to the culture under study to pose challenging questions (Delyser, 2001).

In this context, researcher bias referred to the influence of the researcher's personal beliefs, experiences, and values on the study's methodology, design, and results. Consequently, I needed to maintain an appropriate distance from the participants during the research. Insider researchers were vigilant in avoiding the projection of their own views onto participants or the data analysis. They remained aware of potential biases and took steps to ensure that their research was as accurate as possible. This consideration guided me to listen attentively to participants’ voices, respect each participant’s opinion, and avoid interrupting or misleading participants during the semi-structured interviews.

3.3.7.4 Using Two Languages

I allowed participants to express their MOOC experiences in Chinese during the semi-structured interviews, considering their potential language anxiety and limited

English proficiency. This approach was aimed at enabling participants to express their opinions and experiences more clearly and thoroughly. Qualitative research typically employs open-ended questions and unstructured or semi-structured data collection methods, allowing participants to freely convey their experiences and perspectives. This suggests that by providing flexible language options, such as permitting the use of participants' first languages, researchers can better facilitate authentic expression of experiences and feelings (Burck, 2004).

Furthermore, evidence suggested that learners' backgrounds and motivations are important considerations in MOOC research. Squires (2009) posits that if participants are unable to fully express their learning experiences due to language barriers, the accuracy and depth of the research results may be compromised. Therefore, I felt that allowing participants to use Chinese enhances the clarity and effectiveness of the interviews and ensures the quality of the research data. Allowing participants to use Chinese in semi-structured interviews helped them overcome any language anxiety and insufficient English proficiency, to better support them in expressing their MOOC learning experience and ensured the accuracy and completeness of the research data.

It was anticipated that participants in this study might struggle to respond to interview questions in English with the desired depth and clarity due to anxiety or limited language skills. To assist participants in expressing their MOOC experiences, I allowed the use of Mandarin, if required, during the semi-structured interviews to facilitate ease and clarity of expression.

3.4 Summary

This research aimed to enhance the understanding of MOOCs among both I and participants and to recognise how to effectively utilise MOOC platforms. It encouraged learner participants to reflect on their motivations for online autonomous learning and explore their attitudes toward MOOCs and online learning platforms, thereby facilitating their development and progress. This chapter provided a brief introduction to the theoretical framework and research methodology, outlining the structure of the research process, including how the study was conducted and delivered. The following chapters discussed the theoretical framework in greater detail, from which the formal research on learner engagement with MOOCs in higher education in China through semi-structured interviews and questionnaires.

As a researcher, the analysis of the data collected was essential for understanding student engagement in MOOCs within the context of Chinese higher education. Furthermore, students who participated in this research benefited from the opportunity to engage with the survey process, allowing them to reflect on their online autonomous learning behaviours and gain deeper insights into their own studies. Teachers also compared their experiences, methods, and activities with their students' reflections to design and deliver more effective MOOCs and classroom courses. Through this research, they better understood their students' perspectives and become more attuned to their learning styles. A completed version of the survey was provided to each participant, enabling them to benefit from the researchers' conclusions.

Chapter 4: Analysis of Findings from the Participant Questionnaires

4.1 Introduction

As part of this research, a questionnaire on student engagement with MOOCs was distributed to a sample of ten students and five teachers from the same teaching group at each of two universities. These two specific universities hereinafter referred to as "University A" and "University B" are at the comparable level in China. University A has already launched MOOCs on its official platforms, while University B has not. The questionnaire, detailed in the Appendix C, consists of thirteen multiple-choice questions and one open-ended question related to MOOCs, designed to gather responses from the participants based on their roles as teachers or students. This questionnaire collected information on participants' previous learning experiences and background in MOOC learning to gain an overall understanding of the participants' prior learning experiences and enabled the selection of potential interview participants for the second part of the data collection, and resultant analysis in the findings chapter based on their stated interests and experiences in MOOCs. This chapter will examine and discuss each question individually.

4.2 Student Participants' Views on MOOCs

The first two questions of each questionnaire collected basic information about the participants. At University A, which offers MOOCs on its official platform, ten students participated in the research, four males and six females, all of whom had experience with MOOC learning. At University B, which does not offer MOOCs on its official platform, ten students also participated, four males and six females. Although none had experience with MOOCs via their university's platform, some participants had engaged with MOOCs through other online platforms.

4.2.1 How Were the Participants Introduced to MOOCs?

All student participants from University A said that they were officially introduced to MOOCs by university departments and teachers. During the COVID-19 pandemic, in compliance with the “Class Suspended but Learning Continues” policy (Ministry of Education, 2020), the university adjusted its curriculum from face-to-face teaching to delivery of online courses. This change highlights the fact that university departments and teachers are part of the marketing process to encourage students to participate in MOOCs because they have the responsibility to promote MOOCs in order to finish the teaching plans, as well as enhance student engagement and ensure the successful delivery of MOOCs. This accords with the findings of Guerrero, Heaton and Urbano (2021), who emphasise that teachers’ behaviours are important for marketing MOOCs to learners. The study highlights that some areas need to be of high quality to achieve the university's strategic aims, for example, teacher behaviours, teaching and research, which are all relevant to teaching staff who contribute toward meeting university outcomes through their recommendations and the successful delivery of MOOCs. This demonstrates that teacher behaviours such as encouraging participation and observing student engagement, can significantly influence students' involvement in MOOC learning. Recognising their impact, university departments and teachers should actively promote MOOCs to their students.

Research clearly shows that teachers' attitudes and behaviours significantly influence students' intrinsic and extrinsic learning motivation (Tokan and Imakulata, 2019). Stronge (2018) highlights that factors such as teachers' professional qualities, extensive knowledge of their subject area, and professional interest in their work will directly affect students' learning motivation. Positive teacher expectations, instructional guidance, and motivational teaching styles can further enhance students'

learning motivation and academic success. Chakraborty and Biswas (2020) also found that there is a close relationship between teachers' intrinsic motivation and students' learning motivation. Teachers can promote student learning through effective teaching and guidance. Thus, their support directly impacts individual learning motivation and academic achievement, especially their ability to develop their students' learning autonomy, and thus their engagement within the classroom.

In China, the role of teachers in online education is changing. The traditional teacher-centred approach has gradually shifted to a more diverse learning environment that includes not only face-to-face teaching but also online, remote, and blended learning (Li, 2020). Teachers are now required to develop skills for adjusting to various learning environments, such as virtual classrooms, online platforms, and mobile learning applications, to meet new teaching demands and encourage their students to discover the importance of autonomous learning in all learning environments. This shift aligns with the work of Guerrero, Heaton and Urbano (2021) who found that teacher behaviour is key to effectively promoting MOOCs. This evolving role not only enhances how students acquire knowledge but also highlights the importance of continuous professional learning (CPL) for teachers.

Conversely in University B, four of the ten participants were introduced to MOOCs through Chinese learning communities such as Youku or Zhihu platforms. Five participants learned about MOOCs from their teachers, and one participant was introduced through a friend's recommendation. As discussed in an interview with Chinese Education Minister Chen in October 2020, China had more than 30 MOOC platforms offering over 34,000 courses across various fields. A total of 540 million people in China have enrolled in these courses. Given the rapid development of

MOOCs in China, even if a university's official platform did not offer MOOCs, students could still access them through other online learning platforms.

In addition to university and teacher recommendations, students have multiple ways to access and participate in MOOCs. MOOCs provide high-quality educational resources globally through online platforms, enabling students to engage in diverse courses and materials without geographical limitations (Welsh and Dragusin, 2013). This not only reflects the flexibility of MOOCs, that is, enabling students to learn within and around the limitations of space and time but also illustrates the character of sharing educational resources. Students can select courses that align with their interests, previous learning experiences, and time availability, completing tasks within the course duration. This flexible learning approach not only enhances students' autonomy but also cultivates their learning motivation and investigating abilities.

4.2.2 How Many Courses Are the Participants Learning through MOOCs? (Including University Official MOOCs and Other MOOCs)

Seven of ten participants from University A are currently enrolled in four to six MOOCs, while three are taking seven to nine. In contrast, since University B does not officially offer MOOCs, nine of its ten participants reported taking three or fewer courses, and only one is enrolled in four to six. A comparison between the two universities shows that University A's official transfer from traditional classroom instruction to online learning, which required students to participate in MOOCs, has significantly increased the MOOC completion rate. MOOCs have become part of the teaching curriculum, allowing students to earn grades and credits that directly impact their graduation. As Zhenguo and Guanwen (2017) suggest, encouraging learners to

participate in the discussions and to complete their learning activities through incentives, scholarships, and credits benefits participation in MOOC learning. For example, when MOOC grades are transferable for university accreditation, students are more likely to focus on and engage with MOOCs to ensure successful graduation. This benefits MOOCs, as learners will pay more attention to MOOC programmes and try to finish and complete the courses on time.

The findings also suggest that universities and teachers can increase student engagement in MOOCs and other online courses by highlighting their significance early on. Providing an Introduction to the courses at the beginning of each semester or issuing official announcements, as University A did during the COVID-19 pandemic, can strengthen the connection between course completion and graduation, motivating students to take these courses more seriously. University A, by integrating MOOCs into its curriculum and making course completion essential for graduation, thus enhances students' awareness of the importance of attending the courses, so that most students are enrolled in more than four MOOCs, far more than their counterparts at University B. As Amerstorfer and Freiin von Munster-Kistner (2021) note, when teachers emphasise the importance of certain courses for students' academic development and career prospects, it helps students clarify their learning goals and increases their interest and engagement in the course content. Additionally, Locke and Latham's (2013) goal-setting theory highlights that clear, specific goals can significantly enhance student motivation. In the context of MOOC learning in Chinese higher education, teachers can work with students to set realistic learning goals, while providing feedback and encouragement to maintain the students' learning motivation. This approach not only helps students focus their efforts but also gives them a sense of accomplishment upon achieving their goals, further driving their desire to learn.

4.2.3 Why Did the Participants Choose to Study on the MOOC Platform?

Seven of the ten participants from University A agreed that they engage with MOOCs because it is a requirement of their university curriculum. Three participants indicated that MOOCs support their academic needs. In contrast, at University B, four of the ten participants stated they use MOOCs as an effective way to prepare for their traditional in-class lessons, as MOOCs provide a wide range of learning resources. Another four participants from University B chose MOOCs to acquire new skills and knowledge, while the remaining two used MOOCs to supplement the content of their in-person classes.

These findings suggest that, apart from the university requirements, students choose MOOCs for various reasons, such as fulfilling their academic needs, gaining new skills, or supplementing and reviewing material from their traditional courses. This highlights the versatility of MOOCs in addressing diverse learning objectives. This result indicates that MOOCs are able to meet the needs of different students through the optimal combination of teaching resources with the result that students can individualize their learning plans by using MOOC resources (Guerrero, Heaton and Urbano, 2021). The flexibility and adaptability of MOOCs allow students to select appropriate courses that align with their interests and requirements, thus enhancing both learning initiative and effectiveness (Castro, 2019).

Milligan and Littlejohn (2017) note that MOOCs offer a broad spectrum of course content, ranging from foundational subjects to advanced professional fields, enabling students to choose courses that match their academic and career goals. MOOC platforms often provide high-quality educational resources from leading global universities and institutions, which is a key reason why my participants chose to

engage with MOOCs. According to Voudoukis and Pagiatakis (2022), there are many reasons why students decide to participate in MOOCs and among these, MOOCs are designed by prestigious academic institutions with higher quality and the newest data are one of the attractive reasons. This aligns with the research of Mackness, Mak, and Williams (2010), who identified autonomy, diversity, openness, and interactivity as core characteristics of MOOC classes. These features allow learners to pursue their unique academic goals, contributing to the growing popularity of MOOCs. This point will be further explored in the semi-structured interviews discussed in the next chapter.

4.2.4 What Are the Participants' Course Selection Criteria for MOOCs?

4.2.4.1 Comparing Student Participants from Different Universities

At University A, half of the participants chose to engage with MOOCs due to curriculum requirements, where they were asked to attend courses via the university's official platform. The other half selected MOOCs based on their personal interests. In contrast, at University B, six of ten participants chose MOOCs because the instructors were renowned in their fields, while three participants selected MOOCs to meet the knowledge requirements of their subject curriculum. Only one participant prioritised the global prestige of the host university. This finding, gathered during the first phase of data collection, is particularly noteworthy. Most participants believe that MOOCs effectively support their learning needs, which is a significant factor in their decision to use MOOCs as a supplement to traditional classroom teaching. Even at University B, where MOOCs were not officially integrated into the curriculum, students independently discovered these courses, valuing the instruction of well-known academics and the high-quality content that aligned with their personal interests and academic needs, although this was not a mandatory requirement for their university.

This intriguing result needed further exploration in the interviews, which will be discussed in the next chapter.

Altbach (2014) noted that scholars who create and design MOOCs in all fields are generally from the top universities in English-speaking countries such as America. However, the questionnaire results indicate that students increasingly prioritise their personal academic needs over the prestige of the host institutions. This change in learner focus aligns with the theoretical framework of this study, which highlights the growing importance of learner autonomy. As Mackness, Mak, and William (2010) argue, learners are becoming more aware that how they learn is more critical than the course content itself. Nosratinia and Deris (2015) further suggest that students should change their focus from traditional teacher-centred learning to developing self-directed learning strategies. Students acquiring knowledge through their own initiative is effective in aiding their learning. The questionnaire results also reflect the development of Chinese students' learning motivation and self-regulation, as they increasingly move from dependence on teacher-provided knowledge to taking initiative in their learning.

Additionally, students' reasons for selecting MOOCs are driven by concerns over content suitability, the quality of teaching resources, their own learning interests, academic requirements, and the adaptability of learning formats (Deng, Benckendorff and Gannaway, 2019). These factors collectively ensure that MOOCs offer high-quality educational experience. The findings from my research similarly show that students choose MOOCs based on their individual needs, rather than simply following teacher recommendations.

4.2.4.2 Comparing Students and Teachers from Same Universities

In comparison, one of the five teacher participants from University A believed that their students chose MOOCs because the host universities were prestigious. Two of the five thought that having well-known instructors in academia was an important factor for students when selecting MOOCs. The remaining two teachers felt that students chose MOOCs based on their personal interests or hobbies. In University B, two of the five teacher participants believed students selected MOOCs due to the reputation of the host universities, while another two emphasised the significance of the well-known reputation level of the academics. The final teacher believed the students chose MOOCs according to the subject of their own hobbies or interests.

These responses show an interesting contrast between the two universities. Teachers at University A, which offers and promotes MOOCs officially, hold views that differ from their students' motivations. In contrast, teachers at University B, which does not officially promote MOOCs, share similar responses with their students. This discrepancy is noteworthy, as teachers in University A appeared to place more emphasis on the reputation of the host institution, while students prioritized their individual learning needs. This aligns with Nosratinia and Deris (2015), that students should understand that knowledge needs to be acquired from their own initiative: they need to change their minds from "focusing on teaching" to "focusing on learning". The data suggest that students at both University A and University B are more focused on meeting their own learning needs through MOOCs, rather than on the status or prestige of the host universities.

Based on these findings, I observed that teachers were often unclear about their students' specific learning motivations or prior experiences with MOOCs. As a result, I decided only to choose student participants who already had learning experiences via MOOCs to conduct the follow-up semi-structured interviews. Since each student's

needs and motivations are unique, only they can accurately express their thoughts and experiences. To avoid potential bias and ensure the most relevant data for this study, I excluded teachers from interviews focusing on students' personal experiences, as their responses could involve subjective judgments.

4.2.5 What Factors Could Affect Participants' Participation in MOOCs?

Two of the ten participants from University A believe that technological factors, such as platform page design and internet speed, influence their participation in MOOCs. Three of the ten participants think group factors, such as the varying educational backgrounds or education levels of other peers, are significantly affect their MOOC engagement. The other five of the ten participants attributed their participation to personal factors, such as their personality or the amount of free time they have would influence their learning on MOOCs

In University B, six of the ten participants identified group factors—particularly the educational background and academic level of the peers who chose the same courses as important considerations when choosing MOOCs. Three of the ten participants choose personal influence factors such as their own personality or the amount of free time they have to spend on online learning and the other one participant believes technological factors such as platform page design and Internet speed related to the MOOC platform and courses.

Scholars have analysed various factors affecting learners' engagement with MOOCs, including individual characteristics, external conditions, and the design of course platforms (Lai *et al.*, 2021). Other research highlights the importance of university

encouragement, teacher guidance, gender, academic achievement, and the diverse learning expectations of students (Lee, 2006), as well as the significance of different learner educational backgrounds (Pursel *et al.*, 2016). The results of the questionnaires reveal that there remain some disadvantages to participation in MOOCs, such as limited interaction between teachers and students, a weaker learning atmosphere, and higher requirements for students to be self-motivated (Woolf, 2010). It is clear from the questionnaires that students are most concerned with personal influence factors such as personality or time availability, and group factors such as the educational background and academic level of other participants. This confirms that the factors scholars have previously identified as affecting MOOC engagement are also relevant in the context of Chinese higher education.

Given China's large and diverse student population, educational backgrounds vary greatly depending on regional development levels. Peer attitudes and behaviours during online learning can significantly influence the overall learning atmosphere and the engagement of other students in the same course. This accords with the findings of Xiong *et al* (2015), who argue that one factor contributing to lower MOOC completion rates in China is the limited understanding of learners' prior knowledge and cognitive abilities by course providers. Therefore, these factors should be carefully considered in the design of MOOCs.

4.2.6 What Are the Issues That the Participants Have Encountered When Using MOOCs?

At University A, two of the ten student participants experienced issues with slow internet speeds when accessing foreign websites, which may have negatively affected their learning experiences. Four participants noted that they either do not like or could

not adapt to the instructor's teaching style. The remaining four participants felt that they did not gain the knowledge they expected from the MOOCs.

At University B, six of the ten participants reported that slow internet speeds from foreign websites were the primary factor affecting their online learning experiences. Two participants struggled with the teaching style of the instructors, and two felt that the courses did not meet their learning expectations.

From the result, apart from the technical issues such as Internet connectivity or IT problems, which may improve over time, most of the student participants expressed difficulty in adapting to the teaching style of MOOC instructors. One possible reason is that many MOOC instructors are from top universities in English-speaking countries, and they may speak too quickly or employ teaching methodologies and expressions that are unfamiliar to Chinese students. As Altbach (2014) notes, the course content is likely influenced by the instructor's educational background. Furthermore, since MOOCs are designed to reach a global audience, their content is tailored to a general university-level standard, which may not align with the specific needs of all students (Bralic and Divjak, 2016). Additionally, some courses did not meet the professional requirements or expectations of the participants because the content was not aligned with their university's curriculum. For example, students from University B, which does not officially offer MOOCs, accessed courses through other platforms that may not be well-suited to their teaching curriculum.

4.2.7 How Does Learning on the MOOC Platform Compare with Traditional Classroom Courses?

When comparing MOOC learning with traditional classroom learning, three of the ten participants from University A felt that MOOC learning is less effective than traditional classes. However, seven participants believed that MOOCs could complement traditional classroom learning.

In contrast, at University B, seven of the ten participants viewed MOOC learning as less effective than traditional classroom learning, while two thought MOOCs could serve as a useful complement. One participant from University B expressed hope that MOOCs might eventually replace traditional courses.

The differing opinions may stem from the fact that University A officially offers MOOCs, students in University A had more opportunities to learn via MOOCs and therefore may have more relevant reflection. According to Gore (2014), the change from traditional classrooms to online platforms provides flexible learning opportunities and abundant materials, attracting both learners and the academic community. This could explain why students at University A have gradually changed their attitudes toward MOOCs. Higashi, Schunn and Flot (2017) also believe that MOOCs have transferred learning from teacher-centred education to student-centred education so that students' sense of self-identity and their awareness of autonomous learning will also be greatly enhanced as is noted by student participants from University A. Similarly, Cheng and Ding (2021) support the idea that while traditional classroom teaching remains a common teacher-centred approach in China, MOOCs can effectively combine online and offline learning, serving as a valuable supplement to traditional classroom teaching.

4.2.8 How Often Do the Participants Use MOOCs to Learn?

All ten participants from University A reported the regular use of MOOCs as part of the university curriculum, where MOOCs supplemented the traditional in-class timetable according to the university's teaching syllabus.

In contrast, nine of the ten participants from University B used MOOCs for targeted, occasional learning. One participant used MOOCs for final exam preparation, utilizing the platform's extensive resources as a revision tool to complement their learning.

4.2.9 Why Did the Participants Choose MOOCs Instead of Other Online Learning Platforms?

When compared with other online learning platforms, the response from University A shows that one in ten participants chose MOOCs because they offer open, free access to online learning for everyone. Two participants enjoyed the flexibility in managing their study time, while the remaining seven participants chose MOOCs because the university officially integrated them into the curriculum in response to the restrictions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. This shift from traditional face-to-face teaching to online learning was required by the government, which announced universities to delay in-person classes and begin the spring semester online (Ministry of Education in China, 2020).

In University B, four of the ten participants valued MOOCs for their open and free accessibility, while three participants appreciated the flexibility in arranging their own

study schedules. Two participants believed that MOOCs offer more convenient learning and interactive communication, and one participant noted that MOOCs provide more comprehensive content compared to other platforms.

These responses highlight the key advantages of MOOCs, such as breaking through the limitations of the traditional curriculum, such as time and space. MOOCs rely on the Internet and enable global learners to access courses from prestigious universities, regardless of location. According to Kennedy (2013), MOOCs eliminate the enrolment constraints of traditional classrooms, making it possible to accommodate a large number of students. In addition, due to the large number of learners, participation in MOOCs often requires a high degree of autonomy because the instructors who deliver MOOCs cannot observe and supervise all the students at the same time.

4.2.10 What Problems Do the Participants Think Currently Exist on the MOOC Platforms?

Seven of the ten participants from University A identified a key issue with MOOCs, that students cannot get feedback on their learning on time after class. One participant noted that there were too few after-class exercises or homework tasks to help consolidate the knowledge gained on MOOCs. Another two participants mentioned that questions posted in the discussion forum were not answered promptly.

At the same time, in University B, six of the ten participants felt that the depth of knowledge explanations in MOOCs was insufficient. This may be because MOOCs are designed for a global audience, requiring content to be tailored to a general university level to accommodate a diverse range of learners (Bralic and Divjak, 2016).

Two participants also noted the lack of after-class exercises, while another expressed concerns about delayed feedback. One participant pointed out that discussion forum questions were not addressed on time.

These issues, primarily related to after-class interactions, are common across many online courses. As Yu (2015) explains, unlike traditional classrooms where teachers can observe students' reactions and adjust their teaching methods accordingly, MOOCs suffer from delayed responses and limited interaction through video-based instruction. Even when feedback is provided through forum discussions, the response time is often slow. As a result, interactions between teachers and students in MOOCs can be difficult and time-delayed when compared to traditional classroom teaching. Moreover, interactions between students are also restricted in MOOCs. Collaborative learning and peer interaction are widely recognised as effective ways to deepen understanding through discussion and shared insights (Supena, Darmuki and Hariyadi, 2021). However, even though MOOCs offer some opportunities for interaction, they lack the immediacy and richness of in-person classroom discussions.

4.2.11 What Do the Participants Think Using MOOCs Will Help Them to Develop and Achieve Most?

Five of the ten participants from University A believed that using MOOCs enhances their ability to learn autonomously. Three participants thought through MOOC learning, their information recognition could be improved, while the remaining two felt it increased their initiative to study. In University B, eight of the ten participants reported that MOOCs strengthened their ability to learn autonomously, one participant noted an improvement in information recognition, and another believed MOOCs boosted their motivation to study. As Kennedy (2013) notes, MOOCs require students to learn independently. They offer a structured and comprehensive method of

knowledge acquisition, which fosters students' autonomous learning habits and requires students to manage their own learning schedules.

Learning autonomy is a critical factor in MOOC study. Although MOOCs provide flexible, low-cost learning opportunities, they present challenges in areas such as the development of interpersonal communication among learners, interaction between instructors who deliver courses and learners, course design, and the quality of instruction (Zhu, Bonk and Sari, 2018). According to participants' experiences, many MOOCs are free and open access, which reduces financial pressure and the number of related academic tasks which students must complete within the courses. However, the lack of face-to-face interaction and online supervision can lead to a deficit in self-discipline and time management skills for learners to persist in completing the courses, causing many learners to drop out halfway through the courses. As Liu *et al.* (2023) believe, MOOC learning mainly relies on students' self-management abilities, and the differences in students' previous learning experiences, motivation and study habits may lead to inconsistent learning outcomes. Due to the large enrolment numbers of MOOCs, instructors often struggle to engage and guide individual students, so that students and teachers need to have an awareness of the importance of independent learning.

4.2.12 In What Ways Do the Participants Think Using MOOCs Will Help Them to Develop?

The questionnaire included one open-ended question: In what ways do you think using MOOCs will help you to develop? Some significant responses from the students have been collected and summarised as below.

The final open-ended question collected some interesting and insightful responses. In University A, Participants 1 and 2 noted that MOOCs provide valuable resources, allowing them to acquire more knowledge than through traditional classroom learning. They found their learning outcomes exceeded expectations, suggesting an improvement in their learning autonomy. This accords with the work of Hew and Cheung (2014), who note that MOOCs, which have been developed rapidly in recent years, are easy to use at low cost, covering a wide range of participants and offer diverse autonomous learning opportunities. Participant 1 also highlighted the additional benefit of MOOCs in maintaining social distancing during the COVID-19 pandemic, which recognised their role in emergencies.

Participant 2 further emphasised that MOOCs offer flexibility of learning methods to learners, and, as Participant 7 comments, learning through MOOCs is comfortable and flexible so that students can engage in the courses easily. This accords with the work of Ulrich and Nedelcu (2015), who note that the uniqueness of the MOOC learning process is embedded in the short, intensive video format which is conducive for learners to learn in short bursts of time and the fact that learners can set their own learning pace within a specified time, which, for example, supports teachers' continuous learning as they can be flexible and learn in their free time. Compared with University B, Participant 7 also thought MOOC could make learning more flexible. Participant 4 agrees. Participant 4 shared a unique perspective, suggesting MOOCs might replace traditional courses, as they increase individual interest in learning. She viewed the combination of MOOCs with traditional teaching as beneficial. In addition, she showed great interest in this topic and had some significant ideas related to MOOC learning, so she was selected for a semi-structured interview due to her insights.

Additionally, Participants 3, 4, 6, 8, and 9 noted that MOOCs enhanced their autonomous learning ability and motivation, with half of University A participants affirming this development. Similarly, in University B, Participants 3, 5, 6, 7, and 9 agreed that MOOCs foster autonomous learning ability and learner motivation, also accounting for half of participants. This result accords with the words of Rosell-Aguilar (2018) who notes that MOOCs, like other mobile-assisted learning methods, require students to be highly autonomous and self-disciplined. The participants agreed that MOOCs make their learning more convenient, and they are able to select their courses and arrange the time schedules. MOOCs offer students the freedom to choose their courses and study at their own pace, reinforcing learning autonomy, as noted by Yuan and Powell (2013). It can be regarded as an effective tool to improve the ability of autonomous learning for English major students (Yuan and Powell, 2013).

Participant 5 noted that when learning via MOOCs, some students feel more comfortable and relaxed, which makes them better focused on learning because they do not need to pay much attention to the environment or the relationships with other students. Participants 4 and 9 also felt that MOOCs cater to personal interests, fostering further engagement in learning. Participant 10 added that MOOCs promote adaptability and make learning easier, as they provide targeted resources, supporting the development of positive learning habits. Learners can find the exact material or courses they need through the Internet efficiently. According to Chengjie (2015), MOOCs have expanded the content of traditional teaching with the support of modern information technology. MOOCs are connected to a huge amount of knowledge and are immediately relayed to the students easily and then can be integrated into the teaching. Junhua and Peng (2020) also highlighted that the emergence of the MOOC teaching model has gradually expanded the traditional teaching content by

incorporating courses from foreign universities, benefiting both teachers and students by promoting knowledge integration.

In University B, Participant 1 noted that MOOCs helped develop exam-taking skills, as it was easier to summarise key points of online courses than through traditional classroom lessons which are full of different teaching activities. Participants 2 and 4 believed that MOOCs allowed them to acquire more knowledge than expected during their university years, while Participant 8 found that by engaging with MOOCs, it was easy to find interesting subjects and she can learn more than in the traditional university classes. It was also a good way to help her supplement or review the content of the in-person courses at university. Participant 10 noted that most of the MOOCs are free and offer opportunities to learn from well-known instructors. Additionally, MOOCs help learners identify skill gaps by comparing their abilities with those of other students, particularly in areas like listening and speaking skills.

4.3 Teacher Participants' Views on MOOCs

Information about the teacher participants was collected from the first two questions of the questionnaire. In University A, which officially delivered MOOCs, five teachers participated in the study, four female and one male. Four had been teaching for five to ten years, while one had less than five years of teaching experience. Notably, only one had prior experience teaching on MOOCs. In University B, which did not offer MOOCs on its official platform, five teachers were also selected, four female and one male. Three had five to ten years of teaching experience, and two had less than five years, with none having any experience teaching on MOOC platforms.

4.3.1 Do Teacher Participants Have an Interest in Starting Their Own Classes on MOOC Platforms?

Four of the five teachers from University A had no experience teaching MOOCs, yet all of them expressed interest in launching their own courses on a MOOC platform. In contrast, none of the five teacher participants from University B had any MOOC teaching experience, and only two expressed interests in starting their own MOOCs in the future.

4.3.2 How Many Courses Did the Teacher Participants Teach through MOOCs?

At University A, only one teacher participant had experience teaching on MOOC platforms, having taught three or fewer courses. In contrast, none of the teachers at University B had any experience with teaching on MOOC platforms.

The results suggest that teachers from both universities have limited experience with MOOCs, indicating that average-level Chinese universities did not, at the time of this research, have much experience in MOOC development and delivery. This aligns with Kaplan and Haenlein's (2016) findings, which suggest that MOOCs are primarily developed in more advanced regions and top universities around the world, potentially ensuring their higher quality. This is also in line with the current situation of educational development within higher education in China, where traditional face-to-face teaching remains predominant. MOOCs have not been widely promoted within the Chinese education system, with the result that many teachers have not been exposed to or involved in this form of teaching. According to Shu and Gu (2018), the traditional face-to-face teaching model still dominates the Chinese education system, and the popularity of online education is relatively low. However, this limited uptake

suggests significant potential for growth in China. As educational authorities and universities increasingly recognise the importance of online education, there may be a strategic shift toward expanding teacher participation in MOOCs (Gil-Jaurena and Domínguez, 2018).

4.3.3 What Do the Teacher Participants Think Are Their Students' Selection Criteria for MOOCs?

This has already been discussed in comparison with the results from the student participants' questionnaire above.

4.3.4 What Factors Do the Teacher Participants Think Will Affect Their Students' Participation in MOOCs?

Two of the five teacher participants from University A believed that group factors, such as the educational backgrounds of other participants, influence their students' participation. The remaining three believed that personal factors, such as classmates' personalities or learners' flexibility, are more significant. Similarly, at University B, three of the five participants thought that group factors, like the educational backgrounds of other participants, affect students' participation, while the other two evaluated participation more on personal factors like classmates' personalities or individual flexibility.

In China, the diverse educational backgrounds of students, which vary depending on the level of educational development in different regions, may influence course experiences and participation. Sergis, Sampson, and Pelliccione (2017) suggest that differences in educational backgrounds and learning habits can shape how students engage with a course. Lee (2006) also emphasises that external factors, such as peer attitudes, can strongly influence learning behaviours. For example, a positive group

dynamic, driven by enthusiastic peers, can enhance the learning atmosphere and stimulate more active discussions and ideas.

4.3.5 What Issues Did the Teacher Participants Think Their Students May Encounter When Using MOOCs?

When asked about the issues that students may encounter when using MOOCs, two of the five teacher participants from University A identified teaching style as a major factor affecting how students choose and engage with MOOCs, suggesting it could be a significant issue for their students. The remaining three teachers believed that students may not be able to learn what they want through MOOCs. In comparison, at University B, two of the five teachers highlighted teaching style as a potential problem if students do not respond well to it, while the other three expressed concerns that students may not learn what they want from the courses.

Nearly half of the teachers noted teaching style as a key factor influencing student engagement. This is an interesting result which agrees with Lee (2006), who suggests that in terms of external conditions, the higher the quality of the course content of the MOOC platform, students appreciate the teaching style, and the more likely the students could be well engaged in MOOCs.

4.3.6 What Is the Most Possible Reason the Teacher Participants Think That Their Students Choose to Study on the MOOC Platform?

Three of the five teacher participants from University A believed that the primary reason students choose to study on the MOOC platform is due to the university's

curriculum requirements, which shifted from traditional classroom instruction to online teaching. Two teachers, however, thought their students were motivated by a desire to learn new skills and courses. In contrast, at University B, four of the five teachers attributed students' use of MOOCs to university requirements, while only one believed students are driven by a desire to acquire new skills.

This aligns with Guerrero, Heaton, and Urbano's (2021) research that teachers' behaviours are important for promoting MOOCs to learners. The involvement of university departments and teachers in encouraging students to use MOOC platforms can significantly influence their participation. Although MOOCs were primarily used to deliver compulsory courses in some universities during the COVID-19 pandemic, once students develop a habit of learning through MOOCs, they are likely to continue using them in their future studies.

4.3.7 How Does Learning on the MOOC Platform Compare With Traditional Classroom Courses?

All the teacher participants at University A believe that MOOCs can complement traditional classroom learning. They unanimously agree that the future of education will likely involve a combination of MOOCs and face-to-face teaching. Similarly, at University B, all the teachers shared the belief that MOOCs could complement traditional classroom learning and foresee a future where both modes of instruction are integrated.

The consensus from participants at both universities indicates that MOOCs are increasingly viewed as a valuable complement to traditional learning. This indicates that with the development of the educational landscape, MOOCs have been gradually changing the traditional concept of teaching and learning (Chengjie, 2015). As

MOOCs are adopted by more colleges and universities, the traditional concepts of education are adapting to meet diverse requirements of education. According to the participants, MOOCs have gradually become a mainstream learning tool, and the combination of online and offline courses has improved students' learning efficiency. The incorporation of MOOCs into education has undeniably enhanced the effectiveness of traditional teaching. Khalil and Ebner (2014) emphasise that one of the key advantages of MOOCs is the ability to publish course information and content efficiently through advanced network technologies. In this way, the integration of MOOCs with traditional classroom teaching may represent a future trend in education.

4.3.8 How Often Do the Teacher Participants Think Their Students Use the MOOC Platforms to Learn?

All five teachers at University A agreed that their students regularly use via MOOCs because of the university's curriculum schedule. In contrast, at University B, three of the five teacher participants believed their students followed a similar pattern due to university requirements. One teacher, however, felt that students use MOOCs only for targeted, occasional learning, and the remaining one believed students primarily engage with MOOCs for revision before the final exams.

When compared with student responses from the questionnaire, it became clear that the teachers were not fully aware of their students' actual engagement with MOOCs and this result led to the decision to include only student participants in the semi-structured interviews, as they are the most accurate representatives of their own learning experiences.

4.3.9 What Reasons Did the Teachers Think That Their Students Chose to Learn Via MOOCs Instead of Other Online Learning Platforms?

At University A, three of the five teacher participants believed students chose MOOCs instead of other online learning platforms because the content is more comprehensive. One participant thought students prefer MOOCs because they are open and free, while another highlighted that MOOCs allow students to easily manage their time, which helps develop skills for organising learning and work plans. At University B, three of the five participants cited the comprehensive content as the reason students choose MOOCs, one noted the open and free access, and the remaining participant emphasised that MOOCs help students improve their time management ability and become more organised.

When comparing MOOCs with other online courses, one notable difference is the scale. MOOCs are large-scale open courses launched globally and are increasingly popular with learners (Pappano, 2012), whereas many other online courses are much smaller in scale and often limited to specific countries. MOOCs also offer more comprehensive content, which may attract students. Other online courses face challenges such as lower quality of the software, hardware, and networks, which can lower learner motivation, as well as without efficient observation, the learner motivation is not high enough. For students at University A, MOOCs have been launched through the university's official platform, encouraging students' participation. Moreover, many MOOC platforms collaborate with world-renowned universities like Stanford, Duke, and Yale (Roschelle *et al.*, 2000), which may further explain why students prefer MOOCs over other online learning platforms.

4.3.10 What Problems Do the Teachers Think Currently Exist on the MOOC Platform?

One of the five teacher participants from University A identified the lack of timely feedback after class as a key issue that needs to be addressed, while the other four participants noted that students' questions raised in the discussion forums during MOOCs were not effectively answered. However, in University B, three participants highlighted that students cannot get feedback effectively after class could be an issue that needed to be solved, while the other two pointed out that questions in MOOCs discussion forums were not adequately addressed.

All the teacher participants emphasised the importance of effective feedback for learners in MOOC environments. As Aldowah *et al.* (2020) noted, the inability to provide timely feedback can influence students' decisions to drop out from their courses, which is a significant difference between online and offline learning. In traditional classrooms, teachers can respond to students' questions or engage in discussions face to face, which helps keep students engaged and on track with their learning.

4.3.11 What Do the Teachers Think Using MOOCs Will Help Their Students to Develop or Achieve Most?

All five teacher participants from University A agreed that using MOOCs would enhance their students' self-learning abilities. A similar consensus was found among participants from University B, with all teachers selecting the same option. According to Andersen *et al.* (2018), this is a key difference between MOOCs and other online courses. MOOCs are typically offered by universities or platforms rather than individuals, which lends greater authority to course quality and provides a safer

environment for autonomous learning, as issues such as personal information leakage are minimized. Moreover, MOOCs help cultivate students' self-learning awareness, encouraging them to identify effective learning methods suited to their individual needs, thereby increasing their learning efficiency (Mackness, Mak and Williams, 2010).

4.3.12 In What Ways Do the Teacher Participants Think Using MOOCs Will Help Their Students to Develop?

The questionnaire included one open-ended question: In what ways do you think using MOOCs will help your students to develop? Some significant responses have been collected and summarised below.

In University A, Participants 1, 3, 4, and 5 believed that MOOCs help students develop skills such as self-motivation and independent learning ability, as MOOCs and other online courses require strong self-discipline and self-management, that students should be proactive in learning. The flexibility of MOOCs, unrestricted by time or space, enables students to easily access information, fostering autonomous learning and encouraging the development of independent learning skills. Participants 2 and 4 also suggested that MOOCs help students cultivate good time management habits, enhance their interests, and acquire new study skills. Participant 5 further noted that MOOCs enable students to adapt quickly to new concepts and technologies.

In University B, most teachers agree that MOOCs foster students' time management and independent learning skills. For example, Participants 1 and 2 believed that MOOCs not only enhance students' autonomy in learning but also boost their motivation. Other participants argued that MOOCs provide students with

opportunities to gain new skills and knowledge. Participants 2 and 4 highlighted that MOOCs offer rich learning resources, including free courses from prestigious universities, which are highly attractive to learners. MOOCs give students more chances to learn what they want. The flexibility of time and space, along with the availability of diverse resources, make MOOCs a powerful complement to traditional classroom teaching. This aligns with the findings of Breslow *et al.* (2013), who emphasise that MOOCs have significantly contributed to educational equity by transferring educational resources and courses from top universities to underserved areas. As students engage more with MOOCs, their access to knowledge broadens beyond what traditional methods can offer.

Participant 3 specifically noted that MOOCs enhance students' time management abilities, providing more flexibility compared to traditional classroom settings. Participant 5 noted the role of MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic, allowing universities to continue teaching while maintaining safety. He adds that MOOCs offer students the freedom to select courses from various platforms, which expand their learning opportunities. Yu (2015) notes that MOOCs allow students to choose from a wide range of courses offered by top universities and study at their convenience. As Zhu (2021) suggests, the increasing use of MOOCs will continue to benefit learners by providing greater flexibility and access to education.

4.4 Summary

In this chapter, data from questionnaires delivered to both teachers and students at the two targeted universities have been collected and summarised. The analysis above shows that both students and teachers are paying attention to the development of MOOCs. From the students' perspective, most of the participants recognise that MOOCs can enhance their autonomous learning ability and increase their learning motivation. Teachers, whether experienced in MOOC teaching or not, also

acknowledged the benefits of MOOCs and expressed their opinions about MOOCs. Some noted that MOOCs could help Chinese university students develop stronger learning interests and enable flexibility with regard to time for learning. Both student participants and teacher participants in the research answered the questions relevant to the reasons for choosing MOOCs, the challenges associated with MOOCs, and their thoughts on the future development of MOOCs, laying the foundation for more detailed conclusions when considered alongside the data from the semi-structured interviews in the following chapter.

During the process of investigating students' engagement with MOOCs at the two targeted universities, I initially conducted questionnaires with both student participants and teacher participants. However, after collecting and analysing the data, I decided to conduct semi-structured interviews with only student participants. Firstly, as questions related to personal subjective opinions about MOOC learning experiences, it was evident that teachers often lack understanding of the specific circumstances and personal MOOC experiences of their students, as students tend to engage with MOOCs independently, either at home or in their free time. This limited the teachers' ability to observe their participation directly. Secondly, students' responses provided a more accurate reflection of their MOOC participation, including their motivations for enrolling, as well as the specific challenges they encountered in MOOCs. This student-centred perspective was important to understand the reasons for and issues around their participation and the development of MOOCs. In contrast, teachers' responses mainly involved an overall understanding of the courses and a comprehensive mastery of their student learning situations. When they reflected on the topic and answered the open-ended question, they had more views on MOOC delivery and the changing of teaching methods rather than an understanding of their students' personal learning experiences. There are different focuses of MOOCs in the experiences of students and teachers in MOOC learning. Therefore, when framing and exploring how I could conduct the semi-structured interviews, I had to take into

account the fact that teachers were unclear about their students' previous experiences nor could they comment on the students' experience, therefore I decided only to select student participants who had previous experience of MOOCs to conduct the interviews. This decision was based on the data provided by the responses to the questionnaires.

Although I made the decision to remove the semi-structured interview for teachers from the main methodology of the study, it did not diminish the importance of the teachers' responses to the questionnaires. The data collected from the teachers' responses was still valuable. Students and teachers are two necessary identities in MOOCs, as in any form of learning. Neither is indispensable. They both play important roles in MOOC learning that result in differing perspectives and experiences. For this study, student participants provided responses to the questionnaires, informed by their subjective consciousness. If I had collected and analysed the teachers' opinions, the honest and subjective responses from the students would have been diminished. Their insights, therefore, offer a broader understanding of student engagement, course effectiveness, and the challenges that teachers face in integrating MOOCs into higher education in China. The feedback from teachers also informed my recommendations and enriched my overall analysis of the data, which assisted me in understanding the students and helped me better see the students' classroom performance from multiple perspectives. Furthermore, compared to students, teachers often have demanding workloads and less availability for interviews, which may have further limited their participation.

I retained and carefully analysed the teachers' questionnaire responses to ensure a comprehensive, multidimensional perspective in this study. This approach integrates different viewpoints, thereby deepening my understanding of MOOC learning. I decided, therefore, not to move further with interviewing individual teachers. The

next chapter will focus exclusively on the student participants and their experiences with MOOCs.

Chapter 5: Analysis of Findings from the Participant Interviews

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presented, analysed and discussed the key findings from the semi-structured interviews on participants' experiences and perceptions of using MOOCs. Half of the student participants were from University A, which officially delivered MOOCs, while the others were from University B, which did not. The data analysis was organised into several themes which arose from: the role of MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic; marketing and promotion of MOOCs; student engagement and autonomous learning; the advantages and challenges of MOOCs; and the potential future development of MOOCs.

As discussed in the previous chapter, the questionnaires consisted of thirteen multiple-choice questions and one open-ended question. Participants included both students who enrolled in MOOCs through university official platforms and those who engaged with MOOCs independently. Ten students from each university completed the questionnaires, with four subsequently invited to participate in semi-structured interviews. These students were selected based on the interesting ideas they shared in response to the open-ended questions and their evident interest in the subject.

The semi-structured interviews were conducted in two parts. The first set of interviews took place during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2021, involving four participants. To provide a balanced comparison of MOOC use before and after the pandemic, an additional four participants were interviewed approximately one and a half years later, at the end of 2022, after global COVID-19 restrictions had been lifted. Notably, the second group of participants did not discuss their experiences with MOOCs during the pandemic in as much detail as the first group. Additionally, the first group of participants had already graduated by the time of the second round of interviews.

In this chapter, the experiences of Participants A and B were from University A, which officially delivered MOOCs. Participants C and D were from University B, which did not offer MOOCs officially, though they had personal experience with MOOCs. All four were interviewed during the pandemic. In the second group, Participants E and F from University A, and Participants G and H from University B, were interviewed after the pandemic. I integrated the responses from participants E, F, G and H throughout this chapter, along with the responses of the original four participants to allow for a comparison of MOOC experiences both during and after the pandemic.

5.2 Findings from the Semi-structured Interviews during the Period of COVID-19 Pandemic

5.2.1 Using MOOCs during the COVID-19 Pandemic

This research examined the context in which both universities operated, guided by policies from the Chinese education authorities. In response to government-mandated restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic, Chinese universities were required to delay the return to face-to-face teaching and begin the spring semester online (Ministry of Education, 2020). Based on data collected from the participants' semi-structured interviews, Participant A and Participant B described the learning atmosphere as follows:

Participant A noted:

‘In March 2020, during the COVID-19 pandemic, it was really hard to attend class at my university, especially since my university is located in the northern part of China, but my hometown is located in southern part of China. It will increase the infection rate of coronavirus if I take a plane with a lot of people in a closed cabin space. Then the local government locked down the city where my college was located so my university

decided to conduct MOOCs based on the epidemic situation. I had the MOOCs for one year until now.'

When COVID-19 emerged as a significant challenge for universities and students, online teaching became the primary alternative to traditional 'face-to-face' classroom instruction. Participant A, for example, discussed her inability to return to her university in the northern part of China due to government-imposed lockdown restrictions. She expressed that staying at home and taking MOOCs was an effective way to stay safe, as she could not travel to her university to study as normal. This experience highlights one of the key advantages of MOOCs, the flexibility. MOOCs allow students to study from any location and at any time, unlike traditional classroom settings that usually follow schedules and by definition have to be in the classrooms. For example, learners can continue studying MOOCs even while travelling to other countries or locations, whereas face-to-face teaching at Chinese universities requires students to be present not only at a certain time but also in a certain place.

This change accords with Duan's (2021) observation that in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, all Chinese universities transitioned to online teaching during the spring semester, with over 1.08 million teachers delivering 1.1 million online courses. Duan believes that this rapid and large-scale adoption of online education has laid a strong foundation for the continued innovative development of online education and MOOCs in China. In Participant A's case, this flexibility allowed her to fulfill academic requirements while staying at home with her family, illustrating how MOOCs can cater to the personal needs of students during unprecedented circumstances like the pandemic.

Participant A's experience reflected broader trends in how online education platforms, particularly MOOCs, facilitated continuity in education during the pandemic. The

ability to access educational resources from anywhere not only provided safety from the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, but also demonstrated the potential for MOOCs to support learners in various contexts, beyond emergency situations. As Duan (2021) suggests, the widespread adoption of online learning during COVID-19 has accelerated the integration of digital platforms into mainstream education, which could lead to more permanent changes in how education is delivered, even in a post-pandemic world.

And Participant B added above:

‘During the COVID-19 pandemic, I cannot back to university. Not only me but all the cities lockdown to make people safe. Our university announced to change teaching online and deliver MOOCs instead of classroom teaching, it was the best way for everybody at that moment.’

Similarly, Participant B from the same university noted that at that time, learning online was a positive and safe way, especially going back to the classroom was prohibited by restrictions initiated by the COVID-19 pandemic. She reflected on how her initial attitude towards MOOCs gradually changed as she became more familiar with these courses delivered through her university's official platform. She came to appreciate and enjoy the experience of online learning. As Participant B says,

‘At the beginning, I thought these may not be as good as I expected. I am afraid the online courses are not as useful as traditional classroom teaching. For Chinese students, most of the students are used to teacher-centred teaching methods. Students who have less autonomous learning ability may not perform well in online courses. However, after I took MOOCs, I found it felt pretty good to study here. The courses are interesting and are supported by good materials the teachers are Native American people who are well-experienced.’

Participant B's comments also highlight the adaptability of students when faced with new learning environments. She experienced a change in attitude toward MOOCs, suggesting that the transition to online learning can ultimately lead to positive perceptions once students become accustomed to this learning method. This aligns with research indicating that students' acceptance of online education often improves as they experience its benefits, such as flexibility and accessibility (Li, 2022).

From the data, it is clear that Participant B had higher expectations for online courses, which was influenced by her prior experiences with traditional learning. She expected to improve her English-speaking skills by learning from American speakers, which cannot be available in a traditional Chinese classroom. This led her to focus on MOOCs, which offer a wealth of resources to support diverse learning goals (Huang, 2020). MOOCs' flexibility and rich availability of course options allow students to tailor their education to their specific needs, making them an attractive alternative to conventional classroom settings. This aligns with the findings of Ginting *et al.* (2020), who emphasise that MOOCs require a high degree of learner autonomy due to the lack of direct teacher observation. Participant B was surprised by how positive the learning experience was, as she was initially skeptical about the value of MOOCs, expecting them to be less useful than in-person courses. However, her attitude changed after completing the courses, when she found the learning experience to be very positive. She even felt that she was able to study independently outside of the traditional classroom after the online sessions. This change reflects the potential for MOOCs to exceed students' expectations, particularly when learners are proactive in managing their own studies.

In addition, data collected from students at universities that did not officially offer MOOCs shared their experiences, as described by Participant C:

‘MOOC learning is a very popular way of education these days, so I know something about it before I actually join in. Although our university did not launch MOOCs, we still use them sometimes. I was recommended to take the MOOCs by a good friend of mine. Before I took the MOOCs, I thought it would be similar to other online courses I have ever used before. Just like some recorded lessons with a knowledge points list. But after several courses, I found it interesting and different.’

This comment is notable because Participant C rated MOOCs highly without being encouraged to take them by her university. Although the second target university did not officially offer MOOCs, Participant C participated in MOOC study independently. As Milligan and Littlejohn (2017) suggest, despite some limitations, MOOCs have become a popular method for both professionals and learners to address current and future learning needs. Regardless of whether universities officially deliver MOOCs, learners can easily access them through the Internet and choose to participate on their own. Additionally, many students are introduced to MOOCs through recommendations from friends. Participant D supported this view, and noted that:

‘Our university did not have our own MOOCs. One of my roommates introduced me to this. They’re interesting. For example, if you have a hobby or field of interest, it might be hard to find related learning opportunities at school, MOOCs can help you decide if a specific field of study is right for you.’

One of the key research questions in this thesis aimed to explore in what ways the introduction of MOOCs has affected traditional teaching methods and classroom practice in Chinese universities and in what ways has the introduction of MOOCs has supported the development of students’ learning autonomy, motivation and engagement in their learning. The participants highlighted several advantages of MOOCs, including the flexibility to study during their free time, the ability to learn remotely, and access to a wealth of teaching materials and resources. In the context of

the COVID-19 pandemic, online courses were an effective alternative to traditional classroom learning, as they helped protect both students and teachers from the virus. This situation showed the limitations of traditional courses, which lack the flexibility to respond to emergency events. The wide acceptance of MOOCs can also be attributed to their effective marketing and promotion, which will be further discussed in the following section.

5.2.2 Marketing and Promotions of MOOCs

This section explored the marketing and promotion of MOOCs, with a focus on how students initially become engaged with these courses. Chiu and Hew (2018) suggest that group factors, such as the different learning backgrounds of other learners and individual personality characteristics, are key factors that influence learners when choosing and participating in MOOCs. As a result, many MOOC providers tailor their offerings to align with what students' value most, in order to attract and retain learners. In this study, the participants shared how they were introduced to MOOCs, as discussed below:

Participant A noted that,

‘Our university has launched other online courses before. I thought MOOCs would be like previous online courses. However, before we started to study at home, our leader professors gave us an introduction to MOOCs, which made us feel more curious about MOOCs. She said it is a new way of learning but not the same as the normal online courses we already had. It is more professional and extensional.’

This highlighted the role of university departments and staff in the marketing process, as they have the responsibility of promoting MOOCs to their students so that they can engage effectively. According to Guerrero, Heaton, and Urbano (2021), universities are assessed based on specific competencies, including teaching quality, research

quality, and administrative efficiency, all of which are relevant to all staff and should also be reflected in their MOOC offerings. These factors contribute to achieving the desired outcomes in student engagement with MOOCs in universities. Similar to traditional courses, university MOOCs are expected to cover specific areas of the curriculum. If teachers prioritize marketing MOOCs and emphasise their importance and benefits to students, it is likely that students will develop a clearer understanding of the courses' content and objectives. Participant B noted:

‘During the COVID-19 pandemic, our university delivered MOOCs instead of classroom teaching immediately, it was the best way for everybody at that moment. But actually, it is not my first time taking MOOCs. In order to apply for study abroad after graduation, I signed up for English MOOCs for the first time. It was about two years ago. I got information about this kind of learning platform from the Internet, and some are found through some ads.’

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, MOOC platforms primarily relied on online advertisements to promote their courses as products to potential learners. This participant noted that students could easily get a brief overview of different MOOCs through advertising on the Internet. This reflected the need for effective marketing strategies in the competitive world of online education. As Kaushik (2018) believes, developers of online courses must adopt diverse and efficient marketing methods to help create and promote MOOCs. Various marketing components can be used during this process, including public relations, advertising, advocacy and e-marketing, to ensure that the courses attract the students who may be interested in their courses.

It is also worth noting that Participants A and B's perspectives also indicate the importance of institutional support such as university support in facilitating the adoption of MOOCs. Unlike external platforms, their university's official MOOC system provided a sense of continuity and familiarity, which likely contributed to

their growing comfort with this format. This indicates that universities can not only promote MOOCs but also guide students through the transition to online learning. The university MOOC platform may help bridge the gap between traditional and online education and provide a smoother adaptation for students during emergencies such as the pandemic.

In University B, Participant C also said,

‘Because of the COVID-19 outbreak, offline classes were suspended and replaced with online courses in China. MOOCs can provide a good sense of experience for learners, as there is no contact with each other during this special period of COVID-19. Everybody feels safe and satisfied. I was recommended to take the MOOCs by a good friend and I started to join in MOOCs as well.’

And Participant D observed,

‘The local government locked down the city where my college is located so that some universities decided to conduct MOOCs based on the epidemic situation. Our university has some online courses as well but just recorded by our own teachers. However, I have some experience with MOOC studying on my own through the Internet. Actually, you can find MOOCs advertisements everywhere.’

These findings highlight the importance of effective promotion to influence the growth of MOOCs. As MOOC platforms have expanded rapidly in recent years, they have increasingly focused on marketing their courses to ensure that students receive relevant information through advertisements on various digital platforms. Cho *et al.*, (2024) suggest that MOOC designers not only aim to build and maintain a strong brand but also to attract their target users by promoting content that aligns with the users' needs. This is reflected in the experiences of Participants C and D, who

engaged with MOOCs after encountering well-targeted advertisements. MOOC designers, therefore, can filter potential users on specific platforms, ensuring that once these targeted learners engage with and appreciate the courses, they may introduce them to their friends. This creates a cycle where initial users become informal promoters, expanding the reach of MOOCs through word-of-mouth recommendations, which provides MOOC platforms with an opportunity for a second marketing process through social referral. By leveraging both direct and indirect marketing strategies, MOOC platforms can attract, engage, and retain users more effectively (Dina, Yunardi and Firdaus, 2021). This accords with the experiences of Participants C and D, who discovered MOOCs through peer recommendations, further illustrating the role of user satisfaction in expanding the reach of online courses.

The role of marketing in online education is necessary, especially in an environment where students are overwhelmed with options. By using targeted advertising and digital marketing tools, MOOC platforms can enhance their visibility and reach more learners. However, it is also essential to provide clear and accurate information about the course content and ensure that learners are fully aware of what to expect, thereby reducing dropout rates and making learners better engaged. In addition, the quality of the courses should be ensured. If the content and delivery of the courses match the marketing, learners are more likely to recommend it, thereby amplifying the platform's visibility. MOOCs that fail to meet the expectations set by their marketing campaigns can significantly harm both the platform's credibility and the reputation of the university offering the course. This suggests that universities and course developers must work together to align their promotional strategies with course quality and create a positive learning experience.

5.2.3 Students Expectations of MOOCs

As Voudoukis and Pagiatakis (2022) note, since 2012, top universities like Stanford University in the United States first set up online learning platforms and offered free MOOCs, after which MOOC courses started to develop all over the world. One of the key attractions for learners is that many of these MOOCs are hosted by prestigious universities, which are widely recognised. Prominent universities continue to adapt to the growing demand for MOOCs by transferring course materials from traditional classrooms to online platforms, aiming to expand their influence in education, enhance programme development, and contribute to societal knowledge (Rizvi and Nabi, 2021).

Interestingly, none of the participants in the first round cited the reputation of the host university as a primary factor in selecting or participating in MOOCs. Instead, they were motivated by other factors, such as personal interests or professional development needs. This suggests a shift in the way learners treat MOOCs, where intrinsic motivation and practical needs are more important. These findings may indicate that although university reputation remains an asset, it is not the primary reason for student engagement with MOOCs. As Participant A noted,

‘At the beginning, I hope MOOCs and some other online courses, as well as the daily online contact with universities and classmates can go on well during this difficult period. After a month of MOOC study, I found that MOOCs have more relaxed class atmosphere and more interaction between teachers and students. I am surprised about this.’

Participant A found that participating in MOOCs to be more relaxed compared to traditional face-to-face courses, and she was surprised by the level of classroom interaction, which exceeded her expectations. Despite the enjoyable experience at the beginning, she remained critical of certain aspects of MOOCs. She noted,

‘However, I am an English major student, I would be an English teacher after graduation and during the third year, the university always supports some practise lessons. The MOOCs are not as useful for practise as I expected in this aspect. I know people should not be too absolute, so maybe it just not good for practise or not suitable for some of the majors that need face-to-face experiment.’

Participant A explained that her university course had specific requirements that MOOCs do not adequately address. She noted that students participating in MOOCs face challenges, particularly in subjects requiring interactive engagement. This accords with the work of Rai and Chunrao (2016), who found that in traditional classrooms, students are expected to attend regularly, enabling teachers to adapt their teaching methods based on students' immediate feedback. In traditional education, interaction plays an important role in fostering engagement and enhancing learning outcomes.

As an English major, Participant A expressed that MOOCs are not useful enough sometimes for herself and her peers, particularly in English teaching courses that demand regular practice in communication and interaction. She emphasised that the kind of natural communication needed for language practice cannot be fully replicated in an online environment. This limitation indicates a key shortcoming of MOOCs in fields that rely heavily on interpersonal communication and real-time feedback.

While Participant A acknowledged the flexibility and self-paced nature of MOOCs can appeal to learners, particularly compared to the structured nature of face-to-face classes, she noted that this flexibility also reduces the depth of learning and interpersonal engagement, as well as personalised feedback. This mixed evaluation indicates the need for continued improvement in MOOC design to better meet the expectations of students accustomed to traditional learning environments. This

response leads to the next discussion: the advantages and limitations of MOOCs, particularly in comparison to traditional classroom teaching, and how these two methods are different in supporting and contributing to learning engagement.

When discussing the students' expectations of MOOCs, Participant B noted,

'To be honest, I even did not expect much. I know some online courses are free at the beginning and when it comes to the knowledge point, it starts to take tuition fees. But this is delivered by our university, I think it will be free and structured. And through attending the courses, I hoped that I could practise my speaking and listening skills, as well as understand more about the American speaking style. Apart from that, I also expected to know more about the local culture there. Hopefully, these will help me adapt to life studying there.'

Participant B believed that MOOCs are more targeted, well-organised, and professional than other online courses. In her experience, she has had the opportunity to learn from American native speakers, which helped her improve her English skills. The data from participants supports Vladimirovna, Vladimirovna and Rinatovich's (2021) work that one attractive feature of MOOCs is that many are offered by prestigious universities, leading students to place value on the reputation of the host institution. However, this trend has evolved. According to Howarth *et al.* (2016), students' motivations for enrolling in MOOCs have changed. They believe that most students are led to MOOC enrolment through the "close alignment of the course topic and subject matter with their personal goals and through the establishment of an attractive value proposition" (p.74). In other words, students today prioritise the content and relevance of the courses over the status of the universities offering them. This change explains why participants' expectations of MOOCs are more closely tied to their personal learning needs. Students now focus on whether the courses help them

achieve specific goals. Participant C, for example, highlighted this change in priorities, emphasising content relevance over institutional prestige.

‘My expectations for the MOOCs were that there would be more interaction with the teacher during the class and that there would be a teaching assistant to follow up on our academic progress regularly. The main reason for my expectation is that I found that most of the online university courses are like taking a break, students do not think importance of the lessons and just do what they want.’

This change in motivation indicates the development of online learning. While the prestige of host universities initially attracted many learners to MOOCs, the current focus changed to practical, goal-oriented learning. Students increasingly select courses based on how well the content is relevant to their personal and professional objectives. It can be seen as part of a larger trend toward learner autonomy, where students take greater control of their education by selecting courses that directly meet their needs.

Participant C expected more interaction during the MOOC classes than in traditional classes and felt that students often lacked the motivation to learn independently. She hoped that engaging with MOOCs could help her develop greater self-discipline and improve her ability to learn autonomously. Participant B also had her own specific needs, and she added,

‘I know some MOOCs come from some American universities. What I really need is that I can improve my speaking skill by learning from traditional American speakers or getting content that is relevant to local news. I thought MOOCs may be better than some normal online courses.’

This suggests that MOOCs can better meet students' needs than traditional classroom teaching in certain areas, such as foreign language learning. For example, Participant B needed to improve her speaking skills, and she feels that the specific online courses she selected would support her learning goals. The presence of American teachers delivering the courses allows her to put herself in an English-speaking environment. This aligns with Bralic and Divjak's (2016) research that MOOCs enable learners to choose courses that interest them or meet their needs, unrestricted by the usual constraints of time and space that often limit traditional in-person classes. Similarly, Guo (2017) notes that MOOCs, with their high-quality curriculum resources, can accommodate students' needs at almost any time.

It is also noteworthy that some students had previous experiences with online learning before their universities officially delivered MOOCs. Many participants had clear expectations and requirements when engaging with MOOCs. For example, Participant C specifically chose a MOOC expecting more interaction with teachers than she experienced in traditional classrooms, reflecting her personal learning preferences. This corresponds with Rosell-Aguilar's (2018) findings, which suggest that MOOCs require a high level of autonomy from students. Rosell-Aguilar (2018) further notes that MOOCs employ a different methodology than traditional classes, encouraging students to develop self-discipline and independence. Once students become accustomed to the distinct features of MOOCs, such as flexibility and convenience, they can study more efficiently and gain more control over their learning processes.

In addition, participants prioritised the convenience and alignment of the course content with their specific needs and motivations (Li and Moore, 2018). According to Li and Moore (2018), MOOC learners tend to exhibit a high level of self-confidence, believing that they can achieve their goals through the course. As Participant B noted:

‘I want to study abroad after graduation. What I really need is that I can improve my speaking skill by learning from traditional American speakers or getting content that is relevant to local news. I also had some oral English courses in university before but only for one semester, which is not enough actually.’

Participant B reflected on the importance of autonomous learning, selecting MOOCs that align with her specific needs and motivations. This perspective aligns with findings from the literature of Littlejohn *et al.* (2016). It also relates to students' expectations. However, for Participant A, unlike traditional classroom teaching, MOOCs cannot provide the learning environment she preferred. Certain subjects require more opportunities for interaction between teachers and students, which MOOCs often lack. Participant A highlighted this as one of the key challenges facing MOOCs. As Wang, Dong, and Zhang (2020) note, limited teacher-student interaction is a significant issue for students in MOOC education. This limitation indicates the fact that MOOCs have to suit the needs and motivations of the students.

During the semi-structured interviews, participants from University B which did not officially deliver MOOCs exhibited less motivation for MOOC study. Hollands and Tirthali (2014) explain that universities have adopted various approaches to engaging with MOOCs so that students' desire to learn can be influenced by their university's module content and timetable. If a university has not formally launched MOOCs as part of its curriculum, students may not choose to learn via MOOCs as a priority, as they tend to follow their universities' teaching schedule to complete courses and exams required for graduation. As Participant D responded:

‘Honestly, I didn't expect that much, because I'm not used to online learning. I could get distracted sometimes, even when in the classroom and face-to-face teaching model, so I think MOOCs may not be very helpful for me. But I decided to give it a try.’

and Participant C said:

‘Although MOOCs are convenient and not limited by time and space, there is less contact with the teacher as well, such as in terms of eye contact and classroom atmosphere. I am worried that I will not be able to get feedback from the teacher on how well I have understood and digested the course content. Most Chinese learners are used to traditional teaching ways and just those who have higher motivation can adjust time well for self-online learning. Whether they have high self-control ability or not, feedback is important.’

MOOCs can offer access to learning resources and content that may be difficult to obtain in a traditional classroom setting (Wang and Zhu, 2019). As a result, MOOCs present a valuable opportunity for learners who are willing to expand their knowledge. Some courses, such as those related to literature, are well-suited for delivery via MOOC platforms, while others may not be. Certain subjects require face-to-face intellectual discussions between teachers and students to foster deeper thinking, generate new insights, and enhance learning outcomes. Personal issues or questions raised by students often need direct, in-person communication to facilitate the exchange of ideas and inspiration, which can be challenging to achieve through online platforms. Moreover, MOOCs do not guarantee instantaneous interaction, such as eye contact between teachers and students. This absence of immediate engagement emphasises the need for clearer instructions and guidance in MOOCs. While some students enjoy the convenience of MOOC learning, many still value the interactive atmosphere of a traditional classroom.

These findings suggest that students are increasingly aware of their independent learning capabilities, as exemplified by Participant C’s discussion of her academic

progress. Her experience demonstrates how students' expectations appear to be related to what they can acquire from the course content. Rosell-Aguilar (2018) argues that MOOCs, as an online learning method, take a different approach from traditional classroom teaching, and require students to be highly autonomous. This aligns with the responses of participants, who emphasised that students are becoming more focused on their own needs and the qualities they expect from teachers when choosing to study via MOOCs. When students had a clear understanding of their learning goals, as Participant C noted, MOOCs could effectively support the learning process. In contrast, Participant D did not have high expectations for online learning, as she lacked the motivation to fully engage with MOOCs. As she added:

‘For me, MOOCs can only provide information in a very convenient form and that’s it, nothing more. I view MOOCs only as a source of additional information that will never replace hard work on understanding this information with the purpose of its active application in practice.’

5.2.4 MOOCs vs Traditional Teaching

Yu (2015) notes that students have the flexibility to choose from a wide range of courses offered by top universities and study at any time and in any location that suits them. However, key differences exist between online and classroom teaching, particularly in the context of delivery, relevance to student needs, and the degree of interactivity involved (Wilson and Stacey, 2004). Unlike traditional classroom teaching, MOOCs demand more effort from teachers because they face a potentially large number of students rather than a fixed group of one or two classes. Teachers should attempt to attract students on a larger scale, even sometimes without the benefit of in-person interaction.

The quality of MOOCs is often assessed by students, teachers, and even experts after they are made available online, as learners from various educational backgrounds enrol in these courses. This diversity can sometimes lead to content mismatches, where the course may not meet the specific needs of all students. Consequently, students may need greater motivation and autonomy to check, compare and select the courses that best suit their learning needs (Zhou, 2016). As Participant A noted,

‘We have some theoretical classes, which can be launched online but students also need some time to adjust themselves from the different teaching styles and materials. Not all the courses are recorded by our own teachers. Actually, I expect the courses from my own teachers, because they know us well and the courses may be more targeted, just like we are in our classroom.’

This aligns with Zhou (2016), who emphasises the need for greater teacher input to help students adapt to MOOC learning, as also noted by Participant A. Besser, Flett and Zeigler-Hill (2022) suggest that many students feel it is difficult to adjust to autonomous online learning environments. Traditional classroom teaching often gives students face-to-face guidance and immediate feedback, which can provide timely support for students. In contrast, MOOCs require students to attend the online sessions independently, which may be challenging for those who are accustomed to a more teacher-centred approach.

Participant B added,

‘I believe different students have different learning needs. Classroom learning cannot meet everybody’s needs. However, I know that is a traditional teaching methods. It can maximize satisfy everybody’s needs ultimately.’

This response is particularly insightful, as the participant acknowledges the necessity of autonomous learning in MOOCs while also emphasising the value of traditional

classroom attendance. This aligns with Wang, Dong, and Zhang's (2020) findings, which suggest that one of the key challenges of MOOC learning stems from students' lack of self-discipline. Their lack of experience in independent learning can result in lower learning efficiency. In addition, according to Kim *et al.* (2021), there remains space for improvement in MOOC design. In China, traditional classroom teaching has typically been teacher-centred, allowing teachers to control and adjust the pace of the class to better suit student needs. However, with MOOCs, learners can register from anywhere, so the content is often designed and developed according to the average level of the general university in order to meet the needs of more learners, rather than the needs of learners in a particular university. A similar situation happens in MOOC learning in China. This often diminishes the efficacy of MOOCs compared to traditional classes, as also noted by Bralic and Divjak (2016). As Participant D agreed,

'I still prefer the old school traditional classroom learning, for me, MOOCs can only at best provide information in a very convenient form and that's it, nothing more. I view MOOCs only as a source of additional information that will never replace hard work on understanding this information with the purpose of its active application in practice.'

while Participant A added:

'I feel better engaged in the traditional class. As I said, I am an English major student, I need more chances to practise English with classmates and teachers and make more progress. I need to stand in front of real people and give a speech or lesson. It cannot get the same reflection when doing online.'

The participants' data clearly highlights the differences between MOOCs and traditional classroom teaching. Traditional classrooms typically involve quality feedback and rich interactions between students and teachers, but MOOCs seem to be

more of a one-way system in online classes. In face-to-face classrooms, teachers lead discussions, allowing students to engage actively and exchange important information with their classmates. MOOCs also provide forums for communication, however, they usually involve less discussion, or in some cases, no interaction at all. This aligns with the findings of Gamage *et al.* (2018), who identified that one of the main challenges for learner engagement in MOOCs is the lack of timely, helpful, or constructive feedback.

However, compared to traditional classroom teaching, MOOCs have distinct advantages. They can overcome the limitations of time and space associated with traditional curricula, allowing students to access courses whenever and wherever they choose. Through the Internet, learners from all over the world can study with instructors from prestigious universities in their homes. Additionally, MOOCs can be particularly supportive for shy students who are quiet in the classroom as they do not want to interact with teachers and classmates. MOOCs provide an alternative learning environment that supports these students in engaging with course materials without the pressure of in-person communication. As Participant B noted,

‘I think online and traditional classroom learning both have merits and demerits. For me, I prefer online learning. It brings a more relaxed atmosphere for shy students like me. I feel I participate more in MOOCs than in traditional classroom learning.’

While Participant C thought,

‘I like online classes because I like the freedom to organise my time. Online classes don't just free up the students, they free up the teachers too. I can learn from teachers from different schools and even different subjects through online classes. Exposure to high-quality teaching and open horizons. My teachers consider that the students will get bored staying at home during the COVID-19 pandemic, also recommend we take

MOOCs, such as DIY handcraft, appreciation of Chinese art, Yoga, psychological counselling, etc.’

However, she further explained:

‘But I know I need traditional classroom learning. Because I do online learning back at home, it is hard for me to focus on it. The traditional classroom provides me with the environment to concentrate on my learning. And I like the human interaction, the laughter, the impassioned speech held by my teacher.’

The participant data indicates that MOOCs can be highly beneficial for students who are motivated to learn multiple subjects within a specific timeframe, as these courses often require concentrated learning efforts. Crosslin (2018) suggests that MOOCs are typically offered at no cost or low-cost, and their open-access format allows anyone to participate. However, this openness demands more flexibility from learners in terms of time management. In some subjects, fewer participants may enrol, limiting peer interaction, which in turn requires students to learn more autonomously.

Interestingly, many Chinese students initially viewed MOOCs or online courses as less valuable than traditional classroom teaching. They may believe that the development of education from offline to online is more relevant for the next generation, which may not influence their own learning experience now. This perception might explain why some students do not fully invest in online courses when they begin using MOOCs.

Bralic and Divjak (2016) argue that MOOCs are not always as effective as traditional classes, and Participant B agrees because both methods require students to actively engage in the learning process. However, Participant A highlights that both online and

traditional classes have their positives and negatives. She feels more engaged during MOOCs, while Participant C struggles to focus on online learning. This demonstrates that individual preferences and learning styles significantly influence students' opinions about the effectiveness of MOOCs and traditional classroom teaching.

5.2.5 Experience of Participating in MOOCs

In order to analyse the students' engagement with MOOCs, more detailed data have been collected about the experience of participating in MOOCs. Participants shared their learning experiences in relation to what they like about the courses, why they choose MOOCs and what motivates them to learn. Participant A noted,

‘I have other online classes before. In the beginning, I thought MOOCs would be the same, and students just attend to pass the exam and get the grades when they study at home. However, I feel more relaxed when I participate in MOOCs for a period of time and if I don't understand the course, I can playback the video and self-learn. Apart from the courses that the university arranged, I can go for more than I am interested in. My classmates also recommend other MOOCs on the platform that they already attended, they are interesting and different from traditional online courses that may be just recorded from a class. Some of them are from American universities, which have different teaching styles and content. One more important thing is that they are all free!’

Participant A from University A, which delivered MOOCs officially, said that at the beginning she thought MOOCs were similar to other online courses, but after participating for a while, she found MOOCs more relaxing and useful. This accords with the work of Andersen *et al.* (2018) that the difference between MOOCs and traditional online teaching is that MOOCs are typically launched by universities or established platforms rather than individuals. These MOOCs launched by universities offer greater benefits to students than individually designed MOOCs. For example,

during the COVID-19 pandemic, these MOOCs facilitated safe and effective distance learning for students and teachers. They also provided a more comfortable and accessible learning environment, as the courses were taught by teachers familiar to students, enhancing engagement and ease of acceptance. Additionally, these MOOCs offered higher-quality learning content compared to those randomly selected from various online platforms. She also noted that she attended some MOOCs on other platforms were from American universities, which gave her rich resources for free, which also accords MOOCs characteristics and advantages as discussed in the literature. Participant B added:

‘In the beginning, I thought this was just another kind of online course, but after learning more about MOOCs, I found MOOCs are more targeted and well-organized, also, more professional and detailed. I have joined MOOCs on different platforms. Some have interesting content, some give professional suggestions about how to improve their English speaking skills. I feel happy and enjoy it when my teachers share their local culture and interesting stories with us. MOOCs are flexible and include a huge amount of learning materials and resources.’

Participant B also gave a comparison of MOOCs and the other online courses she attended before and summarised the features of MOOCs as well-organised, professional and flexible, which also indicated MOOCs' advantages and attractions to Chinese students.

Participant C from University B, which did not deliver MOOCs officially, also shared her MOOC learning experience as:

‘The course is not controlled by time and space, which allows me to rationalize my own time. I found it has lots of advantages. MOOC platforms can support more resources for learners than traditional teachers. Using MOOCs can make learning time more

flexible and efficient, and also develop learners' self-reflection ability. However, I think most Chinese learners treated MOOCs as a complement to the traditional classroom not an exactly individual teaching method.'

And Participant D from the same university,

'I normally participate in MOOCs during weekends, because I'm busy with my daily studies and my part-time job from Monday to Friday, so I will use my weekends to learn something that I'm interested in. Normally afternoon or night, because I'm not an early type. I'm not a disciplined person either, I will participate in these courses depending on my mood.'

Participants C and D were all recommended to MOOCs by friends and teachers. Their university did not officially deliver MOOCs, so MOOC learning was not part of their study curricula. According to the participants, their MOOC learning experiences were positive. They all highlighted the advantages of MOOCs such as flexibility and their help in developing autonomous learning ability. As Kaplan and Haenlein (2016) believe, many MOOCs are free and accessible to learners, without time and geographical restrictions. These courses integrate various social networking tools and resources to form a diversified learning atmosphere and further enable learners to access high-quality educational resources (Krasny *et al.*, 2018). These factors all influenced learner engagement.

Despite these positive aspects of MOOC learning, participants also had some concerns. As Participant A highlighted MOOCs, compared with traditional classroom teaching, were less interactive:

‘MOOC learning is positive. It’s a new try for both the teachers and the students. However, one problem was that I could not do face-to-face teaching practice. I know everybody has this issue and I fully understand this special situation under COVID-19. So I just try to make full use of the theoretical part of the courses and wait for the university to be unlocked to do some practice. I use all my time trying to learn and to do observation during this hard time.’

According to Mellati and Khademi (2020), although MOOCs are flexible and accessible, the lack of interaction in MOOCs is a significant limitation when compared with traditional classroom teaching, which could impact the learners' learning experience. In traditional classrooms, interaction between students and teachers is an important feature. Face-to-face classroom teaching supports real-time discussions, immediate feedback, and the opportunity to do group work, which influences the students' engagement (Kemp and Grieve, 2014). Many MOOCs have discussion forums or assessments, in contrast, MOOCs still lack immediacy and interactivity. As Participant A added:

‘As an English major student, I need more chances to take tests and practise how to teach face-to-face. I like the interaction between students and teachers. This is why I prefer to study in class. However, I also need to learn teaching theories and do more reading and observation. In this case, MOOCs are useful as well. I accept MOOCs and other online courses because I know education is getting diversified.’

However, Participant B offered another view on the aspect of interaction; as a shy person, interactions made her struggle sometimes, so MOOCs greatly enhanced her self-learning ability and motivation:

‘I also had some oral English courses in university before but only for one semester, which was not enough. I believe the most important process to improve speaking skills

is to practise as much as possible. Not all the students are lucky enough to have an English learning background while they grow up so I expect I can solve this problem via MOOCs because MOOCs contain rich resources. Students can choose whatever they want there.’

She explained:

‘Traditional classroom teaching has limited time and chance to practise. Students only speak English during the two-hour class, which is not enough. MOOCs support richer content and I can play back again and again and even change resources one by one, which made me really enjoy it. It brings me confidence in speaking English. In previous classroom teaching, we attached more importance to written English instead of oral English. I think in order to improve speaking skills, students need to open their mouths as much as possible. However, I am a shy person. I usually be quiet when I am with other students. I am afraid of making mistakes. Therefore, MOOCs are really useful for me because I can study and practise at home, follow the teachers and practise more by myself.’

In addition, in University A, MOOCs are part of their curriculum, so it has a key role in students’ graduation. Therefore, participant A and B all mentioned this as a factor that influences their learning motivation. As Participant A noted:

‘I choose the time by my living habits, one at 9:30 am, one at 14:00. Almost the same class schedule as I study at the university. I chose these two periods as the university would also help me to adjust to the school hours once the lockdown finished. Because students can take credits if attending the MOOC class, I usually take classes twice a week. I should attend online courses at the predestined time and the teacher will make a roll call sometimes. It is relevant to my graduation.’

And Participant B added:

‘I also get credits from the MOOCs that our university launched. These are relevant to my graduation.’

Without the curriculum requirement of MOOC learning, Participants in University B also acknowledged the flexibility of MOOCs. Participant C said:

‘I can choose to come to class in the mornings and evenings when I am at my best mentally, avoiding the sleepy afternoon hours, and I can schedule some outdoor activities in the afternoon. This way I can balance school and leisure throughout the day. MOOCs enable me to study at home and can save time. I think it will be more interesting and relaxing. MOOCs are convenient and flexible as well. When some parts of the content are unclear, it can be easily playback and learn again.’

In summary, all four student participants had positive learning experiences with MOOCs. MOOCs influenced their autonomy, motivation, and engagement.

5.3 Findings from Semi-structured Interviews after the Period of the COVID-19 Pandemic

This section of semi-structured interviews was conducted approximately one and a half years after the initial set of interviews, at a time when COVID-19 restrictions had been lifted globally, and universities had returned to traditional classroom teaching. The purpose of this section was to gather data and compare participants' experiences of using MOOCs both during the pandemic restrictions and after they were lifted.

5.3.1 Marketing and Promotions of MOOCs

This section explores the marketing and promotion of MOOCs. In the interviews, both Participant E and Participant F shared their initial experiences and impressions of MOOCs, providing insight into their first encounters with these online courses as follows:

Participant E noted:

‘I heard about MOOCs for the first time from my teacher Miss L who taught me the subject of intensive reading. Miss L raised a question in terms of "globalisation", that is "from your perspective, why globalisation is being called a double-edged sword?". Meanwhile, she recommended we analyse it from a class in a MOOC platform taught by a teacher from Hebei Normal University. Then during the COVID-19 epidemic, our university launched a series of MOOCs when I and my classmates were self-isolated at home.’

This student was initially encouraged to take MOOCs by her teacher, then the university began to deliver its own courses. Her response accords with the findings of Guerrero, Heaton, and Urbano (2021), who emphasise that the role of universities and lecturers is important in promoting MOOCs to learners. Their involvement not only helps raise awareness but also enhances student engagement with these online learning platforms.

and Participant E further added:

‘In the beginning, I was just curious about the answer to that question. However, it seems like opening a new world for me to have such an effective method that could help us study something in a completely new field. Then we start to take MOOCs regularly instead of classroom teaching, which is relevant to our credits and final scores.’

According to Zhenguo and Guanwen (2017), providing learners with accreditation whether through grade point averages, scholarships, and credits is an effective strategy to encourage sustained engagement with MOOCs. These incentives can motivate Chinese learners to actively participate in discussions and complete the courses. Participant E's experience reflected this, as the prospect of such rewards played a role in her continued participation in MOOCs.

Participant F, from the same university, noted:

'The first time I was introduced to MOOCs was during the COVID-19 pandemic. Our university announced that all the classes changed online. I was happy at that time because I did not need to go back to school. I thought it would be like other online courses I had before. But one of my roommates, who is ranked top 3 in our class, said she already uses the MOOC platform and feels that MOOCs are better than she thought, and she discussed the experiences with other roommates in our accommodation's WeChat group. Later, our university opened again, and we went back to our classrooms. Now we still use MOOCs to preview the courses sometimes. Our teachers will also recommend and share some nice MOOCs when they find them.'

This is an interesting finding: Participant F was introduced to MOOCs several times by both her roommate and later by her teachers. These experiences align with the promotion of MOOCs as discussed by Chiu and Hew (2018), who emphasise the role of peers and educator influence in encouraging MOOC participation.

Although universities returned to traditional classroom teaching in 2022, and participation in MOOCs was no longer mandatory, MOOCs continue to provide valuable access to learning resources. As Israel (2015) suggests, MOOCs can be seen

as a supplement to traditional face-to-face teaching methods, offering flexibility and additional content that can enhance the overall learning experience.

In University B, which did not officially deliver MOOCs, Participant G and Participant H both shared that they were introduced to MOOCs by their teachers' recommendations, which also proved that teachers are important factors in MOOC promotion (Chiu and Hew, 2018). Participant H noted:

'I was recommended by my high school teacher. We sometimes chat through phones. I have a lot of important courses for our English majors such as History of English and American Literature, Linguistics, and English Lexicography. I am afraid I cannot do well in classrooms and cannot pass the exams, so she recommended MOOCs to me as a supplement to normal classroom learning.'

Participant G added:

'One of my teachers who teaches the History of Western Civilization introduced me to MOOCs first and she advised us to watch some videos especially the lectures about Western history using the MOOCs. I have some other computer-based classes, but she recommended this, and we have tried them. Then I started to attend more MOOCs.'

The fact that students engaged with MOOCs due to their teachers' recommendations highlights the significant part teachers play in promoting MOOCs to students. One reason is the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on students' learning. As discussed earlier, students often turned to MOOCs on the recommendation of their professors when traditional teaching was disrupted. The pandemic triggered a sudden change in educational delivery methods: with cities across China in lockdown and universities being required to close, students were compelled to engage with online learning, including MOOCs. Another reason teachers are key in MOOC promotion is that

MOOCs are still not officially integrated into the curriculum of Chinese universities, and their outcomes are not aligned with the standards typically used by these institutions.

Interestingly, all participants, whether interviewed during or after the COVID-19 pandemic, were introduced to MOOCs by individuals within their universities, either teachers or friends. Although there are many MOOC platforms and companies available online, as Hao, Li, and Bai (2023) suggest, learners choose courses based on their specific academic needs. However, their learning needs are not always fully met, as factors such as the instructors' different backgrounds, the alignment with the university curriculum, and scheduling can affect the quality of the courses. The essence of course selection for students is to find content that fulfils their academic objectives and to take part in the relevant MOOCs. Therefore, recommendations from classmates or teachers become essential, as courses chosen by a majority of learners are more likely to meet the broader needs of the student body (Sheng *et al.*, 2020).

There are also examples of negative experiences from Participants F and G, highlighting that, regardless of how MOOCs were introduced to them, students may not always be satisfied. As Participant F noted:

‘I only believe my teacher's and friends’ recommendations. You know there are so many platforms and courses on the Internet. When some courses recruit students, they will use "famous teachers", "famous universities" or popular content as gimmicks, but when you register or even pay fees on some platforms, you find that it is not what you expected. This is very distressing.’

and Participant G added,

‘When I choose a course, I will refer to the recommendations of other students and teachers. The big data is interesting, once you search some keywords online, you will receive many recommendation ads. I cannot distinguish which fits my needs.’

Since the COVID-19 pandemic, it has become increasingly common for teachers to engage in the ‘self-media industry’ (Zhang and Xiao, 2023). Self-media, also known as citizen or personal media, refers to privatised, civilianised, and autonomous communicators who use modern communication tools to deliver information to an unspecified majority or specific individuals (Zhou and Feng, 2019). Many individuals creating content in this space may lack the qualifications required to teach at universities, as there are no formal threshold requirements for delivering content on self-media platforms. This can result in uneven teaching quality and, in some cases, lower standards for online education, including MOOCs. As a result, the quality of course content and delivery may not always be guaranteed. It is therefore essential for teachers and universities to actively monitor, screen, and tailor their course recommendations to ensure that the content aligns with students' needs and maintains a high standard of instruction.

5.3.2 Learner Expectations of MOOCs

Compared to the interview results from one and a half years earlier, the participants in 2022, post-COVID, showed a greater focus on the practicality of the courses and their personal learning experiences with MOOCs. Their primary concern was that the courses are more detailed, targeted, and aligned with their specific learning needs. As Participant E from University A noted:

‘I have two main expectations. Firstly, I hope that the duration of the partial courses can be extended as long as possible. Another expectation is whether Chinese translation

could be chosen in the video speaking in English, especially for some professional courses, such as Linguistics.’

Participant E expressed a desire for an extension of the course duration and enhancements to certain auxiliary functions, such as translation services and subtitle options. She said,

‘Sometimes I came across a suitable course that could answer my current confusion, but I was told that the semester was over and the courses had been closed naturally.’ and ‘As an English major, there is no denying that English subtitles can improve our listening and reading comprehension skills virtually. However, for some courses difficult to study, it will take a long time to understand the literal meaning without Chinese subtitles, let alone try to understand it deeper, which will make me exhausted to a certain extent.’

In university B, Participant G also explained,

‘I expect that it can note the translation of some difficult words or some proper nouns. Besides, it can play and pause automatically when some important parts are taught according to the learners’ average level of English. Maybe it should require the teachers to leave some time for students. I hope it can improve these functions because sometimes I have to take notes.’

Participants expressed a desire for enhanced functionalities in MOOCs, aligning with the findings of Liu and Correia (2021), who indicate that MOOCs featuring intuitive homepages and easy access to diverse course materials can significantly enhance learner engagement. Additionally, other factors affecting learning engagement were also identified by participants. Specifically, those MOOCs that are well-designed with clear learning objectives, well-referenced documents and interpreted documents, and

interesting content are more likely to attract learners. Notably, half of the participants reported a preference for courses that include Chinese subtitles and content relevant to their compulsory university curriculum. Bawa (2016) argues that poorly designed courses may lead to confusion, and continued engagement with such materials can result in lower completion rates.

From this data, it can be summarised that MOOCs face challenges in specific contexts that demand greater time and flexibility from students. For example, both of the participants think translations and subtitles are needed to enhance their learning at times. In a traditional classroom, these issues can be more readily addressed, as teachers can adjust their teaching methods based on students' behaviour. They can provide adequate time to clarify concepts that may pose difficulties for learners. Williams (2024) believes that in traditional education, teachers are the output side of knowledge, and students are the receiving side. This limitation often results in a relatively fixed relationship between teachers and learners due to the limitations of traditional classrooms. However, in online environments of MOOCs, both teachers and learners often struggle to interact effectively, particularly when students require immediate responses to their inquiries (Williams, 2024). This issue highlights the advantages and disadvantages of MOOCs, as well as the differences between MOOCs and traditional classroom teaching, which will be explored in the next section. Participant F said,

‘I expect our university can input more courses of interest for us, for example, something about music or travelling. I like this content, but I am afraid I cannot keep attending the courses if they do not from university requirements.’

and Participant H added,

‘In addition, from above, I also hope I can learn something from MOOCs that I cannot learn in classes, so as to enrich my professional knowledge and strengthen my

professional skills. It is because my university is at a normal level. I would like to have a look at the courses that top universities have. However, I also worried that I could not focus well without the observation of teachers.’

These findings indicate that MOOCs require a greater investment in autonomous learning from students who engage with these platforms. According to Chengjie (2015), a Wikipedia entry outlines five essential steps for succeeding in MOOCs: identify what you need, submit an application, connect to the network, join a group, and engage with concentration. The first four steps can be easily accomplished by individuals with basic Internet skills; however, the fifth step, engaging with concentration, emerges as a critical factor for success in MOOC courses. Chu (2022) agreed that this open and free learning method requires learners to have stronger autonomy and self-control ability in their learning. This presents a particular challenge for Chinese students, who have typically been conditioned by an exam-oriented educational system that fosters passive learning behaviours.

5.3.3 MOOC vs Traditional Teaching

According to Chengjie (2015), compared with MOOCs, traditional teaching methods are characterised by a relatively fixed structure and high standards regarding classroom discipline and the cultivation of a positive learning environment. These characteristics benefit learners by fostering good learning attitudes and habits. In contrast, the teaching model of MOOC platforms is more flexible, allowing learners to study at times and places that align with their individual lifestyles. However, this flexibility necessitates that learners possess strong self-discipline and the ability to engage in autonomous learning. As Participant E said,

‘I enjoy learning in a traditional classroom, and I can engage better. Compared to online courses, traditional classroom learning provides us with a strong learning

atmosphere due to the presence of our classmates, which is essential in our learning process, no matter it is cooperation or competition. The offline courses are more interactive and participatory, which means that we can communicate with our teachers and classmates at any moment. It also prevents us from being distracted in class to some extent.'

Participant H also noted that,

'I feel that I engage better with traditional classroom learning. I can communicate with teachers and classmates more closely. I can get feedback in time and I can practise English with my classmates. For our English major students, practice is important. The traditional classroom is more dynamic. I can interact more closely with my classmates. It's easier to recognise the difference between me and other people so that I can be aware of what I lack and to improve myself purposefully.'

Jing (2018) asserts that the primary objectives of university English teaching are to enhance students' skills in listening, speaking, and translation, thereby improving their overall proficiency in English. However, since English is a second language for Chinese students, learners require more time to practice and develop accuracy (Zheng, Lu and Ren, 2019). All participants in the interviews are enrolled in English major courses, which may lead them to consider their learning context more critically when discussing the benefits of MOOCs versus traditional classroom learning.

Regardless of whether learning independently or engaging in interactions with teachers, students consistently demonstrate a strong interest in teaching resources that are relevant to their academic needs and aligned with their university curriculum. Consequently, it is important for these learners that their teachers recommend appropriate resources on MOOCs and select teaching methods and materials that

complement classroom learning. This integration ensures that MOOCs provide practical benefits that support in-class teaching (Bralic and Divjak, 2016). However, Participant F and Participant G held different points of view. As Participant G noted,

‘I feel that I engage better with online learning because I like taking notes if I miss something important or if there is something I don't understand, I can also record the lecture and keep it in my equipment so that I can review the class in time. I do not really like answering questions in class. I enjoy learning by myself on my own time.’

While Participant F added,

‘I prefer MOOCs, but I also know that classroom courses are important, and I will take both. I prefer a quiet and free study atmosphere to think by myself. In class, there are many times when I feel like I am a bystander. I am not a good student, my participation and discussion are not as good as some other students, and I don't like to speak. In class, I mostly listen to the teacher and record the key points. But in MOOCs, I can stop and think at any time. Learn at my own speed. I like new things, on the MOOC platforms, there are many different courses that I can choose to learn, or not for mastering, but just knowing. MOOCs are so convenient.’

These findings align with the advantages of MOOCs as discussed by Huang (2020). Compared to traditional classroom teaching, MOOCs are open and flexible, transcending the limitations of in-class instruction, which allows learners to create their own educational experiences and seek information independently (Agonacs *et al.*, 2020). Participant F's reflections on MOOCs support this view. According to Li (2022), MOOCs connect learners from around the world through the Internet, fostering an open learning atmosphere that encourages proactive engagement through micro-videos. This format particularly benefits shy or quiet learners, as it reduces the pressure for direct communication or interaction. For instance, Participant E, who

enjoyed learning by herself and disliked answering questions in class, finds MOOCs more conducive to her engagement.

Meanwhile, participants acknowledge that MOOCs cannot fully replace traditional face-to-face teaching. Human connection is essential, and students benefit from personal interactions with teachers and classmates, which online courses cannot adequately provide. The data from the semi-structured interviews indicate that traditional classroom teaching facilitates interaction between teachers and students, corroborating Zhu and Li's (2019) assertion that the traditional Chinese classroom model remains prevalent due to its unique advantages. In this model, teachers guide students through in-depth explanations and analyses, optimizing the teaching process and interacting with students by focusing on key lesson points while responding to student feedback. This dynamic allows for reflection on both teaching effectiveness and student comprehension (Mag, 2019).

However, traditional classroom teaching can be limited by the availability and quality of teaching materials, as well as fixed class schedules and physical spaces, indicating that it may not be as flexible as MOOCs. Therefore, MOOCs can serve as a valuable supplement to traditional classroom teaching, offering a wealth of resources that allow students to learn at their own pace. Furthermore, MOOCs can alleviate student anxiety (Ma, 2022), as the learning environment tends to be more relaxed, reducing stress. As Krashen (1982) noted, "When language learners become anxious, a filter is raised in their minds that blocks linguistic input from entering," which highlights the importance of a supportive and relaxed learning atmosphere.

5.3.4 Experience of Participating in MOOCs

In order to analyse the students' engagement with MOOCs and get a comparison of MOOC experiences both during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, more detailed

data have been collected in relation to what the participants like about the courses, why they chose MOOCs and what motivated them to learn. Participant E noted,

‘My MOOC learning experience is positive. The variety of MOOC resources avoids the situation where we cannot find appropriate content. Some MOOCs are produced by famous universities or professional teachers. As an English major student, it is not only a procedure of studying the knowledge but also sometimes an enjoyment to follow the teacher and explore a new course. Wonderful pronunciation, accessible structured presentation, unique viewpoint, all of these would make me fascinated by MOOCs.’

In the same university, Participant F said:

‘My roommate first recommended MOOCs to us. I found it very practical and convenient. At that time, I was taking online classes at home so I tried the MOOCs by the way and found it very interesting. It includes many courses related to our university courses, but they are not the same. I also searched for Stanford courses to try out, but I thought it was difficult for me haha. My English level is not enough and needs to be improved.’

Although this university officially delivered MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic, after one and half years, students have already become fond of MOOC learning and participated in MOOCs not only as an immediate action to respond to the government requirements. As Participant F added:

‘During COVID-19, we have MOOCs instead of classroom courses. But after going back to university, it becomes a supplement to traditional classroom teaching. Some of the courses and platforms we have used before continuing to be used. The teacher will still recommend some good cases to us for pre-class preview or after-class enrichment. Now my study frequency is about twice a week, mostly as a supplement to linguistics

and intensive reading, which are a bit difficult for me. At first, I thought I could find the answers and explanations to the after-class exercises here. Although I didn't, it did help my study. Some content is easier to understand if explained in another way. I feel happy when I understand the learning content.'

After the pandemic, students still used MOOCs as a supplement to traditional classroom teaching, as Participant E added:

'In most cases, I prefer to study in MOOCs in order to find the answer to a certain question or to cover a knowledge gap. Meanwhile, I probably spent more time in MOOCs during the holidays than I did in university. The reason is rooted in the fact that learning in holidays is more focused on a particular topic or subject'

In University B, participant G responded:

'MOOCs are good. I like using it because of its rich resources. When I had some classes before in the classroom, teachers were teaching according to the textbook, but during MOOCs, I can search for a lot of relevant content I need on time. Some even raise my interest in relevant fields.'

And Participant H noted:

'I prefer the richness and diversity of MOOCs, which can explain those things I do not know or do not understand in the classroom, and it is also relatively convenient. I can review several times as well and I can choose many videos on the same topic. By listening to different teachers, I can find the best explanation. Well, especially during the epidemic environment, I think it is very helpful to my daily study.'

All the participants showed a high preference for MOOCs, which indicates that MOOCs developed significantly during the COVID-19 pandemic and were a commonly recognised learning method for Chinese students. This accords with the work of Duan (2021), who noted that the Chinese government recognised the importance of online education during the COVID-19 pandemic and actively supported the development of MOOC platforms. Since that time, MOOCs have been accepted by more and more learners.

In addition, the increasing use of MOOCs also indicated that the motivation of learners was enhanced, and their autonomy increased. Participants' responses showed the development of their learning autonomy. As Participant E said:

'I prefer to take courses in MOOC at night. Because I still need to take classes during the day. On the other hand, it is a good time for me to calm down easily to study independently. I prefer flexible time for MOOCs. Just like I said above, I can arrange my time easily. Sometimes learning at university and sometimes learning via MOOCs are efficient.'

And Participant F added:

'I prefer to study or read quietly by myself. MOOCs can suit my preferences very well. Sometimes I find it noisy in the study room or class, and I don't like studying with many people. I like to take MOOCs in the evenings and weekends. It's quieter at night. I can review the parts I didn't fully understand from the previous week or learn about the courses for the next week. Ummm, sometimes I will also be lazy and do not review, or only participate in part of it. I can arrange my time easily.'

Participant G noted:

‘I enjoy learning via MOOCs. After a period of MOOCs, I think my awareness of autonomous learning has improved.’

And Participant F added:

‘I think it has a positive meaning for me because attending MOOCs can not only teach me more knowledge but also enrich my life. It brings me positive experiences in life and study. I feel confident now and I am also searching for some courses of my own interests such as history and poems.’

5.3.5 Summary

5.3.5.1 The Effect of MOOCs on Traditional Classroom Practice in China

Participants A, D, E, and H expressed a preference for traditional classroom teaching due to its ability to foster an interactive learning atmosphere. The interaction between teachers and students is important for learning, as it provides opportunities for reflection and feedback, which are often lacking in online courses. Conversely, Participants B, C, F, and G appreciated the flexibility offered by MOOCs, which allowed them to organise their study time according to personal schedules. This flexibility particularly benefits shy students who prefer independent learning. Furthermore, MOOCs also support access to high-quality teaching resources and can broaden students' educational horizons.

However, Participant C also noted that although she preferred learning via MOOCs, she acknowledged the necessity of traditional classroom learning, stating that it provides an environment conducive to focused study. This sentiment is supported by questionnaire data indicating that half of participants believe MOOC learning is less effective than traditional classroom learning, 9 of my 20 student participants express

that MOOCs could complement traditional teaching methods, while only 1 of 20 believes that MOOCs could entirely replace traditional courses in the future.

According to Zhang *et al.* (2019), MOOCs are still developing in China and are not yet officially integrated into all universities' curricula, their teaching methodologies cannot fully substitute for face-to-face instruction. The current lack of formal endorsement and selection of MOOC courses by government education departments means that traditional classroom teaching remains the standard. However, participants indicated that the introduction of MOOCs could enhance learners' autonomy and that the wealth of resources available through MOOCs may serve as a valuable supplement to traditional classroom instruction.

5.3.5.2 Teachers' Role in Promoting MOOCs

The semi-structured interviews revealed that a significant majority of participants chose MOOCs based on their teachers' recommendations. According to the questionnaires, approximately 15 of the 20 student participants were introduced to MOOCs by their teachers.

Participant A noted that the local government imposed a lockdown in her city, prompting her university to adopt MOOCs in response to the pandemic. Leading professors provided students with an overview of MOOCs, including explanations of the differences between MOOCs and other online courses they had previously experienced. Participant F shared a similar experience, emphasising how universities and teachers facilitated her introduction to MOOCs. Participants E, G, and H also indicated that their first attempt and engagement with MOOCs stemmed from their teachers' recommendations. This trend underscores the significant role educators play in the promotion and adoption of MOOCs, as highlighted by the fact that more than half of questionnaire respondents reported similar experiences. These findings align

with the work of Swai, Liu, and Wu (2024), who believe that MOOC platforms offer rich resources that teachers can utilise to enhance their teaching skills and strategies. Additionally, MOOCs provide a way for teachers to evaluate their teaching effectiveness and apply newfound knowledge in their classrooms. Swai, Liu, and Wu (2024) emphasise the opportunities for teachers to improve their pedagogical practices through MOOCs. The participants in this study equally acknowledged the critical importance of teachers' recommendations. Collectively, these insights affirm the essential role that teachers play in the advancement and integration of MOOCs into the learning process.

The strong reliance on teachers' recommendations for MOOC engagement highlights the pivotal role teachers play in guiding students toward effective learning resources. This suggests that teachers not only facilitate access to MOOCs but also serve as important sources of motivation and credibility for students, which may enhance their learning outcomes. In addition, the potential for MOOCs to serve as resources for teachers to improve their skills and teaching methods is a notable advantage. As the educational landscape continues to evolve, it would be beneficial for teachers to investigate how they can effectively integrate MOOC content into their curricula to optimise student learning.

5.3.5.3 The Future of MOOCs in China: Insights on Evaluation from Diverse Groups

The research indicates that participants believe the future of MOOCs in higher education in China is promising. Recognised as one of the largest education markets globally (Kim *et al.*, 2018), the Chinese government has actively promoted online education, including MOOCs, to expand educational opportunities and improve teaching quality (Dong, Cao and Li, 2020). A critical consideration regarding the future of MOOCs is the question of how and by whom they should be evaluated. Participants expressed varying opinions on this matter. Some argue that evaluations

should be conducted by users, as their insights are targeted and important. Alcarria, Bordel, and De Andra (2018) propose that three roles, students, reviewers, and professors—should be central to the evaluation process, as each group brings unique perspectives and experiences to the development of MOOCs.

In this study, eight participants were interviewed, all of whom have firsthand experience with MOOCs, regardless of whether their universities officially offered them. Their diverse experiences provide a solid foundation for evaluating MOOCs. Furthermore, Participants A, E, F, G, and H noted that their introduction to MOOCs came through their teachers, and 15 of the 20 participants who took part in the questionnaires indicated that they began learning via MOOCs at the recommendation of their teachers. This highlights the significant role teachers play in the MOOC ecosystem. Therefore, teachers' evaluations should be considered important in assessing MOOCs (Swai, Liu and Wu, 2024).

Currently, MOOCs are evaluated primarily as individual learning systems, with effectiveness measured by the system's overall success rather than individual participant outcomes. Given that MOOCs are designed to accommodate a variety of learners, users must have a voice in the evaluation process and feel encouraged to share their experiences. Participants reported that MOOCs effectively replaced traditional classroom teaching during the restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, allowing universities to continue operations while ensuring the safety of students, teachers and other staff in the universities. This adaptability marks early success for MOOCs. For teachers, the success of MOOCs has often been measured by whether students acquire knowledge and meet semester assessment requirements. If students can obtain the necessary certificates to graduate on time, the use of MOOCs will be deemed successful. Consequently, evaluations of MOOCs need to incorporate the perspectives of all groups involved in the learning process. This aligns with the

views of participants and supports the arguments presented by Alcarria, Bordel, and De Andra (2018).

5.4 Findings from the Additional Interviews Concentrating on Students' Understanding of MOOCs Accessibility during the COVID-19 Pandemic

I have focused on this point based on the fact that, now, two and a half years after the COVID-19 pandemic, students are able to reflect better on how they engaged with MOOCs at the time and can more easily look back. I outlined in the methodology chapter how and why I intended to collect further information on the specifics of MOOCs and online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. I returned to four of my original interviewees and specifically inquired about their experiences in this context. The new data was organised into two main sections: how participants engaged during the COVID-19 pandemic and what they felt about their experiences, I also questioned them on other related information, for example, information related to completion rate and compulsory versus optional courses.

The move to online learning was not unique to China but part of a global trend in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. However, in the context of Chinese universities, where traditional face-to-face learning was, for a long time, the dominant mode of delivery, the change to MOOCs and other online platforms posed unique challenges. Participants' reflections offer valuable data as to how students adapted to new learning formats, the effectiveness of MOOCs and other online platforms, and the evolving role of technology in higher education. The following sections will further explore these themes based on the interview data.

5.4.1 The Delivery of MOOCs during the COVID-19 Pandemic

The follow-up interviews discussed here mainly focused on how MOOCs developed during the COVID-19 pandemic. When the COVID-19 pandemic happened in China, universities took immediate action to make sure all the courses were moved online as efficiently as possible. Participant F and Participant G discuss that situation as follows:

Participant F noted:

“In response to COVID-19, my university took several immediate measures to ensure the safety and well-being of students and staff. This included transitioning to online learning, implementing remote work arrangements for lectures and staff, and enhancing communication channels to keep the university community informed about developments related to the pandemic.”

Participant G added:

“I still remember when the pandemic first started, schools and universities were declared closed, the whole city was deserted. The university then made many announcements one after another, including the change to online learning. For a while, we studied at home, then it resumed, and then the university was closed again, and we were quarantined in the accommodation for a while. Everyone took online classes.”

Participants noted that as the first country to confront the COVID-19 pandemic, China took immediate action to ensure public safety and the continuity of education. According to the participants, universities rapidly transitioned their teaching programmes online and employed various online teaching methods. This aligns with Gu and Li's (2022) research, which emphasises that the primary consideration for continuing education during the pandemic was the accessibility and availability of

high-quality online learning resources, factors that significantly influenced learners' behaviours. To fulfil this need, a range of policies and measures were implemented to enhance the availability of these resources. Universities A and B, located in different regions of China, faced varying local government restrictions, leading to distinct online learning methods and styles. As Participant F from University A noted:

“During COVID-19, online learning at my university encompassed a variety of formats, including live lectures, pre-recorded video lectures, online discussions, and assignments. Moreover, MOOCs were offered as supplementary resources to complement traditional course materials. My university offered a wide range of MOOCs covering diverse subjects and disciplines, including but not limited to humanities, social sciences, business, and language learning.”

Participant H from University B, however, noted:

“Different teachers use different teaching apps for their lessons, and most of the courses are live courses. Some teachers asked us to open the camera, some did not, but most asked that. They checked the students' names, shared the screen, and then the teachers showed the courseware and gave a lecture. We used Nail, Tencent meeting and some others from the official system. These courses do not include MOOCs, our university did not deliver MOOCs officially.”

The participants' data clearly indicate that Universities A and B delivered different types of online courses during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Wang (2020), online platforms such as DingTalk, Rain Classroom, Xuedutong, and Tencent Conference experienced dramatic growth during this period. The participants' responses reveal that, regardless of whether they delivered MOOCs, Chinese universities took immediate and effective actions to address the challenges posed by the pandemic. These actions not only allowed universities to adapt to the pandemic

but also provided students with opportunities to develop their online learning skills and make significant progress.

5.4.2 Learner Experiences of MOOCs during COVID-19 Pandemic

In these follow-up interviews, I aimed to collect data on learners' experiences with MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic to further investigate and explore the development of MOOCs during this specific period. Participants shared their memories of study during the COVID-19 pandemic and their responses were rich and interesting.

As Participant F from University A, noted:

“My memories of MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic are generally positive. But I think I still prefer face-to-face teaching methods. MOOCs provided a valuable opportunity for me to continue learning and stay engaged with my studies despite the challenges posed by the pandemic. While the transition to online learning was initially challenging, MOOCs offered a flexible and accessible way for me to access educational resources and continue my academics.”

Participant E from the same university added:

“I did not need to get up early or do makeup. Just stay at home, in my lovely room. My experiences are interesting but don't laugh at me. I sometimes can't answer questions so when the teacher asks me questions, I pretend to have Internet problems and keep my voice down.”

One significant issue with online learning is that academics and teachers had to navigate the challenges it presented. For example, one participant pretended to

experience internet problems to avoid answering questions. Niemi (2021) believes that the environment of online courses is different from traditional classroom settings, where students and teachers occupy the same physical space. This physical separation makes it difficult for teachers to accurately assess and observe students' actual performance. For example, some students may become disengaged during online classes, opting to play games or even sleep. In this case, although the teachers may be able to see a student's profile picture on the screen, it is impossible to discern whether the student is attentively listening or completing other assignments. This lack of visibility constitutes a challenge for online learning.

In University B, Participants G and H also shared positive memorable experiences via MOOC during the COVID-19 pandemic. Just as Participant H noted:

“Yes, my memories are pretty good. MOOCs are useful and targeted. I like it very much. Easy access and flexibility.”

And Participant G:

“Now I have become accustomed to a combination of online and offline learning, as I'm sure many people who went through the pandemic did, and although it has gone, the habit has been developed. As far as learning is concerned, online classes have really evolved too fast. Before the pandemic, it was always face-to-face lessons. Suddenly the pandemic happened, and the way of learning changed.”

All participants described how traditional classroom teaching methods changed during the pandemic and expressed positive attitudes toward MOOCs. They acknowledged the key advantages of MOOCs, particularly their flexibility and accessibility. Whether or not universities officially implemented MOOCs, all traditional classes were shifted online, and both teachers and students frequently

utilised MOOCs. This aligns with Duan's (2021) research, which highlights the Chinese government recognised the importance of online education during the COVID-19 pandemic and actively supported the development of MOOC platforms.

Similarly, Yang, Shen, and Xu (2022) observed that some universities combined traditional classroom teaching with online components, creating flexible and accessible courses for students. This blended learning approach was an effective way to manage the sudden disruption caused by the pandemic and ensured that all teaching was delivered in order. The rapid development of MOOCs during this period shows their potential as a key educational tool in China's higher education system. The following sections explore the details of learner engagement with MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic, shedding light on the evolving role of online education in China.

5.4.2.1 Learner Interactions via MOOCs

Based on the data above, participants from both universities shared memorable experiences of MOOC learning. They provided detailed responses, particularly regarding their interactions with other learners. These interactions highlighted the diverse range of perspectives and learning approaches encountered through MOOCs, which helped enrich their overall educational experience. Moreover, participants reflected on how these peer interactions influenced their motivation and engagement, related to the potential of MOOCs in the development of collaboration. Participant F from University A said:

“Sometimes I interact with other students in MOOCs, and sometimes not. Normally through discussion, we ask questions, share insights, and engage in discussions related to the course content.”

This university had moved some of its compulsory courses online, so she gave more detailed information about her interactions with her classmates. As she added:

“I cannot see other students on the screen. Communications typically happen through written text in discussion forums or through messaging features provided by the platform. While we couldn't talk face-to-face, we could still engage in meaningful discussions and exchange ideas through written communication.”

It is noteworthy that some students chose not to turn their cameras on during online classes, which limited face-to-face interaction. While this may have reduced the sense of engagement typically present in a traditional classroom, the participant still found the experience enjoyable. This suggests that, despite the lack of visual cues and direct interaction, MOOCs can provide a flexible and comfortable learning environment that some students appreciate, particularly those who might prefer less pressure in social interactions. However, the absence of visual engagement could also affect the depth of peer-to-peer interaction. Participant E, from the same university, added that:

“I have some interaction with other students, but not much. I'm quite shy, I don't really like to be the one answering questions or working on some tasks as a group representative. MOOCs, in this aspect, were very friendly to me. I can study and think quietly without the pressure of being asked questions, which allows me to concentrate more and makes it easier to take notes.”

Both participants stated that they made full use of online learning and adapted to find personalised methods to enhance their learning experience. They expressed enjoyment in this new mode of participation and even considered it a more effective way to learn. This aligns with the work of Chengjie (2015), who found that MOOCs allow learners to access course materials, lectures, and assignments via online platforms, providing

flexibility for students to learn at their own pace. Similarly, at University B, participants shared similar sentiments. As Participant G noted:

“We took the classes together, with no face-to-face interaction or discussion with other participants, and I did not need to turn on the camera, we only had some typed exchanges, when learned some new content, we could also see other people's comments, as well as comments left by students in previous classes, which helped absorb ideas and synthesise analyses. I like this way of learning because I can get a lot of knowledge and analysis content. Some other people's comments will help me have a lot of inspiration, there will be a kind of dawning sense of sudden understanding.”

According to the data, most participants did not engage in extensive interactions during MOOCs. However, they participated in various forms of learning that met their needs. For example, Participant F and his group members engaged by typing in discussion forums, while Participant G, who did not use the camera, actively used the comment section. Despite limited interaction, the participants expressed satisfaction with this learning approach.

These findings align with the flexibility and adaptability of MOOCs as discussed in the Literature Review. Qi, Zhang and Zhang (2020) suggest that the higher the level of teacher involvement in MOOCs, the greater the activity and satisfaction of learners. Even though participation in discussion sessions was low, other aspects of course design and implementation were effective enough to ensure learner satisfaction. The flexibility of MOOCs plays an important role in such satisfaction, as they offer open access and a variety of courses, catering to the personalised needs of different students. This flexibility allows learners to study at their own pace and according to their individual schedules, as highlighted by the four participants.

5.4.2.2 Learner Preferences of MOOCs and Traditional Classroom Teaching

This section explores learner preferences for MOOCs versus traditional classroom teaching, drawing on insightful responses from participants during the interviews. Their reflections showed the perceived advantages and limitations of both learning formats, highlighting factors such as flexibility, interaction, and personal learning styles. As Participant F said:

“I found a combination of live lectures and MOOCs to be the most effective online learning method for me during the pandemic. Live lectures provided real-time interaction with professors and classmates, fostering a sense of connection and engagement. Meanwhile, MOOCs offered flexibility and additional resources to supplement my learning, allowing me to explore topics of interest in greater depth at my own pace.”

Participant E added:

“It was pretty good and I felt more relaxed than studying in the classroom. We usually had video lectures and reading materials and I'd type and communicate with my classmates or leave comments on the discussion boards to discuss some points after the class, I didn't have to turn on the camera or expose my little learning environment, It's not like a classroom.”

Participant E highlighted the individual learning environment MOOCs offer, allowing her to study without interacting with others. Her experience of learning about Western Civilisations independently, without the involvement of teachers or academics, made her feel more relaxed. This aligns with the research of Agonacs *et al.* (2020), who emphasise that MOOCs enable learners to create their own personal learning atmospheres, fostering a sense of autonomy. Participant E also talked about another aspect as:

“I like MOOCs because most of them are recorded courses that I can always go back and review what I didn't understand. I can watch the video over and over again to make sure that I understand and remember the key points correctly while I'm working on my homework.”

The importance of recorded courses for students, particularly the ability to revisit content, aligns with Deng and Gao's (2023) findings that many MOOCs are delivered in English, and the option to revisit recordings allows students to choose how frequently they review material. This flexibility can enhance both enthusiasm and initiative in learning, as students can watch videos repeatedly and focus on specific areas to achieve optimal learning outcomes. For those learners whose first language is not English, who participate in MOOCs delivered in the English language, it is especially beneficial, as repeated viewings help increase comprehension. Participant E also highlights the value of recorded courses, emphasising their role in reviewing classroom content and enabling understanding. Students can enhance their memories by repeatedly watching videos, especially during exam preparation. Similarly, Li (2022) notes that Western students appreciate recorded lectures, as they offer the flexibility to revisit material at their own pace, further enhancing the learning experience. Thus, recorded courses serve as a valuable tool for both improving comprehension and supporting flexible, autonomous learning.

Participants at University B also shared their perspectives on their preferences regarding the different types of learning they encountered. Their responses reflected a variety of experiences and attitudes toward both traditional classroom learning and online learning through MOOCs, providing valuable insights into how each format met their educational needs during the pandemic. Participant G said:

“Now I have become accustomed to a combination of online and offline learning, as I'm sure many people who went through the pandemic did, and although it has gone, the

habit has been developed. As for the courses, I like pre-recorded courses because some content was not used for once. Pre-recorded courses were easy to find and review.”

And Participant H added:

“I liked the recorded courses because I was not nervous. when we stayed at the accommodation, our course discussions were done in groups of two. I can be a bit more conscious when I have someone to supervise me and study with me in the recorded courses.”

The data suggests that all four participants recognised the potential for flexibility of learning through MOOCs and enjoyed MOOC learning: they also like combining both online and offline learning. This flexibility accommodates various learning styles and personal preferences. For example, Participant E noted that although she prefers not to attend class without makeup, she is still a conscientious learner. She also expressed discomfort with answering questions in front of peers and teachers, a concern linked to the concept of "face culture" prevalent among Chinese students. Shan (2020) noted that Chinese students are often perceived as passive learners, but it may be the fear of 'losing face' that stops them from speaking or interacting in public. Traditional classroom environments, therefore, can be stressful for such students. In contrast, MOOCs can create a more relaxed learning experience, allowing students to engage with course content privately from the comfort of their own space. This highlights how MOOCs offer flexible learning options that cater to individual needs and reduce the pressure associated with public engagement.

5.4.2.3 MOOCs and Learners' Time Management

This section explores the time management skills required for engaging in MOOCs and how participants balance these skills to enhance their online learning experiences.

Participants highlighted the necessity of effective time management when navigating the demands of MOOCs alongside their other responsibilities. They discussed strategies for setting schedules and allocating specific time slots for study to ensure they could fully engage with the course material. This emphasis on self-discipline and the importance of developing strong time management skills in order to maximize the benefits of online learning highlighted that, by effectively managing their time, participants reported improved engagement and a more rewarding learning experience in the context of MOOCs. As Participant F noted:

“Engaging in MOOCs demands strong time management skills. Balancing coursework, assignments, and extracurricular activities with MOOCs required careful planning and prioritization. Setting specific study schedules, breaking tasks into manageable chunks, and minimising distractions helped me stay on track and make the most of my MOOC experiences.”

This participant recognised the significance of time management in relation to MOOC studies, and she added:

“My time management skills significantly improved through engaging in MOOCs and other online learning. The necessity to juggle multiple tasks and deadlines honed my ability to organise my time effectively and remain focused on my academic goals. Maintaining study discipline without regular classroom observation was a challenge initially. However, setting personal goals, creating a dedicated study environment, and adhering to a structured study routine helped me stay disciplined. Regular self-assessment, seeking feedback from peers or online forums, and leveraging online resources for support were also instrumental in staying on track.”

In the same university, Participant E had different learning habits, and she said:

“This time is flexible for me. Because I can watch MOOCs at any time. I think in general I got into the habit of studying on my own. During the MOOC study, small pieces of time were added together and utilised during online classes. But without time requirements, I often procrastinated. I am not a self-disciplined person, so I often slacked off if there were no teachers to watch over me or if there were no specified deadline requirements. I always procrastinate until the last minute. But finally, it will be done and I can study on my own, but not much haha.”

These two participants were from the university that officially delivered MOOCs, requiring them to complete certain courses as part of their academic programme. However, when discussing time management, they emphasised different aspects. Participant F shared how his time management skills developed and improved, and summarised detailed time management skills. In contrast, Participant E highlighted the potential for flexibility of MOOCs, noting that this format allowed her to study at any time that suited her schedule.

Martin, Stamper and Flowers (2020) emphasise the importance of time management skills in online learning environments. Due to the lack of face-to-face supervision and interaction, students often require greater self-motivation and self-discipline to sustain their learning progress and maintain the quality of their studies. The ability to effectively manage one's time becomes particularly important in this context, as it not only influences the efficiency of learning but also has a direct impact on students' overall performance and final outcomes.

In University B, participants also gave interesting responses. Participant G noted:

“I think MOOCs require a high level of time management skills as it often involves self-directed learning without the structure of a traditional classroom environment. From my experience, I think it's important to set clear goals for what you hope to

achieve at the beginning. Then, creating a study schedule that arranges specific times for MOOC study, can help to establish a routine to avoid procrastination. You know the flexibility of MOOCs may lead to procrastination. Asking yourself to actively participate in MOOCs, such as contributing to discussion forums, working on group projects, or seeking help from peers or instructors, can also enhance learning.”

And Participant H said:

“Online courses really require time management skills, which I did not do very well. I always procrastinate because of the flexibility of time and the lack of teacher supervision and graduation restrictions. I think I should improve my time management skills and efficiency, since I can't be very disciplined, I should improve my efficiency and learn the content while I'm learning it.”

In the second university, participants emphasised two major aspects of MOOCs: flexibility and time management skills. These discussions highlight the inherent advantages of MOOC platforms, particularly their ability to offer learners greater control over their study schedules. The findings align with the research of Huang (2020), who argues that MOOCs are more open and flexible compared to traditional classroom teaching. However, this flexibility also presents unique challenges, such as the need for effective time management.

Lin, Lin, and Hung (2015) note that online learning not only imparts knowledge but also cultivates important time management skills in students. These skills are essential for achieving a balance between work and study, as well as for maintaining efficiency in various aspects of life. In this context, setting clear learning goals and creating structured study plans can help students stay on track. Establishing a shared agenda between students and teachers fosters better communication and a sense of

responsibility, which is particularly important in online learning environments where face-to-face supervision is absent.

One participant, Participant G, stressed the necessity of time management in MOOCs, stating: "MOOCs require a high level of time management skills since they often involve self-directed learning without the structure of a traditional classroom environment." This reflects the need for students to develop self-discipline and autonomy to maximize their learning outcomes. As Participant H also noted, the flexibility of MOOCs can sometimes lead to procrastination due to the lack of direct teacher supervision, highlighting the importance of personal responsibility in managing one's learning. The responses from the second university further illustrate that while the flexibility of MOOCs is an advantage, it also requires learners to develop time management strategies to avoid procrastination. The ability to learn at one's own pace is a double-edged sword: it provides freedom, but also necessitates a high degree of self-regulation.

In summary, while MOOCs offer an open and flexible learning environment, they also demand a significant investment in time management from students. Those who are able to set clear objectives, establish routines, and manage their time effectively are more likely to succeed in these courses. This finding aligns with the literature and suggests that the development of strong time management skills is an essential component of successful online learning, particularly in the context of MOOCs, and highlights the importance of dealing with the relationship between autonomy and engagement.

5.4.3 Challenges of Using MOOCs in China during the COVID-19 Pandemic

During the interviews, participants also discussed the challenges they faced while engaging with MOOCs. These challenges varied widely, reflecting their individual experiences and contexts. As Participant G noted:

“MOOCs are excellent resources but I expect my university to design our own MOOCs, which suit us better.”

While that is an understandable comment from Participant G, who is more used to her own university's teaching style, one of the advantages of MOOCs is that they give learners access to experts across the world, who are not based in their universities. Lv (2020) argues that transitioning from traditional teaching methods to externally delivered MOOCs may not be the most effective approach for enhancing students' online learning experiences. To develop high-quality online courses, teachers must adapt their familiar teaching methods and reconstruct their courses to meet the specific requirements of online learning. This necessitates a thorough understanding of the characteristics of online learning environments, which include networked learning contexts, the absence of face-to-face interaction, and increased student independence.

These features compel teachers to focus not only on effectively conveying knowledge but also on fostering students' self-learning ability and active participation in course design. By recognising and addressing these unique aspects of online education, teachers can create more engaging and effective learning experiences for their students.

As Participant F said:

“I found interacting with other students in MOOCs to be an enjoyable and enriching experience. It provided an opportunity to learn from peers, gain different perspectives and collaborate on assignments or projects. I enjoyed collaborating because it allowed me to benefit from the diverse knowledge and experiences of my peers. It made the learning process more dynamic and interactive. However, collaboration could sometimes be challenging if there were communication barriers or if group members didn't contribute equally.”

This aligns with Lee's (2006) research which notes that external conditions, such as the attitudes and behaviours of peers, significantly influence students' learning behaviours. It highlights the challenge that, in the absence of teachers' supervision, learners must cultivate greater autonomy and enhance their self-awareness regarding effective learning strategies. This observation is consistent with Rosell-Aguilar's (2018) theory that learners engaged in MOOCs and other online learning methods need to be highly autonomous and self-disciplined.

This finding demonstrates the relevance of the theoretical framework established by Mackness, Mak, and William (2010), which posits that it is essential for learners to recognise that the process of learning is more significant than the courses themselves. Furthermore, Nosratinia and Deris (2015) emphasise that learners should shift their focus from "teaching" to "learning," necessitating an understanding of how to acquire knowledge through self-initiated efforts. This shift is important for developing effective learning habits that enhance educational outcomes in online environments.

5.5 Summary

In this chapter, data from semi-structured interviews with participants from two target universities have been collected, analysed, and summarised. I compared data from semi-structured interviews conducted at two different times: one during the COVID-19 pandemic and another one and a half years later. Additionally, follow-up interviews focused on participants' experiences during the pandemic, aiming to explore how learners' attitudes and perceptions of MOOCs had evolved.

At each university, one participant expressed a preference for MOOCs, while another preferred traditional classroom teaching. Notably, more participants indicated a preference for MOOCs during the semi-structured interviews conducted after the COVID-19 pandemic, providing in-depth information on their experiences, performance, and interactions with peers in MOOCs. Their responses were rich and insightful.

The data analysis reveals a consensus among students and teachers regarding the significance of MOOCs as an immediate reaction to the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as agreement on the benefits of MOOC study. Participants shared valuable insights regarding their learning experiences, including how MOOCs developed during the pandemic, their reasons for choosing MOOCs, factors influencing their learning behaviours, challenges faced within MOOC environments, and their perspectives on the future of MOOCs. The findings will serve as a foundation for the conclusions drawn in the next chapter.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

This chapter concludes the thesis, which investigates students' engagement with MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) in higher education in China. It presents a critical evaluation of the research findings, summarises key insights, and reflects on the overall study.

Based on a mixed-method analysis of student engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education, the research demonstrates that MOOCs have played an important role during the COVID-19 pandemic by ensuring the continuity of education. The findings highlight that learner motivation and students' awareness of their learning processes are key factors in the design and delivery of effective MOOCs. These factors should be carefully considered by universities, institutions and MOOC companies when planning course offerings to maximise student engagement and learning outcomes. The analysis of participant responses from two target universities indicates that the development and adoption of MOOCs have accelerated, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, leading to a marked increase in students' autonomous learning behaviours. This change towards teaching to learning suggests that students are becoming more self-directed. They pay more attention to the management of their own learning experiences over external factors that may have previously shaped their educational priorities.

Moreover, the study emphasises the growing importance students place on the quality of their learning processes rather than traditional markers of educational success, such as good grades or the prestige of the institutions. This finding points to a significant development in how students approach learning in a digital age, particularly within the context of Chinese higher education, where MOOCs offer flexibility and accessibility. Universities, therefore, must adapt their strategies not

only to enhance student motivation but also to foster environments that promote independent learning and critical thinking.

6.2 Chapter Summaries

In this thesis, Chapter 1 introduced the study by outlining its rationale, background, and significance. It also set out the research questions and the purpose of the study.

Chapter 2 provided a comprehensive review of the study's context, starting with the definition of MOOCs and their background, including early development and current growth. Key learning theories supporting MOOCs were explored, along with their characteristics and associated learning models. The chapter also addressed the appeal of MOOCs to Chinese university learners, focusing on certification and educational equity. Factors influencing MOOC completion rates were analysed, and MOOCs were compared with other online formats like MALL (Mobile-Assisted Language Learning), SPOCs (Small Private Online Courses), and other courses. The discussion then shifted to the Chinese context, examining the history and policies of online education in China, the role of MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic, and the shift back to face-to-face learning. Challenges and opportunities for MOOCs and factors influencing student engagement were considered, followed by an analysis of MOOCs' transformative potential, particularly in teaching methods, educational democratisation, and personalised learning experiences. The gaps in the literature identified in this chapter directly informed the development of the research questions. These questions addressed key areas such as MOOCs and learner engagement, autonomy in learning, and the development of MOOCs in China, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. This review has provided the necessary theoretical and empirical foundations to guide the research effectively.

Chapter 3 examined the theoretical framework that underpinned the study and guided the development of the research methodology. The chapter introduced the methodology in detail, including the use of questionnaires and semi-structured interviews to collect data as above. It also discussed the research paradigm, epistemological and ontological perspectives, and the study's design, alongside ethical considerations.

Chapters 4 and 5 presented and analysed the key findings, drawing from participant responses to the questionnaires (Appendices J), as well as transcripts from semi-structured interviews (Appendices D-I). The analysis in Chapter 4 focused on student and teacher experiences with MOOCs, exploring participants' experiences and understanding of MOOC learning, such as how participants were introduced to MOOCs, their course selection criteria, factors affecting participation, and comparisons with traditional classroom learning. Chapter 5 analysed the interview data, with particular emphasis on the use of MOOCs during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. It highlighted themes such as the impact of MOOCs on traditional teaching practices, teachers' roles in marketing and promoting, factors that influence participation, the development of autonomous learning and prospects for MOOCs in China. Each chapter concluded with a summary of key insights drawn from the data analysis. Through this data analysis, the study addressed all of the research questions, as discussed in the following sections.

6.3 Findings from the research

This study analysed learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education and was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the potential challenges and benefits to Chinese students in relation to MOOC learning, specifically with regarding to enhancing motivation, developing engagement and building autonomy?

2. In what ways have MOOCs affected aspects of teaching and learning such as traditional classroom practices and learner engagement?
3. What are the specific factors, in relation to student motivation and the development of autonomous learning, that might affect learners' engagement with their learning via MOOCs? In what ways are learners affected by this new method of learning?
4. What is the possible future of MOOCs? In what ways can MOOCs contribute to the development of stronger learner engagement in Higher Education in China in future?
5. How and in what ways did MOOCs develop a different education practice and delivery during the COVID-19 pandemic to support students' individual motivation, and ultimately engagement in their learning?

6.3.1 Answering RQ1- What are the potential challenges and benefits to Chinese students in relation to MOOC learning, specifically with regarding to enhancing motivation, developing engagement and building autonomy?

This research question was addressed through participant responses which can be found in Appendix D, E, F and G.

6.3.1.1 Potential Challenges to Chinese Students in Relation to MOOC Learning

By analysing data from participants at two Chinese universities, the study revealed that most students had experience with MOOCs, both through their university's

official platforms and external online platforms. One of the most prominent issues is related to IT infrastructure, specifically inconsistent Internet connectivity. While China has high Internet penetration (Lin *et al.*, 2017), students accessing MOOCs hosted on platforms outside China often experience unstable connections. When Chinese students need access to Internet connections outside China, for example, to participate in online MOOC platforms delivered from other countries, a stable Internet connection is unsuccessful at times. Another challenge is that the teaching styles in some of the MOOCs are different to those that students have been used to in class and having to rely on technology makes some students tired when watching the screen for a long time.

Another significant challenge highlighted by participants is language. Lecturers often use distinct teaching styles in MOOCs, particularly those from foreign universities who teach in their native languages. Although some students are proficient in English, a large proportion struggle with the language (Yahaya, Yahaya and Ismail, 2011). This linguistic gap can make it difficult for students to adjust to the language and terminologies used by foreign teachers. Therefore, students have to adjust to the particular accents of their different online teachers and also to some of the languages they use.

The teaching methods employed in some MOOCs further complicate student engagement. Some MOOCs use pre-recorded classes, limiting opportunities for interaction and discussion. Lecturers may also fail to adjust their teaching methods for online delivery, continuing to use strategies from traditional in-person classes without adapting based on student feedback. In this circumstance, universities and lecturers have to adapt their teaching methods and pedagogy to better suit the online learning environment of MOOCs, otherwise, it could lead to students not engaging as expected. Therefore, adapting to new teaching styles is also a major challenge for many Chinese

students participating in MOOCs. In contrast to the teacher-centred methods commonly used in Chinese education, MOOCs emphasise learner autonomy and active participation. For example, MOOCs provide a flexible and self-paced learning environment. Learners have the freedom to control their own studies, choosing when and how much content to engage with. The ability to access course materials from any location at any time further supports learner autonomy, allowing students to structure their learning around other commitments. This change can be difficult for students who are not familiar with taking the initiative in their learning or managing their time independently because they are used to teacher-led learning. Some interactive components in MOOCs, such as quizzes, assignments, and discussion forums, require students to be actively involved, which may be challenging for those used to a more passive learning style.

In addition to these challenges, students often face difficulties in selecting MOOCs. With the large number of courses available, students often struggle to choose MOOCs that best match their learning needs. Many participants noted a lack of time and experience in choosing these courses. This aligns with Gao's (2019) research, which highlights that MOOC education is guided and supported by the key principles of constructivist learning theory and humanistic learning theory which require a higher level of autonomy and decision-making from students, as they are required to choose courses that align with their individual learning needs and goals. However, many lack the necessary guidance and self-awareness to choose courses effectively. Chinese students find this challenging due to the fact that the educational system in China focuses on guided learning and structured paths and indeed has, pre-COVID-19 pandemic, always been teacher-led. Faced with the variety of options for MOOCs, students may struggle to select the most appropriate courses, leading on occasion, to poor choices or difficulty staying focused on their academic objectives. This produced one of the key findings: students find it difficult to stay involved in MOOCs because they are so used to face-to-face teacher-centred learning.

Some participants expressed a desire for their universities to develop and launch their own MOOCs. Universities without MOOCs may miss opportunities to enhance their global reputation. With MOOCs delivered globally, high-quality MOOCs can attract international students and encourage curriculum improvements within Chinese universities. However, developing MOOCs requires significant time and resources, and many Chinese universities may struggle to meet both domestic and international standards.

Another challenge is whether teachers can persuade students to engage with MOOCs from other universities that not simply complement or enhance their own teaching content but benefit students' learning engagement, or whether they can select the most suitable MOOCs that best support students' face-to-face learning in the classroom for their students. This accords with the research of Haumin and Madhusudhan (2019) that MOOCs can build a community for students, lecturers, professors, and other users. Lecturers play an important role in promoting MOOC engagement. Haumin and Madhusudhan (2019) found a clear relationship between MOOCs and people involved in the creation and delivery of MOOCs, but the participants of this research did not discuss this in depth because this study developed from the COVID-19 pandemic and the government's actions to support MOOC delivery during that time. The participants for this research gave detailed information on their experiences of MOOCs from their teachers' recommendation and this resulted in teachers playing a key role in the MOOCs' marketing and promotion.

Finally, a major challenge in MOOC participation is the issue of low self-motivation among learners. Unlike traditional classrooms, MOOCs offer less structure and limited tutor support, making it easy for students to lose focus. This finding aligns with Milligan and Littlejohn's (2017) research that MOOCs offer flexibility but require students to be more self-directed and motivated than in traditional face-to-face

learning environments. Moreover, the limited interaction and engagement that some MOOCs provide may also challenge learner engagement. In some Chinese classrooms, interaction between students and teachers and peer collaboration are important sections of the class, but not everywhere. In contrast, some MOOCs lack interaction or have limited opportunities for interaction and can leave students feeling disconnected from both their peers and instructors, reducing their overall engagement with the course. Although Chinese education is traditionally teacher-centred, there is still room for structured interaction in the classrooms. Therefore, the lack of structured interaction in some MOOCs makes it difficult for learners to engage. Additionally, the absence of immediate or personalised feedback in MOOCs can further contribute to feelings of isolation for learners, making it difficult for students to stay engaged and committed.

In summary, while MOOCs provide universities with opportunities to enhance teaching resources and students with more flexible learning environments, nonetheless, several challenges exist. These include technological issues, language barriers, where the language presenter may be difficult to understand, teaching methods which may be different for participants to engage with, challenges in course selection, and the need for increased self-motivation. Chinese universities face additional challenges in developing high-quality MOOCs and promoting their use among students. Addressing these challenges is important for maximising the potential benefits of MOOCs in Chinese higher education.

6.3.1.2 Benefits to Chinese Students in Relation to MOOC Learning

Despite these challenges, MOOCs offer several significant benefits to Chinese students, particularly in fostering motivation for some students and supporting engagement and learner autonomy. One of the most notable advantages is the flexibility and accessibility that MOOCs provide. The ability to learn at one's own pace and access course content anytime and anywhere can be highly motivating for

students, allowing them to balance their education and daily lives. For example, some of my participants talked about not bothering to get up to do online learning. This flexibility supports the development of autonomy, as students are encouraged to take control of their learning process, making decisions about what, when, and how they learn. The research questions are effectively answered by my participants.

In addition, the variety of courses available through MOOC platforms can enhance student engagement. MOOCs provide access to a wide range of subjects that may not be available in traditional university settings, allowing students to explore the content that truly interests them. This variety can increase learner engagement by enabling students to pursue subjects that align with their personal and career goals. Furthermore, the self-paced nature of MOOCs can keep students engaged, as they are not constrained by a rigid schedule and can revisit challenging concepts as needed, fostering a more autonomous approach to learning.

Exposing the learners to global perspectives is another significant benefit of MOOCs. Many MOOCs are developed by universities and educators from around the world, offering students exposure to diverse perspectives and ideas. This global opportunity for integration can be highly motivating and inspiring, as it allows students to connect and collaborate with peers from different cultural backgrounds. Engaging with global content and discussions can enhance students' critical thinking and autonomous learning, as students can reflect on and incorporate diverse viewpoints into their own understanding.

Finally, the free or low cost of MOOCs makes them an attractive option for many students, particularly those who might be unable to afford higher education fees. The reduced financial barriers can boost motivation, as students are more likely to explore various subjects without the pressure of financial constraints. This situation, in turn, can lead to greater engagement and a willingness to experiment with different

learning methods, promoting a more self-directed and autonomous approach to education.

In summary, while MOOCs present certain challenges for Chinese students, such as a lack of in-person interaction, cultural and language barriers, and technological issues, they can also offer substantial benefits. The flexibility, opportunities to access different courses and global perspectives, and low cost of MOOCs can enhance motivation, engagement, and autonomy, making them a valuable component of the educational landscape in China. Understanding these challenges and benefits is central to optimising the effectiveness of MOOCs in supporting Chinese students' learning experiences.

6.3.2 Answering RQ2- In what ways have MOOCs affected aspects of teaching and learning such as traditional classroom practices and learner engagement?

MOOCs have significantly affected teaching and learning in Chinese universities, for example, they have impacted traditional classroom practices and learner engagement. The integration of MOOCs with traditional classroom teaching is expected to shape the future of education in China. This question was answered by participants in the interviews (see Appendices D, E, F, and G).

6.3.2.1 MOOCs and Traditional Classroom Practices

MOOCs have significantly influenced traditional teaching practices and learner engagement by introducing flexibility, diversity, and a student-centred approach to learning and teaching in the Chinese context. In traditional classrooms, MOOCs have facilitated the development of blended learning models, where the use of online learning materials can complement face-to-face interactions. This can also help

students to prepare for or review courses independently, enabling teachers to focus classroom time more on interactive and collaborative activities. This change can help to create a more active and engaging learning environment (Li, 2022).

The integration of MOOCs into traditional classrooms can also lead to positive learning experiences. By delivering some of the learning content online, teachers and students would be able to make full use of classroom time for more interactive activities, such as debates, performances, mock interviews and collaborative projects. This change from a teacher-centred model to a more student-centred approach can keep students more engaged, as they can be actively involved in the learning process rather than passively receiving knowledge and taking notes.

In addition, the rich resources available through MOOCs have expanded the opportunity for teachers to be engaged with different teaching tools. They can integrate high-quality videos and interactive modules into their traditional courses, thus enriching the learning environment. This incorporation of diverse materials can stimulate student interest and motivation, as they are exposed to different teaching styles and viewpoints that may not be available in a conventional classroom setting. Participants, therefore, believe that it is beneficial to combine MOOCs and traditional classroom teaching methods to make learning more interesting and diverse, which indicates that the phenomenon of combining traditional learning with digital learning has emerged in China.

However, traditional classroom-based teaching has distinct advantages and according to participants, remains irreplaceable. Some subjects, such as painting, sculpting, and scientific fields like chemistry, require hands-on practice and face-to-face interaction, making them unsuitable for purely online instruction, which highlights some learners'

preference for in-person teaching, demonstrating that MOOCs are best used as a supplement rather than a replacement. Garcia-Penalvo, Fidalgo-Blanco and Sein-Echaluce (2018) agree that if an online subject is designed for training, experimental and concrete objectives, it would not be necessary or practical to offer MOOCs in that area.

In summary, the introduction of MOOCs has brought significant changes in traditional teaching methods and classroom practices in Chinese universities. While traditional education remains necessary in certain disciplines, the combination of MOOCs with classroom learning offers students greater flexibility and access to diverse resources and enriches their educational experience.

6.3.2.2 MOOCs and Learner Engagement

From the learner's perspective, MOOCs can enhance learning engagement and motivation by offering flexible and personalised learning experiences. The flexible feature of MOOCs allows students to participate in the courses and select learning materials at their own pace. This learning autonomy can increase an individual sense of responsibility throughout the student's educational experience, which can highly motivate them. Moreover, MOOCs allow students to explore subjects and learning content that they are truly interested in. This opportunity to pursue personal academic interests can increase intrinsic motivation, as students can engage with content that aligns with their passions and career expectations.

Through MOOC study, students develop a stronger awareness of autonomous learning, which can positively influence their classroom engagement (Yuan and Powell, 2013). For example, some participants noted that they watch lectures and materials online by themselves as preparation before class or for review afterwards,

allowing teachers to focus more on student engagement and collaboration during in-person sessions. MOOCs have also provided students with access to education and resources outside their universities, enabling them to participate in courses offered by top institutions worldwide. Participants' data shows that MOOCs can enhance learner engagement and learning autonomy by offering diverse and personalised learning experiences and encouraging active participation.

Another motivational benefit of MOOCs for learner engagement is that, for students who cannot participate in a traditional classroom due to a lack of resources or support, MOOCs offer another form of learning. Because students can learn at any time and do anywhere with lower costs, this can be particularly motivating for students who face financial or geographical pressures in traditional classroom education, and further enhance student engagement. The use of online materials can also help learners to engage with content tailored to their interests, boosting intrinsic motivation and encouraging active participation during classroom interactions.

Thus, MOOCs promote learner engagement and learning autonomy by requiring learners to manage their learning time, set goals, and take responsibility for their education without teacher supervision. Teachers use MOOCs as additional resources or to replace certain lessons, enabling students to independently explore and engage with the content. This not only strengthens their autonomous learning abilities but can also encourage active engagement in both online and offline courses.

In summary, the participant data shows that MOOCs have significantly affected traditional classroom teaching practices and learner engagement. As MOOCs continue to develop, their integration into traditional educational models could further enhance

these aspects of student learning, leading to a more dynamic and effective learning experience.

6.3.3 Answering RQ3- What are the specific factors, in relation to student motivation and the development of autonomous learning, that might affect learners' engagement with their learning via MOOCs? In what ways are learners affected by this new method of learning?

Students' expectations of MOOCs and the reasons for choosing them are varied. Several factors influence learners' engagement, as highlighted by the participants. The participants agree that technological factors, such as platform page design or Internet speed of the MOOC site affect learners' engagement. Similarly, in the responses to the questionnaires, 12 of the 20 participants believed that the technological design of MOOCs plays an important role in engagement. Those MOOCs with advanced technology, such as virtual interaction or relevant to artificial intelligence could enhance the learning experience (Yu *et al.*, 2017), and thus, attract learners and keep them interested and engaged.

In addition to technological factors, recommendations from teachers and promotions by universities were identified as key influences on student engagement. The traditional teacher-centred educational model in China emphasises the importance of teachers' guidance. Participants noted that when teachers recommend specific MOOCs or universities promote certain courses, student interest and participation tend to increase. Furthermore, while high-quality page design and reliable internet speed are important, integrating appropriate teaching approaches is essential for effective online education (Su *et al.*, 2021).

Moreover, participants felt that peer factors such as the educational background or academic level of peers can affect MOOC engagement. If the course content is either too difficult or too basic, students may lose interest. Other factors, such as learners' personalities, time availability, and the level of interaction in MOOCs, were also noted as influential. The data from the interviews also showed that there remain some disadvantages to studying through MOOCs, which are mainly experienced as weaker interactions between students and teachers, and a less immersive atmosphere, which demands greater self-motivation (Woolf, 2010). Therefore, the social and collaborative aspects of learning, which are reduced in MOOCs, can affect students' engagement. In traditional classrooms, peer interaction and the opportunities for interactive learning can enhance motivation and engagement. In contrast, the isolated feature of MOOCs, that is, the fact that everyone learns through their computer screen with limited opportunities for real-time collaboration or discussion, may affect students' engagement. This can negatively impact students who learn better in more socially motivated interactive learning environments.

Motivation is another critical factor which impacts students' engagement. Students who have a clear understanding of why they take the MOOCs and what they hope to gain from the MOOCs are more likely to be engaged. This result accords with the theoretical framework of this thesis specifically the work of Mackness, Mak and Williams (2010), which emphasises that successful MOOC participation relies not only on the course content but also on how learners engage with it, and how they develop an understanding of what helps them engage. A change from "teaching-focused" to "learning-focused" environments is essential, as highlighted by Nosratinia and Deris (2015), suggesting that students must develop strategies to acquire knowledge independently. This intrinsic motivation is closely related to a learner's ability to set goals, self-regulate, and stay committed to their learning objectives, which are essential components of autonomous learning (Reeve *et al.*,

2012). As MOOCs are structured in a more individualist way than traditional classrooms, students who are self-motivated and goal-oriented tend to perform better in this environment. However, students who are not self-motivated, may not perform as well in this environment.

Another important factor is the learner's ability for autonomous learning. MOOCs typically require students to manage their learning without supervision or guidance. Learners who struggle with autonomy may find it difficult to maintain focus and motivation. While the ability to study at one's own pace and on one's own schedule is appealing to many learners, this flexibility can also lead to procrastination or disengagement, particularly for students who lack strong self-discipline.

Additionally, effective support from teachers and learning communities could also affect learner engagement. Learners may feel more engaged in a MOOC when they receive timely assistance. With regular feedback, personalised tasks, interesting group work, or high-quality in-person face-to-face meetings, they are more likely to stay motivated. This accords with Rose and Ferschke's (2016) work that students are more engaged when they feel they are part of a supportive and collaborative learning environment.

Finally, the cost is a factor for some students. 5 of the 20 participants who responded to the questionnaires also noted that they chose MOOCs because they were available at no charge.

In summary, factors such as technology, motivation, the marketing of MOOCs, the ability to engage in autonomous learning, peer influence, and social interaction all affect how learners engage with MOOCs. While MOOCs provide opportunities for greater autonomy and flexibility, their success largely depends on students' ability to effectively navigate this new mode of learning.

6.3.4 Answering RQ4- What is the possible future of MOOCs? In what ways can MOOCs contribute to the development of stronger learner engagement in Higher Education in China in future?

This question was addressed by the participants during the interviews, as detailed in Appendices D, E, F, and G, as well as through the questionnaire responses outlined in Appendices B and C.

6.3.4.1 Possible Future of MOOCs

Participants agreed that in the future, MOOCs have the potential to complement traditional classroom learning. They believed a blended approach, combining MOOCs with classroom-based courses, to be a common model of learning in the future. The flexibility of MOOCs would benefit students, particularly in situations where attending in-person classes is not possible, as seen during the COVID-19 pandemic, resulting in home-based work and study. However, participants emphasised that traditional classroom learning remains essential, students also need to have face-to-face communication with teachers and classmates, especially for specialised courses, which require students' team collaboration on special projects. According to Li (2022), through the establishment of a hybrid teaching mode combining MOOCs with the traditional classroom, under the guidance of teachers, students can be the centre of an English class, students can cultivate their independent learning, and form good habits of self-learning so that a blend of online and in-class learning will be a good way for all students to achieve more. As Yuan and Powell (2013) note, MOOCs have many advantages: it has built-in flexibility, it can meet students' personal interests and is even a new and interesting learning method itself. Moreover, participants noted that MOOCs were not only a necessary solution during the pandemic but also a valuable supplement to classroom-based teaching. The expansion

of MOOCs, supported by universities and teachers, reflects their importance as part of future educational strategies.

In addition, the research findings suggest that both the quantity and quality of MOOCs are likely to increase in China. The delivery and development of MOOCs during the period of the COVID-19 pandemic was successful, and the government's attention to developing online education and the learners' demand for flexible MOOC learning methods has increased (Huang *et al.*, 2020). This governmental focus, coupled with the rising need for flexible learning, indicates that MOOCs will play a more significant role in China's educational landscape.

Participants also expressed the potential for MOOCs to become more personalised, tailoring content to meet the diverse learning needs and preferences of students. Advances in IT and data analytics can enable MOOCs to offer customised learning experiences through individually targeted personal survey questions, and then provide customised learning methods and materials. By adjusting content and learning strategies to individual students, MOOCs can provide more effective and engaging learning experiences.

Furthermore, the Chinese government has already invested in domestic MOOC platforms like XuetangX, and this support is expected to continue (Duan, 2021). Participants also noted that MOOCs are not only used for academic purposes but are increasingly attracting learners interested in personal development and career advancement. MOOCs in China are expected to expand beyond traditional academic subjects, offering courses focused on areas of personal interest and professional skills (Impey and Formanek, 2021). This shift reflects that MOOCs, with their rich resources, could also provide opportunities for learners to enhance their employability in the job market.

MOOCs also have the potential to increase the international reach of Chinese universities. By offering courses from prestigious global institutions and showcasing Chinese culture to the world, MOOCs can attract international students to Chinese universities. Moreover, participants believe that MOOCs could facilitate international collaborations between universities, fostering the exchange of teaching methods and resources on a global scale (King and Lee, 2022). Such collaborations would not only enhance the quality of education in China but also provide more learning opportunities for Chinese students.

Above all, participants acknowledged the introduction of MOOCs in reshaping higher education in China would be overwhelmingly significant. With the potential ability to optimise and develop the way education is delivered and represented, MOOCs can provide opportunities for lifelong learning and development, enhance the quality of teaching and learning, and promote the internationalisation of education (Moore, 2022). However, the future of MOOCs in higher education in China will also depend on how well MOOC programmes are able to adapt when faced with more requirements and challenges, such as how to handle quality issues related to the courses, and how to provide more effective support for learners.

6.3.4.2 Ways MOOCs Can Contribute to The Development of Stronger Learner Engagement in Higher Education in China in the Future

MOOCs have the potential to enhance learner engagement in higher education in China in the future for a variety of reasons. One of the primary ways MOOCs can contribute is by offering a more flexible and accessible learning environment (Iniesto *et al.*, 2016). The flexibility inherent in MOOCs allows students to engage with course material at their own pace. By making education more accessible, MOOCs can attract a diverse range of students who might not have access to higher education in

China, such as young people from poor families who have complex disabilities, or older learners who have never had the opportunity to enter universities and find they could continue to learn in this way. This accessibility through MOOCs can lead to stronger engagement for such learners as their lifestyles and their complex needs.

Another way MOOCs can enhance engagement in the future is through personalised learning experiences. As technology develops, MOOCs are increasingly incorporating data-driven personalisation techniques, tailored to individual learners' needs, preferences, and progress (Papadopoulos and Hossain, 2023). Personalised learning methods, mock quizzes, and targeted feedback can provide students with a more engaging and effective learning experience. When learners feel that the content is relevant to their personal goals and learning styles, they are more likely to stay motivated and invested in the course, which can lead to deeper engagement and better learning outcomes.

MOOCs also provide opportunities for interactive and collaborative learning, which are essential components of engagement. This interaction can be particularly valuable in a country like China, where traditional classrooms are often characterised by knowledge delivery, limiting individual participation (Li, Sun and Jee, 2019). In MOOCs, students have the opportunity to interact with peers from around the world, share diverse perspectives, and engage in meaningful discussions that can enhance their learning experience. This could further improve their learning autonomy and engagement.

Finally, in the future, MOOCs may appeal to students by adding entertainment, such as gamification and creative learning, which may enhance learner engagement, for example, adding elements such as a table of ranking and online rewards into online courses to create a more engaging and interactive experience. Gamification focuses on the psychological aspects of motivation, where learners are driven by a sense of

accomplishment and progress (Landers *et al.*, 2015). This can be particularly appealing to younger learners in China who are increasingly familiar with digital tools and game-based learning environments. By trying to introduce some of the positive attributes of online gaming into online learning, MOOCs can sustain student interest and foster a higher level of participation and engagement, and their intrinsic motivation would be increased.

In summary, MOOCs have the potential to enhance learner engagement in higher education in China by offering flexibility, personalisation, interactivity, access to global content, and innovative learning tools. As the Chinese education system continues to evolve, integrating MOOCs into the higher education landscape could play a critical role in fostering more engaged, motivated, and autonomous learners.

6.3.5 Answering RQ5- How and in what ways did MOOCs develop a different education practice and delivery during the COVID-19 pandemic to support students' individual motivation, and ultimately engagement in their learning?

This question was answered by the participants' responses which can be found in Appendices D, E, F, G, H and I.

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and beyond, the development of MOOC has undergone significant changes and challenges. The COVID-19 pandemic led to global restrictions, and the cancellation of offline teaching activities had a serious and long-lasting impact on face-to-face teaching activities. Thus, the delivery of courses through MOOCs quickly became a necessary choice for educational institutions and students. As Mishra, Gupta and Shree (2020) point out, due to the lockdown policies caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, many universities had to switch to an online

teaching mode, among which the MOOC platform became an important solution. In China, the MOOC platform continues to play a central role in maintaining student learning continuity and teaching sustainability. For example, Wuhan, the area in which the pandemic started, had to make online teaching the only teaching method because of continuing lockdown restrictions (He and Wei, 2021). In their responses to interviews for this thesis, all the participants shared the immediate actions that the local governments took in their cities to adjust the delivery of teaching in the universities.

The COVID-19 pandemic not only accelerated the popularisation and development of MOOCs but also promoted the innovation and application of online education technology. With further technological progress and sustained policy support, MOOCs are continuing to play an important role in the global education sector and many Chinese universities. According to Kang (2021), during the pandemic, MOOC platforms and educational institutions increased their investment in technological innovation to improve the effectiveness of online teaching. Other online learning methods have also developed, such as flipped classrooms, where students do the pre-reading online, then attend the classes with more ideas and more prepared for discussion, and later do the homework back online, which makes the class itself become much more focused on discussion around the ideas rather than simply giving students the ideas, so the class becomes more of a tutorial place. This kind of teaching also relies heavily on students' input and their own motivation. Online learning methods such as flipped classrooms are now also widely used in MOOCs to meet the learning needs of different groups of students (Wang and Zhu, 2019). On a global scale, the use of MOOC platforms has significantly increased. This growth is not only reflected in the increase in the number of participants engaging with MOOCs but also in the richness and development of course content. For example, China launched the first batch of international online teaching platforms for universities during the pandemic, further promoting the development of MOOCs (Xinhua News Agency,

2020). The number of users on the MOOC platforms has also sharply increased. This growth is not only reflected in the number of users but also in the market size of MOOCs. It is expected that by 2024, the MOOC market size will reach 22.8 billion dollars, with a compound annual growth rate of 39.20%. The report shows that some big universities and companies are interested in investing in MOOC areas, evidencing that MOOCs have captured a portion of the learning market and will become a key area for investment and further development.

The government has since introduced a series of policies to support the development of online education. For example, the Chinese Ministry of Education issued targeted guidance on organising and managing online teaching in higher education institutions during the epidemic prevention and control period, requiring universities to actively deliver all teaching activities, such as teaching and learning, online. In addition, they established industry norms to ensure the quality and effectiveness of online education. Many universities and educational institutions have also adopted innovative teaching models, combining MOOCs with other teaching methods. For example, Tsinghua University attempted to use the teaching organisation model of "MOOC+online live streaming+flipped classroom+virtual platform" in Pathology courses, achieving significant teaching results (Qiu et. al, 2021). This blended learning model has become mainstream in China.

Xinhua News Agency (2020) reported that during the COVID-19 pandemic, MOOCs attained significant development and progress in user growth, innovative teaching models, vocational training and certification, which address challenges and opportunities for deliverers and learners. This led to policy support and industry norms, as well as initiated the future development and trends of online education area. They noted that MOOC platforms will continue to exist and develop as they provide free learning options for millions of students, enabling them to study various subjects

flexibly and remotely, such as at home or in the office. MOOCs will continue to have a profound impact on the development of the direction of higher education.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, MOOCs played a transformative role in reshaping educational practices and delivery, adapting to the constraints of lockdowns and social distancing while supporting student engagement. The sudden shift to online learning required universities and other educational institutions to adopt flexible and accessible teaching methods, and MOOCs quickly became a primary tool. One of the most significant ways MOOCs adapted was by providing greater flexibility in learning. The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted traditional classroom settings, but MOOCs allowed students to continue their studies from home. This flexibility became essential for many students juggling new responsibilities, such as being provoked by the requirements of the COVID-19 pandemic, for example, taking care of family members or managing health concerns. MOOCs offered more learning opportunities, where students could access lectures and materials at any time, making it easier for them to stay engaged despite external challenges. This self-paced model allowed students to tailor their learning schedules around their personal lives, which was essential for maintaining engagement in a time of uncertainty.

In addition, MOOCs expanded access to high-quality educational content from top universities and institutions around the world. With travel restrictions and lockdowns limiting physical access to education, students were able to enrol in MOOCs to access resources and courses that were otherwise unavailable.

Finally, government and institutional support for MOOCs grew during the pandemic, further enhancing their role in education. In many countries, including China, the government promoted online learning platforms, providing the infrastructure and resources necessary for MOOCs to develop rapidly and further increase the population of students. Many universities also partnered with MOOC platforms to

ensure that their courses were accessible to students who could not attend physical campuses. This institutional endorsement not only recognised MOOC learning as an effective alternative to traditional education but also helped increase student trust and engagement with the platform.

6.3.6 New Knowledge from the Research

During my PhD research, I formulated the research questions based on a comprehensive review of the relevant literature. I first conducted a set of questionnaires, which gave me some insights and also helped inform my interview questions. I then conducted semi-structured interviews to collect data. However, in order to obtain deeper insights, I conducted follow-up interviews with participants and collected data. Notably, the participants' awareness of independent learning had significantly improved. The theoretical framework guiding this research draws from the work of Mackness, Mak, and Williams (2010), who argue that learners' recognition of effective learning methods is more impactful than the course content itself. While their theory was based on the context of Iran, my findings suggest that similar developments are evident in Chinese learners engaged in MOOCs, thus extending the relevance of this theory to the Chinese context.

The questionnaires suggest that both students and teachers are increasingly aware of the importance of MOOCs. From the students' perspective, many recognise that MOOC courses can enhance their autonomous learning abilities and boost their motivation. This was a surprising result, as students demonstrated a higher level of awareness regarding online learning than I expected. Additionally, the semi-structured interviews further advanced my understanding of learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education, and directly answered the research questions.

The key findings regarding the potential future of MOOCs in China hold important implications for scholars and educational institutions in the design and delivery of these courses. These findings contribute to the understanding of learner engagement with MOOCs, particularly in the Chinese context. While there are limitations such as the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic that necessitated a change from face-to-face to online data collection, these challenges do not reduce the value of the research. Instead, they highlight areas for future investigation, particularly in how MOOCs can be further developed.

The research indicates that an increasing number of Chinese students are engaging with MOOCs, driven by several factors, including comparisons with traditional classroom learning. The more motivated students are to take these courses, the more actively they participate in discussions and course activities. The rapid growth of MOOCs in China, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, demonstrates their potential as an effective educational tool. Despite challenges, such as ensuring consistent engagement and addressing varying learning needs, the development of MOOCs is expected to accelerate and expand into a broader range of subject areas.

This study addresses a gap in the literature concerning Chinese learner engagement with MOOCs and offers a foundation for future research. It highlights the potential for MOOCs to play an important role in the future of education in China, and it suggests new directions for the continued evolution of online learning.

6.4 Limitations

6.4.1 Working within the Restrictions of the COVID-19 Pandemic

6.4.1.1 Change to Research Methods

From 2019 to 2023, the COVID-19 pandemic caused unprecedented disruptions to learning across the world, with significant impacts on the economy, politics, and education in many countries. This study initially began before the outbreak of the pandemic, with the original plan being for me, as the researcher, to return to China to conduct face-to-face questionnaires and semi-structured interviews at two selected universities. However, when the time came for data collection, the pandemic lockdowns and restrictions on international travel made it impossible to carry out this plan. To address these challenges, I informed the selected participants of the changes and explained the purpose of the study with the help of the teachers at the target universities. Questionnaires were sent and collected via email, and with the participants' consent, I established contact with them through WeChat, a widely used social media platform in China, to continue with the planned semi-structured interviews. This approach allowed me to conquer the difficulties brought by the pandemic and overcome the limitations of physical distance.

However, this shift to online data collection raised certain challenges. The change from face-to-face to online interactions resulted in less rich data than expected. The lack of physical presence during the interviews made it difficult to make deep, engaging discussions, limiting my ability as the interviewer to encourage participants to elaborate on their responses over the phone. If we had conducted the interviews in person, the data collection process could have allowed for more exploration, guidance, and spontaneous inspiration, leading to richer and more meaningful opinions. In addition, technical difficulties, such as poor audio quality and unstable internet connectivity, frequently hindered the interviews. These issues further limited the depth and quality of the data collected. Moreover, when it became necessary to revisit

certain topics to gather more detailed information, coordinating follow-up interviews was complicated by the eight-hour time difference between China and Scotland, appointments with the participants were not kept as arranged sometimes, which was also a problem during the research.

6.4.1.2 Issues with online interviewing

Due to the restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, the semi-structured interviews were conducted online. According to De Villiers, Farooq and Molinari (2022), remote interviewing is an effective solution when participants are difficult to reach due to geographical constraints or scheduling conflicts, as it reduces travel costs and time consumption. Although online interviews provided convenience and safety for both me and the participants during the pandemic, they also presented some issues and challenges.

Firstly, online interviews rely heavily on a stable internet connection and the proper use of video conferencing software (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018), such as Zoom, Teams, or Skype. During some of my interviews, network instability, at times, led to disruptions in the video calls, which interrupted the flow of conversation and affected the quality of the data collected. Additionally, some participants experienced technical issues, such as malfunctioning microphones or cameras, or were unfamiliar with the operation of the software. Since I was conducting the interviews from Scotland and the participants were located in China, we initially tried platforms like Zoom, Tencent Meeting, and WeChat. Ultimately, WeChat was chosen as the most stable and familiar option for both sides. However, external factors such as background noise from some participants' family members or roommates occasionally interfered, highlighting the importance of a quiet, distraction-free environment for remote interviews.

In addition, due to the lack of face-to-face communication opportunities, communication in remote interviews was less direct and effective. The different time zones between Scotland and China further complicated scheduling and communication, sometimes limiting the flow of conversation, which made the interviews difficult. Another challenge was the psychological aspect of the remote interview adaptation. Online interviews can feel awkward, especially for participants who were not accustomed to this format. To resolve this issue, I encouraged participants to share their experiences and feelings by designing detailed, step-by-step questions that facilitated deeper discussion. I also provided continuous feedback during their responses and used non-verbal cues, such as smiling or nodding, to create a more relaxed and comfortable atmosphere. Interestingly, avoiding direct eye contact, by not always looking into the camera seemed to help some of the shyer participants open up more easily (Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016).

6.4.1.3 MOOCs during the COVID-19 Pandemic

This research was conducted during an unprecedented time, I, as the researcher, along with many people, experienced the COVID-19 pandemic and national lockdowns for the first time. China, being the first country to experience the pandemic, faced unique challenges, particularly in the field of education. With no prior examples to guide their response, both the Chinese people and the government had to swiftly adapt to the crisis. The sudden breakout of the pandemic made not only China but also the global community unprepared for the restrictions and influences that followed.

In the field of education, students and lecturers did not have any prior experience of participating in university courses fully online, prompting a collective effort to meet the challenges brought by remote learning. Lecturers, many of whom had never used online teaching platforms, required immediate and targeted training to effectively deliver instruction to students learning in isolation. Students also needed guidance from universities on how to manage their studies independently and support one

another in this new learning environment. Additionally, school administrators and local education authorities faced considerable challenges in coordinating these rapid transitions.

The sudden need and large volume of engagement in MOOCs during the pandemic forced these platforms to evolve in ways that were different from their previous development models. MOOCs had to quickly adapt to accommodate the large-scale need for remote learning, which caused widespread discussions and evaluations of university practices. While many voices supported and advocated for the integration of MOOCs into mainstream education, some resisted the shift to online learning, expressing concerns about the efficacy and sustainability of these changes.

6.4.1.4 Writing the Thesis During COVID-19 Pandemic

The temporary closure of the University of the West of Scotland campus and its library as a result of the COVID-19 lockdown made it difficult for me to access some literature and academic articles. With limited access to essential materials, the process of writing my thesis became more complex. However, with the help and support of supervisors and friends in China and Scotland, I obtained access to online articles from different academic websites and downloaded materials that enabled me to consider, research and give clarity to the issues involved in this study. The pandemic also transformed the way research and writing were conducted. Isolation and lockdown measures made in-person collaboration impossible at that time, requiring me to rely on online meetings and email communication with my supervisors. All the in-person academic conferences were moved online, and I was unable to attend and practise delivering my thesis in person to others and learn from the peer and specialist feedback. These changes forced me to develop new skills in digital communication, time management and independent research. Although the transition to an entirely online environment was challenging, it helped me improve a deeper level of self-discipline and adaptability in managing my studies.

In addition, the uncertainty and emotional strain caused by the pandemic had another impact on the writing process. I did not go back to China for more than three years, as the travel policies changed frequently. I also changed my employment to part-time as a result of lockdown restrictions. Despite these challenges, overcoming the difficulties associated with the pandemic has not only strengthened my research skills but also enhanced my ability to work under pressure. These experiences ultimately made me a more confident and resilient person capable of navigating unforeseen circumstances and adapting to changing environments.

6.4.2 The Participants' English Level

In order to collect richer data and more diverse perspectives, semi-structured interviews were conducted on two separate occasions to compare participants' perceptions and experiences with MOOCs before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Due to the restrictions of the COVID-19 pandemic, both sets of interviews were conducted entirely online. Some participants, however, faced challenges in expressing themselves in English, and as a result, certain explanations and responses were provided in Chinese. This required additional time for me to collate and translate the data, necessitating multiple reviews of the interview recordings to clarify participants' intended meanings.

In this study, I offered support to participants who were not fully proficient in English, allowing them to respond in a language with which they were more comfortable. Although all participants were from the School of Foreign Languages at their respective Chinese universities, some had never been involved in PhD research before and were unfamiliar with its demands. To ensure the collection of rich, reliable data, before I sent the questionnaires, I gave participants the option to answer the final open-ended question in their first language. This approach facilitated more in-depth

responses, enabling participants to express their thoughts and feelings more clearly. During the semi-structured interviews, I also provided explanations in Chinese when necessary, helping participants better understand the questions and thus allowing them to respond more comfortably and accurately.

As a result, some data was provided directly in English, while other responses were collected in Chinese. When further clarification was required, I returned to participants to gather additional data, which was also sometimes expressed in Chinese. All the data collected in Mandarin Chinese was carefully translated into English by myself, and I checked the translated content to ensure that it accurately reflected participants' true feelings. This process was essential to maintaining the reliability and authenticity of the data. I took particular care in translating participants' responses to preserve the authenticity of their voices. I was aware that translation is viewed as a key element of interpretivism (Van Nes *et al.*, 2010), so I wanted to ensure that the meanings conveyed in the participants' native language were faithfully represented in the English translations. Throughout this process, I received valuable guidance and support from my supervisors to further ensure the accuracy and integrity of the data.

6.4.3 Follow-up Interviews

During the research process, I noticed that some of the initial interview responses were not sufficiently detailed to fully address the research questions. Recognising that the data collected in the interviews lacked the depth and relevance required, I decided to further interview some participants to gather richer and more relevant information. While I aimed to reconnect with all of the original participants, this was not entirely possible, as some participants had graduated several years earlier and were no longer reachable. Nevertheless, I was able to successfully follow up with the four participants I had initially interviewed during the COVID-19 pandemic, allowing me to complete the additional interviews and obtain the necessary data.

6.4.4 Research in Chinese Universities

This research focuses exclusively on the Chinese educational context, analysing the factors that influence learner engagement in MOOCs within China. As a result, its findings may not be universally applicable, especially to different contexts in other countries' universities that have different teaching structures from Chinese higher education. In addition, China has a large population in relation to the rest of the world. There are over 3000 higher education institutions in China, which presents unique challenges. This study examines the context of two 'average' level universities, which may limit the generalisability of the results, especially to higher-tier institutions within China. The diversity of institutions within China, ranging from top research universities to small regional institutions, means that the experiences and engagement of students with MOOCs may vary significantly. Higher-level universities, for example, may have access to more advanced technological infrastructure and resources, which could lead to different outcomes in terms of MOOC engagement and effectiveness. As a result, the findings of this research may not be fully representative of all Chinese universities, particularly those at the higher-ranking end of the educational spectrum. Attention should be paid when applying these findings to other contexts or levels of education, both within and outside China.

6.4.5 Fewer Participants

Another limitation of this study is the relatively small sample size, which limits the representation of the findings. I selected two Chinese universities of similar academic levels and gathered responses from ten participants at each university who completed the questionnaires, with four participants selected for semi-structured interviews. Although English major classes in Chinese universities typically consist of around 20

students, meaning that the ten participants represented approximately half the class, the overall number of participants remains small.

As a result, the data collected was not generalisable to other contexts. However, the insights obtained from this study still provide valuable information for understanding learner engagement in MOOCs within the specific universities and institutions studied, as discussed in the literature review chapter.

6.4.6 Limitations in Comparability

I selected research participants from two targeted universities: one that officially integrated MOOCs into its curriculum and another that did not. All participants had prior experience with MOOCs, which allowed me to compare their learning experiences, and the impact MOOCs had on them, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, I am aware that this study did not include a comparison between students who participated in MOOCs and those who had never engaged with MOOCs. Consequently, the potential differences in learning outcomes between those who attended MOOCs and those who did not were neither discussed nor analysed.

This limitation suggests that the data, while informative within the specific context of this study, is not fully replicable across different learning environments or broader student populations. Future research could address this gap by comparing the learning outcomes of students who have participated in MOOCs with those who have not, providing more comprehensive insights into the effectiveness of MOOCs as a learning tool. Such a comparative analysis could reveal important differences in engagement and overall academic performance, offering a richer understanding of how MOOCs influence educational outcomes.

6.5 Changes I Would Make If I Was Starting Again

6.5.1 Change the Sampling Techniques

At this point, it is important to discuss one of the significant changes instigated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Before the pandemic, the majority of Chinese universities generally adopted a face-to-face teaching method, while some individual universities experimented with MOOCs as a means of integrating online and offline pedagogical approaches. Therefore, the initial research plan involved selecting a sample of ten students and five teachers from each target university to participate in questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. However, following the policy changes in response to the pandemic, many universities launched MOOCs as a direct response to the requirements of the Ministry of Education and the development of MOOCs expanded particularly quickly at that time. This change made the size of the research design appear a little smaller.

If I were to navigate a similar situation again, I would adopt a snowball sampling approach to maximise data collection and analysis. This would involve a larger number of participants to engage in the research and gather diverse perspectives on MOOCs in China, allowing for a comprehensive comparison of opinions. Additionally, I would examine the impact of MOOCs on students' academic performance and grades, as well as investigate teachers' judgments of this innovation in the delivery and methodology of teaching.

6.5.2 Selecting Participants from Foreign Universities

Moreover, if feasible, including participants from foreign universities in this research could provide valuable insights into their experiences with MOOCs. Such a comparative analysis would illuminate both the similarities and differences in the development and implementation of MOOCs in China and globally. This research

would contribute to a broader understanding of the influence of MOOCs on education worldwide and the role these courses played in facilitating learning during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In addition, by examining diverse institutional strategies and pedagogical approaches of MOOCs worldwide, the research could reveal how cultural, economic, and technological factors influence the adoption and effectiveness of MOOCs in different regions, by assessing how MOOCs have been integrated into various educational frameworks, to analyse the importance of MOOCs in reshaping pedagogical paradigms.

6.6 Autobiographical Reflection -- My Own Growth (Academic and Personal)

6.6.1 Academic Growth

6.6.1.1 Development of My Academic Knowledge within the Field

My initial concept for this study was shaped by the manner and contexts in which MOOCs were taught at some of China's top universities in recent years, presenting a significant opportunity for the advancement of online education in China. However, I realised that this topic was too broad. The content of MOOCs from universities' official platforms and other educational platforms was not easy to discuss and analyse in terms of the perceptions of students and teachers of most general-level undergraduate institutions on the development of MOOCs. Therefore, with guidance from my supervisors, I decided to focus on analysing students' experiences with MOOCs by comparing two general-level universities in China. This decision led me to read more academic literature about this field and gain a deeper understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of MOOCs used in Chinese universities. This

comprehensive review enabled me to investigate the topic thoroughly and connect it with the existing academic articles.

In my literature review, I examined numerous articles related to the development of MOOCs in China, the relationship between MOOCs and autonomous learning, and the motivations of Chinese students for learning. Most of these studies indicated that Chinese students' motivations tend to be instrumental and purposeful. Specifically, the findings suggested that the primary motivations for Chinese students undertaking MOOC studies are to pass exams and achieve successful graduation.

However, in the second year of my project, the COVID-19 pandemic emerged, first impacting China before spreading globally. The Chinese government, recognising its unique circumstances compared to Western countries, implemented collective lockdown measures and changed its educational policy from offline to online learning. These policies facilitated the rapid expansion and public adoption of MOOCs. As a result, I gained the opportunity to gather more information regarding participation in MOOCs, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of their impact on students' educational experiences during this unprecedented time.

6.6.1.2 Developing Language Skills

Before started my PhD, I returned to China to work for two years in the field of Internet education. During this period, my use of English reduced, leading to a regression in my language skills compared to the level I had achieved at the end of my Master's programme. However, I realised that after starting my PhD, the language requirements were more specialised and academic, necessitating further development of my language proficiency. In order to enhance my language skills, I began to adopt a more formal writing style, incorporating academic vocabulary with guidance from my supervisors. I also expanded my reading abilities by engaging with English-language articles, attending presentations by other PhD students, participating

in educational forums, and listening to professional academic speech. As a result, I observed notable progress in my language skills, although I acknowledge that further improvement is still needed.

6.6.2 Personal Growth

6.6.2.1 Gaining Confidence

After returning to Scotland as a PhD student, I faced a new set of challenges in terms of learning. The demands of PhD-level work require a higher proficiency in language and research skills, building on the foundations established during my Master's studies. Simultaneously, my supervisors and I formulated an initial plan for my thesis, such as consideration of the issues around Epistemological and Ontological Stances, which I had never encountered previously. As a new PhD researcher, I initially struggled with a lack of confidence in navigating these complexities.

Fortunately, the university offered free pre-PhD preparation courses for Algerian students, which I was also invited to attend. During these courses, professors provided insights into various aspects of PhD academics, with a particular emphasis on methodological choices and the definitions of epistemological and ontological stances. This was very helpful, as it supported my transition from a state of anxiety to one of confidence during the later stages of my writing process.

6.6.2.2 Adaptation to An English-Speaking Environment

Previously, I was shy and reluctant to speak in public, particularly in English. After graduating, I returned to China for two years, during which I seldom used the English language. However, my participation in the Pre-PhD course, where I was the only Chinese student, necessitated regular use of English for communication. This experience motivated me to take the initiative to engage in research colloquia and transfer events organised by other students from the School of Education and Social

Science, allowing me to gain valuable listening and speaking experience in an academic context.

As I participated in these activities, my ability to adapt to the English-speaking environment gradually improved. Additionally, working as a part-time staff member further enhanced my English-speaking skills, as various roles provided more opportunities to practice speaking and listening with local people. Living off-campus, my neighbour, an English teacher, frequently took the time to discuss the focus and ideas of my PhD thesis with me, which significantly facilitated my adjustment to an English-speaking environment.

6.6.2.3 Difficulties of Doing My PhD Study during the COVID-19 Pandemic

The lockdown of cities caused by the requirements of the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in significant disruptions to both work and daily life. In response to government policies aimed at minimising social contact, many shops and restaurants closed down. I, the researcher, found a part-time job at a supermarket during this challenging period to support myself. The extended isolation in student accommodations, coupled with limited contact with family, friends, supervisors, and peer groups, posed additional challenges to maintaining my mental health.

To address this issue, I organised study groups with fellow students and friends through regular video calls and messaging, ensuring that our academic progress continued effectively. Simultaneously, I maintained regular contact with my family and friends in China via social media, keeping noticed of recent developments regarding the outbreak and global news to remain connected to current events.

The COVID-19 pandemic has made a huge difference to people's daily lives, it also allowed me to review previous sections of my study and engage in deep reflection on the potential impact of this research.

6.7 The (Potential) Impact of My Research; Implications from the Research and Recommendations to Universities in China

Based on the findings of this study, ten recommendations for implementation are proposed: five for universities, three for government and two for students.

6.7.1 Recommendations to Chinese Universities

6.7.1.1 Launching MOOCs Officially

According to the findings of this study, participants expressed unfamiliarity with and dislike for the teaching styles of certain MOOCs, including courses from other universities and various online platforms. Participants indicated a preference for the teaching style and teaching pace of their own teachers. Consequently, I recommend that universities develop official MOOC training programmes designed by their teachers, focusing on adapting course objectives from traditional classroom settings to a blended online and offline format. Teachers should tailor the design and delivery of these courses to align with students' learning paces and habits, thereby enhancing the courses' relevance and improving students' learning efficiency and motivation.

Furthermore, the study's findings suggest that, in addition to their compulsory university courses, students should be encouraged to engage in additional courses of interest. Therefore, I recommend that universities establish non-specialist courses to serve as the preparation for the pre-trial of MOOC development. These courses should be structured to avoid interfering with the schedule of major curriculum classes.

Finally, Chinese universities may need to provide additional support to ensure that students fully understand the course content, which could include allowing time for

both teachers and students to adjust to the content and demands of MOOCs. For example, incorporating subtitles, providing supplementary references, and facilitating document interpretation in entry-level courses could significantly help students when they begin to engage with MOOCs.

6.7.1.2 Screening and Introducing MOOCs from other Universities

According to student participants, MOOCs offer a unique opportunity to learn from prestigious universities around the world. Several participants noted that MOOCs provide access to learning experiences that are often unavailable in traditional classrooms at “normal level” universities. This is particularly beneficial for motivated learners seeking to expand their knowledge and access a broader range of resources and materials.

Therefore, it is recommended that universities screen and incorporate MOOCs from other institutions as a means of enhancing teaching methodologies. However, attention must be paid to several critical areas. Specifically, teachers should pay attention to the quality of course content and ensure that the level of MOOCs is appropriate for their students.

6.7.1.3 Encouraging Students to Use MOOCs to Enhance Their Independent Learning Ability

The findings indicate that these groups of students engaged with MOOCs and other online courses more frequently during the lockdown period, which enhanced their ability to learn autonomously due to university closures and the adjustments made to teaching requirements in response to COVID-19 restrictions. This period presented a valuable opportunity to encourage students to engage with MOOCs to enhance their autonomous learning skills. Therefore, it is recommended that universities and teachers capitalise on this experience by implementing several strategies to further promote student participation in MOOCs. For example, universities should consider

developing a system for accrediting MOOC courses, aligning them with course credits in specific subject areas.

6.7.1.4 Continuing Professional Learning for Academics

Regardless of the changes required in the delivery of English language courses, teachers remain indispensable in the process. However, it is often challenging to find suitable teachers who are comfortable and experienced in recording MOOCs to deliver course content. Therefore, universities must ensure that teachers are given sufficient time for their professional development while also conserving their energy as MOOC instructors and researchers. Keeping this balance is important to prevent delays in both classroom preparation and individual research programmes.

Engaging students in the learning process and ensuring that the course content is appropriate for all students can often be challenging. This difficulty may contribute to some teachers' unwillingness to design and launch MOOCs, which can lead to lower student engagement. To address this, it is recommended that universities select a group of teachers and provide training on effective media use for recording MOOCs.

In addition, young teachers may adapt to teaching via MOOCs more easily than older teachers who may be more experienced in delivering classes in traditional classroom settings, as young people are perhaps more familiar with the technology. Therefore, increasing collaboration between younger and older teachers in training programmes can enhance overall proficiency with current MOOC technologies. Older teachers can leverage their extensive teaching experience to master the content, while younger teachers can contribute their expertise in IT and MOOC curriculum design.

6.7.1.5 Customising MOOCs to Meet University-Specific Academic Standards

A further recommendation arises from the analysis of the perception of MOOCs, from the response of Participants B and C. One of the problems with MOOCs is that they are not tailored to the specific academic standards or curricular needs of individual universities. This lack of customization can lead to a disconnect between the content provided by MOOCs and the unique requirements of particular institutions.

Universities should carefully consider this limitation when incorporating MOOCs into their curricula. To solve this problem, universities could work toward adapting or supplementing existing MOOCs to better align with their academic frameworks, ensuring that the courses meet the specific learning objectives and rigour expected at their institution. By tailoring MOOCs to fit institutional needs, universities can better integrate these courses into their overall educational strategies, providing students with a more cohesive and relevant learning experience. Additionally, universities might collaborate with MOOC providers to create specialised courses or learning pathways that meet the demands of their students and faculty. This approach could enhance both the quality and relevance of MOOCs, making them a more effective tool for higher education.

6.7.2 Recommendations to the Chinese Government and Education

Authorities

6.7.2.1 Introducing MOOCs to Younger Students

MOOCs, as a new educational model, have profoundly impacted traditional higher education. The MOOC platform, which experienced significant development during the COVID-19 pandemic, should actively participate in educational reform, and promote the development of higher education towards a more open, fair, and diversified direction. Looking ahead, primary and secondary schools across China could consider designing and integrating MOOCs appropriately, adopting online

teaching methods more widely, and fostering students' ability to make use of educational resources and learn independently from an early age. This would better equip students to adapt to the evolving educational environment so that by the time they reach university, they will already have experience with MOOCs and online learning platforms.

6.7.2.2 Establishing Learning Hubs

The government should provide infrastructure to support learners, ensuring they have access to computers and the Internet when needed after school. One effective approach is to establish MOOC learning hubs. Learning hubs can also be classified into different learning areas and subject areas, enabling learners to better connect with peers who share similar educational backgrounds and form study groups to engage with MOOCs collaboratively.

Additionally, MOOC learning hubs should offer access to resources from top universities worldwide, ensuring high-quality and up-to-date course content. These hubs should also provide professional support services to help learners navigate the platform and make full use of its resources. By offering comprehensive functions, diverse learning materials, and a supportive user-friendly environment, these hubs can deliver an excellent online learning experience.

6.7.2.3 Promoting Inclusivity in MOOC Design and Delivery

Another recommendation is that MOOC providers should recognise and accommodate the diverse backgrounds and perspectives of their learners. This can be achieved through a culturally sensitive course design method that includes global examples, diverse case studies, and inclusive language. In this way, MOOC providers can bridge the gap between Western cultural content and the needs of non-Western learners. Additionally, offering different versions of courses and providing

supplementary materials that contextualize content for different cultural backgrounds may enhance student engagement and motivation. Teachers should also be careful about the potential impact of their personal values and ideological perspectives, striving to present material in a balanced and inclusive manner.

Due to the diverse educational backgrounds and ideological perspectives of MOOC learners significantly influencing their engagement, MOOC designers and instructors need to adopt a globally inclusive approach. This approach should consider the varied experiences and perspectives of learners, ensuring that the content is relevant, accessible, and engaging for a diverse global audience. By implementing these recommendations, MOOC providers can develop a more inclusive and effective learning environment, ultimately reducing dropout rates and enhancing the overall educational experience for all learners.

6.7.3 Recommendations to Chinese Students

6.7.3.1 Developing Time Management Skills

Another recommendation emerging from the interviews emphasises the importance of learners developing effective time management skills to maximise their use of MOOCs. These skills can be cultivated through conscious structured training. Universities could offer specialised courses to teach students the theoretical foundations and practical applications of time management, helping them establish effective learning habits. Students should consciously and flexibly apply their time management skills, develop personalised study plans, and pay attention to self-monitoring and self-examination during the implementation process of the plans. There are also many well-researched methods for time management so that learners can choose the one that suits them based on their personal habits and preferences. These include the GTD method, the Pareto principle, McKinsey's 30-second elevator theory, and the Moffat rest method (Gregg, 2015).

6.7.3.2 Students' Preparation for MOOC Study

Many students are not adequately prepared to engage with MOOCs. They always turn off their cameras, do other things while they should be concentrating on their learning or leave the learning environment without teacher supervision. This behaviour is closely tied to students' learning motivation. When students realise the importance of MOOC learning and improve their independent learning ability, MOOCs will be more effective. Improved preparation and active participation are key to maximising the benefits of these online courses.

6.8 Future Research Areas

The rapid growth and widespread adoption of MOOCs and other online courses in China, driven by the COVID-19 pandemic, present numerous opportunities for future research in this area. Due to the limitations of the COVID-19 pandemic, the researcher was unable to return to China to organise face-to-face interviews but arranged the interviews online through the WeChat voice call, which limited the ability to fully explore participants' nuanced perspectives on certain questions. However, the pandemic has also led many institutions, initially not considered in this research, to adopt MOOCs and achieve significant success. Therefore, the potential data will be abundant, and future research should be rooted in an in-depth analysis of the current research topic and the analysis of a more extensive range of data. The researcher outlines three key recommendations for future research in the MOOC field, aimed at further advancing the understanding and application of this educational model.

6.8.1 Widening the Scope of the Study

The data collected from two Chinese universities was sufficient for the current study. However, the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of both online and offline MOOC teaching methods across a broader range of Chinese universities and online platforms. As a result, the researcher intends to expand the study in the future by gathering data from additional universities in different cities in China. This will allow for a more comprehensive analysis and further development of the current findings.

6.8.2 Using Alternative Data Collection Methods

The research employed a mixed-method approach, using both questionnaires and semi-structured interviews with student and teacher participants from two targeted universities. At the time the research was initiated, the adoption of MOOCs in Chinese universities was slower than it is now. However, the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the development of both official university MOOCs and other MOOC platforms. In the next phase of continued research, snowball sampling could be employed to gather larger and more diverse data, to comprehensively analyse these recent developments.

6.8.3 Hearing More Voices

This study aimed to explore the experiences and feedback of Chinese students and teachers regarding their use of MOOCs. The findings in Chapters Four and Five showed that most participants had engaged with MOOCs as part of their learning. Students generally adhered to their universities' regulations for online and offline learning, with the aim of completing the required learning hours and graduating successfully.

However, I suggest that it is also important to examine whether individuals who have already graduated and are employed continue to use MOOCs independently. If so, it would be valuable to determine whether these graduates participate in MOOCs more frequently or with higher completion rates compared to university students. Additionally, do their learning objectives tend to be more specific, driven by personal or professional development, rather than academic requirements? These questions need further in-depth analysis.

6.9 Conclusion

This study provides an in-depth exploration of MOOCs in general-level undergraduate universities in China, particularly focusing on their development during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Previous research has largely concentrated on the introduction of MOOCs by universities, the differences between MOOCs and other online courses, recommendations for MOOC platforms and courses, and their relationship with autonomous learning during the pandemic. This study further analyses MOOC development during the COVID-19 pandemic and investigates the influence on learning autonomy, motivation and engagement. The thesis acknowledges the recent context of the introduction of MOOCs in Chinese universities, which has developed rapidly, and investigates whether the causes and consequences of the rapid development of MOOCs in the context of the COVID-19 epidemic have far-reaching implications for the development of online courses in China.

This chapter has systematically addressed each research question, providing evidence of how they have been answered in alignment with the study's aims. The findings indicate that MOOCs offer significant advantages for educational development, particularly in reducing the need for extensive human and material resources while

broadening students' and teachers' perspectives and fostering the development of relevant resources. It is recommended that not only top universities but also general universities and institutions in China adopt MOOCs to enhance student demand and support for online learning. Meanwhile, multiple factors can influence students' engagement. Enhancing the autonomous learning ability of students to better engage in MOOCs is a necessity. For future research, the researcher intends to expand the scope of this study, improve the research design and observe developments in the context of economic recovery in the following years of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The survey responses indicated that both students and teachers are increasingly aware of the potential of MOOCs. From the students' perspective, many recognise that MOOCs can improve their autonomous learning abilities and enhance their motivation. This was particularly surprising, as it suggests a higher level of student engagement with online learning than expected. Furthermore, the semi-structured interviews provide deeper insights into learner engagement with MOOCs in Chinese higher education, helping to answer the study's research questions.

The practical implications of my research are related to MOOC design, higher education policies and instructional practices in China. By analysing learner engagement via MOOCs, I answered all the research questions and obtained key findings about the potential challenges and benefits for Chinese universities, the ways the introduction of MOOCs affected traditional teaching methods and classroom practice in Chinese universities, factors that might affect learners' engagement, MOOCs engagement and the enhancement of autonomous learning and motivation and imagining the possible future of MOOCs development in China. These conclusions have practical significance and can help Chinese people to understand MOOCs in-depth, so that MOOCs could play a greater role in other fields such as vocational skills training in the future.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A Participant Information Sheet

Name of department:

School of Education and Social Science, University of the West of Scotland

Title of the study: An Analysis of Students' Engagement with MOOCs in Higher Education in China

Introduction

My name is Yugeng Li and I am conducting research for a Ph.D dissertation at the University of the West of Scotland. My contact details are as follows:

- Email: [REDACTED]
- Telephone: [REDACTED]

Supervisor's contact details:

- Margaret Allan Personal details withheld.
- Email: [REDACTED]
- Telephone: [REDACTED]

What is the purpose of this research?

This study plans to analyse the learner engagement with MOOCs in the Chinese higher education. It aims to investigate learners' engagement as above and their completion rate in relation to MOOCs.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen because you fit the criteria of the participants I would like to interview. As you are a speaker of both English and Chinese and have/do not have the experiences of MOOCs in university, you would be an ideal participant.

Do you have to take part?

You do not have to take part in the study, and even if you do agree to take part, you may withdraw at any time. If you decide to withdraw, rest assured that any data collected up to the point of your withdrawing from the study will be destroyed. Taking part or not taking part in the study will not impact on your relationship with me in any way. If you decide to take part in this study, then you should let me know by **March 5th, 2021**.

What will you do?

If you agree, you will be asked to take part in an interview with me which will be audio recorded. The interview will take place during the month of **March 2021**. You can be interviewed at a time and place that suits you. The interview will last approximately 20-30 minutes, and you will be invited to talk to me about:

- Experiences of attending MOOCs
- Your opinions of MOOCs

What happens to the information?

The findings from this study will be included in my Ph.D dissertation and may be published in the form of a report or article. However, your name will never be mentioned, and all participants will remain anonymous. The information that you provide me with will be kept for up to 10 years to allow for potential publication from the thesis at a future date. You are free to contact the researcher and withdraw your data up to the point of anonymisation.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed by the Ethics Committee of the School of Education, UWS.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in the study, then please let me know by the **5th of March 2021** using the contact details provided above.

If you do not want to be involved in the study, then I would like to thank you for your attention.

After the study has been completed, a report of the findings will be available in electronic form. If you wish to receive a copy, please let me know and I will email it to you.

APPENDIX B Interview Protocol and Interview Questions

An Analysis of Students' Engagement with MOOCs in Higher Education in China

Introductory Statement for Face-to-Face:

We are now recording. Thank you again for agreeing to participate in this individual interview. Please remember that anything you say will be made anonymous in the transcription process and that you are free to stop participating at any time, and without giving explanation. You can also decline to answer questions. There is no penalty for declining to participate. I've also sent you a Participation Information and this contains information about who to contact if you have any concerns or comments about today's interview.

Engagement

#	Questions:
1.	<p>As part of this study, I would like you to consider your experiences of attending MOOCs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- How were you introduced to MOOCs?- Who introduced you to this kind of learning? - What were your expectations of MOOCs?- Why did you expect this (based on your previous experience of learning)?

Exploration

#	Questions:
2.	<p>What is your experience of participating in MOOCs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What did you like about the course(s)? • Has it been positive? If so, why / why not? • How often do you participate in these courses? - Can you tell me why, or what, affects how often (regularly) you participate? • When? At what time of day? - Can you tell me why these times suit you? What affects the time of your participation?
3.	<p>What motivates you to attend and participate in MOOCs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is it just the time of the online courses? Is their regularity/ (how often)? - Is it related to your previous experience of classroom learning? - do you feel that classroom learning is enough for you? - Do you want to learn further, or in a different way from traditional classroom learning? If so, why? - Is this why you chose MOOCs/online learning? - Is it better for you to learn at a different, or a particular time? Why?
4.	<p>Do you feel that you engage better with online or with traditional classroom learning?</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Why? / Why not? - Do you feel more motivated to learn online or in a traditional classroom? - Do you enjoy learning online or in a traditional classroom more? - Why do you think this is?
5.	<p>Have there been any challenges for you engaging in the MOOC platform?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If so, what are they? - If so, how do you resolve these – on your own or by contacting the site? If so, is the support from the site helpful? - Are these challenges easily resolved? Why / Why not?
6.	<p>What have you discovered about yourself from the way you prefer to learn from engaging in MOOCs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Your flexibility - When you concentrate best - What you like and dislike about studying, in general
7.	<p>What have you learned about your motivation to learn, in general, from engaging in MOOCs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do you feel more engaged? If so why/why not? - Do you think that learning via MOOCs has helped you to study better? Why? (more interesting/less boring/modern methods/different teachers?)

8.	<p>What do you hope to achieve by participating in MOOCs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can you tell me why?
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Exit

#	Questions:
9.	<p>How would you prefer to study in the future: fully online; fully in class or as a blend of both?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Why? - Why would this suit you: timing of classes? Regularity of classes? Personal interest? New and interesting?

Thank you very much for your contribution today.

Questions in the follow-up semi-structured interviews

NEW	<p>MOOCs have been divided into two parts. In general, cMOOCs adhere to open-learning principles, fostering learner interaction within an open network where participants contribute and collaborate to build knowledge collectively. On the other hand, xMOOCs typically employ a more conventional pedagogical approach, characterised by a teacher-centred learning model. cMOOCs are generally suitable for courses that require students to actively participate, explore, and collaborate, such as certain fields of the humanities, social sciences, and creative arts. xMOOC is usually suitable for courses that require a large-scale delivery of knowledge, specific learning objectives and assessment of learning outcomes, such as engineering, business and science courses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Do you know this? <p>Tell me something about the MOOCs that you used. Do they belong to cMOOC or xMOOC?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Did your universities use their own MOOCs, or did they import from other universities?- Did you interact with other students via MOOCs?<ul style="list-style-type: none">o If yes, in what ways did you interact with students.o Can you see other students on the screen? Did you talk with each other?o Did you enjoy this form of learning?o Why did you like collaborating? / Why did you not enjoy it?o How exactly were you able to collaborate online? How did the collaboration work?
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If not, why is there no interaction?
NEW	<p>TO ADD – Questions on participants’ experience of working online during Covid?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are your memories of MOOCs? Are they good? - What steps did your university take as an immediate reaction to Covid-19? - What kind of online learning took place during Covid? - What kind of MOOCs were offered? <p>(University offered or lectures recommended?)</p> <p>(Was it easy to access? Was it free? Did your university run online programs?)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What other online learning style was offered? - Which online learning method do you prefer? and why? <p>(Explore which online learning methods students preferred during the pandemic, eg. live, recorded, MOOCs)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What MOOCs did you enrol in, and did you complete? - Was there a formal completion process for you? - What was the breakdown of compulsory versus optional courses? - Did you have to complete it? After completing, can you get a certificate or just required by your university. - What do MOOCs or other online learning require of your time management skills? How do you balance your online management skills in order to engage in MOOCs better? - Did your management skills improve and develop? - How do you maintain your study self-discipline without regular classroom observation by the teachers? If so, how did you do this. If not, why did you not do this. What issues are involved?

Experiences

- Could you share some interesting or memorable experiences with MOOCs during the pandemic?
 - o Were there any special MOOCs or teachers that impressed you?
 - o Did you actively participate in online groupwork? How have these activities helped you in your studies?
 - o Did you make good use of the learning resources provided by the MOOC programme, such as video lectures, reading materials and online tests?

- When did the traditional classroom courses return to normal for you at your university?

- Did you choose to continue to participate in MOOCs after the Covid-19 pandemic?

APPENDIX C Questionnaire for Participants

Dear students:

Thank you very much for taking your time to participate in this survey during your busy schedule. This questionnaire aims to explore the current situation and university students' engagement with MOOCs. It is for academic research purposes only. The information you provide will not be made public.

1. What is your gender?

Male

Female

2. Have you ever had any experience of studying on the MOOC platform from the official university MOOC platform?

Often

Occasionally

Never

3. How were you introduced to MOOCs?

Friend introduction

University curriculum arrangement

Teacher recommendation

Know from learning communities such as Youku or Zhihu

Others

4. How many courses you are now learning through MOOCs? (Including university official MOOCs and other MOOCs)

3 or fewer

4-6

7-9

More than 10

5. Why did you choose to study on the MOOC platform?

Self-preparation of school curriculum (or school curriculum itself)

I didn't understand the content of the class in the school

Learn new skills and courses

Others

6. If you choose to learn via MOOCs, what is your course selection criteria?

The Host university must be well-known

The teacher is well-known in academia

Your major curriculum needs

Your own hobbies

Others

7. What factors do you think will affect your participation?

Technology factors such as platform page design, Internet speed

Group factors such as the degree of other participants

Personal influence factors such as personality or available time

Social influence factors such as politics, economic environment

Others

8. Have you encountered any issues when using the MOOC platform?

Internet speeds on foreign websites are slow

Unreliable WIFI on the website

The teacher's lecture style does not meet my taste

Did not learn what I want

Others

9. How does learning on the MOOC platform compared with traditional classroom courses?

MOOCs are not as affective as traditional classes

MOOCs can complement the traditional classroom

MOOCs can replace traditional courses

10. How often do you use MOOC platform to learn?

Learn regularly as the school curriculum progresses

Targeted occasional learning

Just learning before the final exam

11. Why did you choose MOOCs instead of other online learning platforms?

MOOC content is more comprehensive than others

Open for free

More convenient for learning and interactive communication

Easily time-arrangement

University curriculum arrangement

Others

12. What problems do you think currently exist on the MOOC platform?

Cannot get feedback in time after class

Few after-school exercises

Questions raised in the discussion forum were not answered in time

Knowledge explanation is not deep enough

Lack of imported foreign quality courses, lack of relevant quality lectures

Others

13. What do you think using MOOCs will help you to develop and achieve most?

Enhance self-learning ability

Develop reflective ability

Improve information recognition

Increase initiative

14. Open question: In what ways do you think using MOOCs will help you to develop?

Dear teachers:

Thank you very much for taking your time to participate in this survey during your busy schedule. This questionnaire aims to explore the current situation and university students' engagement with MOOCs. It is for academic research purposes only. The information you provide will not be made public.

1. How long have you been teaching?

5 years or fewer

5-10 years

Over 10 years

2. Have you ever had any experience of teaching via MOOC platforms?

Yes

No

3. According to Q2, if no, do you have an interest in starting your own class on the MOOC platforms?

Yes

No

4. According to Q2, if yes, how many courses you have taught on the MOOC platforms?

3 or fewer

4-6

7-9

More than 10

5. What do you think are your students' selection criteria?

The Host university must be well-known

The teacher is well-known in academia

Their professional needs

Their own hobbies

Others

6. What factors do you think will affect your students' participation?

Technology factors such as platform page design, Internet speed

Group factors such as the degree of other participates

Personal influence factors such as personality or available time

Social influence factors such as politics, economic environment

Others

7. What issues did your students encounter when using the MOOCs?

Internet speeds on foreign websites are slow

Inconvenient interaction on the website

The teacher's lecture style does not meet my taste

Did not learn what I want

Others

8. What is the most possible reason your students choose to study on the MOOC platform?

Self-preparation of school curriculum

They didn't understand the content of the class in the school

Learn new skills and courses

Others

9. How does learning on the MOOC platform compared with traditional classroom courses?

MOOCs are not as effective as traditional classes

MOOCs can complement the traditional classroom

MOOCs can replace traditional courses

10. How often do your students use MOOC platform to learn?

Learn regularly as the school curriculum progresses

Targeted occasional learning

Just learning before the final exam

11. Why did your students choose MOOCs instead of other online learning platforms?

MOOC content is more comprehensive than others

Open for free

More convenient for learning and interactive communication

Easily time-arrangement

Others

12. What problems do you think currently exist on the MOOC platform?

Cannot get feedback in time after class

Few after-school exercises

Questions raised in the discussion forum were not answered in time

There is a charge for some premium courses

Knowledge explanation is not deep enough

There is no distinction between different courses in the same subject

Lack of imported foreign quality courses, lack of quality lectures

Others

13. What do you think using MOOCs will help your students to develop or achieve most?

Enhance self-learning ability

Develop reflective ability

Improve information recognition

Increase initiative

14. Open question: In what ways do you think using MOOCs will help your students to develop?

APPENDIX D Data of Semi-structured Interviews

Data from the semi-structured interviews of students from the first target university, which delivers MOOCs officially (During Covid-19)

Participants	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
SIP1 (A)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How were you introduced to MOOCs? -Who introduced you to this kind of learning? <p>In March 2020, during the COVID-19 pandemic, it was really hard to attend class at my university, especially since my university is located in the northern part of China, but my hometown is located in southern China. It will increase the infection rate of coronavirus if I take a plane with a lot of people in a closed cabin space. Then the local government locked down the city where my college was located so my university decided to conduct MOOCs based on the epidemic situation. I had the MOOCs for one year until now. In the beginning, I felt excited when MOOCs took place of the classroom teaching because I did not need to go back to school, and I could stay</p>	Use of MOOCs.	MOOCs can be used in some emergency situation even take place of the traditional classroom teaching.

	<p>longer with my family. Our university has launched other online courses before. I thought MOOCs would be like previous online courses. However, before we started to study at home, our leader professors gave us an introduction to MOOCs, which made us feel more curious about MOOCs. She said it is a new way of learning but not the same as normal online courses we already had. It is more professional and extensional.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were your expectations of MOOCs? -Why did you expect this (based on your previous experience of learning)? <p>I live in the south part of China and my universities are located in the north, which means I can only stay with my family during the summer and winter holidays. I do not like the covid-19 pandemic, but it is a chance that I can accompany my parents more. So, at the beginning, I hope MOOCs and other online courses and online contact with universities and classmates can go on</p>	<p>Marketing and Promotions of MOOCs.</p> <p>Differences between MOOCs and traditional</p>	<p>MOOCs have been promoted by the university and teachers.</p> <p>MOOCs have some advantages, such as students feel more relaxed than in</p>
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	<p>well.</p> <p>After a month of MOOC study, I found that MOOCs have a more relaxed class atmosphere and more interaction between teachers and students. I am surprised about this. However, I am an English major student, I will be an English teacher after graduation during the third year, the university always supports some practise lessons. The MOOCs are not as useful for practise as I expected in this aspect. I know people should not be too absolute, so maybe it is just not good for practise or not suitable for some of the majors that need face-to-face experiments.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your experience of participating in MOOCs? -What did you like about the course(s)? <p>I have other online classes before. In the beginning, I thought MOOCs would be the same, and students just attend to pass the exam and get the grades when they study at home. However, I feel more</p>	<p>classroom teaching.</p> <p>The disadvantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of</p>	<p>classroom.</p> <p>MOOCs are not useful for some courses that need face-to-face interaction.</p> <p>MOOCs provide a</p>
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	<p>relaxed when I participate in MOOCs for a period of time and if I don't understand the course, I can playback the video and self-learn. One problem was that I could not do face-to-face teaching practise. I know everybody has this issue and I fully understand this special situation under covid-19. So I just try to make full use of the theoretical part of the courses and wait for the university to be unlocked to do some practise. I use all my time trying to learn and to do observation during this hard time.</p> <p>Thanks to the professional MOOCs I have the access to achieve more and observe more. Apart from the courses that the university arranged, I can go for more than I am interested in. My classmates also recommend other MOOCs on the platform that they already attended, they are interesting and different from traditional online courses that may be just recorded from a class. Some of them are from American universities, which has different teaching style and content. One more important thing is that they are all free!</p>	<p>MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>more relaxed learning atmosphere.</p> <p>Students can review the MOOCs again and again.</p> <p>Teachers on MOOCs may have different teaching styles and most of the courses are free.</p>
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	<p>-Has it been positive? If so, why / why not?</p> <p>Yes, it has. Although I have fewer chances to practise, I have more chances to put up questions or interact with my classmates, even though I think MOOCs make the class more ‘active’.</p> <p>It’s a new try for both the teachers and the students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How often do you participate in these courses? <p>-Can you tell me why, or what, affects how often (regularly) you participate?</p> <p>Because the students can take credits if attending the MOOCs, I usually take classes twice a week.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When? At what time of day? <p>-Can you tell me why these times suit you? What affects the time of your participation?</p> <p>I choose the time by my living habits, one at 9:30 am, one at 14:00 pm. Almost the same class schedule as I study at the</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>Factors influences the MOOC completion.</p>	<p>MOOCs make the class more active.</p> <p>MOOCs are relevant to credits and graduation.</p>
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	<p>university.</p> <p>At 9:30 am. in the morning, I have a clear head and can be fully occupied with the course and be more concentrated. At 14:00 pm, after I finish noontime snooze and have the energy to study. I chose these two periods as the university would also help me to adjust to the school hours once the lockdown finished.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What motivates you to attend and participate in MOOCs? -Is it just the time of the online courses? Is their regularity/ (how often)? <p>Yes, I should attend online courses at the predestined time and the teacher will make a roll call sometimes. It is relevant to my graduation. All right it is just a small reason anyway. MOOCs are different from traditional classroom teaching. Maybe it will be stopped when the lockdown finishes, so I want to grasp the chances to learn more from MOOCs, meet a lot of teachers and get more information. This motivates me the most.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>Factors that may influence students' engagement.</p>	<p>The times of MOOCs delivery are flexible.</p> <p>MOOCs can be arranged on students' own time.</p> <p>University or teacher requirements.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible, students can learn via MOOCs whenever and wherever students are.</p>
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	<p>-Is it related to your previous experience of classroom learning?</p> <p>Yes, it's related but expands more content and aspects. For me, MOOCs and classroom teaching can meet different targeted needs. When I take MOOCs during this special time, what I need to do is to recognise the advantages of MOOCs and make full use of them. For example, I can do more observations of more teachers, but I cannot practise teaching like I used to do in the classroom. Then I just do what is the right thing now.</p> <p>-do you feel that classroom learning is enough for you?</p> <p>It depends on... As an English major student, I need more chances to take tests and practise how to teach face-to-face. This is why I prefer to study in class. However, I also need to learn teaching theories and do more reading and observation. In this case, MOOCs are useful as well. It is better to combine</p>	<p>The advantages and challenges of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages and challenges of MOOCs.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs provide more observation and less practise.</p> <p>MOOCs cannot provide learning environment as classroom teaching do but also useful in other aspects.</p>
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	<p>them.</p> <p>-Do you want to learn further, or in a different way from traditional classroom learning? If so, why?</p> <p>To be honest, I prefer traditional classroom learning more, and I like the interaction between students and teachers. However, I also accept MOOCs and other online courses, because I know education is getting diversified.</p> <p>-Is this why you chose MOOC/online learning?</p> <p>-Is it better for you to learn at a different, or a particular time? Why?</p> <p>The MOOCs are more flexible than the traditional classes. So, yes, it's better for us to learn at a different time.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you feel that you engage better with online or with traditional classroom learning? <p>-Why? / Why not?</p>	<p>The disadvantages of MOOC and the possible future of MOOCs.</p> <p>MOOCs are very flexible.</p>	<p>MOOCs may be combined with traditional classroom teaching in the future and even with other new teaching ways.</p> <p>MOOCs can be arranged on students' own time.</p>
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	<p>I feel better engaged in the traditional class. As I said, I am an English major student, I need more chances to practise English with classmates and teachers and make more progress. I need to stand in front of real people and give a speech or lesson. It cannot get the same reflection when done online. This is why I prefer to study in class.</p> <p>-Do you feel more motivated to learn online or in a traditional classroom?</p> <p>In traditional classrooms.</p> <p>-Do you enjoy learning online or in a traditional classroom more?</p> <p>-Why do you think this is?</p> <p>I enjoy learning in a traditional classroom. It can build a teaching atmosphere. We have some tests and practise in class, and we can vividly feel the practice and progress of ourselves.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have there been any challenges for you engaging in the MOOC 	<p>MOOCs are different from traditional classroom teaching. These two teaching methods all have advantages and challenges.</p> <p>Challenges of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs need to support more interaction between teachers and students. (MOOCs have challenges in the delivery of some specific subjects that need more interaction.)</p> <p>MOOCs need to support more interaction between teachers and students.</p>
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	<p>platform?</p> <p>-If so, what are they?</p> <p>For the practise part, we can only watch the videos of some other teachers but cannot do it by ourselves. We also have some theoretical classes, which can be launched online but we also need some time to adjust ourselves from the different teaching styles and materials. Not all the courses are recorded by our own teachers. Actually, I expect the courses from my own teachers, because they know us well and the courses may be more targeted, just like we are in our classroom.</p> <p>-If so, how do you resolve these – on your own or by contacting the site? If so, is the support from the site helpful?</p> <p>Honestly, nothing to do. I can only wait for the school information until the university opens.</p> <p>-Are these challenges easily resolved? Why / Why not?</p> <p>No...I can't find a classroom of students.</p> <p>For other issues with MOOCs themselves.</p>	<p>Challenges of MOOCs.</p> <p>Challenges of</p>	<p>MOOCs need to support more interaction between teachers and students.</p>
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	<p>It can be adjusted better when students are taking more courses and have more experience in it.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you discovered about yourself from the way you prefer to learn from engaging in MOOCs? <p>-Your flexibility</p> <p>Yes. I can even study lying on the bed. That's so relaxing. I can also choose my own interested courses as much I as can.</p> <p>-When you concentrate best?</p> <p>At 9:30 in the morning.</p> <p>-What you like and dislike about studying, in general</p> <p>I like the flexibility of the studying time, but I dislike the boring way of my teacher online sometimes, she just talks and talks but I can understand her, I know she can't show us how to arrange a classroom either at home.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you learned about your motivation to learn, in general, 	<p>MOOCs.</p> <p>MOOCs are very flexible.</p> <p>Challenges of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs need to support more interaction between teachers and students.</p> <p>MOOCs can be used whenever and wherever students want.</p> <p>MOOCs need to support more interaction between teachers and students.</p>
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	<p>from engaging in MOOCs?</p> <p>-Do you feel more engaged? If so why/why not?</p> <p>No. I feel better engaged in the traditional class.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you think that learning via MOOCs has helped you to study better? Why? (more interesting/less boring/modern methods/ different teachers?) <p>No. I feel better engaged in the traditional class. I want more interactions with teachers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What do you hope to achieve by participating in MOOCs? -Can you tell me why? <p>I hope to achieve more interaction in the MOOCs. Maybe there will be some new online interactive sections that make students interested and motivated in the future. Well, the main point is it needs to have usefulness and practicality.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How would you prefer to study in 	<p>MOOCs are different from traditional classroom teaching and has some disadvantages.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p> <p>MOOCs have some challenges.</p>	<p>MOOCs need to support more interaction between teachers and students.</p> <p>MOOCs need to support more interaction between teachers and students.</p> <p>MOOCs also need to have usefulness and practicality.</p>
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	<p>the future: fully online; fully in class or as a blend of both?</p> <p>-Why?</p> <p>I prefer fully in class. But as a trend of the development of society and education. I know there will be a combination of online and offline courses. I also expected.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why would this suit you: timing of classes? Regularity of classes? Personal interest? New and interesting? <p>New and interesting. I learn what I wanted. I know in my university I also need theoretical learning but not practise all the time. In this aspect, MOOC content is fun and rich.</p>	<p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p> <p>Advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs may be combined with traditional classroom teaching in the future.</p> <p>MOOCs are fun and contain rich resources.</p>
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Participants	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
SIP2 (B)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How were you introduced to MOOCs? <p>-Who introduced you to this kind of learning?</p> <p>During the Covid-19 pandemic, I cannot back to university. Not only me but all the cities lockdown to make people safe. Our university announced to change teaching online and deliver MOOCs instead of classroom teaching, it was the best way for everybody at that moment. But actually, it is not my first time taking MOOCs. In order to apply for study abroad after graduation, I signed up for English MOOCs for the first time. It was about two years ago. I got information on this kind of learning platform from the internet, and some are found through some ads. You know ads are everywhere, because of the big data... Oh, my friends also recommend some good courses they took for me. At the beginning, I thought these may not be as good as I expected because there are a lot of courses that are not official and authoritative in our daily lives. To</p>	Promotions of MOOCs.	MOOCs have been widely accepted. MOOCs have been promoted by teachers and ads.

	<p>be honest, I even did not expect much. I know some online courses are free at the beginning and when it comes to the knowledge point, it starts to take tuition fees. But this is delivered by our university, I think it will be free and structured. Another aspect I thought much about is that I am afraid that online courses are not as useful as traditional classroom teaching. For Chinese students, you know, most of the students are used to teacher-centered teaching methods. Online courses are not the main learning ways till these years. Students who have less autonomous learning ability may not perform well in online courses. However, after I took MOOCs, I found it felt pretty good to study here, the courses are interesting, and the teachers are local people who are well-experienced.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were your expectations of MOOCs? <p>-Why did you expect this (based on your previous experience of learning)?</p> <p>For me, the main reason I chose MOOCs is that I know some MOOCs come from</p>	<p>Familiarities with MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs are different from the normal online courses that students may not know.</p>
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	<p>some American universities. What I really need is that I can improve my speaking skill by learning from traditional American speakers or getting content that is relevant to local news. I thought MOOCs may be better than some normal online courses. Another reason is that some of my friends are also taking the courses here. They already introduce some details to me, in other words, they already test the quality of the courses. So, through attending the courses, I hoped that I could practice my speaking and listening skills, as well as understand more about American speaking style. Apart from that, I also expected to know more about the local culture there. Hopefully, these will help me adapt to life studying there.</p> <p>I also had some oral English courses in university before but only for one semester, which was not enough actually. I believe the most important process to improve speaking skills is to practise as much as possible. In other words, we must put ourselves into an</p>	<p>The diverse roles of MOOCs.</p> <p>MOOCs are different from other normal online courses.</p>	<p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching or other online teaching in some specific area, such as foreign languages learning.</p>
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	<p>English-speaking atmosphere. Not all the students are lucky enough to have an English learning background while they grow up so I expect I can solve this problem via MOOCs because MOOCs contain rich resources. Students can choose whatever they want there.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your experience of participating in MOOCs? -What did you like about the course(s)? <p>Actually, I have had other online course experiences before. In the beginning, I thought this was just another kind of online course, but after learning more about MOOC, I found MOOCs are more targeted and well-organised, also, more professional and detailed. I have joined MOOCs on different platforms. Some have interesting content; some give professional suggestions about how to improve their English-speaking skills.</p> <p>I feel happy and enjoy it when my teachers share their local culture and interesting stories with us. MOOCs are flexible and include a huge amount of</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs provide rich resources.</p> <p>MOOCs are more targeted, well-organised, more professional and detailed than other online courses.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible</p>
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	<p>learning materials and resources. Traditional classroom teaching has limited time and chance to practise. Students only speak English during the two-hour class, which is not enough. However, MOOCs support richer content, and I can play back again and again and even change resources one by one, which made me really enjoy it. That's much more surprising than I expected before the course started.</p> <p>-Has it been positive? If so, why / why not?</p> <p>It's positive because it brings me confidence in speaking English. In previous classroom teaching, we attached more importance to written English instead of oral English. I believe, that in order to improve speaking skills, students need to open their mouths as much as possible. In addition, I am a shy person. I usually be quiet when I am with other students. I am afraid of making mistakes. Therefore, MOOCs are really useful for me because I can study and practise at home, follow the</p>	<p>MOOCs.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>and provide rich resources.</p> <p>MOOCs can be reviewed at any time.</p> <p>MOOC learning experiences are positive to shy students.</p> <p>The time of deliveries is flexible. MOOCs</p>
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	<p>teachers and practise more by myself.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How often do you participate in these courses? <p>-Can you tell me why, or what, affects how often (regularly) you participate?</p> <p>I take MOOCs twice to four times a week. I have to accomplish my usual study work which is of higher priority to me.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When? At what time of day? <p>-Can you tell me why these times suit you? What affects the time of your participation?</p> <p>I can choose my own time, so I always attend every Tuesday and Thursday at around 8:00 p.m.</p> <p>1) For me, nighttime is always quiet and calm and suitable for me to learn.</p> <p>2) Considering the time difference between China and America. Sometimes I can also watch some live channels.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What motivates you to attend and 	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>can be arranged on students' own time.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible, it can be arranged on students' own time.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible and MOOC completion can be influenced by students' initial thoughts on when select.</p>
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	<p>participate in MOOCs?</p> <p>-Is it just the time of the online courses? Is their regularity/ (how often)?</p> <p>No, it is not much about the time. I think the expectations of MOOC learning motivate me and my plan to study abroad motivates me a lot. During my MOOC study, I improved my speaking. I got what I expected. I also get credits from the MOOCs that our university launched. These are relevant to my graduation.</p> <p>-Is it related to your previous experience of classroom learning?</p> <p>It's related but expands more content and aspects. In the classroom, I am the kind of person who just follows what the teachers ask me to do but now I can choose more useful courses I really need.</p> <p>-do you feel that classroom learning is enough for you?</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>Factors influencing MOOC completion.</p> <p>MOOCs are different from traditional classroom teaching.</p>	<p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs are relevant to credits and graduation.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p>
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<p>I think classroom learning is not enough sometimes. It depends on...I believe different students have different learning needs. Classroom learning cannot meet everybody's needs. However, I know that is a traditional teaching method. It can satisfy everybody's needs, and the teacher-centered teaching method is the direct way to impart knowledge. So that classroom learning is also unplaceable. I hope these two can combine well in the future.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">-Do you want to learn further, or in a different way from traditional classroom learning? If so, why?</p> <p>Yes, because I want to try different learning methods and styles. Education needs to be developed with technology. We all can see that traditional classrooms suddenly cannot continue due to the Covid-19 pandemic. So, more and more different teaching ways need to be developed.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">-Is this why you chose</p>	<p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs may be combined with traditional classroom teaching methods in the future.</p>
	<p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs may be combined with traditional classroom teaching and other teaching methods in the future.</p>

	<p>MOOCs/online learning?</p> <p>-Is it better for you to learn at a different, or a particular time? Why?</p> <p>Yes, I think a particular time is better for me because this can help arrange the timetable better according to my own plan. I like making plans.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you feel that you engage better with online or with traditional classroom learning? -Why? / Why not? <p>I think online and traditional classroom learning both have merits and demerits. For me, I prefer online learning. It creates a more relaxed atmosphere for shy students like me. I feel I participate more in MOOCs than in traditional classroom learning.</p> <p>-Do you feel more motivated to learn online or in a traditional classroom?</p> <p>Online actually.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>MOOCs are very flexible, and students can arrange MOOCs by their own timetable.</p> <p>MOOCs are different from traditional classroom teaching. These two teaching methods all have advantages and challenges.</p>	<p>Both MOOCs and traditional classroom teaching have advantages and challenges. Some shy students can participant better in MOOCs.</p>
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	<p>-Do you enjoy learning online or in a traditional classroom more?</p> <p>-Why do you think this is?</p> <p>I enjoy learning online because sometimes it's like I am talking with my friend on the phone. It brings me relaxation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have there been any challenges for you engaging in the MOOC platform? <p>-If so, what are they?</p> <p>Yeah of course. For example, the internet connection is not so good sometimes and the teaching styles in some of the MOOCs are different than what I get used to in class. I also feel tired when I watch the screen for a while. The different teachers have different teaching styles, especially some teachers are from foreign countries. I need time to adjust myself.</p> <p>-If so, how do you resolve these – on your own or by contacting the site? If so, is the support from the site helpful?</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>Factors may influence students' MOOC engagement.</p>	<p>MOOCs are flexible. It can make some students feel relax.</p> <p>MOOCs have some challenges in Internet access and physical health for learners. Learners also have to spend more time with different teachers' teaching styles.</p>
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On my own. I think most of the students may choose to resolve the online problem on their own. Because when you contact the website, it takes a lot of time to reply, reply and reply once and once again.

-Are these challenges easily resolved? Why / Why not?

I think **this is not a big issue because normally it goes well.** For teaching styles, I think students need to adapt to different teaching styles. It is also a good chance to improve themselves. I know teachers cannot meet everybody's needs even in the classroom.

- What have you **discovered about yourself** from the way you **prefer to learn** from engaging in MOOCs?
 - Your flexibility
 - When you concentrate best?
 - What you like and dislike about studying, in general?

I found that the more I participate, the more confident I become. I can make full use of MOOCs' advantages and

	<p>adjust myself to keep a good learning condition. I can choose the time and the courses freely and flexibly to keep the most concentrated condition. I can even choose the courses I like. I can change the courses as soon as I find it will not help that saves a lot of time. I like MOOCs in general. Although sometimes I meet some small issues as I mentioned above, no worries, I still enjoy.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you learned about your motivation to learn, in general, from engaging in MOOCs? -Do you feel more engaged? If so why/why not? <p>Yes, because it's more targeted and interesting.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you think that learning via MOOC has helped you to study better? Why? (more interesting/less boring/modern methods/ different teachers?) <p>It helped me to do better in some respects because classroom learning is more based on books. However, in MOOCs,</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>MOOCs are</p>	<p>MOOCs can help increase students' confidence.</p> <p>MOOCs have some</p>
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	<p>it's more of a learning method than as student- oriented. I can decide almost everything for myself.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you hope to achieve by participating in MOOCs? -Can you tell me why? <p>I hope to improve my concentration and interest in the subject and help me achieve my goals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How would you prefer to study in the future: fully online; fully in class or as a blend of both? -Why? <p>As a blend of both. We need to have online courses when we cannot go to class, for example, the covid-19 pandemic results in home-based work and study. However, traditional class is absolutely necessary, because we also need to have face-to-face communication with our teachers and classmates on some issues such as completing some papers or teamwork. A blend of both will be a good way for different kinds of students to achieve</p>	<p>different from traditional classroom teaching and has some advantages.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>advantages that help students increase their ability on autonomous learning.</p> <p>MOOCs can help students achieve their aims.</p> <p>MOOCs can be better combined with traditional classroom teaching.</p> <p>Combing MOOCs with traditional classroom teaching</p>
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	<p>more. Do not just leave the MOOCs even if Covid-19 is getting better, students are getting used to this anyway. So why not keep launching?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why would this suit you: timing of classes? Regularity of classes? Personal interest? New and interesting? <p>I think all of these. MOOCs have a lot of advantages, they have flexible time for classes, it meets students' personal interests, and even a new and interesting learning method itself.</p>		<p>could help students to do better in their study.</p>
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APPENDIX E Data of Semi-structured Interviews

Data from the semi-structured interviews of students from the second target university, which not delivers MOOCs officially (During Covid-19)

Participants	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
SIP1 (C)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How were you introduced to MOOCs? -Who introduced you to this kind of learning? <p>MOOCs are very popular ways of education these days, so I know something about it before I actually join in. Although our university did not launch MOOCs, we still use it sometimes. I was recommended to take the MOOCs by a good friend of mine. Before I took the MOOCs, I thought it would be similar to other online courses I have ever used before. Just like some recorded lessons with a knowledge points list. But after several courses, I found it interesting and different.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What were your expectations of MOOCs? -Why did you expect this (based 	<p>Promotions of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs have been widely accepted.</p> <p>MOOCs can be promoted by friends and classmates.</p>

	<p>on your previous experience of learning)?</p> <p>Because I have had other online learning experiences before, my expectations for the MOOCs were that there would be more interaction with the teacher during the class and that there would be a teaching assistant to follow up on our academic progress regularly. The main reason for my expectation is that I found that most of the online university courses are like taking a break, students do not think importance of the lessons and just do what they want. Although MOOCs are convenient and not limited by time and space, there is less contact with the teacher as well, such as in terms of eye contact and classroom atmosphere, and I am worried that I will not be able to get feedback from the teacher on how well I have understood and digested the course content. You know, most Chinese learners are used to traditional teaching ways and just those who have higher motivation can adjust time well for self-online learning. Whether they have high self-control ability or not,</p>	<p>Differences between traditional classroom teaching and MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages and disadvantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs require students to have higher self-learning awareness and ability.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible and break the limitation of time and space.</p> <p>Students may not have enough self-learning awareness, and the MOOC platform cannot provide teaching assistance or feedback on time.</p>
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	<p>feedback is important.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your experience of participating in MOOCs? -What did you like about the course(s)? <p>Because of the COVID-19 outbreak, offline classes were suspended and replaced with online courses in China. MOOCs can provide a good sense of experience for learners, as there is no contact with each other during this special period of Covid-19. Everybody feels safe and satisfied. I started to join in MOOCs as well. The course is not controlled by time and space, which allows me to rationalise my own time. I found it has lots of advantages. MOOC platforms can support more resources for learners than traditional teachers. Using MOOCs can make learning time more flexible and efficient, and also develop learners' self-reflection ability. However, I think most Chinese learners treated MOOCs as a complement to the traditional classroom not an exactly individual teaching method.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs are flexible and convenient for long-distance teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs can be used whenever and wherever students want.</p> <p>Most learners regard MOOCs as a supplement traditional classroom learning, but not a learning tool.</p>
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	<p>-Has it been positive? If so, why / why not?</p> <p>Yes. Because I can choose to come to class in the mornings and evenings when I am at my best mentally, avoiding the sleepier afternoon hours, and I can schedule some outdoor activities in the afternoon. This way I can balance school and leisure throughout the day. MOOCs enable me to study at home and can save time. I think it will be more interesting and relaxed. MOOCs are convenient and flexible as well. When some parts of the content are unclear, it can be easily playback and learn again.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How often do you participate in these courses? <p>-Can you tell me why, or what, affects how often (regularly) you participate?</p> <p>I have MOOCs three days a week. The factors that influence me are generally the university schedule and my own desire to allow myself to take some time</p>	<p>Perceptions of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs are flexible and result in positive learning experiences and reactions of the students.</p> <p>MOOCs led to efficient time</p>
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	<p>to break.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When? At what time of day? -Can you tell me why these times suit you? What affects the time of your participation? <p>9: 00 a.m. in the morning and 8:00 p.m. This is because these times I have a lot of energy and focus. The main factors affecting the timing of online classes are on the one hand that the school has a fixed schedule of classes, and on the other hand that I myself take my state of mind into account.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What motivates you to attend and participate in MOOCs? -Is it just the time of the online courses? Is their regularity/ (how often)? <p>Adjusting the learning method during the Covid-19 pandemic and then preparing for graduation is the most important reason. Others are such as learning something new and not wasting time. I have MOOCs three days a week on average.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>Factors that may influence students'</p>	<p>arrangements for students.</p> <p>MOOCs can be used whenever and wherever students want.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible.</p> <p>Credits and graduation conditions may influence.</p>
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	<p>-Is it related to your previous experience of classroom learning?</p> <p>There is certainly something about it. Transforming offline courses into online instruction and combining them is a good way for students.</p> <p>-do you feel that classroom learning is enough for you?</p> <p>The classroom learning is good, but I also want to try something else to get the knowledge together.</p> <p>-Do you want to learn further, or in a different way from traditional classroom learning? If so, why?</p> <p>I am willing to experiment with new teaching methods. With the development of time and technology, traditional offline education should also change with it. It can help students to adapt to the world better.</p>	<p>engagement.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p> <p>Perceptions of MOOCs.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>To combine MOOCs and traditional classroom teaching together.</p> <p>MOOCs help students to increase their awareness of education development.</p> <p>MOOCs will also be developed with the development of technology.</p>
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	<p>-Is this why you chose MOOC/online learning?</p> <p>-Is it better for you to learn at a different, or a particular time? Why?</p> <p>A better way, of course. Apart from the education industry, all sectors are now bringing new experiences to people through high-tech means. For people to break the space-time limit and gain more freedom of choice.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you feel that you engage better with online or with traditional classroom learning? -Why? / Why not? <p>I like online classes because I like the freedom to organise my time. But I know I need traditional classroom learning. Because I do online learning back at home, it is hard for me to focus on it. I'm easily distracted. I feel sleepy most of the time when I have MOOCs. Maybe I feel more relaxed staying at home. I just need to hold a computer and let the camera face straight up to my face, in the living room, bathroom or in</p>	<p>The advantages and disadvantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOC learning atmosphere is not as active as traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>bed. The traditional classroom provides me with the environment to concentrate on my learning. I feel that I engage better with traditional classroom learning. I like eye contact with my classmates and teacher. I like the human interaction, the laughter, the impassioned speech held by my teacher, and the chance to stand up on the stage in front of my classmates and make a PPT. Oh, I really miss the day when I was in class. I will try to combine them better and find a good way for myself.</p> <p>-Do you feel more motivated to learn online or in a traditional classroom?</p> <p>MOOCs will give me more motivation because it is a new learning method for participants.</p> <p>-Do you enjoy learning online or in a traditional classroom more?</p> <p>-Why do you think this is?</p> <p>I would prefer to learn more through online classes. Online classes don't just free up the students, they free up the</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs enable flexibility for times of learning.</p>
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	<p>teachers too. I can learn from teachers from different schools and even different subjects through online classes.</p> <p>Exposure to high-quality teaching and open horizons. My teachers consider that the students will get bored staying at home during the Covid-19 pandemic, also recommend we take MOOCs, such as DIY handcraft, appreciation of Chinese art, Yoga, psychological counselling, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have there been any challenges for you engaging in the MOOC platform? -If so, what are they? <p>There may be less interaction with the teacher. I think the problem that exists with MOOCs is not the MOOC itself but how learners and teachers treat MOOCs.</p> <p>Most people consider online courses not as important as traditional classroom teaching and do not think highly of MOOCs. They may believe the education developed from offline to online will happen in the next generation, which may not influence them now. This shows that MOOCs also have challenges</p>	<p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs can fulfil the students' needs of time and rich resources.</p> <p>MOOCs need a better combination with traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>for students. Unlike traditional classroom teaching, MOOCs and other online courses need students to be more self-motivated, because they cannot support an active learning atmosphere, so students are easy to be absent-minded. This may be what to develop in the next stage.</p> <p>-If so, how do you resolve these – on your own or by contacting the site? If so, is the support from the site helpful?</p> <p>Teachers can be contacted online and strengthen the supervision and feedback. Students need to improve their awareness of self-learning and accept new teaching methods.</p> <p>-Are these challenges easily resolved? Why / Why not?</p> <p>I think it is very easy to solve. As long as the teacher gives some time to arrange some guidance for solving the problem. With the development of society and technology, students also know what will happen next and adjust themselves.</p>	<p>The disadvantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs have challenges on some specific subjects that needs more interaction or supervision.</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you discovered about yourself from the way you prefer to learn from engaging in MOOCs? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Your flexibility -When you concentrate best -What you like and dislike about studying, in general <p>I find myself to be a person who can organise my time wisely. In the early mornings and evenings. I have a lot of energy and concentration, which is perfect for studying. For studying, I like to learn something new and fresh, and I don't like to deal with boring exams. MOOCs can also help me with small pieces of time management in order not to waste time anymore.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you learned about your motivation to learn, in general, from engaging in MOOCs? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Do you feel more engaged? If so why/why not? • Do you think that learning via 		<p>The advantages of MOOCs are flexible and help to make use of small pieces of time.</p>
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	<p>MOOCs has helped you to study better? Why? (more interesting/less boring/modern methods/ different teachers?)</p> <p>Of course, I will be more motivated to participate in MOOCs. Because online classes give me more freedom of choice. It certainly helped me. The new format of the online classes is a break from traditional offline teaching and saves time travelling to and from school, which helps me to make full use of time and resources.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you hope to achieve by participating in MOOCs? -Can you tell me why? <p>On the one hand, I am learning in a practical way what my teachers have taught me, and on the other hand, I hope I can adapt to this advanced teaching method, as I believe this is the future trend in the world. Using MOOCs helps students feel free and relaxed when learning and makes us more focused because we do not need to pay more attention to the environment or the</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs are flexible.</p> <p>MOOCs help students to form good learning habits and improve their autonomous learning ability.</p>
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	<p>relationship with other students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How would you prefer to study in the future: fully online; fully in class or as a blend of both? -Why? • Why would this suit you: timing of classes? Regularity of classes? Personal interest? New and interesting? <p>I would like to be able to combine online and offline. On the one hand, I enjoy the convenience of online teaching, and on the other hand, I like the atmosphere of a class where the teacher and students learn and share. This not only gives us the freedom to organise our own time but also deepens our connection with the teacher and our classmates, learning and promoting human interaction between teachers and students. Some normal courses can be delivered well on MOOC platforms while some are not. Some of the subjects need teachers and students to have knowledge collision or discussion in order to have good learning outcomes. Some personalised questions require face-to-face communication and quick</p>	<p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>To be combined with traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>sparks of communication that are not easily achieved by online typing.</p> <p>MOOCs cannot guarantee some instantaneous feelings. This needs better instructions and guidance.</p>		
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Participants	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
SIP2 (D)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How were you introduced to MOOCs? -Who introduced you to this kind of learning? <p>Our university did not have our own MOOCs. One of my roommates introduced me to this. She told me she had been learning for a year and it was really helpful, so she recommended it to me.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What were your expectations of MOOCs? -Why did you expect this (based on your previous experience of learning)? <p>Honestly, I didn't expect that much, because I'm not used to online learning. I could get distracted sometimes, even when in the classroom and face-to-face teaching model, so I think MOOCs may not be very helpful for me. But I decided to give it a try.</p>	<p>Promotions of MOOCs.</p> <p>Factors may influence the engagement of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs have been widely accepted. It can be promoted by students' friends and classmates.</p> <p>MOOCs require students to be focused.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your experience of participating in MOOCs? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -What did you like about the course(s)? -Has it been positive? If so, why / why not? • How often do you participate in these courses? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Can you tell me why, or what, affects how often (regularly) you participate? • When? At what time of day? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Can you tell me why these times suit you? What affects the time of your participation? <p>They're interesting. For example, if you have a hobby or field of interest, it might be hard to find related learning opportunities at school, MOOCs can help you decide if a specific field of study is right for you. I normally participate in those courses during weekends, cause I'm busy with my studies and my part-time job from Monday to Friday, so I will use my weekends to learn something that I'm interested in. Normally afternoon or</p>	<p>Flexibility of MOOCs.</p> <p>The diverse roles of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs can be used whenever and wherever students want.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching</p>
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	<p>night, because I'm not an early type. I'm not a disciplined person either, I will participate in these courses all depending on my mood... but normally twice or three times a week.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What motivates you to attend and participate in MOOCs? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Is it just the time of the online courses? Is their regularity/(how often)? -Is it related to your previous experience of classroom learning? -Is it related to your previous experience of classroom learning? -do you feel that classroom learning is enough for you? -Do you want to learn further, or in a different way from traditional classroom learning? If so, why? -Is this why you chose MOOC/online learning? -Is it better for you to learn at a different, or a particular time? 	<p>in some specific areas that students are more interested in.</p>
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	<p>Why?</p> <p>In the beginning, it was my curiosity... then I found I can control the time of the online courses, so it is easy and more convenient. Because of the Covid-19 pandemic, online teaching and learning have become the trend... However, I still prefer the old-school traditional classroom learning, for me, MOOCs can only at best provide information in a very convenient form and that's it, nothing more. I view MOOCs only as a source of additional information that will never replace hard work on understanding this information with the purpose of its active application in practice.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you feel that you engage better with online or with traditional classroom learning? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Why? / Why not? -Do you feel more motivated to learn online or in a traditional classroom? -Do you enjoy learning online or in a traditional classroom more? 	<p>Advantages and challenges of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs are convenience, flexible and can provide rich resources.</p> <p>MOOCs cannot provide learning environment as classroom teaching do.</p> <p>MOOCs have challenges on some specific subjects that require more interaction between teachers and students.</p>
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	<p>-Why do you think this is?</p> <p>As I mentioned above, I still think a traditional classroom is better. I believe the traditional face-to-face classroom will not be replaced by MOOCs, but it is a kind of traditional teaching mode that is a good supplement, we listen to a way of elite teachers teaching. But, like anything in real life, nothing is purely black or white and all have their good points and flaws. For me, MOOCs help you control your time, you get to choose it flexible, however, there is a sense of loneliness in MOOCs, and there is a lack of face-to-face communication between teachers and students and also students to students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have there been any challenges for you engaging in the MOOC platform? <p>-If so, what are they?</p> <p>-If so, how do you resolve these – on your own or by contacting the site? If so, is the support from the site helpful?</p> <p>-Are these challenges easily</p>	<p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p> <p>MOOCs have some challenges.</p>	<p>MOOCs can complement the traditional classroom.</p> <p>MOOCs lack face-to-face communication between teachers and students and also students to students.</p>
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	<p>resolved? Why / Why not?</p> <p>What may be challenging for me is that I have many hobbies and interests. Faced with so many courses, I didn't know how to make a choice, plus I didn't have enough time and energy... so I chose what I was most interested in, or what was right(useful)at that time, one course or two courses at a time, MOOCs can be very useful and also very time-consuming if you really want to learn a thing or two.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you discovered about yourself from the way you prefer to learn from engaging in MOOCs? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Your flexibility -When you concentrate best -What you like and dislike about studying, in general <p>For me, I learned that for any course, I will need a plan, if you want to take a course, you need to know the courses you are going to take, know what you want to learn, know what you want to do in the first place, and then go for it.</p>	<p>MOOCs have some challenges.</p> <p>Factors may influence students' engagement with MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs have rich learning resources so students may not be able to choose the most suitable one they need.</p> <p>MOOCs require students to have the self-learning ability.</p> <p>MOOCs will be considered good for supporting hobbies.</p> <p>MOOC learning also needs to be prepared and make learning</p>
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	<p>In addition, every course will finish at the end. You can't spend all your time on one course. You need to plan your study schedule. Don't waste time and energy on one thing that can be done all at once. I also learned that I concentrate best at night and quiet environment.</p> <p>Like:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Saving your time by taking notes. If you want to review the course, you can just refer to the previous lesson. 2. Not limited by classroom size so that a good teacher can have the most students in the classroom at the same time. 3. Flexible Time. Make the most of it. 4. The best thing is that you can adjust the speed of the teacher's speech to meet the needs of different students. <p>Dislike:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The recording is a waste of time, and the class lacks interactivity. 2. The quality of the course is very high, and the difficulty must be taken into account when recording. 3. The assessment standards are 	<p>Advantages and disadvantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>plans.</p> <p>Advantage of MOOCs:</p> <p>saving students' time taking notes.</p> <p>not limited by classroom size.</p> <p>flexible.</p> <p>adjusting the speed of the teacher's speech.</p> <p>Disadvantages of MOOCs:</p> <p>the class lacks interactivity.</p>
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	<p>unified and can only be assessed through the final exam and exercises after class.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you learned about your motivation to learn, in general, from engaging in MOOCs? -Do you feel more engaged? If so why/why not? • Do you think that learning via MOOCs has helped you to study better? Why? (more interesting/less boring/modern methods/ different teachers?) <p>I want to learn more and also learn how to manage and invest my time efficiently and how to balance time output between work and rest. I need a scientific schedule and a list of tasks that work for me. I learned critical thinking and reflection. It looks like I'm learning, but the real question is how much am I really learning? It looks like I've got the certificate, but do I really know what the course is? It looks like I'm busy, but is it all paying off?</p> <p>Sure, it helps, I tried to make</p>	<p>The diverse roles of MOOCs.</p>	<p>there are difficulties when recording.</p> <p>assessment standards are unified.</p> <p>Making full use of MOOCs can help students reform their cognitive habits and improve their learning ability.</p> <p>-learn how to manage and invest time efficiently.</p> <p>-learn how to</p>
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	<p>adjustments to different learning methods, different courses, and teachers and also constantly reform my cognitive habits and improve my learning ability.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you hope to achieve by participating in MOOCs? -Can you tell me why? <p>Learn as much as I can. There is still so much I don't know and need to learn about the world. Treat each task seriously at all times. It would be nice if I got certifications, but I truly learned something is important.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How would you prefer to study in the future: fully online; fully in class or as a blend of both? -Why? • Why would this suit you: timing of classes? Regularity of classes? Personal interest? New and interesting? <p>I prefer to study as a blend of both. You can never replace the traditional face-to-face teaching method, we need</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The possible future of</p>	<p>balance time output between work and rest.</p> <p>- learn critical thinking and reflection.</p> <p>MOOCs will help students to achieve more if they treat each task seriously and are eager to gain knowledge.</p> <p>MOOCs will become more and</p>
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	<p>to connect with others, we need to get physical interaction which online courses can never provide. MOOCs give you access to learn something you may hardly know in a traditional classroom. It is also a great opportunity for those who are willing to learn and enrich their knowledge. Maybe not every course is satisfactory, but most of them are great. So, my suggestion is to learn the things you are interested in by MOOCs and using your spare time. But I felt I engaged better in a traditional classroom, with my classmates and teachers and all those interactions and discussions.</p>	<p>MOOCs.</p>	<p>more authoritative if certificates can be awarded to students at the end of the courses.</p> <p>MOOCs need a better combination with traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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FURTHER DISCUSSIONS WITH PARTICIPANTS (ABCD):

Q1- Is there any difference between your online classes and more open MOOCs?

That is, American MOOCs and Chinese MOOCs?

PARTICIPANT A

I think MOOCs are a larger provider (than other online platforms), online classes are "fixed". MOOCs are more focused on "content" because I feel like it was designed to be a platform that can help people work on their professional skills or explore an area of interest, but online study is less focused on "content" and required levels of knowledge or experience. Also, because of the large number of students, there aren't a lot of opportunities to receive critical feedback. Actually, in the beginning, I could not distinguish between MOOCs and online courses, but I can feel some differences between them. We used to have normal online classes, and the contents are relevant to the textbook, in other words, it is just like a record of classroom teaching. However, MOOC material is also relevant to the teaching syllabus, but it contains more content, which is richer and more interesting.

PARTICIPANT B

From my point of view, MOOC platforms may offer certificates of completion, accomplishment or mastery, but no accredited qualification. However, most online studies are provided by universities and colleges which means courses normally come with a qualification attached such as a certificate, diploma, and degree or master's degree. This is what I focus on most. I also know the content differences between MOOCs and online courses. For example, materials or teaching styles.

PARTICIPANT C

In my opinion, I like MOOCs better than normal online courses. Some of the online classes in China are usually pre-recorded, so there is less interaction. Online classes in America are more flexible. I can enjoy the courses better and learn more about American culture, which is helpful for my future study abroad.

PARTICIPANT D

Apart from the teaching materials and teaching styles, contents, I noticed one thing is that, in China, online classes are sometimes taught at home (both teachers and students), but in America, the teacher is in the classroom and also deals with some offline students. I think this is one of the reasons why MOOCs have developed so fast in the past few years. It is not only a teaching method that uses the internet but also wants to be formal and organised. Students seem to like this way.

Q2- Are traditional methods transferable to MOOCs? If not, why not? If yes, then why?

PARTICIPANT A

I do not think it will. MOOCs are best for those who do not have time to attend a classroom to learn something extra or something new. Traditional methods involve quality feedback and interactions with teachers, but MOOCs seem to be a more “one-way system”. Maybe it is because it is still developing progress, but I think the teaching styles or methods based online cannot take the place of the face-to-face traditional teaching method. As we are humans, we need interaction.

PARTICIPANT B

Yes, I believe one day traditional methods will be replaced by MOOCs. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, we don't know if life ever going to be back to “normal”. Online study provides a new way for students or people to learn some new things. During this long period, although it was the first time we had access to MOOCs, the result was not bad. This successful attempt also means education can be developed with technology. However, I also think combining the two teaching methods is better.

PARTICIPANT C

I don't think that traditional lectures can be transferred to new online classes. Traditional lecturing has its own advantages and irreplaceability. For example, some of the subjects cannot be taught online, for example, it is not possible to teach students painting and sculpture remotely. Because painting and sculpting is something you have to experience in person. Some chemical subjects need to do experiments as well.

PARTICIPANT D

I think it is not accurate to say transfer all. Some parts of the traditional teaching can be transplanted to online classes. Adopt simultaneous online and offline teaching. Students can choose whether to attend online or offline classes. It is just like a combination.

Q3- After having this experience of MOOCs eg courses from America: are these methodologies transferable to traditional teaching, i.e. after Covid? What would you like to keep from your learning on MOOCs and your traditional learning? And which areas would you prefer not to have? Why?

PARTICIPANT A

There are lots of benefits to MOOCs, such as free time and space, rich teaching material and so on. For me, time can be one of the good things that MOOCs can provide because, for me, I am really not an early bird!! Having classes (provided by the university) in the morning can kill me, I didn't feel very effective, and normally I will fall asleep after the first 30 minutes. but with MOOCs, I can choose the time. It is totally Self-paced–start any time; finish any time.

PARTICIPANT B

I would say, the critical feedback discussions and class sizes are the biggest advantages of traditional methods. I am a person who loves to learn from others, it can always bring you some new ideas you never thought of before. We have time to

discuss, and everyone gets to talk about their experiences and ideas. Although MOOCs have a large number of people, there is no time for all the people to express themselves and the feedback is not always on time. That is the point that needs to be improved. Maybe more assistance or more feedback sessions will help.

PARTICIPANT C

I think in the context of the epidemic, it is true that online courses are a good method that is better to keep safe. I would like to retain the convenience of MOOCs that can be taken remotely and the interaction with the teacher in traditional classes. But actually, I don't like the distance between my teachers and classmates.

PARTICIPANT D

With the Covid-19 pandemic, traditional teaching method has had to move online. So, I think we can keep online classes that can be watched over and over again. Keep the part of the offline class where you interact with the teacher, make eye contact and combine them. Because some of the majors, for example, like my major in Education, need to have offline interaction and practice. However, during this year, I also found it is really flexible to use MOOCs because I can choose whenever I want to study. By the way, please do not keep the part about being forced to ask questions by the teacher hahaha...

Q4- How and by whom should MOOCs be evaluated?

PARTICIPANT A

By people who use it. Users' opinions are always important. For now, MOOCs are evaluated as knowing systems; as a whole. MOOC effectiveness is then based on the system's success and not on individual participant outcomes. However, it was designed for participants and people, so I believe people who use it should have their voices. If users think it is a nice try of online education, it is a good way.

PARTICIPANT B

From my point of view, MOOCs can be very difficult to assess because there are no established evaluation criteria, there are no “standard rules”, and there are low completion rates, varied instructor involvement and accessibility issues. However, that does not mean that MOOCs are impossible to evaluate. I believe MOOCs can be evaluated by four features, which are autonomy, diversity, openness, and interactivity. Whether improve the learners’ learning autonomy? What makes the education system and learning methods full of diversity? How many people or how can people have access to MOOCs? Are MOOCs as useful as the traditional face-to-face teaching method? If mostly the answers are yes, then MOOCs are successful.

PARTICIPANT C

I cannot say what is the standard for evaluating MOOCs. Different parts of the people that being linked with MOOCs have different standpoints. For the universities, MOOCs can adjust the teaching method during this special period of Covid-19 and keep the universities in operation. That is a successful course. For teachers, if students can acquire knowledge and achieve the semester expectations. That is a successful course. For students, if they can get the certificate to make sure they can graduate. That is a successful course. But there also exist different kinds of universities, teachers and students. I cannot speak for others so maybe a point system can be used to evaluate online lessons. MOOCs should be evaluated by people from all the parts that it organised.

PARTICIPANT D

I think MOOCs should be evaluated primarily by students because it is used for teaching and in order to achieve the teaching objectives. Its target group are students so it should be evaluated by students as well. Maybe assessed by changes in academic

performance before and after use or by interviews just like now. Students can give you direct feelings.

APPENDIX F Data of Semi-structured Interviews

Data from the semi-structured interviews of students from the first target university, which delivers MOOCs officially (After Covid-19)

Participants	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
SIP3 (E)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How were you introduced to MOOCs? -Who introduced you to this kind of learning? <p>I heard about MOOCs for the first time from my teacher Miss L who taught me the subject of intensive reading. Miss L raised a question in terms of "globalization", that is "from your perspective, why globalization is being called a double-edged sword?". Meanwhile, she recommended us to sign up for a specific MOOCs from a MOOC platform taught by a teacher from Hebei Normal University to support our in-class learning.</p> <p>In the beginning, I have to admit that I was just curious about the answer to that question. However, it seems like opening a new world for me to have such an effective method which could help us study something in a</p>	<p>Promotions of MOOCs.</p> <p>The diverse roles of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs have been widely accepted and used.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching in some specific area, such as foreign languages learning and reviewing.</p>

	<p>completely new field.</p> <p>Then during the COVID-19 pandemic, our university launched a series of MOOCs. When me and my classmates were self-isolated at home. We started to take MOOCs instead of classroom teaching, which is relevant to our credits and final scores in the university.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were your expectations of MOOCs? <p>-Why did you expect this (based on your previous experience of learning)?</p> <p>For MOOCs, I have two main expectations. Firstly, I hope that the duration of the partial courses can be extended as long as possible. Sometimes I came across a suitable course that could answer my current confusion, but I was told that the semester was over, and the courses had been closed naturally.</p> <p>Another expectation is whether Chinese translation could be chosen in the video speaking in English,</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The diverse roles of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of</p>	<p>MOOCs can be used in emergency.</p> <p>MOOCs can solve the problem of distance learning.</p> <p>MOOCs are more targeted, well-organised, more professional and detailed than other online courses.</p> <p>MOOCs have been widely accepted and</p>
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	<p>especially for some professional courses, such as Linguistics. As an English major, there is no denying that English subtitles can improve our listening and reading comprehension skills virtually. However, for some courses difficult to study, it will take a long time to understand the literal meaning without Chinese subtitles, let alone try to understand it more deeply, which will make me exhausted to a certain extent.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your experience of participating in MOOCs? <p>I have had several MOOCs before; I chose some according to my teachers' recommendations and others are from my own research on the internet by my interests.</p> <p>-What did you like about the course(s)?</p> <p>I like the variety and professionalism of the courses.</p> <p>-Has it been positive? If so, why</p>	<p>MOOCs such as rich resources.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p> <p>Promotions of MOOCs.</p>	<p>used, especially for some particular majors and subjects.</p> <p>With subtitles.</p> <p>MOOCs can be promoted by teachers.</p>
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	<p style="text-align: center;">/ why not?</p> <p>Yes, it has been positive. The reasons are as follows: firstly, variety means that there are many kinds of courses that could be chosen for university students, avoiding the situation where we cannot find an appropriate course to answer the question we want to know to some extent.</p> <p>In addition, the majority of the courses in MOOCs are produced by famous universities or wonderful professional teachers. Take my own experience as an example, as an English major, it is not only a procedure of studying the knowledge but also sometimes an enjoyment to follow the teacher and explore a new course. Wonderful pronunciation, accessible structured presentation, unique viewpoint to think and so on, all of these would make me fascinated by MOOCs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How often do you participate in these courses? <p>-Can you tell me why, or what,</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs such as rich resources.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible.</p>	<p>MOOCs contain a lot of learning resources that student's needs.</p> <p>MOOC experiences are positive to students.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>affects how often (regularly) you participate?</p> <p>Not often, but when it does, the frequency can be concentrated. Frankly speaking, I haven't developed a good habit of constantly learning in MOOC lesson by lesson. In most cases, I prefer to study in MOOCs in order to find the answer in terms of a certain question or to cover a knowledge gap. However, it is unclear when the confusion was produced and whether it could be answered by courses in MOOC. Meanwhile, based on my own experience, I probably spent more time in MOOC during the holidays than I did in university. The reason is rooted in the fact that learning in holidays is more focused on a particular topic or subject, such as translating or interpreting, while learning in school is more focused on a specific problem, such as what qualities a good interpreter need. In conclusion, it depends on what kind of courses I want to learn.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When? At what time of day? 	<p>MOOCs have many advantages.</p>	<p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs can focus on some aspects that students need in particular.</p>
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	<p>-Can you tell me why these times suit you? What affects the time of your participation?</p> <p>I prefer to take courses in MOOCs at night. On the one hand, sometimes I still need to take classes during the day. On the other hand, it is a good time for me to calm down easily to study independently.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What motivates you to attend and participate in MOOCs? <p>-Is it just the time of the online courses? Is their regularity/ (how often)?</p> <p>From my perspective, the advantages of MOOCs are not only the convenience of time and function but also the excellent quality of teaching that motivates me the most.</p> <p>-Is it related to your previous experience of classroom learning?</p> <p>Yes. Take an instance, I had studied an essay about " globalisation" in the past.</p>	<p>Factors that influence students' engagement.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>The quality of MOOCs and its flexibility.</p> <p>MOOCs can be a supplement of traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>Obviously, only a few offline lessons are far from enough, and it is difficult for us to have a deeper understanding when it comes to this topic. In this case, the study of online courses will not only help us clarify the structure of the text but also expand the types and influences of globalisation. Because of the convenience of the Internet, if we don't understand what the teacher said, we can play it over and over again until it becomes clear.</p> <p>-do you feel that classroom learning is enough for you?</p> <p>Not enough.</p> <p>-Do you want to learn further, or in a different way from traditional classroom learning? If so, why?</p> <p>For me, the combination of online and MOOCs is a better choice.</p> <p>-Is this why you chose MOOCs/online learning? -Is it better for you to learn at a</p>		<p>The flexibility of MOOCs may be combined with traditional classroom teaching methods in the future.</p>
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	<p>different, or a particular time? Why?</p> <p>I prefer flexible time for MOOCs. Just like I said above, I can arrange my time easily. Sometimes learning at university and sometimes learning via MOOCs is efficient.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you feel that you engage better with online or with traditional classroom learning? -Why? / Why not? <p>I enjoy learning in a traditional classroom, and I can engage better. Compared to online courses, traditional classroom learning provides us with a strong learning atmosphere due to the presence of our classmates, which is crucial in our learning process, no matter it is cooperation or competition. The offline courses are more interactive and participatory, which means that we can communicate with our teachers and classmates at any moment. It also prevents us from being distracted in class to some extent.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>The choose of deliveries are flexible. MOOCs can be arranged on students' own time.</p> <p>MOOCs requires students to be more autonomous.</p>
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	<p>-Do you feel more motivated to learn online or in a traditional classroom?</p> <p>Online actually. Because I choose the content I actually need.</p> <p>-Do you enjoy learning online or in a traditional classroom more?</p> <p>-Why do you think this is?</p> <p>I enjoy learning in a traditional classroom. Compared to online courses, traditional classroom learning provides us with a strong learning atmosphere due to the presence of our classmates, which is crucial in our learning process, no matter it is cooperation or competition.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have there been any challenges for you engaging in the MOOC platform? <p>-If so, what are they?</p> <p>There's a little challenge. Since I haven't logged in for a long time, I forgot my password, but my old</p>	<p>The perceptions of MOOCs are less MOOCs.</p> <p>MOOCs are different from traditional classroom teaching.</p>	<p>MOOCs are less cooperative and competitive than traditional classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs have some challenges on Internet technique.</p>
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	<p>account didn't store any important information, so I created a new one.</p> <p>In addition, I mentioned above in the previous questions about the subtitle issue.</p> <p>-If so, how do you resolve these – on your own or by contacting the site? If so, is the support from the site helpful?</p> <p>By myself, I just register another account.</p> <p>-Are these challenges easily resolved? Why / Why not?</p> <p>Yes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you discovered about yourself from the way you prefer to learn from engaging in MOOCs? <p>-Your flexibility</p> <p>-When you concentrate best?</p> <p>-What you like and dislike about studying, in general?</p> <p>I have made two discoveries: one is</p>	<p>The disadvantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs have some IT issues.</p>
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	<p>improving. On the other hand, the study of the courses allows me to enrich my knowledge and broaden my horizons.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you think that learning via MOOCs has helped you to study better? Why? (more interesting/less boring/modern methods/ different teachers?) <p>Yes, I do. I can constantly search for a suitable course and study it independently, so as to clear up my confusion, and then I will gain a sense of satisfaction. In other words, I would like to look for happiness in learning.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you hope to achieve by participating in MOOCs? -Can you tell me why? <p>First of all, I hope to clear up the confusion of some university courses through MOOCs. Secondly, I particularly hope that I can systematically learn a course I like through continuous learning, which is not only a test for myself but also an</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>autonomous learning.</p> <p>MOOCs have some advantages that help students to do better on autonomous learning.</p> <p>MOOCs could be a supplement to traditional classroom teaching and can fulfil the needs of students</p>
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	<p>effective way to improve my professional knowledge and skills as an English major.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How would you prefer to study in the future: fully online; fully in class or as a blend of both? -Why? <p>I prefer to study with a combination of online and offline. Both traditional classroom teaching and new online teaching have their own advantages and disadvantages. For example, offline teaching has its inherent advantages, such as strong interaction, active participation and a good learning atmosphere. Online classes, such as MOOCs, offer a variety of colorful courses that can be watched repeatedly anytime and anywhere, helping us to enrich our knowledge and broaden our horizons.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why would this suit you: timing of classes? Regularity of classes? Personal interest? New and interesting? 	<p>about their learning requirements.</p> <p>To combined MOOCs</p>
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	<p>That is new and interesting. Especially after the COVID-19 pandemic, when some students have more experience with online courses. Why not try this combination of the two and work together to improve ourselves?</p>	<p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>with traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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Participants	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
SIP4 (F)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How were you introduced to MOOCs? -Who introduced you to this kind of learning? <p>The first time I was introduced to MOOCs was during the COVID-19 pandemic. Our university announced that all the classes changed online. I was happy at that time because I did not need to go back to school. I thought it would be like other online courses I had before. But one of my roommates, who is ranked top 3 in our class, said she already uses the MOOC platform and feels that MOOCs are better than she thought, and she discussed the experiences with other roommates in our accommodation's WeChat group. Later, our university opened again, and we went back to our classrooms. Now we still use MOOC to preview the courses sometimes. Our teachers will also recommend and share some nice MOOCs when they find them. I only believe my teacher's and friends' recommendations. You</p>	<p>Promotions of MOOCs.</p> <p>The diverse roles of MOOCs.</p> <p>Promotions of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs have been widely accepted and used.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching in some specific area, such as previewing.</p> <p>MOOCs can be promoted by teachers</p>

	<p>know there are so many platforms and courses on the Internet. When some courses recruit students, they will use "famous teachers", "famous schools" or popular content as gimmicks, but when you register or even pay fees on some platforms, you find that it is not what you expected. This is very distressing.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were your expectations of MOOCs? <p>-Why did you expect this (based on your previous experience of learning)?</p> <p>I expect our university can input more courses of interest for us, for example, something about music or travelling. I like this content, but I am afraid I cannot keep attending the courses if they are not from my university requirements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your experience of participating in MOOCs? <p>My roommate first recommended MOOCs to us. I found it very practical and convenient. At that time,</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of</p>	<p>and friends.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs are practical</p>
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	<p>I was taking online classes at home, so I tried the MOOC by the way and found it very interesting. It includes many courses related to our university courses, but they are not the same. I also searched for Stanford courses to try out, but I thought it difficult for me haha. My English level is not enough and needs to be improved.</p> <p>-What did you like about the course(s)?</p> <p>I like new things, on the MOOC platforms, there are many different courses that I can choose to learn, or not for mastering, but just knowing. MOOC is so convenient.</p> <p>-Has it been positive? If so, why / why not?</p> <p>Yes of course. I think compared with other online courses; MOOCs are guaranteed. Many courses are related to university courses, and even if they are free, the quality is still good enough. I particularly hate some courses. They look good, but after a few</p>	<p>MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>Factors that influence learner engagement.</p>	<p>and convenient and can provide rich learning resources.</p> <p>MOOCs have been widely accepted and used, especially for some particular majors and subjects.</p> <p>Free and high quality.</p>
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	<p>minutes, it's really frustrating to ask for payment for key parts or to jump to some other website.</p> <p>In addition, I prefer to study or read quietly by myself. MOOCs can suit my preferences very well. Sometimes I find it noisy in the study room or class, and I don't like studying with many people.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How often do you participate in these courses? <p>-Can you tell me why, or what, affects how often (regularly) you participate?</p> <p>During COVID-19, we have MOOCs instead of classroom courses. But after back to university, it becomes a supplement to traditional classroom teaching. Some of the courses and platforms we have used before continuing to be used. The teacher will still recommend some good cases to us for pre-class preview or after-class enrichment. Now my study frequency is about twice a week, mostly as a supplement to linguistics and</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs can help increase learning autonomy.</p> <p>MOOCs can be a supplement to traditional classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs can focus on some aspects that students need in particular.</p>
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	<p>intensive reading, which are a bit difficult for me. At first, I thought I could find the answers and explanations to the after-class exercises here. Although I didn't, it did help my study. Some content is easier to understand if explained in another way. I feel happy when I understand the learning content.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When? At what time of day? -Can you tell me why these times suit you? What affects the time of your participation? <p>I like to take MOOCs in the evenings and weekends. It's quieter at night. I like to study quietly by myself. On the weekends, I can review the parts I didn't fully understand from the previous week or learn about the courses for the next week. Ummm, sometimes I will also be lazy and do not review, or only participate in part of it.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What motivates you to attend and participate in MOOCs? 	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOC experiences are positive to students.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible.</p>
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	<p>-Is it just the time of the online courses? Is their regularity/ (how often)?</p> <p>MOOCs are convenient and very helpful for my university studies. I can study via MOOCs at any time I like. Once I haven't mastered the knowledge well, I can review for a second time, a third time, until I totally understand.</p> <p>-Is it related to your previous experience of classroom learning?</p> <p>Yes. Sometimes I cannot fully understand the knowledge in classrooms for some particular lessons such as linguistics. My friends recommended MOOCs to me. She always uses MOOCs to preview the class, and she tells us (we are roommates) how to select good courses and even shares the courses she already participated in with us, which is helpful.</p> <p>-do you feel that classroom</p>	<p>Factors that influence learner engagement with MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs are flexible and can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs can focus on some aspects that students need in particular.</p>
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	<p>learning is enough for you?</p> <p>Not enough. I need more practise after class.</p> <p>-Do you want to learn further, or in a different way from traditional classroom learning? If so, why?</p> <p>Yes, now I still use MOOCs as a supplement to traditional classroom teaching, although our university does not require any more.</p> <p>-Is this why you chose MOOCs/online learning? -Is it better for you to learn at a different, or a particular time? Why?</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible. I can arrange my time easily. I prefer different times when I need to.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you feel that you engage better with online or with traditional classroom learning? -Why? / Why not? 	<p>The advantages of MOOCs can be a supplement of traditional classroom teaching.</p>	<p>MOOCs can be a supplement of traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>I prefer MOOCs, but I also know that classroom courses are important, and I will take both. I prefer a quiet and free study atmosphere to think by myself. In class, there are many times when I feel like I am a bystander. I am not a good student, my participation and discussion are not as good as some other students, and I don't like to speak. In class, I mostly listen to the teacher and record the key points. But in MOOCs, I can stop and think at any time. Learn at my own speed.</p> <p>-Do you feel more motivated to learn online or in a traditional classroom?</p> <p>Online actually. I like study by myself.</p> <p>-Do you enjoy learning online or in a traditional classroom more?</p> <p>-Why do you think this is?</p> <p>Online. More relaxed and comfortable as I said above.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs are flexible.</p> <p>MOOC experiences are positive to students.</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have there been any challenges for you engaging in the MOOC platform? -If so, what are they? <p>Yes, although I like online learning. I cannot keep learning autonomously for a long time. I also have some trouble with English courses sometimes. I choose easy-understanding courses, but I know those are not good for my improvement. In addition, I can practise speaking during online courses with partners.</p> <p>-If so, how do you resolve these – on your own or by contacting the site? If so, is the support from the site helpful?</p> <p>Trying to focus as long as I can to improve my autonomous learning ability and make plans for myself. Do more practice in university classes.</p> <p>-Are these challenges easily</p>	<p>The perceptions of MOOCs.</p> <p>The perceptions of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs require learners to be more autonomous.</p> <p>MOOCs are less cooperative and competitive than traditional classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs could help students do better in autonomous learning.</p> <p>MOOCs can combine with traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>resolved? Why / Why not?</p> <p>Yes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you discovered about yourself from the way you prefer to learn from engaging in MOOCs? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Your flexibility -When you concentrate best? -What you like and dislike about studying, in general? <p>I found that I am not the person I think I used to be. When I was in the classroom I always listened to teachers and classmates. I seldom think by myself. I thought I just attended the classes for graduation. However, when I study alone via MOOCs, I have more critical thinking about the learning content, and I even select the courses by myself through consideration. I have my own ideas and decisions to judge whether a course is good or not.</p> <p>I prefer to study at night. It is quiet to think and learn.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you learned about 	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs help students to do better on autonomous learning.</p>
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	<p>your motivation to learn, in general, from engaging in MOOCs?</p> <p>-Do you feel more engaged? If so why/why not?</p> <p>Yes, more motivated. Sometimes when I understand content via learning with MOOCs. I am more confident about attending the class. I believe I can understand most of the content in class and I am more focused on hearing if somebody's opinion is the same as mine.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you think that learning via MOOCs has helped you to study better? Why? (more interesting/less boring/modern methods/ different teachers?) <p>Yes, I do. Some courses are interesting and related more to history or stories. Different teaching methodologies also make me think about how to be an English teacher. I am an English major student anyway. I never thought about being a teacher before, but after learning through MOOCs, especially</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs have some advantages that help students to do better on autonomous learning.</p> <p>MOOC experiences are positive to students.</p> <p>MOOCs could be a supplement to traditional classroom teaching and can fulfil the needs of students about their learning requirements.</p>
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	<p>when I searched a content taught by different teachers. I started to imagine if I were a teacher, how could I make these clear to students?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you hope to achieve by participating in MOOCs? -Can you tell me why? <p>To study better by myself and try to get a scholarship to surprise people haha.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How would you prefer to study in the future: fully online; fully in class or as a blend of both? -Why? <p>Combined both. This is also a combination of practice and theories, practice offline and learning knowledge points online. Once this form becomes mature, it also saves time and energy for both teachers and students. I think this will be achieved not long.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why would this suit you: timing of classes? Regularity of 	<p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>To combined MOOCs with traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>classes? Personal interest? New and interesting?</p> <p>It contains all these advantages. We have had some online courses before, and MOOC makes online learning more comprehensive.</p>		
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APPENDIX G Data of Semi-structured Interviews

Data from the semi-structured interviews of students from the second target university, which do not deliver MOOCs officially (After COVID-19)

Participants	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
SIP3 (G)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How were you introduced to MOOCs? -Who introduced you to this kind of learning? <p>One of my teachers who teaches the History of Western Civilization, introduced me to MOOCs first and she advised us to watch some videos especially the lectures about Western history using the MOOCs. I have some other computer-based classes, but she recommended this, and we have tried them. I also heard it before from other classmates and checked on the online platform. The big data is interesting, once you search, you will receive many recommendation ads. I cannot distinguish which fits my needs. Then I started to attend some MOOCs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What were your expectations of 	Promotions of MOOCs.	<p>MOOCs have been widely accepted and used.</p> <p>MOOCs can be promoted by teachers and ads.</p>

	<p>MOOCs?</p> <p>-Why did you expect this (based on your previous experience of learning)?</p> <p>I have other online learning experiences and MOOCs are new to me. So, I expected it could solve some problems that I used to meet when I took normal online courses. For example, I expect that it can note the translation of some difficult words or some proper nouns. Besides, it can play and pause automatically when some important parts are taught according to the learners' average level of English. Maybe it should require the teachers to leave some time for students. I hope it can improve these functions because sometimes I have to take notes. In order to save time, I have to use the shortcut keys.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your experience of participating in MOOCs? <p>In addition to the above questions, I think, MOOCs are good. I like using them because of its rich resources. When I had some classes before in the</p>	<p>MOOCs are expected to be different from other online courses.</p> <p>The diverse roles of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of</p>	<p>MOOCs need to pay attention to some details set according to the learners' average learning level.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching in some specific area, such as foreign languages learning and reviewing normal classes.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the</p>
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	<p>classroom, teachers were teaching according to the textbook, but during MOOCs, I can search for a lot of relevant content I need on time. Some even raise my interest in relevant fields.</p> <p>-What did you like about the course(s)?</p> <p>Another reason I like the courses is that MOOCs include some short videos taken from film and courses in which the teacher has very good pronunciation.</p> <p>-Has it been positive? If so, why / why not?</p> <p>It has been positive. I enjoy learning via MOOCs. After a period of MOOCs, I think my awareness of autonomous learning has improved.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How often do you participate in these courses? <p>-Can you tell me why, or what, affects how often (regularly)</p>	<p>MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>needs of students more than classroom teaching in some specific area, such as foreign languages learning.</p> <p>MOOCs can help students to do better on autonomous learning.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching in some specific area, such as foreign languages learning and be a supplement of the classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>you participate?</p> <p>I participate in these courses about twice or three times a week to watch some videos as supplementary materials for my courses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When? At what time of day? -Can you tell me why these times suit you? What affects the time of your participation? <p>I usually participate in these courses at night because I have classes during the day. After class, I can participate in these courses to read more supplementary materials. I like to study during the night because it is silent, and I can concentrate more.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What motivates you to attend and participate in MOOCs? -Is it just the time of the online courses? Is their regularity/ (how often)? <p>In order to read more supplementary materials to improve my knowledge, I attend MOOCs regularly. It is related to my previous experience of classroom</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>Factors that influence students’ engagement</p>	<p>Rich resources and flexible time.</p> <p>MOOCs can be a supplement to traditional</p>
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	<p>learning. I feel that classroom learning is not enough for me, so I always participate in MOOCs.</p> <p>-Is it related to your previous experience of classroom learning?</p> <p>Yes, because I want to learn further, or in a different way from traditional classroom learning because I think various teachers are teaching in online courses so that we can have different experiences, and we won't get bored. This is why I choose MOOC learning.</p> <p>-do you feel that classroom learning is enough for you?</p> <p>Not enough.</p> <p>-Do you want to learn further, or in a different way from traditional classroom learning? If so, why?</p> <p>Yes, because I am an English major student. I need to keep reading and</p>	<p>with MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of</p>	<p>classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students' own learning requirements.</p> <p>MOOC experiences are positive to students.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible and</p>
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	<p>practising. MOOCs can offer me more materials to use. It is a really convenient method. I can get whatever I want, some courses are even from other famous universities and teachers. I am glad that I have access to these materials.</p> <p>-Is this why you chose MOOCs/online learning?</p> <p>-Is it better for you to learn at a different, or a particular time? Why?</p> <p>It is better for me to learn at a different or a particular time because I can choose the time when I'm available.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you feel that you engage better with online or with traditional classroom learning? <p>-Why? / Why not?</p> <p>I feel that I engage better with online learning because I like taking notes if I miss something important or if there is something I don't understand, I can also record the lecture and keep it in my equipment so that I can review the</p>	<p>MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>can provide rich resources.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs are convenient.</p> <p>MOOCs are flexible.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more</p>
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	<p>class in time. I do not really like answering questions in class. I enjoy learning by myself on my own time.</p> <p>-Do you feel more motivated to learn online or in a traditional classroom?</p> <p>Online learning. More Flexible.</p> <p>-Do you enjoy learning online or in a traditional classroom more?</p> <p>-Why do you think this is?</p> <p>I enjoy learning online more because it's very convenient and useful.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have there been any challenges for you engaging in the MOOC platform? <p>-If so, what are they?</p> <p>There have not been any challenges for me to engage in the MOOC platform. I can get what I want, and I can learn through it without any difficulties. I just watch some videos and attend some courses simply.</p>	<p>MOOCs can be arranged on students' own time.</p>	<p>than classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>-If so, how do you resolve these – on your own or by contacting the site? If so, is the support from the site helpful?</p> <p>If I meet any challenges, I will resolve the problems by contacting the site and I believe it will be helpful.</p> <p>-Are these challenges easily resolved? Why / Why not?</p> <p>Yes. I believe the MOOC platform has been more and more mature to support learners. It is also needed to do this to better maintain the users.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you discovered about yourself from the way you prefer to learn from engaging in MOOCs? <p>-Your flexibility</p> <p>-When you concentrate best?</p> <p>-What you like and dislike about studying, in general?</p> <p>I feel more flexible in the aspect of choosing courses. When the courses</p>		
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	<p>include some interesting examples, I will be interested in them and concentrate better. In general, I like studying via MOOCs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you learned about your motivation to learn, in general, from engaging in MOOCs? <p>-Do you feel more engaged? If so why/why not?</p> <p>Yes, I feel more engaged because I like online classes. It is useful for me. Actually, I only represent myself. I know that compared with traditional classroom teaching, most of the students may like traditional ways because they have been learning in the classroom for more than ten years. But I like new things, there are many different courses that we can choose and there are many different materials and documents followed by the videos so that we can print them out and take notes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you think that learning via 	<p>Factors that influence students' engagement with MOOCs.</p>	<p>Rich resources, and its new methodology.</p>
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	<p>MOOCs has helped you to study better? Why? (more interesting/less boring/modern methods/ different teachers?)</p> <p>I think that learning via MOOCs has helped me to study better because it makes studying more interesting and there are different teachers and participants in each course, so I won't get bored.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you hope to achieve by participating in MOOCs? -Can you tell me why? <p>I hope to improve my knowledge and learn more professional or extracurricular knowledge.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How would you prefer to study in the future: fully online; fully in class or as a blend of both? -Why? <p>I prefer to study in the future as a blend of both online and in the classroom so that I can have a better understanding of the knowledge.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs contain a lot of teaching resources that students' needs and the method is new and interesting.</p> <p>MOOCs can be combined with traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why would this suit you: timing of classes? Regularity of classes? Personal interest? New and interesting? <p>I think it's just personal interests and MOOCs themselves are new and interesting methods anyway.</p>	<p>The advantages and attractions of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs have some advantages that help students to do better on autonomous learning. MOOCs can provide new feelings for students.</p>
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Participants	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
SIP4 (H)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How were you introduced to MOOCs? -Who introduced you to this kind of learning? <p>I was recommended by my high school teacher. We sometimes chat through phones. It is my third year in the university, and I have a lot of important courses in our English major such as History of English and American Literature, Linguistics and English Lexicography. I am afraid I cannot do well in classrooms and cannot pass the exams, so she recommended MOOCs to me as a supplement to normal classroom learning. Initially, I thought it was just a kind of online recorded course like what I used when I prepared for the CET-4 exam. However, she said it is more than online courses. It is more comprehensive I can find almost anything I need. If I cannot understand some point in the classroom, I can review it later and there are many courses from other universities and</p>	Promotions of MOOCs.	<p>MOOCs have been widely accepted and used.</p> <p>MOOCs can be promoted by teachers.</p>

	<p>teachers. That probably means if I cannot understand some knowledge, I can find a different explanation on MOOCs to help me better understand. Then I tried.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were your expectations of MOOCs? -Why did you expect this (based on your previous experience of learning)? <p>In addition to the above, I also hope I can learn something from MOOCs that I cannot learn in classes, to enrich my professional knowledge and strengthen my professional skills. It is because my university is at a normal level. I would like to have a look at the courses that top universities have. However, I also worried that I could not focus well without the observation of teachers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your experience of participating in MOOCs? <p>I chose the MOOCs according to the teacher's recommendation of the</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching in some specific areas, such as reviewing and explaining some classroom content.</p>
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	<p>courses I want to learn. I also invited my friends to participate in it with me and then we talked about it after class, trying to learn as much as we can. She also has worries like me and after the second time of learning, we feel better about understanding the knowledge and we have confidence to deal with the professional courses.</p> <p>-What did you like about the course(s)?</p> <p>I prefer the richness and diversity of MOOCs, which can explain those things I do not know or do not understand in the classroom, and it is also relatively convenient. I can review several times as well and I can choose many videos on the same topic. By listening to different teachers, I can find the best explanation. Well, especially during the epidemic environment, I think it is very helpful to my daily study.</p> <p>-Has it been positive? If so, why / why not?</p>	<p>The perceptions of MOOCs.</p> <p>The diverse roles of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs are expected to be different from normal online courses.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching in some specific area, such as additional knowledge.</p>
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	<p>times suit you? What affects the time of your participation?</p> <p>I usually take the courses at night or afternoon on weekends. The main thing that affected my choosing the time was the university curriculum arrangement. Thanks to MOOCs' flexibility, I can spend time on my own courses first and after I finish the class and finish my homework I can attend MOOCs from my own timetable.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What motivates you to attend and participate in MOOCs? <p>-Is it just the time of the online courses? Is their regularity/ (how often)?</p> <p>I really want to improve and strengthen my knowledge to pass the exams and do well in university classes. I believe through MOOCs I can get what I want if I insist.</p> <p>-Is it related to your previous experience of classroom learning?</p> <p>It is related to my classroom</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs provide rich MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs provide rich resources and flexible time.</p>
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	<p>experience. Because many courses are recommended to me by my teacher to support my classroom courses. Moreover, I also hope to expand my knowledge through MOOCs.</p> <p>-do you feel that classroom learning is enough for you?</p> <p>Not enough. However, MOOC is not enough as well. I think it is better to combine them.</p> <p>-Do you want to learn further, or in a different way from traditional classroom learning? If so, why?</p> <p>I prefer to take more chances to use the MOOC platform to learn more knowledge and improve my learning ability. I think this is the significance of MOOCs.</p> <p>-Is this why you chose MOOCs/online learning? -Is it better for you to learn at a different, or a particular time? Why?</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The perceptions of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOC experiences are positive to students.</p> <p>MOOCs can be a supplement of traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>I think it's better to have a fixed time to learn, whether in classrooms or through MOOCs. This will help me to develop a good learning habit and help me to arrange my time better.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Do you feel that you engage better with online or with traditional classroom learning? -Why? / Why not? <p>I feel that I engage better with traditional classroom learning. I can communicate with teachers and classmates more closely. I can get feedback in time, and I can practise English with my classmates. For our English major students, practise is important.</p> <p>-Do you feel more motivated to learn online or in a traditional classroom?</p> <p>In a traditional classroom. The traditional classroom is more dynamic. I can interact more closely with my classmates. It's also easier to recognise the difference between me and other</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of</p>	<p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs can fulfil the</p>
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	<p>students. To find what I lack and to improve myself purposeful.</p> <p>-Do you enjoy learning online or in a traditional classroom more?</p> <p>-Why do you think this is?</p> <p>I enjoy the traditional classroom more than MOOCs, although MOOCs are useful for me. I think the classroom experience is important for all the language students. We need to communicate and practice. These two things are not in conflict.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have there been any challenges for you engaging in the MOOC platform? <p>-If so, what are they?</p> <p>There were no challenges at all. If anything, I think my challenge may be that sometimes I can't understand the teacher's profound knowledge. This is something that platforms can't solve. It is not the problem of MOOCs.</p>	<p>The perceptions of MOOCs.</p>	<p>needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs are convenient and flexible.</p> <p>MOOCs are as important as traditional classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>-If so, how do you resolve these - on your own or by contacting the site? If so, is the support from the site helpful?</p> <p>No problems when study via MOOCs. I need to improve myself.</p> <p>-Are these challenges easily resolved? Why / Why not?</p> <p>No problems when study via MOOCs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you discovered about yourself from the way you prefer to learn from engaging in MOOCs? <p>-Your flexibility -When you concentrate best? -What you like and dislike about studying, in general?</p> <p>In the process of learning MOOC, I found that I could be very focused and engaged. I prefer to study with different classmates via MOOCs and I feel relaxed because no one knows me. I am not afraid of making mistakes. One thing is I don't like the content that</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs can fulfil the needs of students more than classroom teaching.</p>
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	<p>is too hard to understand sometimes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you learned about your motivation to learn, in general, from engaging in MOOCs? <p>-Do you feel more engaged? If so why/why not?</p> <p>I do feel more engaged. After participating in MOOCs a few times, I think I have already made some progress. I can understand most of the content now and I feel more confident.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you think that learning via MOOCs has helped you to study better? Why? (more interesting/less boring/modern methods/ different teachers?) <p>Yes, I think this new form of MOOC contains richer resources. The contents are usually interesting. After using it for a while, it can also stimulate learners' enthusiasm and initiative.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you hope to achieve by 	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOC experiences are positive to students.</p> <p>MOOC experiences are positive to students.</p> <p>MOOCs have some advantages that help students to do better on autonomous learning.</p>
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	<p>participating in MOOCs?</p> <p>-Can you tell me why?</p> <p>I hope to learn more systematic and classroom-related knowledge through MOOCs. Because I want to combine MOOCs with the content of the class. It will make my knowledge system and foundation more complete.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• How would you prefer to study in the future: fully online; fully in class or as a blend of both? <p>-Why?</p> <p>Of course, I prefer a blend of both. Although I get used to the traditional class, I also wish I could arrange my spare time through MOOCs well. It would be better if MOOCs could launch a series of courses which supply classroom teaching accurately.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Why would this suit you: timing of classes? Regularity of classes? Personal interest? New and interesting? <p>I prefer to combine both because each of these two has its own advantages.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs can focus on some aspects that students need in particular.</p> <p>MOOCs can be combined with traditional classroom teaching and to be more accurately.</p>
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	<p>The traditional classroom method can provide students with a good learning atmosphere, while the online courses can improve their self-learning ability and to some extent, be a supplement to traditional classroom teaching.</p>	<p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs can focus on some aspects that students need in particular.</p>
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APPENDIX H Data of Semi-structured Interviews

Data from the semi-structured interviews of students from the first target university, which delivers MOOCs officially (Experiences during COVID-19)

	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
(F) University A	<p>- Tell me something about the MOOCs that you used. Do they belong to cMOOC or xMOOC?</p> <p>Thanks for your brief explanation about MOOC types. Before you tell me the differences, I am not aware of these. I think I used the MOOCs belonging to cMOOC because my major is English, which needs students and teachers to participate in the discussion and collaborate together to practise.</p> <p>- Did your universities use their own MOOCs, or did they import MOOCs from other universities?</p> <p>Some of the MOOCs are from my own university, and some are not. You know that more and more Chinese universities often collaborate with each other or with international partners to develop and offer online courses together. But most of the MOOCs I used are recommended by my teachers.</p>	<p>Type of MOOCs</p> <p>Put in Promoting MOOCs.</p> <p>Promotions of MOOCs.</p>	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Did you interact with other students via MOOCs? <p>If yes, in what ways did you interact with students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can you see other students on the screen? Did you talk with each other? - Did you enjoy this form of learning? - Why did you like collaborating? / Why did you not enjoy it? - How exactly were you able to collaborate online? How did the collaboration work? <p>If not, why is there no interaction?</p> <p>Yes, sometimes I interact with other students in MOOCs, and sometimes not. Normally through discussion, we ask questions, share insights, and engage in discussions related to the course content.</p> <p>I can't see other students on the screen. Communications typically happen through written text in discussion forums or through messaging features provided by the platform. While we couldn't talk face-to-face, we could still engage in meaningful discussions and exchange ideas through written communication.</p>	<p>Interactions in MOOC study</p>	<p>This is an interesting fact that students did not put their cameras on so they cannot see others. There was something missing in this kind of</p>
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	<p>I found interacting with other students in MOOCs to be an enjoyable and enriching experience. It provided an opportunity to learn from peers, gain different perspectives and collaborate on the assignments or projects. I enjoyed collaborating because it allowed me to benefit from the diverse knowledge and experiences of my peers. It made the learning process more dynamic and interactive. However, collaboration could sometimes be challenging if there were communication barriers or if group members didn't contribute equally.</p> <p>Questions on participants' experience of working online during the COVID-19?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are your memories of MOOCs? Are they good? <p>My memories of MOOCs during the COVID-19 pandemic are generally positive. But I think I still prefer face-to-face teaching methods. MOOCs provided a valuable opportunity for me to continue learning and stay engaged with my studies despite the challenges posed by the pandemic. While the transition to online learning was initially challenging, MOOCs offered a flexible and accessible way for me to access educational resources and continue my academics. I spent most of my uni time at home and later, my</p>	<p>interaction, although these participants find it to be an enjoyable experience even though she cannot see them.</p>
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	<p>accommodation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What steps did your university take as an immediate reaction to COVID-19? <p>In response to the COVID-19, my university took several immediate measures to ensure the safety and well-being of students and staff. This included transitioning to online learning, implementing remote work arrangements for lectures and staff, and enhancing communication channels to keep the university community informed about developments related to the pandemic.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What kind of online learning took place during the COVID-19? - What kind of MOOCs were offered? <p>(University offered or lectures recommended?) (Was it easy to access? Was it free? Did your university run online programs?)</p> <p>Access to MOOCs was generally easy, and many courses were offered free of charge or at a discounted rate for university students. In addition to MOOCs, my university also offered other online learning styles such as live lectures delivered via video conferencing platforms, pre-recorded video lectures accessible through the university's learning management system, online discussion forums, and interactive quizzes or assessments. In total, everything is</p>	<p>Interactions in MOOC study</p>	
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	<p>online!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What other online learning style was offered? - Which online learning method do you prefer? and why? <p>(Explore which online learning methods students preferred during the pandemic, eg. live, recorded, MOOCs)</p> <p>During COVID-19, online learning at my university encompassed a variety of formats, including live lectures, pre-recorded video lectures, online discussions, and assignments. Moreover, MOOCs were offered as supplementary resources to complement traditional course materials. My university offered a wide range of MOOCs covering diverse subjects and disciplines, including but not limited to humanities, social sciences, business, and language learning. These MOOCs were either developed and offered by my university or recommended as supplementary resources from other reputable institutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What MOOCs did you enrol in, and did you complete? <p>I found a combination of live lectures and</p>	<p>MOOCs and other online courses.</p>	
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	<p>MOOCs to be the most effective online learning method for me during the pandemic. Live lectures provided real-time interaction with professors and classmates, fostering a sense of connection and engagement. Meanwhile, MOOCs offered flexibility and additional resources to supplement my learning, allowing me to explore topics of interest in greater depth at my own pace. I enrolled in several MOOCs during the pandemic, including courses on the grammar of English and Western cultural history as well as some other MOOCs I used as resources. While I completed some of these courses successfully, I must admit that I did not complete all of them due to the demands of my university coursework and other commitments.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Was there a formal completion process for you? - What was the breakdown of compulsory versus optional courses? - Did you have to complete it? After completing, can you get a certificate or just required by your university. <p>The breakdown varied depending on the program and semester. Generally, there were more compulsory courses in the earlier years of study, covering foundational subjects essential to the</p>	<p>MOOCs and other online courses.</p>	
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	<p>discipline. Optional courses became more prevalent in later years, allowing students to specialize and explore areas of interest. Completion requirements varied for each MOOCs. Some MOOCs require completion to receive the credits, which could be beneficial for academic or professional purposes. Others were optional, with completion serving as supplemental learning. My university sometimes integrated MOOCs into the curriculum, making completion mandatory for credit.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do MOOCs or other online learning require of your time management skills? How do you balance your online management skills in order to engage in MOOCs better? <p>Engaging in MOOCs demands strong time management skills. Balancing coursework, assignments, and extracurricular activities with MOOCs required careful planning and prioritization. Setting specific study schedules, breaking tasks into manageable chunks, and minimizing distractions helped me stay on track and make the most of my MOOC experiences.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Did your management skills improve and develop? - How do you maintain your study 	<p>Preference</p> <p>Interaction</p>	
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	<p>self-discipline without regular classroom observation by the teachers? (If so, how did you do this. If not, why did you not do this. What issues are involved?)</p> <p>Yes, my time management skills significantly improved through engaging in MOOCs and other online learning. The necessity to juggle multiple tasks and deadlines honed my ability to organize my time effectively and remain focused on my academic goals. Maintaining study discipline without regular classroom observation was a challenge initially. However, setting personal goals, creating a dedicated study environment, and adhering to a structured study routine helped me stay disciplined. Regular self-assessment, seeking feedback from peers or online forums, and leveraging online resources for support were also instrumental in staying on track.</p> <p>Experiences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Could you share some interesting or memorable experiences with MOOCs during the pandemic? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Were there any special MOOCs or teachers that impressed you? o Did you actively participate in online groupwork? How have 		
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these activities helped you in your studies?

- Did you make good use of the learning resources provided by the MOOC programme, such as video lectures, reading materials and online tests?

I was impressed by MOOCs on machine learning taught by a renowned professor from a top university. The clear explanations and hands-on projects allowed me to deepen my understanding of the subject, and it gave me the opportunity to learn from a “better” uni, which could not have happened without MOOCs.

Engaging in online group projects was memorable as it facilitated collaboration with peers from diverse backgrounds. We tackled complex problems together, learning from each other's perspectives and skills.

- When did the traditional classroom courses return to normal for you at your university?

Traditional classroom courses gradually returned to normal as the pandemic situation improved. In my city, it was in September of 2020, but later it

The future of MOOCs.

	<p>was also closed for a short time several times. Initially, there were hybrid models with a mix of online and in-person classes, but eventually, most courses transitioned back to fully in-person instruction when it was deemed safe to do so.</p> <p>- Did you choose to continue to participate in MOOCs after the COVID-19 pandemic?</p> <p>Yes, I chose to continue participating in MOOCs even after the COVID-19 pandemic subsided. The flexibility and accessibility of MOOCs allowed me to continue expanding my knowledge and skills beyond the confines of traditional classroom settings. Additionally, the variety of courses available ensured that I could explore diverse interests and stay updated on the latest developments in my field.</p>		
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Participants	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
(E) University A	<p>- Tell me something about the MOOCs that you used. Do they belong to cMOOC or xMOOC? I didn't realise that MOOCs could be divided into cMOOC and xMOOC until you introduced it. The teachers didn't introduce this part to us, just that when the COVID-19 pandemic started, our university used MOOC as an alternative to the traditional classroom because we were isolated at home and couldn't come to the classroom to learn. A couple of other MOOCs were individually recommended by teachers, we take these courses as supplements and extensions of some specific courses, for example, History of Western Civilization.</p> <p>- Did your universities use their own MOOCs, or did they import MOOCs from other universities?</p> <p>They did both, most of the MOOCs were imported, but we also had our own, our university has a collaborative project with a university in the United States, and the design of the MOOCs was done jointly. My teachers were excellent, the course matched what we were learning, and the pace was well mastered. We</p>		

use the online class system for our studies, it seems like a lot of universities have them now.

- Did you interact with other students via MOOCs?

If yes, in what ways did you interact with students.

- Can you see other students on the screen? Did you talk with each other?
- Did you enjoy this form of learning?
- Why did you like collaborating? / Why did you not enjoy it?
- How exactly were you able to collaborate online? How did the collaboration work?

If no, why there's no interaction?

I have some interaction with other students, but not much. I'm quite shy, I don't really like to be the one answering questions or working on some tasks as a group representative. **MOOCs, in this aspect, was very friendly to me, we usually had video lectures and reading materials and I'd type and communicate with my classmates or leave comments on the discussion boards to discuss some points after the class, I didn't have to turn on the camera or expose my little learning environment, It's not like a classroom.**

	<p>But this has a great advantage for me, I can study and think quietly without the pressure of being asked questions, which allows me to concentrate more and makes it easier to take notes. And I found that in the discussion process of many questions, my classmates answered better than they usually did in class when they were asked to answer the questions. I guess at the same time, they also use other devices to search for some materials. This kind of behavior is actually not allowed in the classroom, the teachers did not allow us to use mobile phones, they thought that we were playing games.</p> <p>Questions on participants' experience of working online during COVID-19?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are your memories of MOOCs? Are they good? - What steps did your university take as an immediate reaction to COVID-19? - What kind of online learning took place during COVID-19? <p>Yes, it was pretty good, and I felt more relaxed than studying in the classroom. I did not need to get up early or do makeup. Just stay at home, in my lovely room. We first took a week off to wait for the university notification, then started to study</p>	<p>Preference</p> <p>Interaction</p> <p>Preference</p>	<p>It is very different for most families. The wealth of families is different, making a different learning environment at home. This student's experience is very interesting, for her, MOOCs were individual environment that does not need to interacting with others. And the experience of learning Western Civilization without</p>
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	<p>online and all the activities changed online, including assessments and homework. Some of the classes were live courses, where we had to sign in by name, and some unimportant classes (the kind of non-specialised classes) would send us some recorded resources, or the teachers shared screens and students watched the materials together. Sometimes the teacher just needed to assign the tasks, and the students could arrange their own time to watch them. There were more notifications in the first two weeks, after all, it was an online and offline transfer that had never been done before. Then later, everyone got familiar with online learning.</p> <p>- What kind of MOOCs were offered? (University offered or lectures recommended?) (Was it easy to access? Was it free? Did your university run online programs?)</p> <p>There were a couple of courses that were assigned by the university at the time, but I cannot remember exactly which ones. Oh, I can't believe it has been four years since the pandemic. I remember there were History of literature and Lexicography, and some courses related to our majors were recommended by our teachers as supplemental material. They were all free. It was quick and easy; teachers gave us links to the</p>		<p>teachers or another academic center.</p> <p>These students, because they were not back at university, had a distance in which to reflect to the experience.</p> <p>Banning mobile phones in classrooms can be mistaken when the phones can be learning tools. They helped each other, for example, take photographs of the posters.</p> <p>This really supports different learning personalities. Although she may not want to go to</p>
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	<p>platforms or systems, and we could go straight to them.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What other online learning style was offered? - Which online learning method do you prefer? and why? <p>(Explore which online learning methods students preferred during the pandemic, eg. live, recorded, MOOCs)</p> <p>Yes, both live and recorded courses. I like MOOCs because most of them are recorded courses that I can always go back to and review what I didn't understand. I can watch the video over and over again to make sure that I understand and remember the key points correctly while I'm working on my homework.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What MOOCs did you enrol in, and did you complete? - Was there a formal completion process for you? - What was the breakdown of compulsory versus optional courses? - Did you have to complete it? After completing, can you get a certificate or just required by your university. 	<p>MOOCs and other online courses</p>	<p>class with make-up on, she is a very conscientious learner. She is worried about answering questions, which can also be linked on face culture. This is quite stressful for young people in the classroom environment.</p>
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I signed up for a few courses related to my major and completed the ones required by the university, but not the ones recommended by other teachers as supplements, I just looked at the section where I needed the materials and information.

- What does MOOCs or other online learning require of your time management skills? How do you balance your online management skills in order to engage in MOOC better?
- Did your management skills improve and develop?
- How do you maintain your study self-discipline without regular classroom observation by the teachers? (If so, how did you do this. If not, why did you not do this. What issues are involved?)

This time is flexible for me. Because I can watch MOOCs at any time. I think in general I got into the habit of studying on my own. During the MOOC study, small pieces of time were added together and utilised during online classes. But without time requirements, I often procrastinated. I am not a self-disciplined person, so I often slacked off if there were no teachers to watch over me or if there were no specified deadline requirements. I

	<p>always procrastinate until the last minute. But finally, it will be done, and I can study on my own, but not much haha.</p> <p>Experiences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Could you share some interesting or memorable experiences with MOOCs during the pandemic? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Were there any special MOOCs or teachers that impressed you? o Did you actively participate in online groupwork? How have these activities helped you in your studies? o Did you make good use of the learning resources provided by the MOOC programme, such as video lectures, reading materials and online tests? <p>Haha, my experiences are interesting but don't laugh at me. I sometimes can't answer questions so when the teacher asks me questions, I pretend to have internet problems and keep my voice down. Then one time, I had morning classes when it was in Winter and the weather was really cold my roommate said don't go to the living room to learn, it's too cold, just stay in the room and it won't bother her. Then I got really sleepy and laid</p>		
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Interaction

back down to sleep, thinking I could go back and watch the recorded content to make up for it. I want to try if she can hear this and put the computer next to her pillow. Then she told me she dreamed of attending a class.

As for group work, If the teacher assigns group work, then we will discuss and cooperate together. Otherwise, we will not initiate group discussions.

I have to admit that I didn't make good use of the online resources to study at that time, and **I actually regret it a little bit, thinking that I didn't work hard enough during this period, and the year went by extraordinarily fast, but it seemed that I did not make a lot of progress.**

- When did the traditional classroom courses return to normal for you at your university?

Around six months after the end of the pandemic, I think so, we resumed our regular classes, and it was clear that both the students and the teachers were happier and more active when we went back to the classroom and met each other.

- Did you choose to continue to participate in MOOCs after the

	<p>COVID-19 pandemic?</p> <p>Yes, I still using MOOCs now and should continue to do so. The online courses are resourceful really efficient and convenient. Some of the courses and knowledge are not taught at university. I have actually learnt to stay alone in the past few years of the pandemic, and I am used to doing a lot of things by myself, when I need to go and learn new content, I would naturally think of learning it by myself with MOOCs.</p>	<p>The future of MOOCs.</p>	
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APPENDIX I Data of Semi-structured Interviews

Data from the semi-structured interviews of students from the second target university, which did not deliver MOOCs officially (Experiences during COVID-19)

	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
(G) University B	<p>- Tell me something about the MOOCs that you used. Do they belong to cMOOC or xMOOC?</p> <p>- Did your universities use their own MOOCs or did they import MOOC from other universities?</p> <p>Through your introduction I think the MOOCs I took were cMOOC, my major does not belong to business, on the contrary, it belongs to liberal arts, which is usually lecture-based, with students discussing some articles with the teachers and practising some specific topics. We don't have an official MOOC programme at my university, I was introduced to MOOCs by my roommate, who is a very good student, so I think the resources she recommended should be good. I was exposed to MOOCs before the pandemic, and when the pandemic locked down the city, the universities in all cities were closed, and then online courses replaced the traditional classes, the word MOOCs can be heard in more places. It grew fast.</p>		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Did you interact with other students via MOOCs? <p>If yes, in what ways did you interact with students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can you see other students on the screen? Did you talk with each other? - Did you enjoy this form of learning? - Why did you like collaborating? / Why did you not enjoy it? - How exactly were you able to collaborate online? How did the collaboration work? <p>If not, why is there no interaction?</p> <p>We took the classes together, with no face-to-face interaction or discussion with other participants, and I did not need to turn on the camera, we only had some typed exchanges, when learned some new content, we could write down our own opinions in the discussion forum, and could also see other people's comments, as well as comments left by students in previous classes, which helped absorb ideas and synthesis analyses.</p> <p>In traditional classrooms, classmates have limited topics, and many groups reach a consensus once they discuss something, and there are not many personal opinions shown. I like this way of</p>	Interaction	
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	<p>learning because I can get a lot of knowledge and analysis content. I cannot consider things so comprehensive, then some other people's comments will help me have a lot of inspiration, there will be a kind of dawning sense of sudden understanding, such as a moment I realise oh yes yes yes, this is the point.</p> <p>Questions on participants' experience of working online during COVID-19?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are your memories of MOOCs? Are they good? <p>Now I have become accustomed to a combination of online and offline learning, as I'm sure many people who went through the pandemic did, and although it has gone, the habit has been developed. I can't say whether the experience was good or not, after all, many people lost a lot of things in the pandemic. But as far as learning is concerned, online classes have really evolved too fast. Before the pandemic, it was always face-to-face lessons. Suddenly the pandemic happened, and the way of learning changed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What steps did your university take as an immediate reaction to COVID-19? <p>I still remember when the pandemic first started,</p>	<p>Preference</p>	
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schools and universities were declared closed, the whole city was deserted, and even going out privately to do something was illegal during that period. The university then made many announcements one after another, including the change to online learning. For a while, we studied at home, then it resumed, and then the university was closed again, and we were quarantined in the accommodation for a while. Everyone took online classes. Some courses were live, where the teacher asked us to turn on the camera to determine the number of people and make sure we were listening. There were some other courses the teacher recommended were recorded classes for us to watch and learn by ourselves. The university had an official learning system and websites, all free.

- What kind of online learning took place during COVID-19?
- What kind of MOOCs were offered?

(University offered or lectures recommended?)

(Was it easy to access? Was it free? Did your university run online programs?)

That is, the traditional courses were transferred online, through the Tencent meeting and other apps, the teacher gave online classes, and we listened to the class as usual. We had to turn on the camera, sign in, and answer questions. There were no official MOOCs offered by the university, some

	<p>of the courses I took were recommended by my teachers and classmates, and most were used as the content of the background information.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What other online learning style was offered? - Which online learning method do you prefer? and why? <p>(Explore which online learning methods students preferred during the pandemic, eg. live, recorded, MOOCs)</p> <p>Live and pre-recorded courses. I like pre-recorded courses because some content was not used for once. Pre-recorded courses were easy to find and review.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What MOOCs did you enrol in, and did you complete? - Was there a formal completion process for you? - What was the breakdown of compulsory versus optional courses? - Did you have to complete it? After completing, can you get a certificate or just required by your university. <p>Our university did not deliver MOOCs officially, but I have met there were formal completion</p>	Preference	
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processes for MOOCs offered by some MOOC platforms. Upon successful completion of a MOOCs, students were often issued a certificate or digital badge to recognise their achievement. Additionally, some courses offered the option to earn academic credit or transferable credentials, providing further incentives for completion.

- What does MOOCs or other online learning require of your time management skills? How do you balance your online management skills in order to engage in MOOCs better?
- Did your management skills improve and develop?
- How do you maintain your study self-discipline without regular classroom observation by the teachers? (If so, how did you do this. If not, why did you not do this. What issues are involved?)

I think MOOCs require a high level of time management skills as it often involves self-directed learning without the structure of a traditional classroom environment. **From my experience, I think it's important to set clear goals for what you hope to achieve at the beginning. Then, creating a study schedule that arranges specific**

times for MOOC study, can help to establish a routine to avoid procrastination. You know the flexibility of MOOCs may lead to procrastination. Asking yourself to actively participate in MOOCs, such as contributing to discussion forums, working on group projects, or seeking help from peers or instructors, can also enhance learning.

Experiences

- Could you share some interesting or memorable experiences with MOOCs during the pandemic?
 - o Were there any special MOOCs or teachers that impressed you?
 - o Did you actively participate in online groupwork? How have these activities helped you in your studies?
 - o Did you make good use of the learning resources provided by the MOOC programme, such as video lectures, reading materials and online tests?

An interesting experience was that once I looked up MOOCs delivered by Cambridge University to see what courses the best universities in the world delivered, my mum saw it and asked me what I was studying I said I was taking Cambridge courses and

	<p>I was going to study there, haha, and until these days she still asks me if I've got an offer.</p> <p>My university did not have official MOOCs, so I've just taken some courses on my own, initially to supplement the traditional classroom teaching. In this regard, I hardly ever go to discussions and collaborations and mostly watch recorded courses to seek to draw what I need. However, in other online classes, I am willing to participate in discussions, and I like to listen to other people's ideas.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When did the traditional classroom courses return to normal for you at your university? <p>Six months later, after one semester, offline classes resumed, but then there was a period when the city was closed again, not too long. However, after these six months, students and teachers have become familiar with the online course model and will keep using it later. I think universities will also make some considerations and put some courses to be taught exclusively through online systems.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Did you choose to continue to participate in MOOCs after the COVID-19 pandemic? 	Interaction	
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	<p>Yes, why not? MOOCs are excellent resources, but I expect my university to design our own MOOCs, which suit us better.</p>		
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	Interesting opinions from interview	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
(H) University B	<p>- Tell me something about the MOOCs that you used. Do they belong to cMOOC or xMOOC?</p> <p>- Did your universities use their own MOOCs or did they import MOOCs from other universities?</p> <p>My teachers didn't give such detailed instructions on types of MOOCs, and they just recommended it as a resource for our study. The university did not officially offer MOOCs either. But based on your description, I think I went to a cMOOC, English major, lecture-based with some lectures and exercises.</p> <p>- Did you interact with other students via MOOCs?</p> <p>If yes, in what ways did you interact with students.</p> <p>- Can you see other students on the screen? Did you talk with each other?</p> <p>- Did you enjoy this form of learning?</p> <p>- Why did you like collaborating? / Why did you not enjoy it?</p> <p>- How exactly were you able to collaborate online? How did the collaboration work?</p> <p>If not, why is there no interaction?</p>		

	<p>The MOOCs I took were recommended by my teachers and classmates as supplemental material for basic learning, so I almost had no interaction because I just wanted to look up what I wanted or listen to the part of the lecture and go back to my university courses.</p> <p>Questions on participants' experience of working online during COVID-19?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are your memories of MOOCs? Are they good? <p>Yes, my memories are pretty good. MOOCs are useful and targeted; I like them very much. Easy access and flexibility.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What steps did your university take as an immediate reaction to COVID-19? <p>The pandemic suddenly happened and the city where my university was located happened to be a key area for the pandemic. During that time, China would notify each province and city of new positives and adopt special policies for areas with high numbers of new positives.</p> <p>I remember when the pandemic started, the university was in session, and then it was a small holiday, it got worse during the holiday, and the university announced closed then. I took online</p>	Interaction	
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	<p>classes at home. I took online courses for one semester, and then the next semester started normally, but then the city was closed again, and the students were in lockdown at the university this time I took online classes in the accommodation. I was quarantined for about a month.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What kind of online learning took place during COVID-19? - What kind of MOOCs were offered? (University offered or lectures recommended?) (Was it easy to access? Was it free? Did your university run online programs?) <p>Different teachers use different teaching apps for their lessons, and most of the courses are live courses. Some teachers asked us to open the camera, some did not, but most asked that. They checked the students' names, shared the screen, and then the teachers showed the courseware and gave a lecture. We used Nail, Tencent meeting and some others from the official system. These courses do not include MOOCs, our university did not deliver MOOCs officially.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What other online learning style was offered? - Which online learning method do you prefer? and why? 		
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	<p>(Explore which online learning methods students preferred during the pandemic, eg. live, recorded, MOOCs)</p> <p>We have both live and recorded courses. Some teachers just followed the schedule, and when it was time for class, they called the roll, and then shared the PPT with us on the screen, sometimes they asked questions. Some teachers let us study through the recorded courses by ourselves. After the lecture, they gave us homework, and we had a WeChat group to share this homework.</p> <p>I liked the recorded courses because I was not nervous. When we stayed at home, there were no group discussions and then later in the accommodation, our course discussions were done in groups of two. It was a group of two girls or a group of two boys because everyone was in their accommodation, and they couldn't get out. I can be a bit more conscious when I have someone to supervise me and study with me in the recorded courses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- What MOOCs did you enrol in, and did you complete?- Was there a formal completion process for you?		
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What was the breakdown of compulsory versus optional courses? - Did you have to complete it? After completing, can you get a certificate or just required by your university. <p>I used some of the MOOCs recommended by my teacher as a supplement to my basic studies, not completing them in their entirety and just watching whichever parts I needed. Because there was no credit transfer or graduation involved. It was just used as a learning resource to help me better understand some of the content.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do MOOCs or other online learning require of your time management skills? How do you balance your online management skills in order to engage in MOOC better? - Did your management skills improve and develop? - How do you maintain your study self-discipline without regular classroom observation by the teachers? (If so, how did you do this. If not, why did you not do this. What issues are involved?) <p>Online courses really require time management skills, which I did not do very well. I always procrastinate because of the flexibility of time and</p>	Preference	
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the lack of teacher supervision and graduation restrictions. **I think I should improve my time management skills and efficiency, since I can't be very disciplined, I should improve my efficiency and learn the content while I'm learning it.**

Experiences

- Could you share some interesting or memorable experiences with MOOCs during the pandemic?
 - o Were there any special MOOCs or teachers that impressed you?
 - o Did you actively participate in online groupwork? How have these activities helped you in your studies?
 - o Did you make good use of the learning resources provided by the MOOCs programme, such as video lectures, reading materials and online tests?

I and students of Design major were living in the same accommodation building. Some of my friends are also from that major. **When attending online courses, some of the students did not have computers, and then the teachers lent them office computers to use, some also came to our accommodation to borrow.** Students from design

Some online learning needs particular computer devices.

	<p>majors need to use the computer more often, so the university later arranged for a teacher specifically responsible for fixing the setup and the equipment. I meet them waiting at the maintenance on the ground floor of the accommodation building every day. MOOCs and online learning really need computer devices.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When did the traditional classroom courses return to normal for you at your university? <p>We just locked down for one semester and traditional classroom courses returned to normal, but later happened again. Online courses have been used till now.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Did you choose to continue to participate in MOOCs after the COVID-19 pandemic? <p>Yes, it makes studying flexible and comfortable. MOOCs offer a level of flexibility that traditional classroom learning often cannot. Students can learn at their own pace. I will use it when I need it.</p>	<p>The future of MOOCs.</p>	
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APPENDIX J Data of Open-ended Question of Questionnaires

Data from significant responses from students' and teachers' questionnaires open-ended question from University A.

Participant s	Significant responses from student questionnaire feedback: open-ended question (include Participant quotations)	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
SQP1	Using MOOCs will help me to enrich more knowledge than I learn in the classroom. It helps to keep social distance, and everybody can be safe during COVID-19.	The advantages of MOOCs. The emergency use of MOOCs.	MOOCs are flexible. It helps university students to acquire new skills and knowledge. MOOCs help students to keep social distance.
SQP2 SQP2 was selected to do the semi-structured interview.	Using MOOCs can help students acquire more knowledge than expected during the university period. MOOCs give students more free and flexible time.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs are flexible. It helps to develop the university students' expectations of their learning.
SQP3	Using MOOCs can help me to develop autonomous learning	The advantages of	MOOCs help students to develop

	ability.	MOOCs.	their perception of their autonomous learning ability.
SQP4	Using MOOCs can develop my autonomous learning ability and increase my learning motivation. MOOCs can be chosen by my own hobbies, which will help to develop my learning interests.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs help to develop students' perception of their autonomous learning ability. MOOCs help to develop students' learning interests.
SQP5 SQP5 was selected to do the semi-structured interview.	Using MOOCs help students feel free and relaxed when learning and makes us more focuses because we do not need to pay more attention to the environment or the relationship with other students.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs are helpful to do individual learning. MOOCs help students feel free and relaxed while learning.
SQP6	Using MOOCs help to develop the learning method and increase learning motivation.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs help develop students' autonomous learning ability and increase learning motivation.
SQP7	Using MOOCs can make	The advantages of	MOOCs enable

	learning time more flexible.	MOOCs.	flexibility for times of learning. MOOCs help develop students' autonomous learning ability.
SQP8	Using MOOCs help me to be self-disciplined on study.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs help develop students' autonomous learning ability.
SQP9	MOOCs help me to get used to the online learning model and provoke my learning habit that in other subjects I can also do autonomous learning.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs help develop students' autonomous learning ability.
SQP10	MOOCs help me to develop my ability to accept new things. MOOCs help to make studying easier because I can find the material that I need through courses.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs can provoke learning habits. MOOCs help to develop students spirit of discover.

Participants	Significant responses from teacher questionnaire feedback: open-ended question (include Participant quotations)	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
TQP1	Using MOOCs will help students develop skills such as self-motivation in study and autonomous learning ability.	MOOCs help to develop students' perception of their autonomous learning ability.	MOOCs develop the way that students learn and increases learning motivation.
TQP2	Using MOOCs will help students to develop good time management habits.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs enable flexibility for times of learning and helps to develop students' perception of their autonomous learning ability.
TQP3	MOOCs and other online courses require students to have strong self-discipline and management skills.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs help to develop students' perception of their autonomous learning ability.
TQP4	Students develop independent learning habits by getting used to the MOOCs, which can also apply this habit to their other	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs help to develop students' perception of their autonomous learning

	interests, in order to acquire more skills.		ability and to acquire new skills and knowledge.
TQP5	The students themselves have a strong ability to accept new things. As MOOC learning is not limited by space and time, it is easy to look up information for autonomous learning, which is a way to train themselves.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs develop the way that students learn increases learning motivation and helps develop students' autonomous learning ability.

**Data from significant responses from students' and teachers' questionnaires
open-ended question from University B.**

Participant s	Significant responses from student questionnaire feedback: open-ended question (include Participant quotations)	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
SQP1	Using MOOCs will help me to develop the skill to take exams, such as summarising the main points through online courses.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs help university students develop learning skills.
SQP2	Using MOOCs can help students acquire more knowledge than expected during the university period.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs help to develop the Chinese students' expectations of their learning and to acquire new skills and knowledge.
SQP3	Using MOOCs will help to develop skills such as self-estimated ability and autonomous learning ability.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs help to develop students' perception of their autonomous learning ability and to acquire new skills.
SQP4	MOOCs can replace traditional	The possible future	MOOCs help

<p>SQP4 was selected to do the semi-structured interview.</p>	<p>courses.</p> <p>MOOCs help to increase personal learning interests and it's a good way to combine MOOCs with traditional classroom teaching.</p> <p>MOOCs are good for students to discover new skills and new knowledge.</p>	<p>of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>university students acquire new skills and knowledge</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - helps to combine online and traditional courses - can tailor learning to students' interests - develop students' autonomous learning.
<p>SQP5</p>	<p>Using MOOCs helps students to study more efficiently.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs help develop students' autonomous learning ability.</p>
<p>SQP6</p>	<p>Using MOOCs help to develop the learning method and increase learning motivation.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs help develop students' autonomous learning ability.</p>
<p>SQP7 was selected to do the semi-structured interview.</p>	<p>Using MOOCs can make learning time more flexible and develop the students' self-reflection ability.</p>	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs enable flexibility for times of learning and develops students' autonomous learning ability. It also increases students' self-reflection ability.</p>

SQP8	<p>Using MOOCs makes it easy to find interesting subjects and learn more than in the classroom.</p> <p>Using MOOCs to review sometimes can help with courses in the university.</p>	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs can help with university courses. MOOCs help develop students' autonomous learning ability and to acquire new skills and knowledge.
SQP9	MOOCs have a lot of advantages, and using MOOC helps students to develop their self-learning habits and even get more skills.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs can develop the way students learn, increase learning motivation and help develop students' autonomous learning ability and to acquire new skills and knowledge.
SQP10	Most of the MOOCs are free and it is a very good chance to learn from other famous teachers and reflect on what students lack.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs are free and provide opportunities to learn from well-known teachers. It can also help increases students' self-reflection ability.

Participants	Significant responses from teacher questionnaire feedback: open-ended question (include Participant quotations)	Emergent Themes (Themes arising)	Sub-themes emerging
TQP1	Using MOOCs will help students to enhance their autonomous learning ability.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs develop the way that students learn increases learning motivation and helps develop students' autonomous learning ability.
TQP2	Firstly, using MOOCs will help students to enhance their autonomous learning ability. It also provides rich resources for them to use. Free courses from top universities are really attractive.	The advantages of MOOCs.	MOOCs develop the way that students learn increases learning motivation and helps develop students' autonomous learning ability. MOOCs provide rich recourse. Some MOOCs are free.

TQP3	MOOCs will help students to develop the ability of time-arrangement. It makes study more flexible than traditional classroom teaching.	The advantages of MOOCs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -enables flexibility for times of learning. -develops the way that students learn and increases learning motivation. -develop students' perception of their autonomous learning and time-arrangement ability.
TQP4	MOOCs give students more chances to learn what they want. With rich resources, free time and spaces, MOOCs will be developed fast and co-operate with classroom teaching better.	<p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p> <p>The possible future of MOOCs.</p>	MOOCs are flexible and may be combined with traditional classroom teaching methods in the future.

TQP5	<p>Some universities started to deliver MOOCs during COVID-19, which is a good way for teachers and students to stay safe. Although our university did not do this. Students also choose their own courses on the MOOC platform. This is a good way for them to learn more and achieve more.</p>	<p>The emergency use of MOOCs.</p> <p>The advantages of MOOCs.</p>	<p>MOOCs can be used in some emergency situation.</p> <p>MOOCs develop the way that students learn increases learning motivation and helps develop students' autonomous learning ability.</p>
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APPENDIX K Consent Form: Participants (interview)

Name of department:

School of Education, University of the West of
Scotland (UWS)

Title of the study:

**An Analysis of Students' Engagement with
MOOCs in Higher Education in China**

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study and the researcher has answered any questions to my satisfaction.
- I understand that taking part is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- I understand that I can withdraw my data from the study up to the point of anonymization.
- I understand that any information recorded during the study will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- I consent to being a participant in this study.
- I consent to being audio recorded as part of the study

I (PRINT NAME)	Hereby agree to take part in the above study
Signature of Participant: Date:	

APPENDIX L Definitions of Terms Used in this Thesis

Constructivist Learning Theory: It is a theory of learning that is proposed as a way of improving teaching and learning. Constructivist learning theory posits that learners acquire knowledge based on their own experiences, individually, socially, and actively (Narayan, Rodriguez & Araujo et.al, 2013). With the primary aim of understanding how various activities in the developmental process can trigger learners' self-learning and how teachers can appropriately play the role of supporters in the learning process (Tam, 2000).

Humanistic Learning Theory: It emphasises that humans have natural learning desires, and the desires can be released under suitable conditions. When the learners realise that the learning content is related to their own needs, their enthusiasm for learning is most likely to be stimulated (Combs, 1982; Knowles, 1975; Rogers, 1951). This theory, therefore, focuses on inspiring the learner's experience and creating their potential abilities, guiding them to combine cognition and experience. The humanistic learning theory focuses on how to create a favourable environment for the learners to help perceive the world from their own perspective and needs, and therefore develop an understanding of the world.

Affective Filter Hypothesis: It is a theory proposed by linguist Stephen Krashen as part of his broader theory of second language acquisition. The hypothesis suggests that certain affective factors can act as filters that hinder or facilitate language acquisition. According to Krashen (1982), language acquisition is most successful when learners are in a low-anxiety, low-stress environment, where they feel motivated and have a positive attitude toward the target language.

Connectivism Learning Theory: It is a network-oriented learning theory that suggests students should combine thoughts, theories, and information (Vas, Weber & Gkoumas, 2018). It suggests that the development of technology is important to learners and that the process of connecting to the outside gives learners' opportunities to have more choices of learning.

Behaviorism Learning Theory: It advocates all behaviours are learned through conditioned interaction with the environment (Clark, 2018). Scholars who are guided by this learning theory believe that behaviours are learned from the environment and that inherited factors have little influence on learning behaviours.

Open Learning Pedagogy: It is a form of experiential learning that advocates collaboration, student agency, and authentic audiences (Baran & AlZoubi, 2020) while recognising the differences between privilege and progress, that impact the students' behaviour of how to balance the benefits of sharing and keep privacy (Hare, Frye & Samuelson, 2020). Open pedagogy is different from traditional teaching methods, which change the educational experiences of teachers and students.